

D3.2 Framework for Governance Processes and Interoperability

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Executive Summary

This is a report on the application of the Risk-Tandem Framework (RTF), specifically fulfilling Task 3.2 of the Grant Agreement. The application of the RTF through its four phases - Foundation, Growth, Learn and Sustain - has resulted in a refined framework, which is tuned to account for the various governance processes in the Real World Labs, and geared towards enabling interoperability to facilitate Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) integration.

The Framework was developed and applied through Work Package 3, in collaboration with Work Packages 4, 5 and 1. The application of the RTF was crucially driven by the indicators, which allowed for the assessment of each Real World Lab (RWL) during the Foundation Phase. The Risk-Tandem indicators, while based on the initial set of indicators developed in Deliverable 3.1, are revised and operationalized based on the feedback and input garnered from the engagement with each RWL. Based on the assessment made possible through the application of the indicators, the report provides insights into the various governance challenges each RWL faces, how they can be dealt with, and how the continuous application of the RTF enables reflection and learning. The main challenges, focal points, and emerging technical solutions and governance mechanisms of each RWL are presented below.

In RWL 1, the Capital Region of Denmark, the main governance challenge was around intermunicipal exchange and coordination with emergency services in the Roskilde Fjord area. To address this, the RWL focused on co-designing the Data Fabric to facilitate dialogue, identify priority hotspots, and explore different interventions. Importantly, recent Danish regulatory changes have removed the ability for regions to be involved in CCA activities or initiatives, including European projects. Consequently, Region Hovedstaden (the RWL host), has withdrawn from the DIRECTED project and the RWL hosting role is now fully taken over by the Danish Technical University (DTU).

In RWL 2, the Emilia-Romagna Region, the priority was to improve access to new modelling tools for rapid coastal and pluvial flood mapping. This included enhancing the interoperability between different data providers within the Data Fabric, with the main user being Civil Protection Officers. Improving wildfire risk communication to the public was another key priority, which led to the creation of a communication kit including information boards and social media cards. One challenge identified during the RWL process was securing attendance and engagement from non-governmental actors (e.g., beach owners, hotel owners, campsites).

While the Danube model is capable of representing events throughout the entire Danube catchment, due to the vast scale, RWL 3 (the Danube Region), was divided into two focus areas, namely the Vienna Region in Austria, and the Zala Region in Hungary. The Vienna Region's main focus was to better integrate information by various stakeholders, especially from the insurance and research sector, into the DRM and CCA decision-making processes. For Zala, the key area of interest was building a shared vision for DRM and CCA in the West

Balaton region through RWL engagement activities and facilitating data sharing through the Data Fabric.

In RWL 4, the Rhine-Erft Region, the main findings were that there is a drive to improve interinstitutional communication, public engagement, and further integrate CCA strategies into the portfolio of the RWL hosts (Erftverband). While the initial engagement and exploration in the RWL has revealed some gaps in this regard, the hosts and the consortium have jointly worked on solutions, such as co-creation processes via workshops and the institutionalization of a conference call with local districts.

Through the iterative application of the RTF to the RWLs, several cross-cutting issues around interoperability have been identified. Firstly, varied implementation gaps were identified among RWLs where there is potential for knowledge transfer and innovation. Secondly, there is a communication gap among the various stakeholders with regard to sharing and exchanging information in relation to DRM and CCA. These issues were addressed with the RWLs through the Growth and Learn Phases of the RTF. Looking forward the aim is to sustain these co-produced technical solutions and governance mechanisms to address these gaps. This includes providing the RWL with the skills and capabilities to address these issues themselves in the longer term, which is facilitated by activities in other work packages.

Through the RTF's application to the individual RWLs, the project was able to develop an updated and operationalizable version of the Risk-Tandem Framework. As an iteration, the updated RTF has shown to be adaptable towards the specific needs and interests of the user, especially through the help of the refined indicators that allow for a modular application of various points of interest throughout the DRM and CCA decision-making process. This moves the RTF from conceptual design towards an on-the-ground process for supporting improved decision-making. This was a crucial step in the RTF's development, and highlights its straightforward applicability and dynamism.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
APSFR	Areas of Potential Significant Flood Risk
ARPAE	Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy
ARSTPC-ER	Regional Agency for Territorial Safety and Civil Protection
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
COC	Municipal Operational Centres
COR	Regional Operations Center
CP Code	Civil Protection Code 2018
DCA	Danish Coastal Authority
DEMA	Danish Emergency Management Agency
DCNA	Disaster Competence Network Austria
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DMP	Data Management Plan
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
DTU	Danish Technical University
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ERCC	European Emergency Response Coordination Centre
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable And Reusable
FRMP	Flood Risk Management Plan
GA	General Assembly
InKA	Industrial Adaptation to Climate Change
KAnG	Klimaanpaasungsgesetz
KIAnG	Klimaanpassungsgesetz Nordrhein-Westfalen
LOS	Local Operational Staffs team
LANUK	Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Klima Nordrhein-Westfalen
NAP	National Action Plan

NAS	National Adaptation Strategy
NOST	National Operational Staff
OKF	National Directorate General for Disaster Management
OVF	General Directorate of Water Management
PNACC	Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici
RTF	Risk-Tandem Framework
RWL	Real World Lab
SKKM	Federal Crisis and Catastrophe Management
SOUP	Permanent Unified Operations Room
TTX	Tabletop Exercise
TVB	Zala County Territory Protection Committee
WP	Work Package
MEL	Monitoring, Evaluation, & Learning
ZCDMD	Zala County Disaster Management Directorate
ZSRT	Zala Special Rescue Team

1 Introduction

This report shows how the Risk-Tandem Framework (RTF), developed in the first phase of the DIRECTED project (see Deliverable 3.1/Task 3.1) has been applied to the Real World Labs (RWLs) through the application of indicators. The practical application of the initial RTF has led to the development of an updated version. The purpose of this Framework is to foster local DRM and CCA governance processes for decision-making by building on interoperability and knowledge co-production, including the integration of DRM and CCA strategies.

The practical application of the RTF has entailed the RWLs working through the four phases of the RTF. The four phases provide temporally divided forms of interaction with different focal points. The report further explores cross-cutting issues, key takeaways of both the project and the RWLs, and gives an outlook on the final year of the DIRECTED project.

The structure of this report starts in [Section 2](#) with the RTF methodology, which includes the theoretical and conceptual basis of the RTF, the phases of the RTF, the monitoring, evaluation and learning aspects, the indicators, and how this framework is applied.

[Section 3](#) focuses on the application of the RTF for each of the RWLs. This encompasses the four phases of Foundation, Growth, Learn, and Sustain. Each phase represents the various temporal and topical points of application of the framework. A key element of the Foundation Phase is the application of the indicators. This section represents the main body and focal point of this report, presenting the various knowledge co-production processes, resulting outputs and governance mechanisms and insights facilitated through the RTF and the DIRECTED project so far.

[Section 4](#) builds on previous sections by analysing the major findings and identifying cross-cutting issues. This section discusses the challenges of interoperability in terms of implementation and communication gaps identified throughout all the RWLs.

[Section 5](#) outlines the RTF's inherent process of Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning. This process ensures that the framework is continuously evolving, and can always be re-assessed and tailored to the specific needs of the actors applying it.

Finally, [Section 6](#) gives an outlook on how the framework will be further developed and applied in the last year of the project, including through the development of the Risk-Tandem Toolbox. This section also discusses how the RTF can continue to be used after the project's conclusion.

2 Methodology - Risk-Tandem

Framework

At its core, the RTF is an analytical tool that provides a set of questions in the form of indicators. These indicators, in turn, serve as means to better understand the DRM and CCA strategies in place in a given context. The methodological basis for the RTF consists of qualitative analysis and assessment processes, including quantitative data which is used to inform these processes. The data for these processes is based on extensive desktop reviews, interviews with RWL hosts and stakeholders, workshops and transcripts, and presentations.

The RTF builds on five different approaches from the DRM and CCA fields. The Institutional Analysis and Development framework (Ostrom, 2011) alongside the International Risk Governance Council approach (IRGC, 2017) provide the theoretical foundation, defining the scope and conceptual landscape of Risk-Tandem. The SHIELD model (Lauta et al., 2018) and Risk-Layering (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2021) both serve as additional sources to define the action space and provide an evaluative background for the application of the framework. Finally, the Tandem approach (Daniels et al., 2020; Bharwani et al., 2024) underpins and guides the engagement with all partners, RWL hosts, and local stakeholders, ensuring mutual learning and shared knowledge creation through knowledge co-production and associated capacity development.

Accordingly, the first task in WP 3 was concerned with establishing the conceptual foundation of the RTF, building on the synergies between these approaches, and where necessary filling conceptual and practical gaps. Establishing these synergies has been a primarily conceptual effort and ultimately culminated in a shared publication among partners (Parviainen et al., 2025).

The RTF is iterative and practically grounded by design. The “*research through design approach*”, uses design as a method of enquiry, which entails an inherent dynamism in the way in which the framework presents itself, allowing for a tailored application and high context-sensitivity in each case. Empirical data that is gathered via engagement activities, such as workshops, questionnaires, or interviews is accordingly fed into the framework and shapes its application. User needs and capacities are assessed and serve as input for the scope of Risk-Tandem (see DIRECTED Milestone 19, *Scoping Consultation and Capacity Development Needs*). At the same time, the kinds of research questions and concomitant problems the project seeks to explore in the respective RWLs and between them, are centrally shaped through constant interactions with the RWL hosts in the bi-weekly task-force meetings, and through 1-1 scoping and planning consultations preceding all workshop activities (see [Annex 1.2](#), Milestone 13 *Documentation of Co-Production Activities*). In line with the Tandem framework that guides the project partners’ engagement with the RWLs,

knowledge co-production plays a central role for the successful implementation of Risk-Tandem and DIRECTED in general. Structured according to the Tandem steps of 1) scoping; 2) co-exploration; 3) co-design and appraisal, and; 4) integrating knowledge and partnerships, the 4-year process of Risk-Tandem has been designed to enable locally-led exploration of risk governance challenges and development of fit-for-purpose solutions. Capacity development under WP 4 (Deliverable 1.2) seeks to build the capacities of RWL hosts to lead and facilitate co-production processes following the Risk-Tandem structure, to co-produce risk information, risk governance challenges, and to co-design interventions and solutions to identified challenges.

Risk-Tandem activities have further been aligned with DIRECTED's Data Fabric (WP 5) activities and development, through the co-exploration of user needs across stakeholder groups. This process also included the user story development, related co-design process of the Data Fabric and associated interoperability workflows in each RWL (see [Annex 2](#)).

With the co-production approach as the guiding principle for engagement, it is important to keep in mind that the knowledge production and sharing process is neither theory-neutral nor value-neutral. Research endeavors of any kind require an ontological scope and conceptual schemes, whether the researcher acknowledges this or not. Similarly, the RTF inherently emphasizes certain values and theories, and pays less attention to others. This becomes obvious in the baseline analysis and assessment pieces (as presented in through the indicators of the Foundation Phase), as well as the context-specific application of the framework through the Growth, Learn and Sustain Phases. The refined indicators that serve as an evaluative frame of reference for the RWL activities are a combination of ethical and governance considerations salient in the DRM and CCA field. Accordingly, they highlight the importance of criteria such as inter- and intra-institutional communication, fairness, equity, and meaningful participation, social vulnerability, and science-policy gaps. This focus inevitably and necessarily excludes various issues, such as the deeper socio-political context that influences the actors' capacity and interest to improve DRM and CCA synergies.

This leads to two central methods upon which the RTF relies. One, the scholarly and academic effort provided by the partners, which serves as the theoretical basis for the conceptual scoping of the research endeavor. Two, it draws information and data from stakeholder interviews, workshops, tabletop exercises, and regular meetings with the local stakeholders and the RWL hosts. Importantly, these two methods are interdependent and shape each other, wherein theoretical assumptions are aligned with the practical challenges, and institutional praxis is informed by conceptual theorizing.

Finally, the direct engagement with the RWL hosts and partners raises some important ethical concerns. In regard to free and informed consent, the project has ensured that RWL hosts and stakeholders are informed about their collaboration, especially during engagement activities via consent forms. The right of life and human dignity are non-negotiable aspects of the application of the RTF, and the framework, provides space for the reflection and implementation of assessment processes that go beyond cost-benefit analysis and monetary value (for example, see Multi-Criteria Decision-Making in Capital Region of Denmark). Similarly, the participatory process developed through the RTF is geared towards being able

to account for structural injustices, such as a lack of diversity, fairness, and forms of racist, sexist, ableist, and other forms of discrimination. A process for whistleblowing is in place as well. Privacy and data protection and governance are ensured through the use of the European based Nextcloud server. Lastly, all the output is publicly available through a robust open science approach (either via the DIRECTED website, open access publications or online platforms like Zenodo and GitHub), and the RTF is specifically designed, and will be stored publicly as an open, interoperable, accessible, and reusable tool for DRM and CCA governance.

2.1. The Risk-Tandem Framework as a Toolbox

The RTF is both an analytical toolbox for the assessment and evaluation of the RWLs, as well as a heuristic through which the RWLs and their governance context can be framed. The idea of the toolbox highlights the fact that the various modelling and governance tools can be used in a modular fashion, geared towards the needs and interests of the user (this is also central to the further development of the RTF, see [Section 6](#)). The framework is accordingly a crucial part of DIRECTED's aim to integrate DRM into CCA processes, and thereby provide guidelines on how the resilience of the RWLs could be increased.

In order to operationalize the RTF, it was structured around three dimensions, which explore a region's governance and institutional context, the various degrees of risk management and risk knowledge, and the level of co-production. These dimensions are further divided into individual indicators and key questions, which provide guidance on the structure and substance of a region's analysis.

The core innovation of the RTF rests upon the conceptual and practical linkage of co-creation and risk-governance. This connection ensures that the framework is not only conceptually sound and at the forefront of Disaster Risk and Climate Adaptation scholarship, but also immediately relevant and applicable to the local users and stakeholders. Additionally, this connection is built upon involvement of a diverse set of experts, ranging from social scientists, to modellers and climate scientists, all the way to practitioners, first responders, and the public at large, which all find a shared methodological language through the RTF. Consequently, the framework facilitates the creation of a highly inter- and transdisciplinary decision-space that ensures broad and meaningful participation while also breaking disciplinary silos.

In order to facilitate the understanding of how the RTF has been applied so far, it is worthwhile to reiterate the conceptual structure laid out in Deliverable 3.1, and the subsequent academic publication (Parviainen et al., 2025) upon which it rests.

Figure 1: Risk-Tandem Framework.

Starting from the nucleus of this graph working outwards, the two central approaches that ground the RTF can be identified. Namely the Tandem-Approach, represented through the stakeholder engagement core and the orange co-production puzzle pieces. This part of the RTF process is achieved through workshops, tabletop exercises, and other co-creative activities that build the foundation for the knowledge co-production and co-creative aspects of the framework, and is connected via the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) process (see [Section 2.1.2](#))

The white circle represents the four phases of the Risk Governance approach that serve as a general orientation for the temporal division of a given risk governance and climate adaptation action. These phases have further been developed in this Deliverable as the Foundation, Growth, Learn, and Sustain Phases (see [Section 2.1.1](#)). Finally, the green outermost layer of the figure describes the various factors relevant for the substantive assessment of a given DRM or CCA strategy. This layer is represented in this Deliverable through the indicators.

2.1.1 Risk-Tandem Framework: Introduction of Phases

The development and application of the RTF is divided into four overlapping phases: Foundation, Growth, Learn, and Sustain. The DIRECTED timeline places Deliverable 3.1 and the initial conceptualization and co-exploration with the stakeholders within the first two years of the project, namely the Foundation and Growth phases, respectively.

The Foundation Phase, starting in the first year of the project, was focused on producing the RTF and involved building partnerships between the consortium and the RWLs, seeking out opportunities for co-productive risk governance strategies, mapping the various stakeholders, and a general scoping of the risks at hand. Specifically, this process required that attention be paid to two critical aspects. First, the gaps in existing DRM and CCA had to be identified and analyzed. Second, the appropriate conceptual tools to fill these gaps was necessary. The process of filling these gaps further required intellectual labor in synergizing various concepts stemming from different methodologies, theories, and disciplinary backgrounds.

Importantly, the output of this process was not just geared towards use in the various RWLs. The hosts and stakeholders of the individual labs all played a crucial role in the development and tuning of the RTF to suit their respective needs. With its focus on co-creation and contextualized applicability, the RTF was designed by the DIRECTED partners alongside and with crucial input from the RWL hosts, stakeholders and affected communities of the RWLs. The close collaboration also had an important impact on the creation of the Risk-Tandem indicators (see [Section 2.1.3](#)). These indicators would allow a first baseline assessment of the RWLs, setting forth a path on how to evaluate the labs' development and evolution over time. At the same time, these indicators were not meant to be final. Rather, in line with the iterative and co-productive approach inherent to the RTF, these indicators were open to refinement and reiteration, being tailored to the various needs of the RWLs. This refinement is the core aspect of this report.

The Growth phase is centered around applying the RTF on a conceptual and practical level to the RWLs. Conceptually, this required analysing and assessing the governance baseline of each RWL through the lens of the RTF, especially via the indicators first developed in D3.1. The practical application, through a host of on-going meetings, workshops, and presentations with the RWLs, further ensured that the indicators were both up to date with current developments in risk governance scholarship, while also ensuring that the needs of the RWLs were met. In this phase, the user and climate storylines were also implemented as a means to better gauge stakeholder needs and capacities, alongside the capacity needs and development reports, approaches for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) and Theories of Change. The user storylines critically link Risk-Tandem and the Data Fabric, developing use-case studies and examples for various models and datasets provided by the DIRECTED consortium in order to facilitate the decision-making process in a given RWL (see Pontius et al., 2025).

As with all phases, the Learn Phase importantly overlaps with the Growth Phase. Through the ongoing application of the RTF, via various workshops, presentations, tabletop exercises, continuous meetings and other forms of engagement ([Annex 1.1](#)), the Framework is continuously developing. The Learn Phase also builds on the Risk-Layering approach (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2020), aiding the user stories as a tool for uncertainty reduction, and further enhancing local decision-making and deliberation by simplifying and streamlining complexity. In this phase, co-design for developing interventions towards the specific challenges that the RWLs face takes place. The challenges and potential leverage points for interventions are highlighted in this report through the application of the indicators in [Section 3](#).

Finally, the Sustain Phase consists of ensuring the continued applicability, availability and continuous development of the RTF throughout the end of the DIRECTED project and beyond. This entails that the practices which supported knowledge-exchange between various institutions, the shared forms of data-collection, and other decision-supporting tools are sustained and built upon.

2.1.2 Risk-Tandem Framework: Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

The Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) system is designed to assess the performance, outcomes, and impacts of the RTF across the RWLs, and represents a crucial connecting piece between the various phases. It brings together institutional, governance, knowledge integration, boundary conditions, and co-production dimensions of monitoring with systematic evaluation of outcomes and impacts in each RWL (Parviainen et al., 2025). Through this approach, the MEL system both generates lessons learned and supports replicability of the RTF in other contexts.

The first MEL dimension focuses on institutions and decision-making, assessing both formal and informal rules that shape governance processes. This includes determining whether and how decision-making structures have changed following the implementation of the RTF, with particular attention to governance effectiveness, inclusivity, and adaptive capacity.

The second MEL dimension evaluates the feasibility of developed risk governance strategies in human, economic, and environmental terms, as well as the inclusivity and equity of these solutions. This aspect considers whether proposed strategies are robust, responsive to diverse stakeholder needs, and capable of sustaining long-term outcomes.

The third MEL dimension builds on knowledge integration approaches, assessing synergies and trade-offs generated during the RWL processes. This includes evaluating clarity of goals and aims, the integration of diverse forms of knowledge, and the role of participation in enabling shared understanding and collaboration. Special emphasis is placed on inclusivity, as participation and recognition of multiple knowledge are central to effective integration and learning.

The fourth MEL dimension examines boundary conditions for risk management. Here, attention is given to whether the proposed solutions, whether technical, financial, communicative, or organizational, align with available risk information, local perceptions, and community capacities. This includes evaluating whether risk information has been used effectively and appropriately depending on the RWLs needs, and whether solutions are coherent with local realities.

The fifth MEL dimension addresses co-production and capacity development, given the central role of these processes in the RTF. This involves monitoring the quality of co-production practices and evaluating the extent to which they enhance local capacity. Indicators include the contextual accuracy of the co-production process, the degree and plurality of stakeholder engagement, the trust and relationships built, the effectiveness of interactive and non-hierarchical methods, and the ability of the framework to facilitate the creation of shared goals and priorities across actors. This dimension builds on both the Tandem Framework and the principles of “good” knowledge co-production articulated by (Norström et al., 2020).

The implementation of the MEL framework will be operationalised in Deliverable 1.4. Overall, the MEL system provides evidence of the effectiveness and impacts of the RTF. By generating lessons learned and refining methods and tools, MEL will not only demonstrate project outcomes and impacts but also promote the replicability of the approach in other contexts through guidelines, recommendations, and best practices.

2.1.3 The Risk-Tandem Framework

Indicators

While the phases provide a procedural backdrop for the application of the RTF, the substantive analysis has taken place through the application of the Risk-Tandem indicators. Based on and further developed from the initial set of indicators in Deliverable 3.1, these indicators have been operationalized to help assess the strengths and potential gaps of the current Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation systems of the respective labs. This includes to what degree Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation frameworks have been integrated, what the current level of risk management knowledge is, and to what degree co-creative practices are taking place. The indicators have been organised into key dimensions including, the governance/institutional context, risk management/risk knowledge, and knowledge co-production. These key elements are based on the first iteration of the RTF, laid out conceptually in Deliverable 3.1 and published in Parviainen et al., (2025), as well as the connection with knowledge co-production capacity development in RWLs as published in Cumiskey et al., (2025).

The following subsection provides an overview of the various RTF dimensions and indicators. Importantly, each indicator comes with one or more key questions. Answering these questions allows us to assign a quantitative and qualitative yardstick to the assessment of the DRM and CCA context in a given RWL.

2.1.3.1 List of Risk-Tandem Framework indicators

The Governance and Institutional Context represents the first dimension, and consists of 5 interrelated indicators. Here, the central aim is to understand the broader decision-making context and action-space that each of the RWLs finds themselves in. This entails an assessment of the polycentric governance structure, and the division of responsibilities and accountability that come with such a structure.

Table 1: The Governance and Institutional Context Dimension of the RTF Indicators.

Indicator	Key Question
Legal framework for DRM/CCA	To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM/CCA integration?
Clarity of roles and responsibilities	To what extent are the roles and responsibilities for DRM/CCA clear within the legal framework?
Functionality of roles and responsibilities	To what extent are roles and responsibilities functional for DRM/CCA in practice?
Multi-level governance	To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM/CCA?
Accountability	To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support decision-making DRM/CCA?

Legal framework for DRM/CCA

When analyzing institutional decision-making processes, and throughout any policy analysis, it is key to understand the legal context under which decisions are being made (Polski & Ostrom, 2017). The legal framework includes legislation, plans, policies, and other legal instruments (Cubie & Natoli, 2022). This indicator helps the user understand how regulation and the law may facilitate or inhibit potential action with regard to DRM and CCA integration.

Clarity of roles and responsibilities

This indicator highlights that the evaluation of the DRM and CCA process necessitates understanding the lines of responsibilities of the respective actors' roles, which in turn gives insights into who can act under what capacity and authority (Ostrom, 2011).

Functionality of roles and responsibilities

Following up on the clarity of actor responsibilities, the functionality of those roles is further important to understand (see Alexander et al., 2016). How and to what degree the assigned responsibilities actually enable DRM and CCA action is in focus here.

Multi-level governance

Due to the multi-governance structure within which all the RWLs are placed, there are various governance levels to be taken into account when it comes to the analysis of DRM

and CCA strategies, and their integration (Birkmann & von Teichman, 2010). This indicator accordingly allows the user to assess to what degree the different governance levels (e.g., local - regional - federal/national - international) relate to each other, and how that relationship can be used to facilitate CCA and DRM integration. On the flipside, this indicator may also reveal dysfunctional relationships and highlight how certain connections inhibit DRM and CCA integration.

Accountability

Finally, the indicator on accountability considers it as a mechanism where an institutional relationship or arrangement exists where an agent (for example a mayor or emergency responder) can be held to account for their actions by another agent, institution, or the general public (Bovens, 2010). Accountability can be used to both understand and evaluate risk governance and stakeholder engagement as explored in Bovens (2010). This indicator examines accountability considerations that may support or hinder DRM and CCA actions.

The second dimension is the Risk Management and Risk Knowledge status-quo of each RWL, and consists of 8 indicators. These indicators are mainly concerned with the relationship between DRM processes and underlying CCA agendas. The inquiry here ranges from understanding existing DRM and CCA policies (e.g. Fekete et al., 2014), to social justice and citizen participation aspects (Hofbauer et al., 2025), as well as the feasibility of developing, improving, and implementing an integrated DRM/CCA concept like the RTF (c.f. Rivera et al., 2015).

Table 2: The Risk Management and Risk Knowledge Dimension of the RTF Indicators.

Indicator	Key Question
DRM/CCA policy/plan coherence	To what extent do policy objectives/goals and plans at different levels align to address DRM/CCA challenges?
Synergies/tradeoffs of Interventions	To what extent are synergies maximized, and trades-offs minimized across DRM/CCA interventions?
Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships	To what extent do DRM/CCA actors interact at appropriate levels? To what extent is there willingness/openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements?
Risk assessment data/models/tools	To what extent are (existing) risk modelling data/models/tools fit-for-purpose to address key DRM/CCA challenges? To what extent can DRM/CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools and interoperability across DRM/CCA?
Legal implications of data/modelling	To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support 'best' data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?
(Citizen) Inclusion and participation	To what extent do frameworks enable/ require citizen involvement in decision-making? To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion /participation in decision-making?
Public warning/risk communication	To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?
Social justice	To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM/CCA?
Feasibility	To what extent is the political, social and economic situation supporting DRM/CCA action?

DRM/CCA policy plan coherence

This indicator highlights to what degree existing DRM and CCA policies and strategies cohere. Understanding this is crucial to see whether the existing structures can be leveraged for further integration.

Synergies/Tradeoffs of interventions

The way in which DRM and CCA interventions (e.g., infrastructure projects, participation and stakeholder engagement events, regulations, etc.) are implemented, can produce mutual benefits or lead to counter-productive outcomes. This indicator explores this relationship.

Strength of CCA/DRM actor relationships

Informal norms and modes of interaction are central to an institution's behavior and development (Ostrom, 2011), which this indicator explores. The first part enables the user to question to what extent DRM and CCA actors, emergency services and urban planners, for example, interact in the necessary settings (e.g., during decision-making procedures). The second part of the indicator further explores to what degree there is a willingness and interest from the actors to build and foster these interactions beyond the existing structures.

Risk Assessment Data/Models/Tools

The indicator on Risk Assessment and Data is divided into three parts. First, the indicator provides input on the state of existing models and tools, and to what degree they are adequate for the integration of DRM and CCA. Second, the indicator explores whether existing DRM and CCA strategies and models are capable of incorporating new and innovative approaches. Finally, the indicator looks at interoperability. All the DIRECTED models aim to be adopted by diverse end-users to discuss their respective DRM and CCA strategies. At the same time, it is generally impossible for any single model to describe all the complex, nonlinear phenomena arising from the countless components of reality; each model will fit some aspects of the phenomena relatively well, while fitting others relatively poorly. For example, the Future Danube Mode is primarily compliant with insurance industry standards due to its development process, and it has expanded its target users to various stakeholders, including water managers, urban planners, climate service providers, etc. (Matuschek et al., 2020). Keeping in mind that models develop incrementally, as exemplified by the FDM, this section of the indicators aims to understand the scope of validity and interoperability for Data/Models/Tools of each RWL.

Legal Implications of Data/Models/Tools

This indicator highlights the legal mindsets or norms surrounding the use and application of 'best' data/models for DRM/CCA decision-making. The focus is whether the legal framework or concerns around accountability make decision-makers more hesitant to embrace new data/models, or whether they support this innovation.

Citizen Inclusion & Participation

Inclusion and participation are cornerstones when it comes to ensuring effective and equitable public decision-making processes (Schweizer and Renn, 2019). To explore the current state of this in each RWL, the indicator on citizen inclusion & participation is split into two parts. First, it asks to what degree existing regulation may require or enable inclusive and participatory approaches in DRM and CCA processes. Second, the indicator seeks to

answer to what extent current actors are willing to engage and potentially enhance existing inclusion and participation practices.

Public Warning/Risk Communication

From a DRM perspective, it is critical to understand how effective current systems of risk communication and public warning are, especially given the risk of intensified (and “out of the norm”) events due to climate change. This indicator therefore inquires on the state of existing public warning and risk communication systems.

Social Justice

This indicator focuses on the ethical and justice issues inherent in DRM and CCA decision-making (for example, Hofbauer et al., 2025), and offers a space for users to reflect the degree to which social justice issues are taken into consideration. Here, the focus is on the active inclusion of vulnerable and most affected communities in the decision-making process, as well as the degree to which these voices are taken into account when it comes to DRM and CCA planning.

Feasibility

DRM and CCA action can only be effective if it is also feasible. Accordingly, the final indicator of this dimension asks to what degree the current political, social, and economic situation provides feasible grounds for change and intervention in regard to DRM and CCA.

Knowledge co-production is the third and final dimension, and is split into 3 indicators. These indicators represent the level of collaborative arrangements that exist within and between institutions, the goals and needs that a given RWL and its institutions might have in regard to co-production, as well as the skills to engage in knowledge co-production activities.

Table 3: The Knowledge co-production Dimension of the RTF Indicators.

Indicator	Key Question
Collaborative mechanisms	To what extent do collaborative mechanisms exist to foster diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders?
Goals/needs for knowledge co-production	To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?
Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production	To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacity/skills for knowledge co-production?

Collaborative mechanisms

To better understand the knowledge co-production context of a given region, it is first important to understand its collaborative arrangements and the institutional settings. Accordingly, the first indicator looks first at the existence of arrangements that might foster transdisciplinarity. The interaction between different experts and the sharing of different kinds of knowledge are critical for the development of feasible and sustainable DRM and CCA strategies.

Norström et al., (2020) identified four principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research which are that the co-production process should be context-based, pluralistic, goal-oriented and interactive. To understand to what extent collaborative arrangements exist to foster transdisciplinary collaboration, we draw from Norström's first two principles for co-production, context-based and pluralism. The context principle also means *“taking into account the different needs, interests and beliefs of the different social groups who are invested in or affected by the challenge at hand”*. This links to the indicator above around social justice and engaging disenfranchised groups.

The pluralistic principle highlights that research should explicitly recognise and value multiple ways of knowing and doing. This links to indicators discussed above, such as citizen inclusion, strength of CCA/DRM actor relationships and participation and multi-level governance, but considers them collectively to understand to what extent both horizontal and vertical collaborative mechanisms exist. Through this approach, this indicator should capture whether formal/informal mechanisms for collaboration already exist in the lab, and whether these mechanisms enable meaningful, diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders.

Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production

Beyond understanding the structures that enable knowledge co-production, it is also important to inquire to what degree the actors and people affected see a need for co-production. This further helps understand whether the actors and affected people identify problems or challenges with which a co-productive approach could help. These goals and needs for knowledge co-production indicator links to the other two principles identified by Norström et al., (2020), that the research needs to be goal-oriented. The goals need to be clearly defined and reflect the challenges identified by the research. This requires active engagement and frequent interactions. Our evaluation of this indicator is based on coding of lab documents, where lab ‘challenges’ and ‘goals’ were coded. The results of this coding are explored further in D4.1 (Ng et al., 2025) and D4.2 (Parviainen et al., 2025a).

Capacities and skills for knowledge co-production

The final principal identified by Norström et al., (2020) is that knowledge co-production needs to be interactive to allow for ongoing learning between the partners and stakeholders. This is reflected in this indicator, which focuses on understanding to what degree knowledge co-production capacities and skills are already available in a given context. Drawing on Cumiskey et al., (2025), our evaluation focuses on three skills, design, research, and facilitation, and four core capacities, systems thinking, reflexivity, creativity, and collaboration.

These provided the basis for the Capacity Needs Assessment of which the results are analyzed in D4.1 (Ng et al., 2025) and provide the basis for our evaluation of this indicator.

2.1.3.2 Assessment of Risk-Tandem Framework indicators

Through the questions developed alongside the indicators, the application of the RTF was made operationalizable, and allowed for the assessment of the given RWL’s DRM and CCA context. There are two important notes to be made in order to explain and contextualize the indicators properly. First, the scoring of the individual indicators is driven by the context of the respective RWL. This means that a low-scoring indicator primarily represents potential room for growth and development and does not reflect a lack of engagement from the RWLs. Crucially, as the RTF is itself an innovative toolkit to foster DRM and CCA integration, the aim of its application is to highlight possible institutional and governance leverage points to facilitate such an integration. It is in this sense not an evaluative scoring board, but rather a guiding mechanism for development.

Second, and deriving from this contextualized understanding of the RTF’s application, is the fact that the scores cannot be translated into a comparison between the RWLs without further contextualization. Enabling shared learning practices, not just within but also between RWLs is a central part of the DIRECTED project, a part that is driven during the recurring jour fixe meetings and the general assemblies. Yet, the RTF is foundationally a context-driven process, the outcome of which is inherently geared towards the needs, capacities, interests, and structures of a concrete region. While the scoring helps identify shared opportunities for growth, it accordingly does not offer an objective, generically applicable means of comparison or evaluation.

With these notes in mind, the indicators are assessed on a scale of 1-5, with 1 indicating a potentially wide range of options for improvement and leverage, and 5 indicating a strongly developed indicator, with less immediate need for development. These assessments were undertaken using the key indicator questions, which were then answered using the evidence from the baseline literature review and learnings from the RWLs. The following table provides an overview of this assessment structure.

Table 4: Assessment board of the individual indicators.

1 = high potential for growth	2 = potential for growth	3 = intermediate	4 = reasonably developed	5 = strongly developed
#8c0273	#974e3e	#9c961c	#6cd48c	#b3f2fd

This assessment structure allows for a general overview of where and how RWLs could further develop and improve the integration of their DRM and CCA strategies. However, another contextualizing element is necessary in order to account for the fact that each RWL faces different challenges and seeks to emphasize different focal points. In short, while some

RWLs may be interested in further developing their public outreach and engagement methods, others may be more focused on integrating climate models into their interinstitutional communication processes.

In order to account for this distinction, the indicators also include the following tags:

- **High Priority:** Highly relevant indicator for the RWL (“must-have”)
- **Medium Priority:** Relevant indicator for the RWL (“should be considered”)
- **Low Priority:** Not applicable to the RWL, restricted feasibility due to legal restrictions, for example (“out of scope”)

These tags allow for the assessment to be concretely contextualized, while still offering the possibility for comparison and mutual learning. If an indicator is tagged as a High Priority, this means that there is a strong interest from the RWL hosts and stakeholders for this aspect to be further developed and focused on via the RTF. The tag Medium Priority entails that while not immediately relevant to the hosts and stakeholders, this indicator may be of concern and addressed further down the road. The Low Priority tag demarcates limited focus on this indicator, often due to legal limitations and policy structures that cannot, under current circumstances, be addressed by the hosts and stakeholders, or that the issue is simply not an immediate priority.

2.2 How does the Risk-Tandem Framework Work?

The phases outlined and indicators outlined provide a procedural and substantive guideline for the application of the RTF. Accordingly, the indicators have been applied throughout the Foundation Phase of each RWL, providing the basis for the Growth, Learn, and finally Sustain Phases. As laid out in the Task Description 3.2 of the Grant Agreement, as well as Deliverable 3.1, the Foundation Phase focuses on facilitating the engagement of the RWLs through the RTF, and laying the groundwork for the further phases.

The Foundation Phase first sets out a general overview of the RWL, presenting the existing Actor Networks through the lens of the conceptual tools introduced by the RTF in D3.1. On the basis of this overview, the Risk-Tandem indicators are applied. Here the sub-sections are divided into the different elements which make up the indicators. The Governance/Institutional Context element provides an analysis of the existing policy structures and institutional setting upon which the RWL’s DRM and CCA decision-making relies. Building on this analysis, the Risk Management/Knowledge element assesses what kinds of risk management processes are already at play in the RWL. Finally, the Knowledge co-production sets out to understand the potential of the given RWL to practice co-creation and knowledge co-production (for an exact documentation of each RWL interaction, please consult Annex 1, *Documentation of Co-Production Activities*).

On the basis of the engagement and research activities throughout the Foundation Phase, Key Risk-Governance Gaps/Aligned Indicators have been identified. This section summarizes the findings and critical risk-governance challenges identified through the application of the Risk-Tandem indicators of the previous sections, and develops possible ways forward. How these gaps have so far been resolved, and how those solutions can be further refined is then explained in the Growth and the Learning Phases. Within the Growth Phase priorities based on the outcome of the Foundation Phase are established, and governance mechanisms are explored that can help in supporting and leveraging these priorities. The Growth Phase is characterized by a particular focus on trying out potential tools and solutions to bridge the various gaps that may have come to the forefront throughout the RWL's initial assessment.

A key part of the Growth Phase is to identify leverage points and find possible windows of opportunity wherein co-production activities and governance mechanisms can support the improvement of a given DRM and CCA challenge. On the basis of these potential mechanisms and solutions, the Learn Phase then introduces iterations and learnings from the interactions with the RWL hosts and stakeholders so far. Through co-exploration activities initiated in the Foundation and the Growth Phase, the Learn Phase is geared towards providing tailored solutions that seek to address DRM and CCA challenges together with the RWLs.

The insights from the Foundation, Growth, and Learn Phases, finally set the consortium and the RWL hosts up for the Sustain Phase. The final phase of the RTF serves to upscale and institutionalize the solutions developed so far. Most importantly, during the Sustain Phase the RWLs and the DIRECTED consortium will be exploring mechanisms to allow for the continuous deployment of the selected RTF tools beyond the DIRECTED project's duration. The following sections will go through each RWL individually, exploring these phases and their respective engagement activities and learning processes.

Ethics and Social Justice Aspects

An examination of the following sections reveals a recurring feature. Ethical and social justice considerations are not substantively addressed across the RWLs. The RTF, by design, possesses the capacity to engage with such concerns by incorporating a plurality of perspectives from socially diverse stakeholder groups and by addressing both distributive and procedural dimensions of justice. Their limited presence in the current application can be explained by two interrelated factors.

First, questions of social justice were not afforded a high degree of emphasis or urgency within most RWLs. The extent to which decision-making processes should integrate a wide range of stakeholder perspectives was not a central point of orientation for the laboratories. Consequently, the malleable and modular character of the RTF facilitated an emphasis on other priorities, thereby reducing the visibility of justice-related concerns.

Second, while RWL hosts and their local partners served as highly effective actors in

advancing DRM and CCA processes within their specific contexts, their institutional roles and legal mandates were typically circumscribed. As such, their capacity to address the more systemic and structural dimensions of inequality and injustice in decision-making processes remained limited.

These factors are closely tied to the selection of RWLs and the focal themes around which they were organized. Accordingly, they suggest an opportunity for refinement in subsequent applications of the RTF. Future projects that are guided by principles of co-creation may benefit from explicitly foregrounding inclusion and diversity, thereby ensuring that Ethical and Social Justice considerations are integrated more systematically and contribute more substantially to transformative and enduring outcomes.

3 Risk-Tandem Framework

application in RWLs

The following subsections present the results of the RTF application in the four RWLs. The order of the application is: RWL 1 - Capital Region of Denmark, RWL 2 - Emilia-Romagna, RWL 3 - Danube represented by the focus regions Vienna and Zala, and RWL 4 - Rhine-Erft. First, an outline and actor-network of each RWL is laid out. Then, the indicators are applied according to the RTF's Foundation Phase. The information of that phase is subsequently used to outline how the Growth Phase has been developed, and what the Learn Phase provided in terms of iteration and reflection. Finally, the Sustain Phase explores further means of sustaining the RTF's implementation beyond the DIRECTED project's duration.

3.1 Real World Lab 1: Capital Region of Denmark

Figure 2: Capital Region of Denmark, DIRECTED Project Mapping of Regions.

The Capital Region of Denmark is characterized by its high number of independent municipalities. The main study area is the Roskilde Fjord, which is bordered by five municipalities (Frederikssund, Halsnæs, Egedal, Roskilde, and Løjre). Besides intermunicipal cooperation, the region also seeks to improve the collaboration between and with the respective emergency services in the area. The main risks for the region are storm surges and sea level rise that leads to coastal flooding, as well as pluvial and fluvial flooding. There is further a risk of fires as well as severe droughts and heat events, however these are not the focus for the RWL.

Figure 3 provides an overview of the Risk-Tandem application for the Capital Region of Denmark RWL covering the priority gaps in the Foundation Phase, the key activities during the Growth and Learn phases and the governance mechanisms/technical solutions being prepared for the Sustain Phase. Annex 1 presents an overview of the RWL activities and the support meetings from researchers across DIRECTED.

Figure 3: Overview of Risk-Tandem application for Capital Region of Denmark RWL.

3.1.1 Foundation Phase

3.1.1.1 Actor Networks/Setting the Scene

Figure 4: Stakeholder Map: RWL Denmark.

Real World Lab 1 spans the five municipalities bordering Roskilde Fjord (Halsnæs, Frederikssund, Egedal, Roskilde, and Lejre) as well as the three local emergency management services (fire services) - see [Figure 4](#). In Lejre and Roskilde municipality, the local emergency management service is linked directly to the municipality. In Halsnæs, Frederikssund, and Egedal, the local emergency service is jointly owned and operated (together with two municipalities outside the Roskilde Fjord area).

This RWL prioritised bringing together these municipal and local emergency management services because they rarely take the opportunity to exchange knowledge. In addition, national and regional level actors were involved in the RWL including the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA), Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), the administrative Region of Zealand and the Capital Region of Denmark and the Danish Coastal Authority (DCA). Noting that by 2026, the Capital Region and Region of Zealand will merge to form the new Region of Eastern Denmark, at the same time all regional activities regarding Climate Change Adaptation in Denmark are discontinued (Danish Ministry of Health, 2024).

The national flood risk assessment was carried out by the DCA in 2024, inline with the requirements of the EU Floods Directive (2007). The municipalities that are identified by this risk assessment are legally responsible for preparing risk management plans to manage extreme climate events. This includes the impacts of coastal and riverine flooding on human health, cultural heritage, economic activities and the environment. For the first time this risk assessment identified the Roskilde Fjord area (including its connection to the nearby Arresø

lake) as a high-risk zone, related mainly to coastal flooding, urban areas, and economic impacts¹. The region is indicated in orange on the map of Zealand, Denmark (Figure 5). This means that the five municipalities for the first time will have a strong incentive to work together on the flood risk management plan, although responsibilities will remain within the individual municipalities. Although this was a development during the course of the project, it reaffirmed the initial focus on the potential for intermunicipal exchange and collaboration between these agencies through the RWL.

Figure 5: Organisation of the emergency management services and the municipalities in the Roskilde Fjord (Right) and the area of the Roskilde Fjord that is now allocated for risk assessment in the Floods Directive (left).

3.1.1.2 Governance and Institutional Context

Legal framework

The core piece of legislation for Danish DRM at the national level, is the Emergency Management Act that was implemented in 2009. This Act sets out the responsibilities for DRM at the national, regional, and municipal level. Part 5 establishes that municipal councils are responsible for preparing an overall emergency management plan. This Act also highlights that the key responder for emergencies is the fire and rescue services, this occurs initially at the municipal level and then at the national level for large-scale events.

The governance structure for implementing the DRM framework is set out through the Danish Crisis Management System. The purpose of this system is to set out how agencies and organisations at different levels of government coordinate and respond to emergencies. This system sets out the “preconditions for a resolute and coordinated government response to handle crisis, disaster or catastrophes...”.² This system can be used at any level (municipal, regional or national) and the response required will depend on the size, complexity and impact of the event. At the municipal level the crisis management should be handled directly at the incident scene. The municipal crisis management staff include

¹ <https://oversvømmelse.kyst.dk/> [25.09.2025]

² <https://www.fmn.dk/en/topics/national-tasks/the-danish-crisis-management-system/> [10.09.2025]

representations from local Police, the Danish Defence, the Home Guard, DEMA and both regional and municipal authorities.³ At the regional level the crisis management transfers to the local crisis management staff, who belong to the 12 regional police districts, and is led by the local police director. Their role is to coordinate the response of emergency management services. Finally, at the national level, the crisis should be managed through the national crisis management organisation and National Operational Staff (NOST). The national level usually becomes involved if the event covers multiple police districts or if it is considered to have reached the scale/complexity of a national emergency. At this stage, NOST will facilitate operational coordination. This will involve the Danish Defence Command, DEMA, and representatives at the executive level. The Danish Crisis Management System also identifies the police as having the coordinating responsibility when there are several different agencies involved in an event. This includes the first responders and fire departments, such as the Frederiksborg Brand og Redning, the Roskilde Brandvæsen and the Lejre Brandvæsen.

In 2008, the Danish government established the National Adaptation Strategy (NAS) which is also referred to as Denmark's Strategy for Adaptation to a Changing Climate. The NAS addresses climate change from a governmental level and aids the eleven most vulnerable sectors. This includes technical support for the development of local adaptation plans, and fostered the creation of the "Klimatilpasning.dk" (the national adaptation portal). Klimatilpasning.dk is a consolidated site for citizens to find all information regarding climate adaptation and disaster preparedness in Denmark. Although the national level government provides technical support and advice, under NAS the adaptation planning is delegated to the municipalities. There have been several iterations of NAS since 2008, all increasing the responsibilities and authorities of the municipalities to adapt to increased weather extremes and implement mitigation measures (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023).

In 2012, the Danish government enacted the National Action Plan (NAP) to further "climate proof" Denmark by ensuring that adaptation was taking place at the appropriate levels of society. The NAP states that it is a societal responsibility to limit the adverse effects of climate change and established a regulatory framework for local Climate Change Adaptation. This framework resulted in the Planning Act, the Floods Act, the Act on Water Courses, the Water Supply Act, and the Environmental Act. These were well received by the municipalities who later agreed to carry out risk assessments and adaptation plans monitored by the Ministry of Environment (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023).

In 2018, the Planning Act created a legal obligation for municipalities to consider flooding revisions and coastal erosion. Previously, this aspect of climate change was not a part of municipal adaptation plans. In later revisions, the Danish government provided official guidelines to ensure compliance. By 2019, the Climate Act was signed into law, which created a legally binding target for the reduction of GHG by 70% by 2030 and net-zero by 2050. Currently, the Danish Government is trying to push this goal forward to 2045, but as of

³ <https://www.fmn.dk/en/topics/national-tasks/the-danish-crisis-management-system/> [10.09.2025]

now it is not legally binding. This was the first overarching climate change document in Denmark.

Furthermore, in 2021, the government enacted the Service Level Act making wastewater companies responsible for enacting flood risk adaptation to mitigate the impacts of heavy rains. Recently in October 2023, the government launched their Climate Adaptation Action Plan 1, which established new national initiatives regarding management of high groundwater levels, guidance for municipalities on environmental considerations, and coastal protection to protect vital infrastructure.⁴

The Danish legal framework also incorporates the EU Floods Directive (2007), which was implemented through the Danish Flood Risk Act 2009. This Act sets out the processes for identifying risk flood areas, mapping flood hazards and risks in these areas, and developing the corresponding risk management plans.

The legal framework was a point of discussion in the first RWL 1 workshop in March 2023, where participants expressed a desire for better emergency management plans or plans for continuous operation. During the “World-Café” exercise in this workshop, the need for improved emergency management plans alongside daily practice was highlighted. As well as a need for greater focus on long-term planning and the connection between DRM/CCA and urban planning.

Denmark’s substantial frameworks have led to an assessment that Denmark’s legal framework to enable DRM/CCA is reasonably developed and has been given a rating of 4 (Low Priority). This has been identified as a Low Priority as Denmark’s framework is reasonably developed, and it is beyond the scope of DIRECTED to amend or introduce new legal frameworks including legislation, plans and policies.

<p>Legal Framework: To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM & CCA integration?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Clarity of roles and responsibilities

The government agency for managing disasters at the national level is the DEMA. This agency sits under the Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness and works to “*prepare society for, prevent and respond to crises, accidents and disasters*”.⁵ This is a recent change, as before August 2024, DEMA worked under the Ministry of Defence. The Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness (Ministeriet for Samfundssikkerhed og Beredskab) was created in August 2024, and will oversee DEMA and the new Agency for Resilience responsible for cybersecurity and digital information security, and coordinating responsibility for crisis

⁴ <https://eng.klimatilpasning.dk/national-adaptation/climate-adaptation-in-denmark> [23.09.2025]

⁵ <https://www.brs.dk/en/> [10.09.2025]

management and supply security.⁶ DEMA and its related responsibilities, including state rescue services and strategic emergency planning, have been transferred from the Ministry of Defence to this new Ministry. DEMA has regional agencies with staff that can be activated during an event as needed. DEMA relies on data and information from DMI.

DEMA's role in DRM is to focus on contingency planning for municipalities, and training of personnel. DEMA supports local communities by offering training courses for disaster preparedness, ranging from national crisis management to on-scene incident commanders. To ensure the functionality of these roles, a National Risk Assessment is conducted every 4–5 years, which is then published in the National Risk Profile Report. This was previously undertaken by DEMA, but was moved to the new Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness in January 2025. DEMA also advises the authorities on questions arising in relation to the fire and rescue services. As DEMA has limited response resources they can determine where these go, particularly for large-scale events which impact more than one municipality. If a municipality requests resources, DEMA can refuse if they decide that the resources are needed more elsewhere.

As introduced above, NOST was established in 2005, and their purpose was to strengthen the relationships and coordination between defence, police, and other civilian authorities during emergencies. The new Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness is now responsible for NOST, moving it from the police and Ministry of Justice to this new ministry in August 2024.

The Emergency Management Act 2009 clearly identifies that the fire and rescue services have a key role in responding to/managing events, this includes to “*prevent, limit and redress personal injury and damage to property and the environment arising from accidents, disasters and catastrophes...*” (Part 1(1)). There are fire and rescue services at both the municipal and national level. At the national level this service is managed by DEMA as set out in Part 2(5) of the Emergency Management Act, whilst at the municipal level the service belongs under the municipal council (Part 3(9)). There can be coordination between two or more municipal councils for their fire and rescue services, as set out in Part 3(10). However, there is no formal mechanism to support this collaboration. Discussions with the RWL highlighted that any collaboration between (neighbouring) municipalities will be at their own initiative, as it is beyond the formal/legal requirements.

Incident response sits at the municipal level and the incident commanders include police, health and fire. The police are the responsible authority for managing incident command.⁷ The municipal fire and rescue service is immediately managed by an emergency management commission who is appointed by the municipal council, as set out in Part 3(9)(2) of the Emergency Management Act. It is up to the municipal council to decide who

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<https://mssb.dk/nyheder/2025/januar/ministeriet-for-samfundssikkerhed-og-beredskab-omorganiseres/> [22.09.2025]

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<https://www.brs.dk/globalassets/brs--beredskabsstyrelsen/dokumenter/indsats--retningslinjer-o.l/2023/-retningslinjer-for-indsatsledelse-.pdf> [22.09.2025]

sits on the commission and which tasks the commission will undertake. The Act specifies that the commission must have an uneven number of members and must include the mayor (who acts as the chairman), the police commissioner, and a majority elected by the municipal council. The commission also needs to have a representative of volunteers.

The national fire and rescue service can assist the municipal service for events that are beyond the capacity of the municipality, either due to the scale, geographical size or complexity of the event (Part 2 (7) Emergency Management Act). For managing large-scale events, the deployment of the fire and rescue services will be coordinated by the police commissioner (Part 4). The police commissioner is responsible for “*the sounding of alerts and warnings, cordoning off, evacuation and other necessary measures*” (Part 4 (17)(2)).

The police also hold an important role in Denmark's DRM and emergency response. Denmark has 12 police districts, each of which have a Local Operational Staffs team (LOS) led by the chief of police. The purpose of the LOS is to coordinate emergency preparedness tasks. Some areas are covered by more than one police district, for example the Roskilde Fjord area is covered by two police districts (Nordsjællands Politi og Midt- og Vestsjællands Politi).

As introduced above, the responsibility for emergency management (DRM) planning sits at the municipal level, as set out in Part 5 of the Emergency Management Act. Once the plans are drafted, they are sent to DEMA to be checked. There is no requirement for municipalities to adopt the advice/recommendations from DEMA, however interviews with stakeholders (April, 2024) have highlighted that in practice this feedback is usually taken on board. As part of Halsnæs Municipality's emergency preparedness plan the decision was made to include “action cards” which are related to high water levels. These action cards set out roles and responsibilities (who does what and when, who is responsible in various situations). These are an important resource as they identified the roles and responsibilities for various situations, for example if the wind blows from the south or if the water rises above 1m, as well as for different warning levels, for example green or yellow.

In Denmark, the municipalities are primarily responsible for CCA and are considered to be the Climate Adaptation Authority. This is part of a decentralised system for CCA, which stems from a recognition by the government that municipalities are best connected with local issues. Municipalities are responsible for planning and prioritizing climate adaptation efforts like erosion, flood risk management, and adaptation of sewage systems to ensure responsible land use. There are also a number of roles involved in modelling, as flood modelling and mapping is required for specific coastal and riverine areas under the EU Floods Directive (2007). For flood mapping in relation to the Floods Directive, the DCA are responsible. These are to be used for the appointed municipalities' Flood Risk Management Plans (FRMPs). In Denmark, it is the municipalities who develop the FRMPs due to the decentralisation-principle, while the DCA are responsible for providing the flood maps for this. For the FRMPs the municipalities have to use the flood maps by DCA for this purpose, but can also use other maps. For CCA, the municipalities can use the national flood maps the government (both EPA, DCA and the Agency for Climate Data (Klimadatastyrelsen)) provide,

but can also use other maps. If they want to use other maps, they are responsible for creating them themselves.

The DCA, has been a part of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) under the Ministry of Environment since August 2024. This ministry has the overall responsibility for CCA in Denmark, providing guidelines, legislation and data for the municipalities’ climate adaptation. DCA and EPA are also responsible for advising the government on issues related to CCA. Additionally, DCA is responsible for both the planning and implementation of coastal protection on the West Coast of Jutland. The coastal protection on the West Coast is funded in collaboration with the affected municipalities. This is due to the large exposure of the West Coast to the North Sea and potential coastal retreat of an average of 8 m/yr in some areas.⁸ DCA is also responsible for implementing EU Floods Directive in Denmark, where DCA performs the preliminary flood risk assessment for appointing the Areas of Potential Significant Flood Risk (APSFRs). The APSFRs are officially appointed by the Minister of Environment. In the APSFRs, the DCA is responsible for the more detailed flood hazard and flood risk mapping, which are then used by the municipalities to develop their FRMPs. DCA is responsible for developing guidelines for the FRMPs, collecting the plans and making a coordinated plan for each river basin district.

Discussions with stakeholders highlighted a lack of clarity at the municipal level around how coordination mechanisms across municipalities operate. They also indicated that there are no coordination mechanisms supporting joint CCA planning. Some municipalities pointed to potential legislation which will address the distribution of protection responsibilities in vulnerable coastal areas highly exposed to storm surges (Pancioli et al., 2024).

The legal framework clearly places the responsibility for DRM and CCA at the municipal level. Although there is support at the national level through DEMA for DRM. Based on this evidence, the question has been assessed at 4 (Low Priority), as the clarity of roles and responsibilities within the Danish DRM/CCA framework are reasonably developed. This has been identified as Low Priority as it is beyond the scope of the RWL/DIRECTED to amend/introduce new legal frameworks.

<p>Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities for DRM & CCA clear/functional within the legal framework?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Functionality of roles and responsibilities

Discussions with stakeholders have revealed that the identified roles and responsibilities are functional in practice to a certain extent. For example, municipalities are supported by the police and fire departments. In Roskilde, some of the decision-making powers for emergency

⁸ <https://kyst.dk/klimatilpasning/faellesaftaler/faellesaftale-lodbjerg-nymindegab> [22.09.25]

response have been delegated to the fire department, so that they are empowered to help further with disaster response. The mayor made a choice to delegate this power, they were not required to do this and the delegation is not necessarily the same for other municipalities. This means that when the person with this delegated power is put onto a team with the police, they act as a municipality representation (not a fire department representative). The Roskilde fire department is embedded in the municipality and has a seat on the emergency management commission.

Discussions with stakeholders also highlighted that some municipalities have good working relationships with their emergency services, including between municipalities. However, this is not universal. The trend appears to be that urban municipalities are more used to having to work with other municipalities/agencies, so the relationships are stronger, in comparison to more rural municipalities.

The response phase involves cooperation from a number of different agencies, as there is no single response decision-maker. Instead, each decision is made by separate agencies. For example, the decision to close schools and the decision to evacuate are made by the different organisations with this specialty normally. This means that there are lots of decision-makers, and it is unclear how these decisions/decision-makers are coordinated based on the framework. Discussions with stakeholders, suggested that the coordination relies on pre-existing relationships rather than the formal roles and responsibilities in practice.

Making responsibilities clear and delegating powers are decisions for the municipalities. These are not required by any statute or mandate. Discussions with stakeholders highlighted that during joint agency/municipality practical exercises it would quickly become clear who was unsure of their decision-making mandates and who holds responsibility. From this perspective, it appears that the roles/responsibilities are not working in practice, unless the people involved are willing to go above and beyond the legislative frameworks. This highlights that the functionality of the roles and responsibilities is more to do with the relationships between the different agencies/municipalities, rather than the functionality of the role itself.

Based on this evidence, it appears that the functionality of the roles and responsibilities in practice is an area where there is potential for growth. Consequently, the roles and responsibilities require further clarity to be functional for DRM/CCA in practice. Currently, the definition around roles and responsibilities is coming from the municipalities/agencies and their own plans/relationships/relationship building, rather than the legal frameworks. For this reason, this question has been assessed as a 2 (Low Priority). It has been tagged as Low Priority as it is beyond the scope of this project as it requires adjustment of the legal frameworks.

Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities **functional** for DRM/CCA in practice?

2 [LP]

Multi-level and polycentric Governance

This region is characterized by a large number of municipalities that are formally independent, but highly interdependent in practice. Within the Danish system, the role of the national government is to ensure consistency with EU rules/regulations/frameworks. The national level government also provides funding to the local (municipal) level, who are then able to decide how this funding is best spent to address the needs of their region. The municipalities can also decide which adaptive measures are best suited for their region. This autonomy is important as different regions face different challenges for CCA and require tailored plans and measures.

Issues around how the different levels of governance work in practice were highlighted during the Cologne General Assembly RWL World-Café held in September 2024. A practical issue that was raised was that although decisions for DRM/CCA are made at the municipal level, often the boundaries for these areas do not match the river catchments or coastlines. Moreover, there is currently no governance mechanism that facilitates inter-municipal dialogue and decision-making between municipalities. A multi-level collaboration would help to address the mismatch between municipality boundaries and catchment/coastlines, and facilitate exchange between DRM and CCA actors. Issues around financing for this model were also raised as the current system is considered not to be fit-for-purpose. The focus on municipalities carrying out projects means that there are no 'joint funds' available to support activities that could be implemented across municipalities. This puts municipalities in a tricky situation as there is a lack of sufficient financing at municipal level for funding large scale coastal protection or flood protection infrastructure. Municipalities can apply to the coastal protection fund for joint coastal protection projects.⁹ However, the fund is not large enough to cover the whole coast for a common flood protection measure. Additionally, the fund will only cover building costs, but the municipalities will also need support with the whole planning phase including paying for consultancies to provide detailed projections, mapping effects on the environment and more.

The different actor roles at different levels appear to be working reasonably to support integrated DRM/CCA, although gaps/weaknesses within this system were identified. This indicator has been assessed as a 4 (High Priority) as it has been reasonably developed but more support for more collaboration between municipalities and emergency management across boundaries is a priority.

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<https://stateofgreen.com/en/news/danish-government-presents-plan-to-ramp-up-climate-adaptation/> [10.09.2025]

<p>Multilevel/Polycentric Governance: To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM and CCA processes?</p>	<p>4 [HP]</p>
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Accountability

The decision-making power for emergency response in Denmark is not held by a single person (like a mayor), but is instead spread across a number of different decision-makers. This follows the “sector-responsibility” principle, which states that *“the department or agency that has the daily responsibility for a given sector retains responsibility for that sector during [a] crisis”* (Danish Emergency Management Agency 2021) This means that these different decision-makers are accountable for their decisions made during emergency response. For example, school directors will make decisions around closing schools.

Following this approach, it is critical to know who has the responsibility for making decisions during emergency response. Discussions with RWL stakeholders highlighted that it is not always clear who is responsible for certain decisions, and therefore it is unclear who is accountable for these decisions. Clarifying who is responsible (and accountable) for which decisions, is a role for the municipalities/agencies. Although there will be some level of accountability, because these decision-makers will be making choices as part of their role within the public service.

Another issue around accountability that was highlighted at the Cologne General Assembly (GA) RWL World-Café in September 2024, was the lack of clarity in the legal frameworks about whether one municipality can ‘force’ another municipality (who collects funds from local taxpayers) to pay for coastal or upstream flood protection infrastructure.

Although it does not appear that accountability concerns are hampering decision-making for DRM/CCA, it is also unclear how accountability is managed for these decisions. For this reason this indicator has been assessed as being a 3 (Low Priority). It has been tagged as Low Priority as it has not been identified as a priority by the RWL, and is beyond the scope of this project.

<p>Accountability: To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support decision-making DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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3.1.1.3 Risk Management/Knowledge

DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence

Municipalities are responsible for creating their own emergency plans, so that they can ensure that these plans are tailored to their specific region. This means that each municipality can have different goals for DRM/CCA. The focus of these goals can also be different, as some municipalities focus on broad overarching goals like aiding the community, whilst others focus on smaller and more concrete goals. Regardless, 63% of municipalities have indicated that they have a deadline to adapt and create a climate resilient region by 2050.¹⁰

In 2019, Realdania initiated the DK2020 project, which aimed to meet the goals of the Paris Agreement at the municipal level. This project is a partnership involving municipalities, the five Danish regions and Realdania. DK2020 supports municipalities throughout Denmark in:

“developing, upgrading or adjusting their existing work on climate action to global best practice, and in ultimately developing climate action plans in line with the 1.5 degree goal in the Paris Agreement.”¹¹

This has made Denmark the first country where municipalities are creating climate action plans in line with the targets of the Paris Agreement. The climate action plans developed with the support of DK2020 comply with C40’s Cities Climate Transition Framework (formerly the Climate Action Planning Framework). This common methodological framework partially limits divergence and supports coherence across municipal climate action plans. While municipalities still set their own targets and priorities, DK2020 ensures a minimum level of coherence and provides a common reporting structure.¹² Although Realdania has a good framework and support that makes the plans coherent among municipalities, it does not appear to be as strong for the implementation phase, as responsibilities and funding streams are fragmented, instruments are mostly non-binding, and delivery capacity varies widely. In addition, the intermunicipal coordination is a structural weakness, since collaboration is voluntary and incentives for joint delivery are weak, which leads to sub-scale projects and uneven outcomes.

There could also be greater support at the national level to improve policy/plan coherence for DRM as there is a lack of national legislation and financial regulation to develop intermunicipal coordination and collaboration. Discussions with the RWL have highlighted emergency plans that are considered to be adequate but sometimes outdated. One example was given of plans missing recent infrastructural flood protection updates. Another example is that there are different warning levels/systems used by the different municipalities, even

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https://concito.dk/files/media/document/Adaptation_approaches_in_Danish_municipalities_climate_action_plans_2024.02.05_red.pdf [15.09.2025]

¹¹ <https://www.realdania.org/whatwedo/grants-and-projects/dk2020> [15.09.2025]

¹² <https://www.realdania.org/whatwedo/grants-and-projects/dk2020> [15.09.2025]

when they are covered by the same emergency agency. This is an area that could be standardized (Pancioli et al., 2024). Furthermore, there is a lack of systematic coordination or communication mechanism in place to support cross-municipality coordination when developing their emergency plans. This is problematic when events can impact, and require, a response from more than one municipality. Another opportunity for further collaboration is post-event, as currently municipalities have different methods of evaluating the event/response. This may be an opportunity for a more systematic evaluation system to be developed among recovery actors. Collecting data and undertaking analysis during the recovery is critical for informing future CCA strategies (Pancioli et al., 2024).

A lack of coherence becomes problematic when an event impacts more than one municipality, as there is no single incident management system for events which impact the entire Fjord. This has practical consequences as the municipalities differ in terms of structure and capacity. An example used was Fredriksborg Fire and Rescue, which covers five different municipalities. This creates additional organisational challenges compared to services that cover just one municipality.

Discussions with the RWL also highlighted the difficulties with linking CCA to DRM plans. In particular, there is a lack of resources to support coordination between areas, this in turn impacts DRM operations and prioritisation. This is due to resources being primarily related to the national level buy-in and prioritisation of DRM/CCA. Consequently, in areas where national buy-in is limited, there is a lack of resources. This prioritization is then linked back to political issues.

Several strategies for improving this coherence have been suggested during discussions with the RWL, including the need to improve emergency plans and long-term planning including exploring the coherence and coordination of the existing plans, and by incorporating risk information from the local levels. This could include identifying vulnerable infrastructure such as dikes, bridges, or unprotected buildings.

Although there does appear to be a level of coherence in plans/policies to address CCA challenges through the DK2020 project, there seems to be a lack of coordination between CCA and DRM plans. Concerns have also been raised about the implementation of the climate action plans. For this reason, this question has been assessed as being 3 (Medium Priority). It has been tagged as being of Medium Priority as it is an issue that is relevant to the RWL and should be considered, but it has not been highlighted as one of their high priorities.

<p>DRM/CCA policy/plan coherence: To what extent do objectives/goals and in plans at different levels align to address DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Synergies and tradeoffs

Discussions with municipality stakeholders highlighted two examples where synergies have been maximized and trade-offs minimized across DRM/CCA interventions. Firstly, in the Roskilde municipality, the decision was made to undertake a CCA intervention following a number of storms. The decision was made to construct a flood wall between the harbour and a row of buildings which were immediately adjacent to the harbour. These buildings encompassed both residential properties and other recreational buildings (rowing clubs etc). It was decided that a flood wall would be constructed, with green spaces planted in the area between the wall and the properties. The wall is high enough to prevent water from entering from the harbour and flooding houses, but not too high that it impedes the view of the houses. The view was a critical point of contention for this CCA strategy, as the view is the main reason that the houses were purchased, and losing the view would have a significant impact on the house value. Paths were also constructed between the houses and the harbour with slotted gates at the end of the paths. These were created so that other panels could be slotted into these gates for an event to make the wall a complete barrier. This CCA initiative was funded 50-50 between the municipality and a group of citizens. These citizens are the people/organisations whose buildings were impacted by the flooding and have now been protected by the wall. The amount paid was based on the size of the property/land and how it would be impacted. It is estimated that each household/property owner paid €20,000 into this floodwall scheme.

Furthermore, in Roskilde, the Harbour Park will be a place of multiple climate-adaptation functions. Firstly, the Viking Ship Museum will be relocated to a higher level in the Harbour area in a facility designed to withstand sea-level rise, elevated groundwater, and more frequent extreme weather events. This is an important move as the museum currently depends on expensive temporary water tubes to be installed when there is a storm alert in order to manage the risk of flooding. This shifts investment toward CCA and reduces the dependence on DRM measures and personnel. Secondly, the redesign will ensure that cloudburst water from some elevated central Roskilde streets will be conveyed directly to the port. This has been done in connection with a hydraulic analysis for a large-scale drainage channel which is being conducted between the roads and the fjord. The city Climate Plan also identifies the construction of a new dike with a longitudinal depression to pass cloudburst water to the fjord.

Another example is in Halsnæs Municipality at the northeast of Roskilde Fjord, where the utility company and the municipality collaborated to adapt and ensure resilience to extreme weather events. The interventions included a flood gate with built-in pumps and upgrading a dike to protect the surrounding areas from flooding and the wastewater treatment plant being overwhelmed. This was funded 25% by the utility company and 75% by the municipality, with an agreement in place for the utility company to manage the flood gate operation. By having built in pumps, they no longer risk the police deciding to reallocate such resources during a large-scale event. These measures also reduce the need for the municipality to implement evacuations which relied on support from the emergency services.

Figure 6: Flood gate at Halsnæs Municipality and flood wall at Roskilde Municipality.

Another instructive case is Frederikssund. For years the town centre has depended on temporary watertubes and sandbags, but in June 2024 the council approved a permanent coastal-protection plan covering five stretches of the midtown waterfront (NIRAS & LYTT Architecture, 2024). The scheme replaces ad-hoc measures with a continuous system of sheet-pile flood walls, small dikes, and selective road/terrain raising, plus four closable flood openings that the emergency services install when a storm-surge warning is issued. The crest level is set at +2.50 m, so the defences are designed to meet a 1-in-100-year surge through to 2075. The project is coordinated with utility owners so that protection does not impede drainage, and it keeps the harbour publicly accessible and lively as a place to visit. Overall, the plan aims to secure the town centre against extreme high water while reducing reliance on emergency deployments.

Based on these examples of CCA interventions, this indicator has been assessed as 4 (Low Priority). This has been tagged as Low Priority as it was not one of the priorities identified by the RWL and it is beyond the scope of this project to implement DRMC/CCA interventions.

<p>Synergies/tradeoffs Interventions: To what extent are synergies maximized, and trades-offs minimized, across DRM/CCA interventions?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships

The strength of DRM/CCA relationships was discussed during the March 2023 workshop. Participants explained that they thought that the collaboration/relationship between municipalities and emergency management was quite good. Furthermore, participants said that the collaboration between stakeholders during an extreme weather event is good. However, questions were raised about whether the resourcing in the municipalities was being fully utilised. A suggestion put forward by several participants to strengthen relationships was

to have a simulation of an extreme event which would provide everyone with a joint experience. The value of a joint exercise was raised again during the RWL World-Café exercise at the Cologne GA in September 2024.

In the 2023 workshop, the need for more political awareness around CCA and DRM was highlighted. This relates to the need for more advocacy and national level buy-in (sustained commitment and resourcing). This issue was reiterated in the 2024 GA during which participants identified challenges with vertical communication to the national level of government as well as having to communicate with multiple administrative layers including municipalities, emergency management and regions. Challenges with horizontal communication within municipality departments were also raised.

The RWL acknowledges the importance of building strong relationships, particularly as there is currently no communication mechanism in place between municipalities as they develop their emergency plans. Especially as any cross-municipal relationships tend to rely on personal connections. This is problematic as often hazards are cross border, for example storm surges and water course flooding events that impact more than one municipality (even the whole fjord area). Consequently, the response to the hazard may also need to be cross-border. For example, the Roskilde Fjord area is covered by two police districts (Nordsjællands Politi og Midt- og Vestsjællands Politi). Another practical reason for communication between municipalities is to have plans in place for when events occur on weekends or holidays. During these times municipal employees may not be available, so relationships (and communication) between other DRM actors will be critical. To build this relationship emergency agencies/actors should be provided with information such as updated contact lists and maps before any event occurs.

Discussions with the Municipalities of Egedal, Frederikssund and Halsnæs have highlighted the relationships that have been built between civil protection actors including the collaboration between Egedal Municipality and Frederiksborg Fire and Rescue Service. Although during the interview (April 2024) the challenges of relationship building were identified as one participant stated that *“[c]urrently, it [the relationship] is somewhat superficial, and there is room for improvement, but this depends on economic resources.”*

Discussions with stakeholders at the 2025 General Assembly in Copenhagen also highlighted the actor interaction between DEMA and municipal fire departments. Recently in Roskilde there was a big fire which the fire department initially responded to, they then asked DEMA for resources. Municipalities cannot ask other municipalities directly for additional resources, instead the request needs to go via DEMA, who then facilitates this. In this example DEMA became involved very quickly, and stakeholders reported that this system of requesting resources does not delay their ability to respond, especially as they have a good overview of both their own resources and the resources of their neighbouring municipalities.

Strength of relationship will be even more important moving forward, as the area of Roskilde Fjord was classified as an APSFR under the EU Floods Directive (2007) in December 2024. This means that they will need to develop a FRMP and send it out for public consultation no

later than spring 2027. As there are several municipalities in the APSFR, they can either decide to make one FRMP together, make one each and coordinate them, or make one each and not coordinate them. Relationships will be critical for making this decision, as a more coordinated response would be preferable but this will rely on actors interacting at appropriate levels. In other municipalities that have had the same requirements imposed, there has been improved coordination between CCA and DRM. Furthermore, as part of the FRMP, the municipalities have to consider prevention, protection, and preparedness measures. In the guidelines, the DCA strongly recommended that the municipalities involve relevant stakeholders such as the utility and emergency response in developing the FRMP.

There appears to be semi-developed DRM/CCA relationships at different levels. However, it has been identified by the RWL that these could be strengthened further, and that these relationships tend to be personal rather than formalised. For this reason, this indicator has been assessed as 3 (Medium Priority). It has been tagged as Medium Priority which is relevant for the RWL as the ability of DRM/CCA actor roles at different levels to interact was highlighted throughout the initial DIRECTED meetings.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent do DRM/CCA actors interact at appropriate levels?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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As identified in the section above, many of the relationships between DRM/CCA actors are personal rather than formalised. This reflects a willingness/openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements. During the RWL workshop in March 2023, the participants identified a desire to participate in in-person workshops at least twice a year. In addition, participants were open to attending online meetings/webinars between the in-person workshops. The possibility of bilateral meetings with the Capital Region of Denmark and DTU was also raised and accepted.

Participants at the 2023 Cologne GA also discussed the lack of emergency management exercises. In particular, a lack of regular exercises to work through different scenarios. The discussions also raised issues around clear action plans for different protection levels. A suggestion made to rectify this would be for the RWL to run an emergency management exercise based around an extreme climate event which has large-scale impact. This would involve all of the different RWL participants. This exercise would help to ensure that all the actors are aware of the procedures, actions, roles and responsibilities that everyone has.

Due to a lack of formal requirements for collaboration, relationships need to be stronger and between more actors so that the connections between different DRM/CCA agencies remain even if there is staff turnover. The participants discussed the consequence of being over reliant on one person to hold knowledge across a range of areas at the municipal level (Cologne GA, 2023). This type of relationship is highly dependent on the motivation and commitment of individuals who choose to ‘span boundaries’ and make

connections/collaborations outside of their formal role or responsibilities. An alternative would be to build a culture of collaboration and learning, this includes skill building capacity, and knowledge exchange between municipalities and emergency management actors. Another point raised was the importance of 'boundary spanning' roles. An example shared during the workshop was the benefit of having a PhD student who worked across different agencies, as this enabled them to be familiar with different data/tools, understand the various perspectives, and present solutions to the municipality.

Discussions with RWL stakeholders have highlighted practice examples where there has been a high level of willingness/openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements. This was raised during the World-Café exercise during the 2023 RWL workshop participants in relation to the collaboration between Lejre Municipality and Lejre Brandvæsen, which goes beyond formal requirements. As part of this collaboration, Lejre Brandvæsen has taken an active role in helping to shape the CCA plan of Lejre Municipality. Another example is the creation of the Water Management Centre at the Roskilde Fire Department. This centre was built to simulate flood scenarios in a controlled environment and is used to train emergency response teams as well as test flood equipment. This initiative took 8 years to build and required public-private cooperation. There was no funding available for this centre, so fundraising was required. Carrying out exercises using this centre allows for relationship building and knowledge sharing between municipalities and emergency response agencies, as well as connecting public and private enterprises. All of this relationship building/collaboration is beyond the legal requirements, and is the initiative of individuals. These relationships take years to develop. The Roskilde Fire Department also has connections with the chiefs/leaders of the different organisations, including access to the private sector. This gives them an excellent opportunity to give insights on new developments from a hazard/risk perspective and help to ensure that developers are considering the impacts of climate change.

Another example of collaboration is between Halsnæs Municipality and a local steel works. The municipality had identified a potential future scenario where (during an extreme weather event) the sea comes through the steel works and into the city. The municipality has developed a relationship with the steel works to put/create a temporary dike in the steel works. There is an agreement for the municipality to go in and create the dike, but this has not been tested yet.

This RWL has shown a strong willingness/openness to collaborate beyond formal roles/requirements. Although, this is an area that can always be strengthened. This question has been assessed as 4 (Medium Priority) as this is a relatively developed area. It has been tagged as Medium Priority, this is an area of focus that will be worked on further through engagement with the DIRECTED project.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent is there willingness/openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements?</p>	<p>4 [MP]</p>
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Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools

For imminent flood threats, the DMI provides municipalities with weather and water level forecasts alongside warnings, which are usually sent as documents supplemented with simple flood maps. However, the need for accuracy, precision and timeliness of this data was raised in workshops (March, 2023) including the need for covering wave heights in forecasts. Municipalities need at least 24-48hrs warning to prepare actions such as activating Fire Departments, filling and rolling out watertubes, or closing flood gates. The uncertainty associated with the forecast was also raised because several centimeters difference in forecasted water levels will determine which actions should be taken. Additionally, there is a general need for more real-time information sharing between municipalities proactively ahead of events, and improved measuring stations to validate models.

Overall, no common pluvial/fluvial flood model exists for climate adaptation and there is a lack of standardisation. The existing flood modelling and mapping capacities at municipalities for climate adaptation planning are limited, varied, and typically based on freely available and government supported models and tools like the national hydrological model (DK-model), Danish Climate Atlas (Klimaatlas¹³), and the Climate Adaptation and Land Use (Klimatilpasning mapping KAMP¹⁴). The municipalities use the Klimaatlas for adaptation planning showing future changes in temperature, precipitation, extreme precipitation, relative sea level and storm surge heights but not flooding. Klimaatlas offers climate projections for multiple scenarios, and stakeholders reported a challenge that it is not always clear which climate change scenario and time horizon they should use. Discussions with the RWL have highlighted that these discrepancies have created uncertainties around these models. Municipalities (September 2023 Workshop) highlighted the need for alignment across municipal maps and models and a standard for climate scenarios. However, guidelines around the use of climate scenarios are available from DMI, first published in 2018 and updated in January 2025 with DMI and the EPA (Danish Meteorological Institute, 2025).

Private consultants like SCALGO offer more detailed and accurate flood mapping solutions but depend on the resources being available in the municipalities to use them. Stakeholders highlighted a need for models that assess the consequences of coupled events (high water levels in the Roskilde Fjord area in combination with heavy rainfall and increased river discharge). However, this is a challenge as these are generated for different purposes and by different consultants.

¹³ <https://www.dmi.dk/klima-atlas/data-i-klimaatlas?paramtype=temp&maptype=kom> [10.09.2025]

¹⁴ [KAMP - et Klimatilpasning- og Arealanvendelsesværktøj til Miljø- og Planmedarbejdere](#) [10.09.2025]

Since 2020, the DCA also provide risk assessment data related to the EU Floods Directive (2007) mapping requirements with updated calculations of coastal and fluvial flood hazard and risk available through a webGIS portal¹⁵ and through Kystplanlægger (Coastal Planner)¹⁶ including for coastal flooding and erosion hazard and risk data for 2020, 2070 and 2120, which uses a separate webGIS portal¹⁷. Since 2024, the Roskilde Fjord is an APSFR under the EU Floods Directive, meaning that the DCA will develop new flood modelling for the area by the end of 2025, which should be used to inform planning for the area by municipalities, offering an opportunity for intermunicipal collaboration around data sharing and interoperability.

KAMP provides a basic screening tool for climate adaptation that can support the municipalities' planning work by giving the individual employee a comprehensive overview of both area data (buildings, nature, conservation areas, planning areas, low-lying areas, etc.) and impact data (including flood maps, sea level rise, near-surface groundwater, etc.) without prior knowledge of models and advanced GIS. It does include pluvial flood mapping from a bluespot calculation that typically overestimates. It also integrates some groundwater data from the national level available from the Agency for Climate Data and EPA through HIP - Hydrologisk Informations og Prognosesystem¹⁸ showing the expected water level above/below sea level. Other more advanced impact assessment tools like the DTU Cost-Benefit Assessment Model are available but typically not used by municipalities. The tool represents a comprehensive bottom-up approach developed specifically for Danish coastal flooding risk assessment integrating highly detailed Danish GIS information on land use, infrastructure, traffic, buildings, population, industry, public services, tourism, recreational values, and biodiversity. Its depth damage cost functions are derived for 10 sectors including buildings, roads, health, tourism, public service, ecosystem, etc., and each function is estimated by using detailed data.

¹⁵ <https://gis.nst.dk/portal/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=d7ea2181f1f84d3dadffc3de3c2e76d5> [10.09.2025]

¹⁶ <https://kystplanlaegger.dk/> [10.09.2025]

¹⁷ <https://gis.nst.dk/portal/apps/experiencebuilder/experience/?id=6ffe5a471a584bd38f6fa7fc78cbf99b> [10.09.2025]

¹⁸ <https://hip.dataforsyningen.dk/> [10.09.2025]

Figure 7: Klimaatlas mapping of the Region of Denmark.

Figure 8: Klimatilpasning mapping of the Region of Denmark (KAMP Model).

Overall, the Capital Region of Denmark has a number of models available, but there is a strong desire for improvement. Based on this evidence, this question has been assessed as being 4 (High Priority) as it is an area which is reasonably developed and is High Priority to advance through the RWL activities.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent are (existing) risk modelling data/models/tools fit-for-purpose to address key DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>4 [HP]</p>
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One of the challenges with publicly available data, models and tools from the national level is the multitude of platforms. Overall, there is an openness to embrace new technology to improve accuracy, timeliness, and integration of multiple data sources. However, this desire is constrained by institutional human and financial resources in municipalities. As highlighted above, some municipalities are using more innovative tools such as the SCALGO Live model, which is a hydrodynamic flood modelling tool that supports event-based modelling for rapid flood assessments and allows users to test specific measures. This SCALGO model is similar in design to the SaferPlaces tool used in DIRECTED. SaferPlaces can help to visualise the impacts and embed remote sensing data (post-event data). RIM2D model is also incorporated; it is a two-dimensional hydraulic model that simulates overland water flow and flood extents based on rainfall-runoff dynamics. The central opportunity of the Data Fabric is not to standardize on one tool, but to integrate models with different assumptions and strengths. This ensemble approach enables like-for-like scenario comparisons, makes uncertainty explicit (across model structures and inputs), and provides harmonized outputs to support consistent, cross-municipal analysis and collaboration.

The RWL raised concerns about the lack of experts with the technical skills required to provide the necessary (updated) map information at the municipal level to the Fire Departments/emergency services. Although DMI do have maps combining forecasts and flood mapping, these are not publicly available and only provided to emergency response services, such as the incorporation of groundwater data. A key innovation for the Data Fabric would be to represent the DMI forecasts in a GIS map as inundation of the coastal areas, making these maps more accessible to all municipalities and emergency managers in the region. In response to municipal requests, the platform will also integrate groundwater datasets to support a clearer understanding of subsurface contributions to flood risk. Another innovation is to integrate the SkadesØkonomi, a Damage Cost Assessment Model (DTU) that will be deployed on a shared, easy-to-use platform and driven by an ensemble of three hazard models—RIM2D, SaferPlaces, and SCALGO. This ensemble approach enables uncertainty-aware loss estimates.

For these reasons, this question has been assessed as 3 (High Priority). This has been tagged as High Priority because accessing innovative risk models/data/tools has consistently been a high priority for the Danish RWL.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent can DRM and CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools and interoperability across DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools

Municipalities use Kilmatatlas to support their climate action plans. They can then choose to incorporate further data/models when developing these plans. It is unclear how this works formally, but discussions with RWL stakeholders have identified that in practice, municipalities will rely on/incorporate KlimaAtlas data first and foremost, supplemented by local high resolution data in specific locations.

The recent categorisation of the Roskilde Fjord as an APSFR under the EU Floods Directive, means that this area will now need to develop additional flood risk plans. This provides an opportunity for municipalities to develop a single plan together, or develop their own plans but coordinate them. Both options provide opportunity for collaboration, although this is not a legal requirement. Creating coordinated and cohesive plans would help ensure the consistency of the data across the regions. DCA also needs to create detailed flood maps for this whole area, which will also help to decrease discrepancies around the data used by different municipalities. Discussions with stakeholders have highlighted that other areas that have been identified as APSFR have seen an increase in collaboration.

An issue that arose during the “World-Café” exercise at the 2023 workshop was that often historic data cannot be shared between municipalities due to data laws such as the General Data Protection Regulation. This is a legal norm which hinders sharing data to inform DRM/CCA decision-making.

It is unclear how other legal mindsets or norms may support ‘best’ data/models in DRM/CCA decision-making. For this reason, this indicator has been assessed as 3 (Low Priority). It has been tagged as Low Priority, as it is beyond the scope of the project to change legal mindsets or norms.

<p>Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools: To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support ‘best’ data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation

Denmark facilitates citizen inclusion and participation through an accessible webpage, which provides important climate information, including CCA strategies.¹⁹ Citizens can also use the webpage to request subsidies for CCA measures on their property. This webpage provides

¹⁹ <https://eng.klimatilpasning.dk> [10.09.2025]

information about disaster preparedness strategies and provides access to the KAMP water impact tool. KAMP is a screening tool which showcases different national data, and allows citizens to see which areas are vulnerable to flooding. This tool was developed to assist the municipalities with CCA. Citizens can use the tool to simulate the potential impact of extreme weather on their area. This is available for a range of scenarios including: precipitation in plains, stream flooding, rising groundwater level, and increased seawater level. KAMP also gives citizens projections regarding erosion, renaturing procedures, and future projections. This tool even maps landslide activity, so that the public is able to adequately prepare for increasing climate risks.²⁰ Although this webpage enables data and information to be made available to citizens, it is unclear that it empowers citizens to have a role in decision-making.

Theoretically, citizens are able to become involved in decision-making through the ‘citizen’s initiative’.²¹ This mechanism was introduced in 2018 to provide citizens with a way to put an item of interest on the parliamentary agenda. However, for this to be successful it requires the support of 50,000 people. There does not appear to be an explicit legal requirement in Denmark to enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making.

In the September 2023 workshop, participants acknowledged that the municipality’s CCA plans would be strengthened through the incorporation of knowledge from the emergency services. Further experience and knowledge can be gained through citizen involvement, in order to guide municipal CCA strategies/measures. In this workshop, another point that was raised was the need for the public to have access to the data platform.

For these reasons, this question has been assessed as a 2 (Low Priority), as this is an area where there is potential for growth. This question has been tagged as Low Priority, as it is beyond the scope of this project to amend frameworks to enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent do frameworks enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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As the Danish frameworks appear to lack a requirement for citizen involvement in decision-making, this will instead fall to DRM/CCA actors who are willing to enhance citizen participation. The Roskilde flood wall is an example of a climate change intervention that involved citizens in the decision-making. The Coastal Flood Protection Act states that those who benefit from a coastal protection measure must pay for it. Consequently, citizens are always involved in coastal protection.

²⁰ <https://eng.klimatilpasning.dk/tools> [10.09.2025]

²¹ <https://www.thedanishparliament.dk/news/2018/02/citizens-initiative> [10.09.2025]

In general, it is the responsibility of the landowner to protect themselves against flooding. The municipalities have responsibility for making the overall plans and take responsibility when there are areas of municipal-interest at stake as well (such as city centres). However, municipalities can also say that they do not want to be involved in a process, and then it is only up to the landowner(s) to plan and pay for the CCA measure. For some larger-scale measures (e.g. coastal protection) the landowner is not allowed to just do it, but have to apply for permission to build, for example a sea wall, even if it is only located on their own land. The landowner can also be denied permission to build the coastal protection if there are arguments raised against it. For example, it has negative effects downstream or the proposed solution would not work in practice. Normally, the municipality would have dialogue with the landowner(s) about the solution, to find a common ground.²²

In the Roskilde wall example, citizen feedback was taken onboard and was reflected in the height of the wall built (so that it did not impact the view of the harbour from the houses) and the integration of the slotted gates/paths so that the houses could still access the harbour from their houses.

Citizens can also be involved in DRM through volunteering. Volunteers can be at both the national/municipal level. Discussions with RWL stakeholders highlighted the growing relationship between emergency services and civil society, in particular the Danish Red Cross. This has been identified as a good way to manage spontaneous volunteers, as the Red Cross can organise these volunteers and ensure that they are deployed where needed. Municipalities/emergency response agencies do appear to encourage the involvement of volunteers for DRM. However, it is unclear if this extends to citizen involvement in decision-making.

There does appear to be a level of willingness for actors to enhance citizen participation in decision-making in relation to specific CCA projects. However, it is unclear how this works at a broader scale, or for DRM projects. For this reason, this question has been assessed as 3 [Low Priority]. It has been tagged as Low Priority, as this will be explored more in relation to the strength of DRM/CCA relationships and risk communication.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion/participation in decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Public Warning/Risk Communications

Another issue that was raised during the March 2023 workshop related to risk communication. Although the participants thought that the warning email from DMI was

²² <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2025/245> [22.09.25]

excellent, some suggestions were made about the broader risk communication system. The participants noted that the municipalities delivered the GIS data. There also needs to be a direct line of communication from emergency management to the health care system. At this workshop, it was suggested that there could be a platform to share information between the different stakeholders. This way, everyone would be able to access the information, and the different municipalities could gather/share information around events that impact the whole fjord.

The participants highlighted the benefits of coordinating announcements, as this would create clear announcements and provide an overview of the information that has been provided to citizens/emergency management/municipalities. The participants also identified a need for a higher level of communication directed towards citizens. This needs to clearly explain what the citizens' individual responsibility is during an extreme event, alongside how they can best prepare before a storm lands. This includes managing expectations and emphasizing civil responsibilities. Part of this will be teaching/communicating the risks of living near the coast or water basins. These initiatives are important to promote a shared culture of risk. For example, in the aftermath of Bodil (2013) training programs have been introduced to address how citizens need to prepare themselves for storms, this includes practical steps such as how to use sandbags to protect their home. In addition, in June 2024, a Water Management Centre opened in the Roskilde Fire Department. This new initiative tests new solutions and offers training to both emergency services and volunteers (citizens).

A challenge around this is how to communicate uncertainty, as this was an area highlighted as needing improvement. Another challenge is identifying the best mode of communication. The participants noted that participants were *"not that excited about Facebook"* but that they did use SoMe, so this may be a better platform for sharing risk information and warnings. A practical concern is ensuring that the risk communication is able to manage the situation where a warning is cancelled or stopped, once the event is over or is no longer a high-alert event. It is important that the warning is called off when the storm is over.

During the workshop, participants also raised the need for there to be resources that address how to handle volunteers. For example, making sure that volunteers understand what their role is/responsibilities are so that they can be the most helpful/effective. This also links to the need for local knowledge to be shared in a useful way.

Discussions with RWL stakeholders highlighted the importance of communicating the role of emergency response actors in the response phase, and what they can/will do. For example, since flooding in Denmark happens slowly so it is anticipated that people will self-evacuate. Under Danish law it is the responsibility of citizens to protect their private property, however in practice there is an expectation that they will be helped during an event. Due to this personal responsibility, municipalities/emergency services do not sandbag residential homes during an event. Municipalities will provide the sand and the bags, but it is up to citizens to put these together and put them around their home. Discussions with RWL stakeholders also highlighted examples where people were evacuated, but the dam did not burst. The

impression was that people were not upset by this ‘false alarm’ but instead accepted that these would occur, but it was better to be prepared.

Based upon these examples, it appears that communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public is an area which is reasonably developed, and for this reason this indicator has been assessed as 4 (Medium Priority). It has been tagged as Medium Priority because it is a relevant priority for the RWL and should be considered.

<p>Public warning/Risk Communication: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?</p>	<p>4 [MP]</p>
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Social Justice

DCA developed a national social vulnerability index (SVI) and social flood risk index (SFRI) for Denmark (Prall et al., 2024). Indicators included age, health, socio-economic situation, ability to acquire and understand information and neighbourhood resilience etc. This method was developed to, together with the economic risk, be used to identify additional areas of high risk (including Roskilde Fjord) based on the national flood risk assessment in the 3rd cycle of the Floods Directive²³. Nielsen et al., (2023) point out that although areas like Frederiksberg in the Capital Region of Denmark (but not in Roskilde Fjord) are affluent areas which are “characterised as resourceful, socio-political stable and has a high-quality infrastructure” this does not mean the vulnerability is not present in these areas. Nielsen et al., (2023) identify a risk that vulnerable individuals may be overlooked if these communities are treated homogeneously, this is a problematic approach as there may be “intersectional conditions that could produce hidden vulnerabilities”. This means that engaging with disenfranchised groups is important, even in more affluent areas.

Communication is a critical part of enabling disenfranchised groups to engage in DRM/CCA. This includes requiring that public warnings and risk communication strategies are available in a number of different languages and modes such as in paper format, online, audio, visual and through social media. Additional support around digital literacy may be necessary to ensure that disenfranchised communities are able to engage with the public warnings and risk communication.

It is important that the municipalities, emergency management, and other agencies working in DRM and CCA are aware of these vulnerabilities and address them through their DRM/CCA plans. It is currently unclear how these groups enable disenfranchised groups to engage in DRM/CCA. For this reason, this indicator has been assessed as 1 (Low Priority), as this is an area where there is high potential for growth. This indicator has been tagged as Low Priority, as it was not identified as a priority for the RWL.

²³ <https://oversvømmelse.kyst.dk/> [10.09.2025]

<p>Social Justice: To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM and/or CCA?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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Feasibility

Discussions with the RWL in the 2023 workshop highlighted the importance of political involvement/engagement and buy-in when trying to pursue DRM/CCA action. This has been a theme that has arisen throughout interactions with the Danish RWL. Political involvement has been identified as important to ensure that better resources are available for prevention and preparedness exercises. These are viewed as initiatives that need to be done at the national level as well.

Furthermore, Denmark has a “burden sharing” principle where the person being protected by the DRM/CCA action is expected to pay for this initiative. This came through in the Roskilde flood wall example where there was a clear expectation that if people could afford a home along the Roskilde harbour then they could afford to help with CCA interventions.

Denmark’s political, social and economic situation for supporting DRM/CCA actions is reasonably developed, and thus has been assessed as 4 (Low Priority). This has been tagged as Low Priority as it is beyond the scope of the RWL/DIRECTED project to change the political/social/economic situation in Denmark.

<p>Feasibility: To what extent is the political, social, and economic situation supporting DRM or CCA action?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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3.1.1.4 Knowledge co-production

Collaborative mechanisms

Horizontal collaboration between municipalities is not coordinated at a local level, limiting cross municipality collaboration. Additionally, there is a lack of coordination between Disaster Management Authorities and municipalities. This highly localized structure, which tends to reinforce municipal silos, has resulted in many municipalities calling for improvements in intermunicipal and cross-sectoral communication. While the desire is there from municipal partners, and there are some partnerships for specific projects or funding opportunities, these are not systematically coordinated at the regional level. Indeed, recent policy shifts have exacerbated this fragmentation. As previously discussed, the transfer of Climate Change Adaptation responsibilities away from regional authorities (such as Region Hovedstaden, Capital Region of Denmark) back to the municipal level has reduced an important coordinating layer and risks further entrenching fragmented approaches. As such,

there is a lack of collaborative mechanisms to connect these actors and strong need for such RWL collaboration being enabled through DIRECTED. Therefore, this is rated at 1 and identified as High Priority.

<p>Collaborative Mechanisms: To what extent do collaborative mechanisms exist to foster diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>
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Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production:

The RWL stakeholders, throughout the set-up of the RWL, placed strong emphasis on exploring the extent to which DRR and CCA practitioners work and collaborate at the local level. Coordination across municipalities and more collaborative approaches to enable knowledge co-production are repeatedly identified as key goals. These priorities directly respond to the institutional and structural barriers to knowledge co-production highlighted earlier.

Overall, there is a broadly shared understanding among DRM and CCA stakeholders of the problems and challenges that make knowledge co-production necessary. Across the RWLs, stakeholders consistently identified fragmentation, limited cross-municipality coordination, and entrenched institutional silos as barriers to effective collaboration. This recognition signals a growing awareness of the need for more integrated and collaborative approaches to address climate and disaster risks. At the same time, the depth and scope of this understanding varies across actors. This highlights the ongoing need for alignment, capacity development, and shared framing to translate recognition into sustained collaborative action.

While the RWLs articulate collaboration and integration as shared objectives, these goals at times remain broad and aspirational rather than translated into concrete, measurable steps. As previously discussed, due to the diversity of the region, there are various stakeholders affected by these risks such as utility companies, households, farmers, hoteliers, and so on. However, there is limited evidence of a shared understanding of the needs of knowledge co-production to stretch to this plurality of voices. Rather, the focus is on intermunicipal cooperation and the collaboration between and with the respective emergency services in the area. For some, knowledge co-production is primarily viewed as a tool for improving emergency management and coordination practices. For the project partners, it is understood more broadly as an opportunity to transform governance structures by embedding DRM and CCA within more holistic and participatory frameworks. As such, while there is consensus in principle on the importance of collaboration, the interpretation and application may differ in practice.

However, RWL 1 has consistently provided spaces for active engagement, frequent interactions, and iterative feedback loops. These processes will help ensure that goals remain aligned with the identified challenges, while also being continuously refined as contexts evolve. Consequently, this indicator has been assessed as a 3 and Medium Priority,

as the RWL have a good shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production, but still require practical interventions and solutions for institutionalising collaboration.

<p>Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production: To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production:

The extent to which RWL 1 DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production appears mixed across the different skills and capacities. RWL hosts reflected varying levels of confidence in Design, Research and Facilitation skills, as well as capacities such as collaboration, systems thinking, and creativity and reflexivity (Cumiskey et al., 2025). The RWL hosts successfully used interactive methods (namely World-Café) during the first RWL workshop in March 2023 to scope barriers and capacities for risk data, modelling and tools, governance and communication. RWL hosts were satisfied with their facilitation skills, and had previous experience given their background as anthropologists, but recognized that more could have been done to create a balanced discussion between the interests of emergency management actors and municipalities, as the conversations steered towards emergency management. However, staff turnover was a challenge in this RWL, as the hosts changed early during implementation (end of Year 1). New hosts reported (in Capacity Needs Assessment, Ng et al., 2025) varying skills in facilitation, design and research capacities but strong evidence of widespread openness and willingness to engage in collaboration, and increasing interest in experimenting with more creative, reflexive, and systems-thinking approaches.

Overall skills and capacities remain uneven, but there is broad openness and commitment to engaging in knowledge co-production processes. As such, this indicator is rated at 3 and Medium Priority, as it creates a strong foundation for further capacity development and locally-led co-production initiatives.

<p>Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production: To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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3.1.1.5 Key Risk Governance Gaps and Aligned Indicators

Firstly, the assessment of the indicators shows that increasing collaboration both at the intermunicipal level and between municipalities and fire departments is crucial for integrating

DRM and CCA. As such, the High Priority indicators are the multi-level governance rated 4 and collaboration mechanisms rated 1. Using the RWL as a collaborative mechanism to strengthen these relationships for operations and planning will shape the coproduction activities and expected outputs for the Data Fabric.

→ **Key priority:** Support knowledge exchange and communication across municipalities and between emergency management actors in the Roskilde Fjord area.

Secondly, the indicators highlighted priorities around fit-for-purpose data, models rating 4 and tools and interoperability and innovation rating 3. The Data Fabric development offers a key opportunity to combine different data sources in one place and support easy to access tools for operational decision-making, planning and training scenarios.

→ **Sub priority:** Support local emergency management services and municipalities with easy to access data/models/tools to support decision-making/planning with minimal training

Thirdly, the indicators highlighted priorities around improving DRM/CCA policy/plan coherence rated 3. The development of the MCDM and uncertainty analysis for planning in the Data Fabric will aim to address this.

→ **Sub priority:** Support CCA/DRM planners in municipalities to consider multiple hazard severities, multiple sectors, adaptation/DRM options and related models to account for uncertainty, and support multi-criteria decision-making.

3.1.2 Growth Phase

Key priority: Support risk knowledge/data exchange and communication across municipalities and between emergency management actors in the Roskilde Fjord area

The first RWL workshop in March 2023 confirmed the need for closer interaction and knowledge exchange between municipalities, emergency managers, and other relevant actors - such as municipal GIS experts, dike associations, and utility companies. As one host reflected during the debrief: *“The workshop was very useful for different stakeholders to interact and exchange who normally would not, with lots of discussions in coffee breaks and lunch.”*

The workshop also highlighted a central challenge for CCA: the overlap and variation between municipal and sectoral boundaries and emergency management areas. This underscored the importance of building a “common community” to bridge DRM and CCA efforts. As documented in Deliverable 1.1 (Pancioli et al., 2024), stakeholders identified the need to improve alignment of data and information exchange between municipalities, including access to each other’s measuring systems - ideally through a shared platform. They also stressed the importance of more precise forecasts and warnings, with wave modelling included. Across workshops, stakeholders consistently emphasized the value of better knowledge sharing and risk communication, with the development of a shared

inter-municipal and emergency management platform, such as the Data Fabric, emerging as a key solution.

Building on continued engagement between stakeholders, RWL hosts, and scientists/developers, two sub-priorities were identified to guide the targeted development and use of the Data Fabric:

1. **Support local emergency management services and municipalities** with easy to access data/models/tools to support decision-making/planning with minimal training
2. **Support CCA planners in municipalities** to consider multiple hazard severities, multiple sectors, adaptation/ DRM options and related models to account for uncertainty and support multi-criteria decision-making

Figure 9: Impressions from RWL Capital Region 1st Workshop (March 2023).

Staff turnover

In 2024, the RWL hosts in the Capital Region of Denmark **underwent staff changes**, which delayed the organisation of the follow-up workshop. While the previous hosts had already established strong relationships with stakeholders, the new team had to rebuild these connections from the ground up. To address this challenge, strengthen personal ties, and respond to gaps identified during the first workshop (particularly the need for improved communication between emergency management and municipal actors), the new RWL hosts conducted a series of **group interviews** in April and May 2024. These interviews included: (1) the municipalities of Egedal, Frederikssund, and Halsnæs, (2) Frederiksborg Fire and Rescue, (3) Lejre Fire Department & Lejre Municipality, and (4) the Municipality of Roskilde together with Roskilde Fire Department. In addition, separate interviews were then held with the Danish Emergency Management Agency in July.

Prioritisation

The **2nd RWL Workshop (August 2024)** shared results of the interviews conducted in Spring 2024 to identify priorities for future activities. Stakeholders identified their top priorities as developing models that can simulate coupled events, such as heavy rainfall combined with storm surges, and incorporating wave height into storm surge warnings. The workshop included a presentation of a scenario of the potential consequences of a storm surge event similar to Storm Bodil but under the worst-case sea level rise scenario. At the next level, they

expressed the need for more localised measuring points and weather stations to supplement model data, while noting that limited staff resources make it difficult for some organisations to handle GIS and mapping tasks. Lower-priority concerns included improving the accuracy of sea-level rise data during storm surges and strengthening alignment of expectations between municipalities, emergency services, and citizens.

Figure 10: Impressions from co-production prioritisation activities in 2nd Workshop (August 2024).

Output - Data Fabric as a knowledge sharing platform

A RWL meeting took place in November 2024 to get feedback on a mock up of the Data Fabric. This included an online presentation from 52⁰ North to 8 stakeholders covering most of the municipalities and emergency services in the Roskilde Fjord area. The mock-ups presented possible solutions to two user-stories, identified via the material from interviews and workshops held with the stakeholders in 2024. The demonstrations highlighted key functionalities for simulating extreme coastal flooding scenarios (Figure 11).

Stakeholder feedback on Data Fabric

The municipalities emphasized the importance of a clear and intuitive user interface for the new data platform, noting that limited GIS expertise in some municipalities makes simplicity essential. They welcomed optional online learning modules, but stressed that the platform should be easy to use without them. DTU suggested the platform should go beyond DMI's *KlimaAtlas* while still considering its capabilities, and Lejre highlighted its potential value for both municipal climate adaptation and emergency services. Halsnæs requested that the

platform display actual water and flood levels rather than percentages of precipitation increase based on Storm Bodil. Stakeholders also requested transparency in the data, including uncertainty ranges, sources, and data age. Following the presentation, Halsnæs shared contact details for their water utility and measuring station, while also pointing to existing data available through the Water Portal.²⁴ Additionally, the Municipality of Lejre requested groundwater levels to be included, as this is receiving political attention in Denmark given the record wet years in 2019 and 2023. One RWL host summarized their reflections in the debrief meeting *“The Data Fabric has to be simple and intuitive, it has to be very targeted, it doesn’t need to do everything, but it needs to do the right thing.”* (December 2024).

Figure 11: Data Fabric mock up presented by 52^o North to RWL stakeholders (November 2024) for User story 1: to aid in the ease and accessibility of viewing geographic information system (GIS) data through flood simulations and impact assessments toward Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Management (DRM) in the Roskilde Fjord.

A questionnaire related to the Data Fabric (incl. data sources, variables and most relevant compound events and related consequences) was distributed among the RWL stakeholders before the workshop and most responses collected after the workshop (Figure 12) for the responses.

²⁴ <https://vandportalen.dk/> [10.09.2025]

Municipality/Emergency Service	Compound events that are relevant to you	Possible consequences of the compound events
Egedal M.	Successive rain events	-
	High tide and storm	-
	Prolonged drought followed by heavy rain	-
Halsnæs M.	High groundwater level, heavy rainfall, high tide	Flooding of built-up areas near Arresø (lake) and/or Frederiksværk city.
	Drought, forest fire, strong northerly wind	Fire in the summer house areas of Asserbo and Liseleje.
Lejre M. & ES.	Elevated water levels in the fjords combined with heavy extreme rainfall, which puts pressure on the municipality's watercourses	Water backing up in the watercourses when drainage to the fjords is blocked due to high water levels.
	Extreme rainfall combined with already high soil moisture.	The high soil moisture hampers the natural infiltration of rainwater.
Roskilde ES.	Prolonged rainfall combined with elevated water levels in Roskilde Fjord.	Extended periods of rainfall will lead to increased water levels in Værebros Å due to drainage from the catchment area/hinterland. This may cause flooding of areas upstream of the river's outlet.
	Heavy rain showers combined with 'water-saturated' soil.	Intense rainfall on already saturated soil can lead to significant local flooding, affecting both homes and infrastructure.
	An unfavorable wind direction after a general rise in water levels.	A west-northwest wind generally increases water levels in Roskilde Fjord. If the wind shifts further north, it leads to additional filling of the fjord, as seen in previous significant high-water events.

Figure 12: Summarised responses to questionnaire on the Data Fabric.

The **third RWL workshop in April 2025** involved a presentation of the live Data Fabric and an opportunity for hands-on use including testing different features and functionalities. This involved discussions around compound events and modelling needs from stakeholders. Interactive exercise to identify hotspots for municipal DRM and CCA based on initial suggestions emerging from the municipal climate adaptation plans. The participants placed stickers on a map and had to explain why these were hotspots for them (Figure 13). The Data Fabric provided trial flood maps for pluvial floods and storm surges across 20-, 50-, and 100-year return periods, three climate scenarios (SSPs for storm surges, RCPs for pluvial floods), and three time slices (1981–2010, 2041–2070, 2071–2100). It also included daily and hourly rainfall return values to support modelling. DTU complemented these with damage cost calculations to generate an additional set of maps. The aim was to get participants to think about and work with the hotspots in their areas using the tools, and helping them to frame the possibilities for emergency management and CCA measures that can be developed in the next workshop.

Figure 13: Impressions from Capital Region of Denmark RWL 3rd Workshop (April 2025).

Stakeholder feedback

Feedback from stakeholders on the **draft Data Fabric (Figure 14)** revealed that stakeholders found the platform promising but highlighted several usability challenges, particularly when working on laptops where menus and drop-down boxes occupy too much space and cannot be hidden or moved. Both Halsnæs and Roskilde Fire Department emphasized the need for retractable or dynamic menus, with Halsnæs also requesting clearer pixel-level information, more distinct color variations with explanatory pop-ups, and consideration of missing risk factors such as wind direction and storm surge duration, which can lead to groundwater push-up behind dikes. Frederikssund proposed renaming and merging layers into a single dynamic layer with a slider to switch between scenarios, while also noting that some storm surge data lacked sufficient detail. Stakeholders further stressed the importance of clear explanations for each layer and suggested features such as info boxes for menu items, municipality-specific filtering, improved alignment of map views, integration of historical wind data, and more flexible cost analysis tools including the ability to combine or import polygons from existing GIS systems. Finally, views diverged on data priorities: Halsnæs underlined the need for real-time data and short-term forecasts to support climate adaptation, while Roskilde Fire Department prioritized long-term planning data, arguing it would also meet significant real-time needs.

Figure 14: Draft of the Data Fabric used in workshop showing mean sea level deviation forecasts (April 2025).

Legislation changes

From a legislative perspective, as highlighted in the Foundation Phase, there is no framework for coordination at the regional or coastal zone scale like Roskilde Fjord. However, this is changing due to the EU Floods Directive (2007), which was implemented in Denmark through the Danish Flood Risk Act 2010. Under this Act the national level government identifies flood risk areas, and maps flood hazards and risks in these areas. It is then the role of the municipalities to develop risk management plans for these identified risk areas. As of

December 2024, there are 25 identified designated risk areas, and the municipalities covering these areas must prepare individual flood risk management plans (Lind, 2024), now including Roskilde Fjord. The social consequences of flooding were used alongside economic consequences to identify these areas including Roskilde Fjord which was newly identified²⁵. Although the DCA is the responsible national authority for mapping the flood hazard and risk, the municipalities are responsible for coordinating their own plans. This provides an opportunity for the municipalities in Roskilde to work together if they choose to do so - they are not obliged to but it is strongly recommended by DCA. The RWL collaborative activities can provide space for municipalities to explore this.

Another legislative development was the Danish Health reform which was introduced in 2024. The decision was made to merge two of the regions, as part of this change the government decided to streamline the areas that regions are involved in (Danish Ministry of Health, 2024). Subsequently, the decision was made to stop regions involvement in CCA activities, since the mandate for CCA technically sits at the municipal level. The government justified this decision by saying that the limited part of CCA managed by the regions will still happen, just at the municipal level. This means that regions are no longer able to be involved in CCA activities or initiatives, including EU projects. Consequently, the Capital Region of Denmark will be leaving the DIRECTED consortium in October 2025. All these changes were shared in the workshop and will require further discussion moving forward to adapt the RWL activities accordingly. Concerns have been raised in discussion with RWL stakeholders that municipalities lack the capacity and resources to properly engage in CCA.

Sub priority 1: Support local emergency management services and municipalities with easy to access data/models/tools to support decision-making/planning with minimal training

The Data Fabric, discussed above, is designed to serve multiple purposes beyond simply enabling data sharing and exchange. One key need identified in the workshops was to support local emergency management services (EMS) and municipality staff with simple digital tools that provide direct access to real-time precipitation data, forecasts, and flood maps for coastal and flood risk areas. This would reduce their dependence on municipal GIS specialists, who often act as bottlenecks since they are not available 24/7. This requirement became one of the core User Stories for the Data Fabric.

By equipping EMS and non-GIS municipal staff with a tool they can use independently, municipalities can improve coordination with neighbouring municipalities and EMS during heavy precipitation and storm surge events. This would require the inclusion of real-time flood maps, ideally linked to DMI data, along with a discharge hydrograph. As highlighted in the 2nd RWL workshop, modelling and preparing for coupled incidents are a challenge that both municipalities and emergency services recognise.

²⁵

<https://www.plan.aau.dk/new-research-leads-to-the-inclusion-of-vulnerable-groups-in-flood-risk-assessments-n125342> [27.08.2025]

Another important objective is to provide training for municipal staff, both GIS specialists and other employees, who regularly interact with EMS. This is particularly critical for smaller municipalities with fewer staff and limited capacity. Roles and responsibilities for emergency preparedness vary widely across municipalities, depending on their size and resources. At present, many EMS still rely on printed maps from municipal GIS experts to prompt their response, underscoring the need for more direct, accessible, and digital solutions.

Output - Data Fabric (operations and training)

The development of the Data Fabric to meet this need is currently ongoing in alignment with DMI and RWL stakeholders. [Figure 15](#) below shows the real-time sea level mean deviation forecasts in the Roskilde Fjord integrated via the open data portal at DMI. Other datasets/results available currently include precipitation forecasts and it is planned to also include wind direction and wind speed at the request of the RWL stakeholders. The DMI open data portal offers hundreds of both historic and forecast data, which could be seamlessly included into the Data Fabric due to open standards.

The Data Fabric can be used by non-specialists in the local emergency management services and/or the municipalities. The schematic of the workflow in the Data Fabric, including the standardised data and interoperable modelling components are presented in the Interoperability Fact Sheet Real World Lab 1 (see Annex 2).

Figure 15: Data Fabric (as of September 2025) showing real-time sea level mean deviation forecasts in the Roskilde Fjord.

In addition to supporting day-to-day data sharing, the Data Fabric platform could also serve as a scenario tool for **training and future planning exercises** around extreme events. Across both the first and second workshops, stakeholders expressed strong interest in such exercises. At the second workshop, a representative from the Danish Emergency Management Agency (DEMA) introduced the concept, stressing the importance of shifting from crisis management to crisis planning. This approach creates space for dialogue and

helps address complex challenges by showing that severe disaster scenarios can only be managed effectively through collaboration among authorities, infrastructure managers, critical companies, and citizens. It would also provide an opportunity to test new technologies, including communication tools, to strengthen situational and resource awareness.

Building on the identified need to better understand and model extreme and coupled events, such as storm surges combined with pluvial flooding, the Data Fabric could be used to test targeted scenarios. For example, a forensic analysis of Storm Bodil, which remains a key reference event for local actors, could serve as a basis for reflexive exercises that explore what could be done differently. A major challenge in designing such an exercise is that the Roskilde Fjord area spans three different EMS regions, each operating with distinct technical systems and organizational cultures. Here, the Data Fabric could play a critical role in bridging these differences and supporting shared information flows.

Sub priority 2: Support CCA planners in municipalities to consider multiple hazard severities, multiple sectors, adaptation/DRM options, and related models to account for uncertainty and support multi-criteria decision-making

Another priority identified for the Data Fabric is to include more functionality to support planners to consider different hazard scenarios, multiple interventions across sectors and to understand uncertainty. This need is reflected in a specific User Story (see Pontius et al., 2025) for a municipal employee who is interested in uncertainty maps for long-term planning with and without adaptation measures to help decide where to allocate measures. These uncertainty maps would compare different model outputs, and ideally include certainty data in near real-time to inform communication with local EMS.

The 2nd workshop included demonstrating the capability of the Data Fabric to show uncertainty information ([Figure 16](#)). However, based on interactions with municipality stakeholders especially during the Field Trip (September 2025), it is clear that the critical information for their real-time decision-making is the forecasted sea level with accommodation of varying wave height. Therefore, having multiple model runs available showing the flood maps for specific sea levels and wave heights is critical for planning under different scenarios. Whereas running multiple simulations may or may not be computationally expensive based on the resolution and complexity, one can accommodate this need using a statistical approach, e.g. such as the feature offered by CLIMADA.

Figure 16: Data Fabric mock up presented by 52° North to RWL stakeholders (November 2024) as an example to view the uncertainty of model outputs in the Roskilde Fjord.

To enable testing different measures and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) the CLIMADA platform is being made interoperable with the Data Fabric. CLIMADA (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019) is an open source probabilistic natural catastrophe and Climate Change Adaptation model which can also calculate the potentially averted damages due to implemented adaptation measures incorporating Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques to evaluate different adaptation strategies in terms of their multiple objectives and criteria such as cost-benefit, but also feasibility for implementation, impact on ecosystems and acceptability.

For cost-benefit assessment, the DTU Cost Damage Assessment Tool is also embedded within the Data Fabric and needs to be made interoperable with CLIMADA. While inherently similar, the damage costs calculated by the DamageCost tool are in absolute numbers (DKK) whereas CLIMADA employs a relative approach. The damage cost curves used by the DamageCost tool are locally calibrated based on e.g. Danish insurance data. Meanwhile the damage cost curves embedded in CLIMADA are based on more generic data; they are effectively meant to be replaced by local damage cost curves when available. Being the more generic tool, the Danish curves have been implemented into CLIMADA to facilitate interoperability and to allow access to the broader set of features integrated into CLIMADA. Additionally,

Outputs - Multi-Criteria Decision-Making module in Data Fabric

The MCDM functionality has now been integrated into the Data Fabric as a module and tested at the DIRECTED General Assembly in September 2025 including a mock-up workshop to test the co-production nature of using the tool in a workshop setting (Figures 17 & 18). The MCDM module in the Data Fabric enables the comparison of a defined pre-computed set of adaptation options and risk metrics criteria, enables users to select and

weigh them, as well as define additional custom criteria. This setup will be tested in a RWL 1 workshop in early December 2025.

The MCDM workflow relies on the modelling of the effect of multiple adaptation measures using the different models of the Data Fabric. For areas in the Roskilde Fjord, SaferPlaces is used to model the effects of different barriers/dikes, while new building zoning or relocation, as well as changes in the vulnerability of buildings to floods are modelled using CLIMADA. Impacts with and without adaptation measures in effect are computed within CLIMADA, yielding multiple risk metrics (e.g., impacts on building using the DTU damage cost curves, impacts on people distinguished by social vulnerability indices from the Danish Coastal Authority). These metrics, in addition to known or estimated characteristics of the measures (e.g. cost), serve as a first set of possible criteria to consider in the MCDM. In addition, the MCDM module enables the definition of custom criteria such as public approval, feasibility, esthetical value, or cultural meaning (where each adaptation option performance has to be provided). Following, based on a chosen selection of criteria, optionally weighted, the MCDM module provides a corresponding ranking of the different options. Different selection and weighting of the criteria can easily be compared to support planners to go beyond traditional cost-benefit analysis, and stakeholder to reflect on their priorities.

In preparation for the next RWL workshop the RWL hosts are preparing model runs to obtain the flood hazard maps and impacts for the Frederikssund municipality with and without specific adaptation and emergency management measures. The measures considered here are those planned by the municipality in the recent *Frederikssund Meets the Water* project (NIRAS). The project sets out specific adaptations for a +2.50 m scenario intended to exceed the 100-year storm-surge level through 2075 by explicitly accounting for ~0.4 m of sea-level rise. The principal measures are earthen dikes; sheet-pile/high-water walls; deployable flood gates; targeted terrain and road raising; drainage upgrades; and provision for emergency gate installation and mobile pumps. The scheme also aims to upgrade the waterfront public realm, aligning with the city’s goal of bringing more life to the harbour.

CLIMADA Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) ×

 Please weight each criteria and press submit to view results. ← Back

Cost: How important is the cost of implementing the measure?

Not important Somewhat important Highly important

Averted Risk: How important is it that the measure helps to avert risk to people?

Not important Somewhat important Highly important

Approval: How important is it that the public approves of the measure?

Not important Somewhat important Highly important

Figure 17: Criteria weighting toolbox from the Data Fabric frontend.

Figure 18: Impressions from General Assembly MCDM Workshop (September 2025).

3.1.3 Learn Phase

Emergent lessons - knowledge coproduction

A challenge for this RWL was the **staff turnover** of RWL hosts, which resulted in a gap of engagement and follow up after the first workshop and patchy attendance at different knowledge co-production training activities. This also meant that the new RWL hosts, despite having access to a report on the first workshop, did not have the personal experience with the stakeholders to really understand the challenges and needs that the project could address. Likewise, the new RWL hosts had quite different professional backgrounds than their predecessors, who are trained anthropologists. In the Capacity Needs Assessment (analysis available in Deliverable 4.1) conducted with new hosts who began in Year 2, one host reported being confident and experienced in facilitation, while another expressed uncertainty and a lack of confidence. Similarly, across design and research, capacities were uneven, highlighting the different starting points and experiences of stakeholders.

The new RWL hosts recognised the need to adapt plans and reaffirm relationships with the RWL hosts, and organised four group interviews between municipalities and emergency management agencies with overlapping jurisdictional boundaries. The process of conducting the interviews helped the RWL hosts to reflect on how the project can support these actors as demonstrated by the following quote, *“I feel like there is so much to gain from connecting these stakeholders and want to ensure the project can stimulate dialogue and enhance their communication around climate adaptation and emergency management beyond the project’s lifetime”*. Reflections after the 2nd RWL workshop one RWL host highlighted that

“stakeholders already learnt from talking to each other – more than we could teach them” (September, 2024). Reflections from the 3rd RWL workshop debrief (September 2024) RWL hosts indicated that they were satisfied with their facilitation of the hotspot mapping exercise, and enabled well balanced and mixed groups. However, they pointed out that it was challenging to keep all participants in the group engaged, as the hosts noticed there was clear leadership in some groups and other participants who were tired and engaged less.

Reflections from the 3rd RWL workshop planning (April 2025) pushed developers to think about different multi-hazard or compound flood scenarios that would create additional pressure for emergency management and municipal agencies across borders. Overall there had been plans to move forward sooner with the MCDM module and related co-production activities, however it was decided by hosts not to overload the stakeholders with multiple functionalities of the Data Fabric and that a step wise approach was needed. Instead, this is the focus of the upcoming November 2026 workshop.

Emergent lessons - governance and institutional context

Policy/ and Legal framework changes

As introduced in the Foundation Phase, shortly after the second DIRECTED workshop in August 2024, Denmark announced the creation of a new Ministry of Resilience and Preparedness, tasked with strengthening national resilience to crises such as extreme weather events. The new ministry will coordinate efforts across sectors, with a strong focus on enhancing crisis management and preparedness. It will oversee DEMA, cybersecurity and digital information security, and have coordinating responsibility for crisis management and supply security.²⁶ DEMA (and its related responsibilities) was previously under the Ministry of Defence but has been transferred to this new Ministry.

Debriefing from the second workshop (September 2024) also pointed to forthcoming legislation for the Roskilde Fjord, requiring all five municipalities in the area to develop a single, shared climate adaptation plan. This follows Denmark’s obligations under the EU Floods Directive (2007). In addition, the Danish Coastal Authority (DCA) is expected to produce more detailed flood and coastal mapping to support this process, although DCA was not present at the workshop to confirm details.

Together, these developments underline the continued relevance of the DIRECTED project and its mission: to reduce vulnerability to extreme weather events and foster disaster-resilient European societies by improving the interoperability of data, models, communication, and governance across all levels and among all actors engaged in Disaster Risk Management and climate adaptation.

Improving collaboration and governance

Stakeholders showed strong interest in data and modelling solutions, but much less in developing governance arrangements. The Data Fabric was generally seen as a practical

²⁶

<https://mssb.dk/nyheder/2024/august/regeringen-opretter-nyt-ministerium-for-samfundssikkerhed-og-beredskab/> [10.09.2025]

stepping stone, while broader coordination mechanisms were acknowledged as necessary but accompanied by a sense of “powerlessness” to address them. As a result, discussions tended to focus on concrete, technical measures, such as a shared data platform, rather than the more complex governance challenges. The RWL hosts also noted that stakeholders often “held back on the details” when governance issues arose.

As one host reflected after the second RWL workshop (September 2024): *“The data/modelling they don’t know about, so it’s easier to say it’s a priority than to admit they need stronger organisations.”* Similarly, another host commented in December 2024: *“It’s not so important for them to focus on communication and governance, ‘we’ll reorganise ourselves’ although they know this is just as important. It’s easier to talk about the technical aspects and imagine how we might work together better.”*

At the policy level, the second Climate Adaptation Plan is expected by the end of 2025, though upcoming municipal elections may influence its direction. Other national priorities, such as the *Re-naturing of Denmark* programme, are also gaining traction. Since many of the same municipal staff are responsible for both climate adaptation and nature conservation, priorities are shifting, with conservation rising on the agenda. RWL hosts therefore believe it is unlikely that the Data Fabric outputs will directly shape current adaptation plans, as these are tightly managed within ministries through a top-down process.

Looking ahead, a dedicated RWL workshop in April 2026 will focus on governance aspects and seek to identify concrete actions that DIRECTED can support.

Emergent lessons - data, models and tools - interoperability

Overarching prioritisation challenge

Stakeholders raised a wide range of needs, particularly around the demand for “more and better data”, that are challenging to address within the limited timeframe of the project. Although the second workshop focused on prioritisation, even within the scope of the Data Fabric there are still numerous potential directions, making it difficult to establish clear priorities. As one RWL host reflected, *“If you offer a lot of opportunities, then you get a lot of ticks - they haven’t really prioritised, they want everything.”*

Training exercise

During the debrief following the second workshop, RWL hosts welcomed DEMA’s proposal and expressed interest in integrating scenario exercises into RWL activities. However, it would be difficult for DTU to lead on such an activity, support would be needed from the Ministry for Resilience and Preparedness/ DEMA to design and implement such activities, as well as to secure buy-in from local EMS and municipalities. Since no mechanism currently exists for cross-sectoral training of this kind, significant planning and commitment would be required. One possible approach could be to position the exercise as part of a final “wrap-up” of RWL activities, using it to demonstrate the cumulative learning and collaboration developed between municipalities and emergency management agencies throughout the project. This will be further explored as part of the training related to the Data Fabric.

3.1.4 Sustain Phase

Data Fabric as a governance mechanism. Challenges have been identified for hosting and sustaining such a platform, given the lack of governance/institutional mechanisms for collaboration. DMI showed interest in the platform (during the 3rd RWL workshop) to show the data they have and support more use of it. RWL hosts shared during debriefing sessions that municipalities would likely not be willing to pay to host such a platform, and the regions would not be allowed, raising the question whether a more resourced municipality could host the tool and ensure access to all the other municipalities. Another option would be DEMA at the national level. Furthermore, other synergies can be looked at in the Government Authority for Data to explore how to align data and initiatives on Digital Twins, as well as the Mission on Academy for Technical Sciences – digital agenda in climate change and emergency management. All these options need to be explored during the Sustain Phase, including discussions about IP, data sharing agreements and similar. This will also be aligned with the Business Development Planning process.

Training (Planning Exercises) on the Data Fabric will be required by the stakeholders beyond those involved in the RWL. This can target specific staff in the municipalities and the emergency management authorities, focusing on the different use cases of the tool to support operations and planning for DRM and CCA. Further exploration of a cross-sectoral planning exercise will be explored with key national stakeholders with the aim to run an exercise in February 2026.

The RWL plans to have a more high-level workshop in April 2026 specifically addressing different agencies that could host the platform, while also exploring how the **interactions in the RWL can be sustained** beyond the project. For example, can a municipality agree to host a yearly forum or align/connect existing meetings to widen participation of stakeholders across geographic and sectoral boundaries. Furthermore, the role of DTU in strengthening relationships with these key stakeholders will be crucial to facilitate continued exchange and innovation through future applied research. Considering the staff turnover of the RWL, the most recent host at DTU comes from a practice-policy background, with a previous role working in the DCA on climate adaptation in collaboration with the municipalities, which will be valuable for maintaining and sustaining the relationships within the RWL.

3.2 Real World Lab 2:

Emilia-Romagna

Figure 19: Map of Emilia-Romagna Region.

The Emilia-Romagna RWL is hosted by the Regional Agency for Territorial Safety and Civil Protection (Agenzia regionale per la sicurezza territoriale e la protezione civile (ARSTPC-ER)) together with the Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy (ARPAE) Hydrometeo Service Civil Protection Function Centre, with technical support from GECOSistema. The Emilia-Romagna Region is exposed to a number of natural hazards including extreme rainfall events, coastal flooding and erosion, and wildfires. Marine ingression and windstorm risks are the focal point for the coastal strip of the Rimini province, which includes the municipalities of Bellaria-Igea marina, Rimini, Riccione, Misano Adriatico, and Cattolica. Addressing wildfire risks at the coast of the Ferrara province, including the municipalities of Comacchio and Mesola, is also a key concern for the RWL.

The application of the RTF ([Figure 20](#)) in the Emilia-Romagna RWL, involved applying the Risk-Tandem indicators in the Foundation Phase which highlighted priorities around improving interoperability of data, models and tools for coastal and fluvial flooding and improving wildfire risk communication. The knowledge co-production activities during the

Growth and Learn Phases of the RWL (see Annex 1) are expected to result in the co-designed Data Fabric for coastal and pluvial floods, and an extension to address wildfires, and a wildfire risk communication kit to support in improving public wildfire risk communication, which can be sustained beyond the lifetime of the DIRECTED project.

Figure 20: Overview of the Risk-Tandem application in Emilia-Romagna RWL.

3.2.1 Foundation Phase

3.2.1.1 Actor Networks/Setting the Scene

Figure 21: Stakeholder Map of Emilia-Romagna.

The region houses a number of emergency services, with the voluntary coordination units from the Ferrara province and Rimini forming the backbone of the immediate DRM responses. The Rimini Provincial Civil Protection Voluntary Coordination covers Riccione, Cattolica, Bellaria Ugea, Misano Adriatic and Rimini. Whilst the Ferrara centre covers Comacchio and Mesola. Other key stakeholders include the Protected Areas, Forests, and Mountain Areas Development Sector, the Romagna Reclamation Consortium, the Soil Defence Sector, the Po Delta Parks and Biodiversity Management Authority, the Environmental Police, and the Riviera del Conca Civil Protection Operative Centre.

There are a number of actors at different levels involved in the Italian DRM/CCA system. Many of these actors are involved in DIRECTED as RWL stakeholders, for example ARSTPC-ER, Rimini Civil Protection, Ferrara Civil Protection, ARPAE and the other stakeholders identified in [Figure 21](#) above. These actor networks are at the national, regional and municipal (local) level. The role of regional and municipal civil protection offices is particularly important as Italy has a decentralised, multi-level civil protection system, based on the subsidiary principle, as set out in the Civil Protection Code 2018 (CP Code). Consequently, the responsibility for managing emergencies falls to the regions and municipalities. While the responsibilities are divided up, there is a heavy focus on DRM strategies over CCA.

There are important decision-making roles for DRM beyond these stakeholders. Article 3 of the CP Code identifies the town mayors and metropolitan city mayors as local civil protection authorities. Consequently, when an emergency occurs, the mayor directs and coordinates both response assistance and relief. The mayor's more general decision-making responsibilities are set out in the Notes to Article 12, whilst the responsibilities that are specific to civil protection are set out in Article 12(5). The mayor is also responsible for calling for the intervention of other regional and/or national forces and operational structures when the response required for an emergency is beyond the capacity of the municipality.

Beyond the civil protection departments, there are a number of organisations involved in the response phase for emergency events. These include the (national) Fire Brigade Corp and Voluntary Coordination organisations. Firefighters are identified as a key operation structure of the civil protection services, as they have responsibilities in relation to all disasters (not just fires). The role of the National Fire Department/Fire Brigade corp for recovery and reconstruction activities is regulated by Article 10 of the CP Code. Responsibilities during response include the *“most urgent technical search and rescue operations, taking on the direction and responsibility in the immediate through the technical-operational coordination and collaboration with other components of the facilities involved”*. This means that for every major event, the technical responsibility for checking and reactivating critical infrastructure falls with the fire department.

Additional operational structures of the National Service of Civil Protection are set up in Article 13 and cover the armed forces, police, research institutions and technical bodies, National Health Service facilities, civil protection volunteer services registered in the national list (including the Italian Red Cross Association), National system for the protection of the environment, and services dedicated to weather forecasting and monitoring at the national level. Discussions with the Regional Civil Protection System (ARSTPC-ER) also highlighted the roles of the forestry force, port authorities, regional department of health, land reclamation authorities (the Po River Interregional Agency), and the Environment Prevention Regional Agency (ARPAE) which is the civil protection functional centre for the Meteorological Forecasting service. These roles are critical to ensure that the Italian Civil Protection Service operates as planned.

A key element for this service which links to the availability of models/data/tools is the alert system as set out in Article 17 of the CP Code. Article 17(2) establishes that the government and management of the alert system are assured by the Department of Civil Protection and by the Regions (and Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano). This means that they guarantee the functions and activity of the alert system. The Directive also sets out the regulation of all aspects related to risk communication, including the drafting of civil protection plans and communicating these to the public.

Coordination of the implementation of interventions during a state of emergency of national importance is provided through civil protection ordinances, to be adopted in derogation of all existing provisions, within the limits and according to the procedures indicated in the state of emergency resolution and in compliance with the general principles of the legal system and European Union regulations. Ordinances are issued with the agreement of the Regions and Autonomous Provinces territorially affected.

3.2.1.2 Governance and Institutional Context

Legal framework

The civil protection department at the national level is the Dipartimento della Protezione Civile (Civil Protection Department), as set out in Article 1 of CP Code. Since DRM is a cross-cutting issue there are a number of other departments, plans and strategies involved, however the focus of the RWL has been at the regional/municipal level, so the national level governance framework has not been explored in detail.

Under this decentralised system, the ARSTPC-ER is in charge of DRM in the Emilia-Romagna Region as set out in Article 11 of the CP Code. The overarching function of the regions is to *“regulate the organization of civil protection systems in the framework of their respective territories”* which includes the implementation of civil protection activities. ARSTPC-ER also has a Regional Operations Centre which undertakes the identification, control and coordination of strategies and activities for emergency management. In case of events that need to be faced with extraordinary resources, personnel involved in this centre include operational structures involved in civil protection. For example; the fire department, armed forces, police, national health service facilities, ARPAE, voluntary coordination centers, and services Providers. The centre is also continuously in contact with the President of the region and Prefects

ARSTPC-ER has introduced a number of plans/resolutions following the introduction of the CP Code 2018.²⁷ For example, Resolution no. 1103 was introduced in July 2022 titled *“Regional planning of civil protection: identification of the Optimal Territorial Areas (ATO)”*. This resolution combined with the organizational criteria set out in the CP Code, the *“Agreement scheme for the constitution, in the presence of civil protection emergencies of a Rescue Coordination Center (CCS) and the Integrated Provincial Operations Room (SOPI)”* provides the basis for the Emilia-Romagna Regional Civil Protection Plan. This is built upon with Resolution no. 2278 which was introduced in December 2023. This resolution defines the scheme for the civil protection plan, provides some reference scenarios and sets out the regional intervention model which will be utilised in emergency situations. More recently in February 2023, Resolution no. 228 was introduced which is a *“Scheme for the preparation of civil protection plans at the provincial/metropolitan and scope city level”*.

²⁷ <https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/pianificazione-ptc> [22.08.2025]

ARSTPC-ER is then complemented by the territorial civil protection offices, such as the Rimini and Ferrara Territorial offices. DRM is identified as a fundamental function of municipalities in the Notes to Article 3 of the CP Code. Planning and preparedness at this level is critical, as it is anticipated that the ARSTPC-ER Territorial offices will manage smaller scale events alongside response agencies such as the Fire Department and the Rimini provincial Civil Protection Voluntary Coordination. This expectation is set out in Article 7 of the CP Code, only once the event is beyond the territorial capacity does it become a regional event.

The core CCA plan at the national level is the Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici (PNACC) which was introduced in December 2023. This is a national level planning tool which identifies the potential impacts of climate change. Similarly to DRM there are a number of different departments, plans, and strategies that are involved in CCA at multiple levels. Public consultation was conducted as part of the process of drafting the PNACC. At the national level, the main focus of the CCA frameworks is mainly on mitigation rather than adaptation and the focus is on carbon emissions, renewable energy and water scarcity. The PNACC does identify DRM as one of the (many) sectors that CCA will cut across, but it does not address the relationship between CCA and DRM, the role of DRM in implementing CCA or the need to integrate these frameworks together.

Emilia-Romagna as a region has responsibilities in relation to CCA, which led to the introduction of the Strategia di mitigazione e adattamento per i cambiamenti climatici della Regione Emilia Romagna (Climate change mitigation and adaptation strategy for the Emilia-Romagna Region). This is a notable achievement as there is currently no legislative obligation for regions, provinces and cities to develop and adopt mitigation or adaptation plans (Pietrapertosa, et al., 2021). Section 7 of this strategy addresses governance and the role of the territorial civil protection offices. In particular, the civil protection reorganization law L.R. 13/2015 which led to ARPAE and the Civil Protection Agency being assigned the technical and operational functions. Whilst the Regional Directorate for Land and Environment Management became responsible for the plans and programmes related to the environmental sector. This is an example of a plan which has attempted to integrate CCA and DRM together. This is unusual, as generally DRM and CCA plans tend to be kept separate. Additional legislation has also acknowledged the need to address CCA in other areas of the legal framework such as planning. This was introduced through the New Urban Planning Law (Law 24/0217) which emphasizes limiting land consumption, urban regeneration and quality of urban and building environments. This law also introduced the Strategy for Urban and Ecological-Environmental Quality which (among other things) aims to increase resilience to climate change.

The Rimini Municipality has also introduced the Piano di azione per l'Energia Sostenibile in July 2014. This is a Sustainable Energy Action Plan, which was drafted in line with the European “Covenant of Mayors”. This initiative involves local communities to reduce their CO2 emissions through the implementation of the Sustainable Energy Action Plans. The focus of these plans is mitigation rather than adaptation.

The integration of CCA and DRM frameworks is a theme that came through during interactions with the RWL stakeholders. At the DIRECTED Second Meeting for RWL 2 in 2023, an issue that was raised was the fact that climate change does not influence intervention models for forest fires. This discussion also identified a lack of regulation on climate change. A barrier for institutions and governance identified at this meeting was the lack of integration between planning instruments (CCA-DRM). This meeting also made a link with the broader legal framework and identified a need to consider forest fire risk within land use planning, which is an area linked with CCA. Insights from stakeholder meetings revealed there is no coordinated approach for regulating Climate Change Adaptation planning for the municipal level.

This extensive framework has led to the assessment that Italy’s legal framework to enable DRM/CCA is reasonably developed and has been given a rating of 4 (Low Priority), as there is room for improvement around DRM/CCA planning and regulation at the municipal level. This has been identified as Low Priority as the framework is reasonably developed and it is beyond the scope of the RWL/DIRECTED to amend/introduce new legal frameworks.

<p>Legal Framework: To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM & CCA integration?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Clarity of roles and responsibilities

The Civil Protection Code 2018 makes it clear that the responsibility for DRM lies with the regions and municipalities, with the municipality being the first line of response.²⁸ It is also clear that during disaster response the mayor is the key decision-maker as set out in Article 12(5). However, roles and responsibilities for CCA are less clear. The framework states that regions and municipalities have a role in addressing CCA, however there is a lack of clarity around specific roles and responsibilities. One example that was highlighted in the DIRECTED Consortium meeting in 2023, was the responsibility for paying for adaptation and how this will be split between the private sector and public households.

²⁸ See Articles 6, 9, 10, 11, 12, 12(5) and 13 of the Civil Protection Code 2015.

The CP Code recognises the important role of volunteers for civil protection in Article 31, which identifies citizen participation as one of the initiatives to be promoted by the National Civil Protection Service. Article 31(3) states that citizens “may” participate in civil protection activities by participating in organized voluntary work, which recognises the critical role of volunteer organisations within the civil protection system. It is up to the Regions (and autonomous provinces) to introduce other forms of participation by citizens beyond emergency relief activities. The National Civil Protection Service requires the enrollment of volunteers with an organization, which is then registered with the National List of civil protection volunteers. For example, a Municipal Civil Protection Volunteering Group. This ensures consistent guidelines and coordination in line with the applicable territory. Article 38 sets out “*Participation in organized voluntary work provided in civil protection planning*” where the voluntary organizations are recognised as taking part in the “*activities for the preparation and implementation of civil protection plans*”. Depending on the applicable authority, volunteer organizations may also be included in the activities for the preparation and updating of civil protection plans.

The Strategy for Mitigation and Adaptation to Climate Change of the Emilia-Romagna Region identifies a need to integrate DRM and CCA. Section 7.1 sets out the functions and structure of the ARSTPC-ER and the creation of two other central services.²⁹ Furthermore, a reorganization of law L.R.13/2015 has led to the Regional Directorate for Land and Environment Management being assigned planning and programmes related to the environmental section, and technical and operation functions being split between ARPAE and the new Civil Protection Agency. This strategy also set out the responsibilities for the ARSTPC-ER which cover both DRM and CCA activities, including designing and implementing interventions to prevent hydrogeological instability and ensure hydraulic safety, undertaking flood service functions (including authorizations and hydraulic surveillance), and the management of the Ferrara waterway. However, it is unclear how these responsibilities and plans are being implemented in practice.

Overall, the framework does identify the roles and responsibilities for DRM/CCA, although greater clarity around CCA roles would be helpful. For these reasons, this indicator has been assessed as 4 (Low Priority), which reflects that the legal framework identifying roles and responsibilities for DRM/CCA is reasonably developed. This indicator has been tagged as Low Priority as the roles and responsibilities are reasonably clear within the existing legal framework, and it is beyond the scope of the RWL/DIRECTED project to amend/introduce new legal frameworks.

<p>Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities for DRM & CCA clear/functional within the legal framework?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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²⁹ Two new central services were established: the Coordination of Special Programs and Assigned Responsibilities, and the Coordination of Emergency Interventions and Safety Measures.

Functionality of role and responsibilities

Although the legal framework for DRM is strong, the review of past experiences in the 2023 extreme floods in Emilia-Romagna (Irvine et al., 2025) highlighted the need for a more unified response framework. This flood event revealed gaps in the DRM around interoperability of systems and community engagement. Irvine et al., (2025) identified difficulties around data-sharing between the regional and municipal authorities, this led to delays in decision-making during critical phases of the disaster response. This event also highlighted gaps around community understanding of early warnings (particularly in rural areas), which impacted how some communities acted in response to these warnings.

A more unified response framework would help to ensure that all of the relevant services (emergency services, police, fire department etc) operate under a unified command structure. This would include greater coordination between agencies (including for data-sharing). Better collaboration was also identified at the regional level between municipalities and regional governments (and national disaster agencies when required). The need for better collaboration and an improved operational system indicates that the roles and responsibilities identified in the legal framework are not functioning as intended.

For these reasons, this indicator has been assessed as a 3 (Medium Priority). The gap identified above around the roles and responsibilities for CCA is also reflected in this score, as it is unclear how functional the CCA roles are in practice. This indicator is of Medium Priority, as it is a relevant indicator for the RWL. This is due to the feedback at the initial DIRECTED meetings, where the RWL identified a challenge for local governance in DRM was their limited ability to coordinate and support multiple stakeholders. This was an issue both for early warning, DRM, and CCA.

<p>Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities functional for DRM/CCA in practice?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Multi-level governance

The Italian DRM system is polycentric, as it is decentralized and DRM responsibilities have been assigned to the regional and municipal levels of government. Consequently, the regional and municipal civil protection offices make decisions around DRM planning and response. In April 2021, a Directive was introduced which set out "*Directions for the preparation of Civil Protection Plans at the different territorial levels*". This identified the cooperation that is required between all levels in governance (national, regional, provincial, territorial (municipal) etc).

For the case study of Rimini, the regional civil protection office is ARSTPC-ER, and the municipal office is the Territorial Office of Civil Protection for Rimini. There are control rooms at each level which are active in planning and monitoring for future events. The Regional

Operations Center (COR)³⁰ is located in Bologna and is operational on a daily basis. The COR undertakes critical activities both before, during and after an event. During the management of a sovra-provincial event, the Agency organizes itself by activating the operations room where all the regional components, the technical and operational structures, the service managers, and the volunteers are present. It also coordinates operations at local level through the Agency territorial offices by progressively activating all the necessary functions and connecting with the national level.

Each of these structures will have different capacities and decision-making powers. For wildfire risk, in the summer, the Permanent Unified Operations Room (SOUP) is established at the COR to manage fire emergencies.³¹ SOUP is a collaboration with operators from the Forest Carabinieri, Fire Brigades and civil protection volunteers. This operation runs 24 hours a day during the summer.

Figure 22: Regional system activation for hazard events that require extraordinary resources.

There are also Municipal Operational Centres (COC) which are a key reference point for DRM. These centres focus on a single location (e.g. Rimini) and ensure that the Territorial Offices are able to undertake DRM support functions activated by the administration. These include weather monitoring, flood service coordination, and volunteer coordination. To respond to a large-scale event (like the 2023 extreme floods) will require the coordination of different levels of governance, as set out above in Figure 22. It is particularly important to ensure that the various operational rooms are connected, and that there is further connection to the national system through the activation of the National Crisis Unit (Irvine et al., 2025). During the response phase for the May 2023 extreme floods there was also a connection between the COR and the National Civil Protection Operations Committee. This involved the

³⁰ <https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/agenzia/centro-operativo-regionale> [10.09.2025]

³¹ <https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/agenzia/centro-operativo-regionale> [22.08.2025]

participation and collaboration of a range of different agencies at varying different levels, including: the operational structures, bodies, and administrations of the National Civil Protection Service (National Fire Brigade, Army, Navy and Air Force, Carabinieri, State Police, Penitentiary Police, Guardia di Finanza, Harbour Master's Offices-Coast Guard, Italian Red Cross, Civil Protection Volunteers, National Alpine and Speleological Rescue Corps-CNSAS, personnel of the scientific bodies of the National System for Environmental Protection, and personnel of the companies providing essential services - telephony, energy, gas and mobility).

The Emilia-Romagna RWL Workshop (September 2023) highlighted further multi-level governance arrangements as it highlighted that the Ferrara Office was working in collaboration with UTG Prefecture of Ferrara and the Carabinieri Forestry Corps, Fire Brigade, Municipality of Comacchio, Port Authority of Porto Garibaldi, and Coordination of the Civil Protection Volunteer Association of Ferrara. As part of this, all of these actors have signed an ad hoc procedure which relates to bonfires. The focus of this collaboration is more targeted towards DRM, although CCA will also require collaboration between the agency/structures involved. An additional pre-existing relationship was between ARTSPC-ER, Rimini Civil Protection, and GECOSistema.

The GAR report also identifies some concerns around the practicalities of collaborations within the DRM system. Although the Italian system is decentralised, coordination (particularly in relation to scientific aspects) tends to follow a top-down approach. Studies have indicated that using a bottom-up approach and incorporating local DRR knowledge would help strengthen the overall approach to DRM (e.g., Mercer et al., 2009; UN-DRR, 2009; Hiwasaki et al., 2014). This is supported by the principle of subsidiarity which is enshrined in the CP Code 2018. However, the practical implementation of this approach faces many challenges.

Overall, actor roles appear to be working at different levels to support either DRM or CCA, but is less clear to what extent the roles are working towards integrated DRM and CCA. This has resulted in an assessment of 3 (Medium Priority). This is a relevant priority for the RWL as the ability of actor roles at different levels to coordinate and support DRM/CCA actors was highlighted in the initial DIRECTED meetings.

<p>Multilevel/Polycentric Governance: To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM and CCA processes?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Accountability

As discussed above, the key decision-maker for disaster response is the mayor, and consequently they are accountable/liable for the consequences of the decisions that they make. This can become problematic during disaster response as the mayor will need to balance the disaster response decisions with other considerations such as the impacts on tourism. Discussions with the RWL highlighted a tendency for mayors to question civil protection officers before making their decision, particularly if new data/models/tools are utilised. There do not appear to be any mechanisms or strategies in place to support accountability concerns around DRM/CCA decision-making.

In the aftermath of the 2023 Emilia-Romagna floods there were calls for improved infrastructure and climate adaptation measures (Irvine et al., 2025). Issues around accountability have also been raised via questions submitted to the European Parliament around the implementation of DRM and CCA frameworks. This raised concerns around maintenance around rivers.

Based on these examples, this indicator has been assessed as 2 (Low Priority), as this is an area where there is potential for growth. This indicator has been assessed as a low priority, as although concerns around accountability can impact decision-making, these are being addressed through the communication of the value of the updated models/data tools to key decision-makers.

<p>Accountability: To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support decision-making DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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3.2.1.3 Risk Management/Knowledge

DRM/CCA policy/plan coherence

As discussed above, there are a number of plans in the Italian system for DRM and CCA at the national and regional level. This includes a legal requirement set out in Article 18(3) of the Civil Protection Code 2018 that there must be coordination between civil protection (DRM) plans at the regional and municipal level in alignment with the national level plans and any international obligations (like EU Directives). These are guided by the Directive of 30 April 2021 ('Guidelines for the preparation of Civil Protection Plans at the various territorial levels'). To implement these regulations the Emilia-Romagna Region prepared and approved the *"Outline for the preparation of civil protection plans at the provincial/metropolitan city and district levels"* through Resolution No. 228 of February 20, 2023.

This complements Resolution No. 1103 of July 4, 2022, *"Regional civil protection planning: identification of Optimal Territorial Areas (ATO)"*. This relates to the organizational criteria pursuant to the Civil Protection Code and approval of the draft 'Agreement for the establishment, in the event of civil protection emergencies, of a Rescue Coordination Center (CCS) and an Integrated Provincial Operations Room (SOPI)'. These defined the initial contents of the Regional Civil Protection Plan. A further reference document for civil protection planning (particularly for municipalities) is the *"Approval of the document "Guidelines for the preparation of municipal civil protection plans"* introduced through the Resolution of 10 September 2018 no. 1439. An updated version is now being drafted to be aligned with the Directive of 30 April 2021.

The level of coherence between such DRM plans and CCA plans is unclear, however, CCA interventions are being implemented in Rimini which benefit DRM (further discussed below), thus the goals can align.

Issues around DRM/CCA policy/plan coherence were raised during the wildfires workshop (September 2023). An initial concern was the lack of regulation around climate change. Further points of weakness included a need for greater balance between sector regulations for the various actors, and a need for greater economic resources for volunteers and municipalities. The need for further resources was also brought up in relation to the management/maintenance of green areas. This is critical for preparing for wildfires as it helps to avoid the triggering of forest fires due to lightning. This kind of event is becoming more likely due to the increase in storms as a result of climate change.

To address these issues there needs to be coherence between the policies/plans for both DRM and CCA. An example which was identified in the 2023 wildfire workshop was the need for forest fire risk to be considered in land use planning frameworks. Furthermore, there is a need for territorial planning to be involved in the CCA actions that are going to be implemented. It is also critical that DRM frameworks recognise the impact of climate change of drought periods and adapt accordingly, one suggestion for this is to extend the AIB (Forest Fire Fighting) period. The final improvement action identified in the 2023 workshop was the need for verification of the type of vegetative area for different operating modes.

Due to the existence and alignment of DRM plans at all levels, this indicator has been assessed as a 4 (Low Priority) as it is reasonably developed. However, there is room for improvement to further align DRM with CCA planning. This indicator has been identified as low priority because the alignment of objectives/goals is reasonably developed and it is not feasible to address.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent do objectives/goals and in plans at different levels align to address DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Synergies/tradeoffs interventions

In Rimini, two existing interventions were identified that highlight the synergies between CCA and DRM, the Parco del Mare and water storage areas. The Parco del Mare is a major seafront redevelopment project undertaken in the city of Rimini, with the first section completed in September 2023.³² It was created as a CCA measure to increase the “urban and environmental quality of the promenade of the city”. This turned 15 kilometres of waterfront into “green infrastructure”.

The Parco del Mare encourages biodiversity as it features a variety of plant species and acts as a sustainable urban drainage system. The SaferPlaces tool by GeoSistema contributed detailed analysis of the hazards and related damage that could result from a variety of flooding scenarios. These scenarios showed the benefit of implementing the Parco del Mare and highlighted the consequences if it had not been built including the net economic damage from extreme weather events. This CCA intervention has co-benefits for DRM as more people are protected from extreme events, reducing the need for response by the Civil Protection system, and increasing their capacity to support other vulnerable areas.

³² <https://saferplaces.co/rimini-and-climate-change-the-added-value-of-the-sea-park-parco-del-mare/> [16.08.2025]

In relation to flood mitigation, Rimini has large water storage areas which can contain 20,000m³ of water and can be used when required to help prevent flooding in Rimini. The mayor and civil protection officers must make decisions around when it is appropriate to use these facilities, and weigh up the consequences and/or benefits for the city. For example, if the water storage tanks are full and there is more rain predicted, they need to decide if they release water to the sea allowing for more water storage to prevent flooding, but this will result in poor water quality for 2–3 days and no swimming, impacting local tourism. These decisions rely on accurate precipitation data which is when/tools like SaferPlaces including high-resolution data from the HERA radar network are critical.

Based on these examples it appears the synergies have been maximized (where practicable) and trade-offs minimised, which has resulted in an assessment of 4 (Low Priority) as this indicator has been reasonably developed. This indicator has been assessed as Low Priority because the goal of the RWL within the DIRECTED project is not to implement DRM/CCA interventions (like the Parco del Mara), thus it is not feasible to address.

Synergies/tradeoffs Interventions: To what extent are synergies maximized, and trades-offs minimized across DRM/CCA interventions?	4 [LP]
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Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships

The Emilia-Romagna RWL hosts and technical support partner (ARSTPC-ER, ARPAE, GECOsystema) already had strong pre-existing working relationships before the DIRECTED project. This is due (at least in part) to agreements and memorandums of understanding between different actors. There is an agreement between ARSTPC-ER and ARPAE for forecasting and prevention activities in order to strengthen the civil protection system and manage the regional alert system as set out in Regional Council Resolution no. 1212 of June 24, 2024. ARSTPC-ER also has agreements and memorandum of understanding for emergency interventions with the National Fire Brigade, Forestry Carabinieri, Porto-Guardia Coastal Authorities, State Police, FSI-Italian State Railways Group, Multiutility Services Companies for water and waste management (IREN/IRETI, HERA, ATERSIR), Telephone Operators (Telecom/Tim, Wind3, Iliad, Vodafone), and Energy Managers (ENEL, TERNA).³³

In addition, ARSTPC-ER and ARPAE identified pre-existing collaboration and tight connections with municipalities, land reclamation and irrigation authorities, and water utility companies, which enabled them to actively involve them in the RWL as stakeholders.

Additionally, civil protection officers from both the ARSTPC-ER and the Rimini and Ferrara Territorial Offices have formed strong working relationships. Furthermore, Article 13(2) of the CP Code creates an obligation for different civil protection agencies to cooperate together. Therefore, they are likely to have strong relationships. Article 14(4) states that:

“National and regional operational structures carry out the [civil protection] activities ...particular forms of participation, integration and collaboration with the operational structures of the National civil protection service are regulated.”

This means that collaboration between operational structures of the civil protection service is required under the CP Code. Again, this will lead to relationships between DRM actors.

Although these relationships are recognised in the CP Code and there were strong pre-existing relationships between some DRM actors, the ability to coordinate and support multiple stakeholders (for both early warning and CCA) was identified as a challenge for the RWL in the initial DIRECTED meeting. This difficulty was viewed as a “critical barrier in implementing integrated DRR and CCA strategies” (Pancioli et al., 2024, pp35). These challenges were reflected in discussions during the wildfire workshop (September 2023) where a closer relationship between all institutions was identified as missing. Additionally, there was a need to involve other actors such as the beach establishment managers in governance, managers of essential services, and the Fire Brigade even in ordinary times. This meeting also identified a need for coordination between managers of the bathing establishments, as they currently act independently. This is then linked to perception issues as the managers of these bathing establishments view the institutions as causing the problems. An additional relationship to strengthen is the involvement of the Essential

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<https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/gestione-emergenze/convenzioni-e-protocolli-d2019intesa/convenzioni-per-attivita-di-previsione-e-prevenzione> [17.09.2025]

Services Provider, CADF. This is a critical collaboration for managing withdrawal points (hydrants).

Generally in Italy there is strong collaboration between scientists and civil protection, as highlighted in the 2022 GAR report (UNDRR, 2022) which identified hybrid experts who have experience in a scientific field related to civil protection and then work in a management role to enable coordination and collaboration between science and practice. This is reflected in Article 19 of the CP Code which addresses the role of the scientific community. Although it does not appear to create a legal obligation for the inclusion of the scientific community, it does assume that they will have a role. Furthermore, the Civil Protection Department does have a technical-scientific advisory body in the form of the commission for the forecasting and prevention of major risks as set out in Article 20. Collaboration between civil protection and ministries with technical-scientific expertise is also promoted by the Civil Protection Department under Article 21.

The interactions with the RWL have highlighted how different DRM/CCA actors interact. Based on this evidence this question has been assessed as being a 4 (Medium Priority) as these relationships are reasonably developed. This is identified as being a Medium Priority for the RWL as this is something that will be developed as part of the DIRECTED project through meetings, workshops and scenarios (e.g. the wildfire scenario). The RWL has indicated that they want to improve coordination, especially for wildfire risk, with the simulations.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent do DRM/CCA actors interact at appropriate levels?</p>	<p>4 [MP]</p>
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As mentioned above, the interactions with the RWL have shown a high level of willingness to collaborate. Another area for collaboration was identified in the RWL Second Workshop (September 2023) where a willingness to strengthen collaboration with volunteers was highlighted. This included increasing the prevention activity undertaken by volunteers and monitoring wooded areas where cleaning and mowing is needed year round. Participants also indicated that they wanted to involve beach establishment managers, managers of essential services and the fire brigade to build relationships through the RWL during ‘ordinary times’ before events. They also wanted to engage private businesses (such as hoteliers and beach owners). However, RWL 2 has found that there is an unwillingness to engage after invitations to workshops and simulations were not taken up. Stakeholders identified the Whatsapp group created by COI Riviera del Conca (Cattolica- Misano Adriatico- Riccione- San Giovanni In M.- Coriano) as a method to communicate with local stakeholders affected by coastal events.

Further collaboration for DRM/CCA plans comes from public consultation. In Italy there is no overarching legal obligation to consult with the public when drafting legislation or plans.

However, there are Guidelines for Citizen Participation which invite public administrations to promote citizens’ participation.³⁴ At the national level public consultation was used when drafting the PNACC and the Integrated National Plan for Energy and Climate. In addition at the regional level a public consultation process was undertaken when developing the “Proposal for a local strategy to adapt to climate change by the Municipality of Reggio Emilia”.³⁵ However, no public consultation has been identified for the Civil Protection Code or DRM plans. This type of process can lead to greater collaboration between the public, practitioners, researchers, other experts, and decision-makers. However, there is no evidence that these examples went beyond formal requirements.

This question has been assessed as being a 4 (Low Priority), as the willingness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements is reasonably developed. The interactions with the RWLs has shown a willingness/openness for collaboration beyond formal requirements. This question has been identified as Low Priority for the RWL, as this is already reasonably developed and will continue to be built through the interactions (meetings, workshops, scenarios) with the DIRECTED project.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent is there willingness/openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Risk assessment data/models/tools

There are extensive risk modelling and related forecasting and monitoring systems in place in the Emilia-Romagna Region through ARPAE and the ARSTPC-ER. For coastal risk this includes the MeteoAlert Emilia-Romagna and Infomet websites, which are managed by ARPAE who handle the integration of multiple models, and monitors data/ forecasts. While Infomet includes a wildfire propagation and susceptibility index for wildfire risk ([Figure 23](#)).³⁶

³⁴ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2017/07/14/17A04797/sg> [22.08.2025]

³⁵ <https://consultazione.gov.it/it/le-consultazioni/le-consultazioni-regionali-e-locali/emilia-romagna/strategia-locale-adattamento-ai-cambiamenti-climatici-reggio-emilia/> [22.08.2025]

³⁶ <https://allertameteo.regione.emilia-romagna.it/> [16.09.2025]

FORECASTS AND REAL-TIME MONITORING PLATFORMS

Coastal risk

- Allerta meteo Emilia-Romagna website
- Infomet - ARPAE:
 - COSMO5 model
 - COSMO2I model
 - ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System
 - ARPAE's meteo-marine monitoring network
 - Porto Corsini's tide gauge - ISPRA
 - ARPAE's coastal critical warning forecasts
- CAE's monitoring network
- Sirem Efforts' monitoring network
- Dewetra platform (developed by national department of civil protection)

Wildfire risk

- Infomet - ARPAE
 - wildfire propagation and susceptibility index
- 'Registro incendi' (Fire register) webapp - Firefighters

Figure 23: ARPAE Forecasting and Real-Time Monitoring Platforms.

The meteorological numerical modelling, marine and coastal modelling and hydrogeological modelling are all set out in [Figure 24](#) below. ARPAE also has access to the Marine and Coastal Numerical Forecasting Unit, the Air-quality Numerical Forecasting Unit, the Regional Observation Network Unit, the Climate Observatory, the Control Room and Functional Centre for Civil Protection.

Figure 24: Overview of modelling available in the Emilia-Romagna ARSTPC-ER and ARPAE used for early warning and forecasting.

The suitability of the existing data/models/tools and critical gaps were identified by RWL (September 2023) including a lack of tools and data for forecasting fire risks, a need for data from live meteorological/marine events to predict the impacts of flooding on the coastal strip, the need to improve and harmonize monitoring networks, and for coastal alerting systems. Additionally, for pluvial forecasting, civil protection in Rimini identified the need for more high resolution, accurate and fast predictions to support their coordination and decision-making activities ahead of rainfall events. They only have data about potential rainfall or sea level but no tools for mapping flood hazard and risk related to upcoming storms in high resolution.

Additional points of weakness discussed were the lack of integration between the monitoring networks of the different operators, and the issues around the arrival times of data from the sensors especially for intense rainfall events that arrive with little warning. Discussions revealed that the Hera service manager monitors coastal events using its own Radar (Santa Giustina), and has a network of hydrometers and rain gauges, which are not yet integrated with ARPAE’s regional monitoring or forecasting network. Additionally, it was recognised that in order to shorten the arrival time, the type of access must be diversified, not as a common citizen. A practical issue raised was access to data whereby municipalities need to be able to direct access. This can be enabled through a management system to carry out monitoring directly. The number of people that can access the system simultaneously is critical as the Municipal Operations Center must be able to access the data without risking finding the weather alert site being overloaded by people trying to access it during an event.

For wildfires, drones and thermal imaging cameras are used, but the system currently lacks a fire risk forecasting platform. In addition, there is a need for the implementation and integration of fire propagation models, and an increase in anemometers.

Although gaps have been raised around the suitability of the tools, there is a strong system for coastal/flood forecasting, which has gaps that can now be improved upon. For this reason, this question has been assessed as a 4 (High Priority), as it is reasonably developed and there is a lot of scope to improve via RWL activities in DIRECTED.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent are (existing) risk modelling data/models/tools fit-for-purpose to address key DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>4 [HP]</p>
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Given the strong foundation of collaboration between ARSTPC-ER, ARPAE and GeoSistema pre-DIRECTED and the scientific background of the hosts, this enabled an openness and desire for innovation. Since 2020, SaferPlaces has been applied in Emilia-Romagna with regional civil protection, the hydrometeorological service, and municipalities supporting planning and preparedness initiatives, including coastal-risk and urban-resilience, flood-damage assessment, and municipal planning. SaferPlaces uses geospatial, satellite, climate data, and AI-based model combined into a cloud computing environment to simulate event-based fluvial-pluvial-coastal floods. It can also simulate the building-level damages caused by floods of any scale. The model directly calculates inundation, and the rates of damages are calculated by the function where water depth is input. The geographical target of the model is 1-5 meter resolution. The model can integrate all city-level risk reduction measures such as levees, elevation, and infiltration tanks on roofs (customizable with real-time results) but measures on altering sewage systems cannot be integrated.

As such through the RWL, the activities could further apply and advance application of SaferPlaces platform specifically for Provincial Civil Protection Officers based in municipalities to cover more hazards, combine hazards and support an operational and risk mapping/planning service that support interoperability and integration for DRM and CCA.

As such, given the preexisting relationships and knowledge of the SaferPlaces tool by the RWL, it provides scope for innovation in its co-design and customization with civil protection representatives at the municipal level. It will act as the foundation technical solution development in this RWL while supporting interoperability of existing data and predictive models provided by ARPAE and others like HERA SpA.

As such, this RWL was in a strong position for embracing innovative risk models/data/tools but has room for improvement in enabling interoperability by advancing the SaferPlaces platform which is identified as a High Priority for the RWL and is assigned a rating of 4.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent can DRM and CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools and interoperability across DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>4 [HP]</p>
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Legal implications of data/modelling

As set out in the CP Code, the mayor is responsible for making any major decisions around DRM, including for response. This responsibility impacts the mayor's approach to using new data/models in DRM/CCA decision-making. Discussions with the Civil Protection officers (June 2025) around the integration highlighted that although the Safer Places model is accurate, the decisions mayors take must be validated by something by the network or the region. The mayor will often question the civil protection officers, as ultimately the responsibility for any 'wrong' decisions will lie with the mayor. Civil protection officers are concerned about mayors using the formal data sources because this data is not the most up-to-date (e.g. using old Digital Elevation Model that does not include some updates the dike/bank level, evolution of the critical infrastructure roads, airport, electricity network) nor is it event based which is more useful for planning and preparedness at local level. Therefore, the mayor needs to fully trust the 'innovative' data/model outputs being provided to decide to use them over official sources.

This tension was seen in the aftermath of the May 2023 flooding event, as often the mayor's priority is tourism, which conflicts with some of the strategies that need to be taken to minimise flood damage/risk. For example, the water storage tank example above, where if the decision is made to open the flow of water to the sea then there will be no swimming allowed for several days which will impact tourists. The Civil Protection officers in Rimini commented that their relationship and trust with mayors in the hilly areas is stronger as they are more aware of the dangers/hazards/vulnerabilities and less dependent on tourism.

Due to the key decision-maker (mayor) being accountable for decisions made during emergency response, it appears that legal mindset/norms can limit rather than support the use of the 'best' data /models in the decision-making for DRM. For that reason, this indicator is assessed at a 2 (Medium Priority), as there is potential for growth around using legal mindsets or norms to support 'best' data/models. This indicator has been identified as a Medium Priority for the RWL, as improving data/modelling has been highlighted as a High Priority for the RWL so it is important that these models can then be used by decision-makers.

<p>Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools: To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support 'best' data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion/participation

The Civil Protection Code 2018, DRM plans and the interactions with the RWL has shown that citizen involvement in DRM is high through the volunteer organizations. Furthermore, Articles 31, 32, 38 and 39 all address citizen participation in civil protection (DRM). Article 18(2) then addresses the participation of citizens in civil protection planning. Although these sections address the role of volunteers/citizens in civil protection activities, these do not appear to include decision-making. Instead, citizens can only participate in planning and decision-making if the relevant authority chooses to involve them in the process. It is important to note that this is at the authorities’ discretion and is not a legal requirement. Citizens can also be involved with making submissions on legislation but this is only through a formal process so the engagement is fairly limited. Although the implementation of Directive 2007/60/EC in Emilia-Romagna has included the public participation process for each cycle of the Flood Risk Management Plan.

As there is little evidence that frameworks enable or require citizen involvement in decision-making, this question has been assessed as a 1 (Low Priority) as this is an area where there is high potential for growth. This indicator has been tagged as a Low Priority as it is beyond the scope of the RWL/DIRECTED project to adapt framework to address citizen involvement in decision-making. Furthermore, this indicator is dependent/interlinked with improving the risk communication indicator which is a higher priority.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent do frameworks enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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An example where citizens have been involved in decision-making was through the LIFE PRIMES (Preventing flooding Risks by Making resilient communitiEs) project. The aim of this was to “build resilient communities by engaging them in early warning and flood risk prevention measures”.³⁷ This project included the development of an online dissemination tool, consultation around alerts with the three Italian regions involved (including Emilia-Romagna), and the compilation of Civic AdaptAction Plans (CAAP). CAAP was an innovative online tool which enabled the activation of communities in local policies, including for DRM/CCA. This tool allowed citizens to propose actions to civil protection authorities, to improve their knowledge through short tutorials, and to test their skills. These tutorials covered topics such as: flood risk and seas storms, climate change, adaptation actions, and alert and civil protection plans. To increase the participation of citizens in the development of CAAP, a co-productive process was undertaken which involved local communities of the pilot project areas and schools. These interactions included preparatory meetings with the administrations alongside informative and operational workshops with the stakeholders, flood risk exercises and demonstration actions.

³⁷ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE14-CCA-IT-001280/preventing-flooding-risks-by-making-resilient-communities#:~:text=The%20LIFE%20PRIMES%20project%20aimed%20to%20build.early%20warning%20and%20flood%20risk%20prevention%20measures.> [17.09.2025]

In the aftermath of the 2023 Emilia-Romagna floods steps were taken to engage citizens post-event (Irvine et al., 2025). For example, a dedicated portal was created “Emilia-Romagna. Rebuilding after the flood”³⁸, which provides information about the event including the reports. The region has also made a conscientious effort to remember the events and commitment made in emergencies through a range of different initiatives including “A day to say thank you” in Faenza on June 15 2024, organized together with institutions, state forces, and the world of volunteering.³⁹ Although these activities are making good progress in enhancing citizen inclusion/participation, they still do not reach the level of involving citizens in decision-making.

The LIFE PRIMES project is an example of enhancing citizen participation in decision-making. Furthermore, the role of volunteers is recognised as being highly valuable, although the RWL workshop (November 2024) did identify a need to increase the recognition of volunteers for DRM at various territorial activities. However, it is unclear how volunteer activities translate to decision-making. Due to this reasoning, this question has been assessed as a 3 (Low Priority) as this is an area where there is potential for growth. This question has been identified as being a Low Priority as enhancing citizen inclusion/participation will be focused on more in relation to public warning/risk communication.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion/participation in decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Public warning/risk communication

The initial meetings with the RWL showed that public warning/risk communication is a gap that the stakeholders were already aware of and wanted to improve.

³⁸ www.regione.emilia-romagna.it/alluvione [25.08.2025]

³⁹ <https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/novita/video/una-giornata-per-dire-grazie-alluvione-un-anno-dopo> [25.08.2025]

In Emilia-Romagna there is an advanced regional warning system for flood alerts and warnings. (ISPRA, 2023). The Emilia-Romagna Region's warning system is based on the collaboration between ARSTPC-ER, ARPAE-Meteo, and some of the Region's technical services (DGR. 1761/2020). This warning system involves four colour codes (green, yellow, orange and red). The colour codes correspond to the activation of the civil protection operational phases: attention, pre-alarm, and alarm. The alert system is active both in the forecast phase and in the event phase. It both prepares specific preventive and preparedness activities for the management of expected phenomena, and activates actions aimed at addressing critical situations that may arise. This colour code system is set out in [Figure 25](#) below.

Color-Coded Risk Assessment and Operational Response

Color Code	Description	Operational Phase
Green	No significant phenomena expected.	Normal conditions <i>Routine monitoring</i>
Yellow	Possibility of localized events with low danger to people. Limited damages.	Attention <i>Increased monitoring and preventive measures</i>
Orange	Possibility of more intense and widespread events, or a single severe phenomenon. Medium danger and more extensive damages.	Pre-alarm <i>Activation of emergency plans and mobilization of resources</i>
Red	Possibility of very intense and widespread events, or one extremely severe phenomenon. Very high danger to people and extensive, severe damages.	Alarm <i>Full activation of emergency response</i>

Figure 25: Color-Coded Risk Assessment and Operational Response.

Public warning communication was an area of reflection in the aftermath of the 2023 Emilia-Romagna floods, as highlighted in Irvine et al., (2025). During this event, flood warnings and emergency alerts were issued by the Civil Protection Department. These were disseminated using a range of different methods including SMS messages, social media, radio, and television broadcasts. Authorities also used dedicated emergency apps to ensure that both municipalities and the public were kept informed. The direct coordination between municipalities and the regional crisis management team was facilitated through teleconference systems. Although the communication during this event has been viewed as largely effective, a number of challenges were highlighted. There were practical impacts of the weather event, as infrastructure damage caused the communication networks to suffer temporary disruptions. This was remedied through the use of backup systems such as satellite communication.

Effective public risk communication plays a critical role in updating the public as an event unfolds. This includes evacuation orders and other safety measures. A challenge that arose for Emilia-Romagna in 2023, was around the overload of information. This was particularly problematic with social media as there was an issue with misinformation. Although steps were taken to address this misinformation, it was challenging to manage this task during the large-scale response.

Figure 26: Risk Assessment in Relation to Threshold Markers for Emergency Response.

There are a number of different non-governmental stakeholders involved in managing coastal-hydraulic risk on the Emilia-Romagna coast, as highlighted in the 2nd RWL workshop (September 2023). These include trade associations, beach establishment managers, lifeguards, hoteliers, tourist facilities and fishermen. These actors are involved informally as part of a customary arrangement, meaning there is no regulation or procedure to manage their involvement. The RWL identified that an institutional channel to manage their involvement would be beneficial. A point of weakness identified in the governance framework for coastal-hydraulic risk is the need for more frequent updates once a storm warning has been issued. This highlights an issue in the warning communication system.

During the September 2023 workshop, the RWL also discussed points of weakness for communication. A key issue is how to communicate to citizens, this is problematic as many municipalities have delegated this responsibility to the ARPAE which refers to the weather alert portal. As highlighted earlier there is also an issue with timing for data, as during the event, information and data can be delayed, and arrive late at the Municipalities which will impact the COC and other decision-makers like the mayor. Furthermore, using Telegram as a communication method is complicated as it is not possible to know the territorial coverage of the users, instead only the number.

There were also issues with risk communication that were identified during this workshop. The RWL identified that there was a culture of risk that was missing, and thus the perception of risk was skewed, which impacts the actions to be taken by individuals in preparing for future events, and the behaviours to be followed during them. Part of what is missing is an understanding by citizens that they are part of the civil protection system, and thus have a responsibility to reduce and mitigate risk. The civil protection officers have also identified a need to build their capacity to engage with citizens during 'ordinary' times, rather than just focussing on communicating warnings/actions more effectively at the local level. These gaps need to be focused on during training and be communicated using effective methods.

The RWL also identified a number of improvement actions including the need to invest in communication, address the problem of geo-localization of information, evaluate the consistency of the tools used by municipalities to disseminate civil protection information to citizens, and ensure that these communication tools reflect local scenarios (and are updated as needed). The final improvement point around risk communication relates to strategies to combat the generalized and often catastrophic media information that citizens receive. To counter this misinformation, the communications from local civil protection administrations and managers needs to be improved.

Furthermore, during a wildfire workshop in September 2023, a gap was identified in the “last mile” of communication between institutions and citizens. This gap has been emphasised for the wildfire scenario, as there have been difficulties with communicating the risks of wildfires with vulnerable groups, in particular with tourists (who are unlikely to be connected with the national system). This is an area which has been identified as having room for improvement. It is also an issue for storms, as beaches are often not accessible after a flood event. This is currently communicated through a system of flags which needs to be communicated to vulnerable groups.

Risk communication around wildfires is critical as lighting bonfires can be part of local celebrations, for example on the Ferrara coast it is customary to light bonfires on the beach for the holiday of Ferragosto. However, recently due to severe drought weather conditions steps have been taken to reduce the risk of wildfires including a ban on bonfires along the beaches which was issued by the Municipality of Comacchio. Risk communication requires the collaboration of a range of different actors. The Ferrara Office together with the UTG Prefecture of Ferrara and the Carabinieri Forestry Corps, Fire Brigade, Municipality of Comacchio, Port Authority of Porto Garibaldi, Coordination of the Civil Protection Volunteer Association of Ferrara and LIDA Ferrara provincial section of Ferrara, have signed an ad hoc procedure in the event that critical situations are identified relating to preparatory activities for the lighting of bonfires or bonfires already lit.

During the wildfire workshop the RWL identified strengths and weaknesses of the current approach to risk communication. Strengths included the bulletin on forest fires published on the website of the Agency for Territorial Security and Civil Protection. This forest fire bulletin is very clear and communicative. Dissemination of this information should be implemented. Furthermore, it was found through the *“Forest Fire Surveillance Service Project - Spotting Project”* that the communication strategies employed through this project were effective. A practical strength is volunteers who ensure that campsites are well organized and encourage the dissemination or risk information.

Although there are a number of strengths around Emilia-Romagna’s risk communication approach, there are also gaps that have been identified. Although the forest fire bulletin is clear and communicative, it is not well known. This is problematic in terms of the dissemination of this risk information. There appears to be significant gaps in the risk communication as a whole. Firstly, there is a lack of information for citizens (particularly tourists) explaining the risk of forest fires. Next it is unclear which communication channels are most suited to disseminating this information for different population groups such as young people, adults, seasonal tourists, day tourists. There are practical issues around communicating this information as the coverage of the Tetra radio network needs to be expanded to Lido di Spina. There is also a lack of information for citizens/tourists on how to act in the event of a fire, and where it does exist it is not very effective. There are also issues with the risk information/communication materials themselves as the current resources often use repressive messages and information. This highlights a need for education around forest risk. A further challenge is that although risk communication is recognised as being critical for disaster preparedness, the municipality lacks resources to activate a communication campaign. For these reasons, this indicator has been assessed as 3 (High Priority). The RWL has indicated that public warning/risk communication is one of their high priorities.

<p>Public warning/Risk Communication: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Social justice

Building onto the public warning/risk communication indicator, it is critical that disenfranchised groups can engage in DRM/CCA. It is currently unclear to what extent this currently occurs or could occur within the existing governance framework. The integration of disenfranchised groups is critical to ensure communication around DRM/CCA is reaching these vulnerable groups. This includes ensuring that public warnings and risk communication is available in a number of different languages and via different modes (e.g. in paper format, online, audio, visual, through social media etc.). Increasing digital literacy outreach may also help with this risk communication. This could be implemented by launching community-based training to support vulnerable populations in areas like accessing digital alert systems and understanding emergency messaging. This mechanism may be particularly useful for the elderly or migrants, as recommended by Irvine et al. (2025). It was identified that municipalities do hold data on the vulnerable groups (e.g. elderly, those with disabilities) but this is not directly used by Civil Protection to prepare/respond to events.

Due to the lack of evidence around the engagement of disenfranchised groups in DRM/CCA, this indicator has been assessed as a 1 (Medium Priority), as this is an area where there is high potential for growth. This indicator has been assessed as Medium Priority as it is linked with risk communication, which has been identified as a High Priority indicator.

<p>Social Justice: To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM and/or CCA?</p>	<p>1 [MP]</p>
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Feasibility

The Emilia-Romagna Region is traditionally viewed as a stronghold of the Italian Communist Party and its successors which has emerged as the present-day Democratic Party. This region is also considered to be strong financially as the GDP is above the national average, there has also been positive GDP growth, job creation and exports (DEFRA, 2019).

As mentioned above, Emilia-Romagna (and Rimini) have extensive frameworks for DRM and CCA. The CCA framework in particular is more advanced than other regions of Italy and the plans for Bologna have been assessed favourably by academic reports (see Serra et al., 2022, Colocci et al., 2024, Pietrapertosa et al., 2024). For example, Emilia-Romagna scored highly for preparing the ground for adaptation, assessing climate change risks and vulnerabilities, and identifying adaptation options in a study undertaken by Colocci et al., (2024). In this study, Emilia-Romagna (along with Lombardy and Sardinia) was identified as the best performer for the development and performance of regional policies for CCA. It has also been identified as a strong performer for the potential of its regional policies to drive change. Furthermore, a study by Pietrapertosa et al., (2021) identified Emilia-Romagna as the only region to have an Integrated Mitigation and Adaptation Strategy. This study also identified Bologna as being “very active in climate planning”, and scored it as having the best overall performance when evaluating local adaptation and mitigation climate plans (alongside Ancona). This was due to Bologna and Ancona being the only two municipalities that had urban adaptation plans.

Due to this evidence, this indicator has been assessed as being a 4 (Low Priority) as this is an area which is reasonably developed. This has been tagged as Low Priority as this is already a reasonably developed area and it is beyond the scope of the DIRECTED project to change the political, social and economic situation.

<p>Feasibility: To what extent is the political, social, and economic situation supporting DRM/CCA action?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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3.2.1.4 Knowledge co-production

Collaborative Mechanisms

The RWL in Emilia-Romagna already has formal vertical collaborative mechanisms that institutionalise communication among key stakeholders (as outlined in the indicator Legal framework for DRM/CCA and expanded in actor relationships, indicator rating at 4).

Horizontal collaboration is also strong with the RWL. At the start of the project, strong pre-existing relationships existed between RWL hosts including the technical support partner GECOSistema (and its platform SaferPlaces) which helped build a strong foundation to foster transdisciplinary collaboration, allowing the engagement of a wide range of professional

actors across different sectors relevant at different levels needed to address the priorities (flooding and wildfires).

However, there is scope for improving relationships and fostering additional collaborative arrangements. For example, to connect the DRM and CCA actors at the municipal level, and for enabling more multi-stakeholder collaboration around wildfires (e.g. firebrigade), supporting collaboration with utilities to access and share more data (e.g. HERA Group radar/monitoring network) and engaging with business/community representatives to bridge connections with tourists. Additionally, while collaboration with volunteers is strong, as highlighted under the indicator (Citizen) Inclusion and Participation, broader citizen involvement in co-production processes remains limited. However, the existing mechanisms provide a solid foundation with potential for expansion.

Overall, the RWL has been placed in a clear context and is pluralistic to enable transdisciplinary collaboration. It is assigned a rating of 3 (intermediate) and is a Medium Priority as this will be naturally addressed through the RWL setup.

<p>Collaborative Mechanisms: To what extent do collaborative mechanisms exist to foster diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production

The goals/needs for knowledge co-production in the Emilia-Romagna RWL were well defined at the start given the pre-existing relationships around fluvial and coastal flooding between RWL hosts and technical partners. However, there remained space and interest to expand this collaboration to address other goals and priorities in different municipalities i.e. wildfire risk in Comacchio, through the RWL which required engagement of additional stakeholders like the Po Delta Parks and biodiversity management body and fire fighters who did actively engage. The work being undertaken by the Emilia-Romagna RWL is clearly goal oriented with priorities established and confirmed within the first year to co-develop the Data Fabric to enable more interoperability, and building risk communication tools especially to share with tourists around the risks of wildfires.

Overall, there are clear goals, and the RWL process enables active engagement and interactions to ensure that the research is interactive. For these reasons this indicator has been assessed as a 4, because the shared understanding of problems/challenges/needs for knowledge co-production is reasonably developed and is a Medium Priority as these goals will naturally evolve and be addressed throughout the RWL process.

Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production: To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?	4 [MP]
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Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production

The extent to which Emilia-Romagna RWL stakeholders have capacities and skills for knowledge co-production appears uneven but developing, as the lab hosts have demonstrated a strong interest and desire to improve. RWL hosts highlighted that they had participated in/supported co-production work pre-DIRECTED, including some collaboration work with CCA practitioners on certain projects, but with limited scope, often linking to specific projects or tasks. In particular, working on the Civic Adaptation Action Plan (CAAP - Life Primes). Examples were also provided around the design processes and creative methods which were used pre-DIRECTED, including stakeholder engagement for other projects (Life Primes, Stream, Floods Directive Public Participation). Furthermore, the RWL hosts had experience engaging with technical/risk modellers and were very receptive to the training and support around facilitating creative/interactive methods. For example the first meeting of the RWL (March 2023) was quite formal and presentation oriented which then shifted in the next workshops (September 2023, November 2024) which used interactive and systems thinking and creative methods.

This shows that the RWL were willing to build upon their capacities/skills for knowledge co-production with the support of DIRECTED. For these reasons this indicator has been assessed as being a 3 and Medium Priority, as the DRM/CCA stakeholders capacity/skills for knowledge co-production are reasonably developed, and there is a clear openness and willingness to engage in new methods through the RWL process going forward.

Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production: To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production?	3 [MP]
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3.3.1.2.5 Key Risk Governance Gaps/Aligned Indicators

The assessment of the Risk-Tandem indicators in the Emilia-Romagna RWL identifies three key risk governance gaps, i.e. those indicated as the highest priorities to be addressed through the Risk-Tandem application.

The first two high priorities relate to the fit-for-purposeness of data/models/tools to address key DRM/CCA challenges (rated at 4) and embracing innovative data/models/ tools and interoperability across DRM and CCA (rated at 4). There were strong pre-existing relationships between RWL hosts ARPAE and ARSTPC-ER, and technical partners GECOSistema, and related collaboration on the SaferPlaces platform. This allows for a strong starting point to further advance interoperability of existing data and models, while embracing new models and tools supporting innovation in coastal and pluvial risk modelling and mapping.

The third high priority identified improving public risk and warning/ forecast communication (rated at 3) especially for wildfires. This includes ensuring that public warnings and risk communication is available in a number of different languages and via different modes (e.g. in paper format, online, audio, visual, through social media etc.) to reach different societal groups especially tourists, drawing a connection with the social justice indicator. Doing so requires improving relationships and interaction between ARSTPC-ER, Po Delta Parks and the biodiversity management body, which will be strengthened through the RWL knowledge co-production activities.

Overall the other medium priorities around improving collaboration mechanisms (rated at 3), functionality of roles and responsibilities (rated at 3), and strength of actor relationships (rated at 4) are expected to be addressed indirectly by focusing on the highest priorities through the co-production work in the RWLs.

3.2.2 Growth Phase

To address key gaps highlighted, the Emilia-Romagna RWL further refined their key priorities in their different geographic locations and identified expected outputs to address the related challenges through the RWL activities.

Firstly, to address the challenge of enhancing the risk assessment data/tools/models and improving interoperability for DRR and CCA, the RWL aimed to co-design the “Data Fabric” platform with a focus on forecasting and real-time flood monitoring/mapping for coastal and pluvial flooding in the Municipality of Rimini (Rimini Province). Secondly, to address the challenge of public wildfire risk communication, the RWL aimed to focus on developing practical communication materials for the Municipalities of Mesola (the coast of Ferrara Province) and Comacchio (Ferrara Province).

The Growth Phase of the RWL in Emilia-Romagna involved multi-stakeholder workshops, simulation exercises and online meetings, as well as support, training and reflection between the RWL hosts and the researchers in DIRECTED - see details in Annex 1 Milestone 13 *Documentation of Co-Production Activities*. These RWL activities specifically addressed the priorities and expected outputs as detailed in the below sections. Additionally, the RWL activities are expected to address other risk governance indicators like strengthening multi-actor coordination and actor relationships.

Priority 1: Improved interoperability for coastal and pluvial flooding

The first meeting (March 2023) in the Emilia-Romagna RWL confirmed that support was needed for municipal emergency planning to improve the timing of data availability for real-time risk scenarios for flooding, and that the Regional level saw the value in the SaferPlaces tool to develop such real-time scenarios within the Data Fabric.

The next meeting (September 2023) was an interactive workshop using co-production methods with one group focused on understanding coastal risk using a hypothetical coastal event scenario with storm surge, thunderstorm and wind. The stakeholders mapped the strengths, weaknesses, and improvement actions related to risk knowledge, governance, communication, and policy ([Figure 27](#)). One of the areas for improvement highlighted by Civil Protection stakeholders was *“the need to have information tools that can be consulted during a meteorological-marine event, with some significant parameters also deduced from tools external to the institutional network (wave meters, tide gauges) which can provide information on the evolution of the phenomena in the short term (nowcasting).”* This demonstrates the need for interoperability and more fit-for-purpose models that provide near real time flood mapping and monitoring to support decision-making locally in Rimini.

To address this challenge a related User Story was developed (in line with Pontius et al., 2025) focusing on a regional Civil Protection Officer (based in Rimini). Their role is to inform (including early warnings) and coordinate with municipal Civil Protection Officers for disaster preparedness and response actions (incl. Sandbags/physical barriers and volunteer coordination) for potential flooding (pluvial and coastal) events. A rapid flood modelling tool and interoperable web platform that integrates real-time data (both nowcasting sensors, radar and sea/weather forecasts) to produce high resolution data of near-real time and short term forecast of pluvial and coastal flood events would improve their decision-making capacity. Additionally such a tool would help in municipal civil protection planning scenarios e.g. testing different physical barriers to decide the optimal location and design based on impact reduction, and exploring future scenarios that integrate climate data.

An online webinar (November 2023) with key stakeholders enabled a deeper discussion on existing data, models, and tools, and reflected on how the Data Fabric could meet the needs of such Civil Protection Officers. A representative from the Municipality of Rimini explained that *“We are the last mile; we are interested in the detailed scale and real-time for territorial protection.”* To enable the interoperability of data, meetings were held by HERA in Ferrara to finalize the high-resolution data that would be shared through an API to integrate it into the Data Fabric platform.

Figure 27: Co-production exercise for coastal risk in Emilia-Romagna RWL (September 2023).

Flood Simulation exercise was then organised in Rimini in June 2024 to test the regional forecasting and early warning system for coastal, river and rainfall/storm flooding using extreme weather and climate event modelling/data/tools, and to test implementation of risk management measures in a modelling setting with stakeholders and in real-life by volunteers.

The exercise also aimed to analyse the communication, coordination and governance procedures for early warning and early action. In order to guide and update civil protection planning for extreme scenarios, and understand how the municipality can communicate early warnings more timely and accurately with societal groups. To achieve this the key actors involved were the Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of the Emilia-Romagna Region - Hydro-Meteo-Climate Service - Functional Centre, Regional Agency for Territorial Safety and Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region, Rimini and Ferrara Territorial Office, Municipal Operations Centre, and Provincial Civil Protection volunteers. The exercise involves simulating the following concurrent events: 1) Intense storm precipitation characterised by 100 mm in 1 h localised over part of the territory of the municipality of Rimini, 2) Marine intrusion reaching a level of 1.85 m above mean sea level corresponds to the 2050 scenario with a 10-year return time according to Copernicus estimates. In terms of the impact and mapping of the hazard on the affected territory, modelling simulations were carried out using the Saferplaces platform and the RIM2D model, which are tools provided by the DIRECTED project which will be integrated into the Data Fabric. High-resolution maps were then available that could analyse in detail the extent of the impacted areas and the critical points that will be subject to mitigation measures to reduce the impact (Figure 28). As part of the exercise, volunteers were instructed to protect a dike with tarpaulin and apply sandbags to an area at high risk of flooding (Figure 29).

Figure 28: Coastal Flooding with Mean Sea Level at 1.85 m without protection (sandbags) (left image) and with protection (sandbags) (right image) at critical points on the canal port.

Figure 29: Flood simulation Rimini June 2024 using extreme coastal and flood scenarios from SaferPlaces to test volunteer actions including tarpaulin dike protection and sandbag application.

Outputs - Data Fabric for flooding

Based on the insights generated from the simulation and workshops, a **mock-up of the Data Fabric** for flooding was co-developed and presented to RWL stakeholders in November 2024 ([Figure 30](#)). The co-design process was led by GECOSistema in collaboration with project partners and stakeholders involved in RWL 2 and 52° North (consortium partner responsible for the Data Fabric). The interface is designed to offer analytical and visualization tools to support users and regional civil protection officials in Rimini in their ability to predict and manage coastal and pluvial flooding issues in real time. For pluvial risks, the platform offers real-time data monitoring through radar and rain gauges, weather analysis using advanced models such as ICON, and risk maps. For coastal risks, it enables monitoring of tides, sea-level rise forecasts, and real-time data on coastal events. A map highlights areas affected by precipitation, allows users to select and view data from various sources (e.g., HERA or ARPAE).

A graph displays rainfall intensity and accumulation over time, enabling civil protection officers to simulate scenarios by manually adjusting parameters such as rainfall and event duration. Additional maps illustrate simulation outcomes, such as flooded areas and economic damage calculations based on different analysis models, such as SaferPlaces. Users can activate various layers to overlay useful information, such as flooded areas, economic damages, and critical infrastructure (e.g., underpasses, parking lots, or underground residences). The platform also provides synthetic indicators to monitor the number of potentially affected sensitive receptors, highlighting the severity of anticipated impacts. The platform integrates practical functionalities for exporting or printing maps and results, facilitating information sharing with other actors involved in risk management. This well-structured and intuitive interface is designed to support strategic decision-making, enhancing collaboration between entities and improving community resilience in the face of extreme climate events.

Figure 30: Draft of the Data Fabric for flooding presented in November 2024 during RWL workshop.

Between November 2024 and April 2025 a **technical demo of the Data Fabric for flooding** was developed. An online workshop with the RWL stakeholders focused on walking through the Data Fabric's capabilities, emphasizing its integration with real-time forecasts, offline functionality, interpolation capabilities, and geometric data visualization. Participants discussed comparative analysis tools and explored specific functionalities, highlighting control room productivity and on-the-fly processing. The feedback helped to further refine the visualisation and design of the Data Fabric interface and finalize the implementation details within the Municipality of Rimini.

In June 2025, a further developed version of the Data Fabric for flooding was showcased at the **European Climate Change Adaptation Conference** in Rimini in the DIRECTED booth and was the focus of DIRECTED Side Event entitled *"Training for impact: Learning exchange on extreme flooding in Rimini using interoperable tools and governance frameworks."* The workshop involved 20 participants, including Territorial Civil Protection officers from Rimini and representatives from the technical coordination centre of ARSPTC-ER. Group exercises used extreme coastal or pluvial flooding scenarios from the Data Fabric for flooding, asking participants to map short term operational and long-term planning/ adaptation actions, and reflect on barriers and enablers for bridging these. The coastal scenario included mapping with and without the Parco del Mare (in the south), and discussions were raised around the cost and feasibility of another Parco del Mare (or similar barrier) in the north of Rimini. Other long-term measures were also discussed, such as moving critical infrastructure in hotspot areas, as well as the importance of warning communication among the changing seasonal population, highlighting the need to engage hoteliers to communicate warnings with tourists.

Figure 31: Demo of the Data Fabric for flooding showing pluvial real time rainfall radar data (as of June 2025).

Figure 32: Impressions from the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (June, 2026, Rimini) demonstrations of the Data Fabric (left) and side event training for impact (right).

Social vulnerability maps, developed by University College Cork, using available Census data (Figure 33) were also used in the group exercise which sparked interest from the Civil Protection Officers in using the data to support their decision making. Discussions highlighted that there are a lot of elderly homes in the Northern areas (which was not evident in the Census data) and the importance of civil protection to take into account needs of vulnerable groups in their response, e.g. evacuate old people first. A resulting action was to collect more detailed data from the Municipality of Rimini and update the Social Vulnerability Index and then include it in the Data Fabric as an additional source of information to use for civil protection planning and/or in operations.

The Data Fabric for flooding is expected to be finalised in early 2026, aiming to test the final Data Fabric in another Flood Simulation Exercise to document the benefits of having the tool.

A supporting user training manual and video will also be developed targeting the civil protection officers. The RWL priority and capacity has shifted more towards achieving Priority 2 on wildfire risk communication, as discussed further below.

Figure 33: Social Vulnerability Index mapping for Rimini, Italy using Census data (used within ECCA side event).

Priority 2: Wildfire Risk Communication

The second key priority for the Emilia-Romagna RWL is wildfire risk communication. In the province of Ferrara, the municipal territory of Comacchio has large areas of mixed forests and the Municipality of Mesola has wooded areas, mostly located in the coastal zone, both at risk of wildfires. The challenge is worse in the summer, especially August, with low rainfall and high tourism increasing the likelihood of fires.

The RWL workshop in September 2023 used a hypothetical wildfire scenario that penetrates the town centre to explore - risk knowledge, governance, policy, and communication. An important finding was that the communication of wildfire risk and prevention to the public is crucial, as highlighted by a representative from ARPAE *“We need to work more on communication. Many ideas have emerged, and innovation lies more in communication and improved sharing with stakeholders”*.

Parco regionale Delta del Po

Figure 34: Map of wooded areas in Comacchio and Mesola - and interactive discussions (September 2023) focused on wildfire governance, communication and data/models and tools.

The next workshop in Mesola (November 2024) then focused more on the co-exploration of communication around wildfire risk, collecting more detail on the available warning/risk information and coordination mechanisms (Figure 35) for an impression of the interactive knowledge co-production activities.

Figure 35: Impressions from the interactive exercise focused on understanding wildfire risk, communication, and governance (November 2024).

Significant events, such as the wildfire in Pianoro in August 2024, were highlighted to demonstrate the importance of coordination via SOUP (Unified Permanent Operations Room), as it coordinates activities among the Fire Brigade, Forestry Carabinieri, Civil Protection, and ARPAE. Their concerns were highlighted around the increasing vulnerability of forested areas due to climate change, with hotter and drier summers necessitating more precise planning. Insights were shared on the preparation of Wildfire Risk Bulletins (AIB -

Antincendio Boschivo) (Figure 36) derived from periodic operational meetings including collaboration between meteorologists and field operators to mitigate risks and enhance response effectiveness. Meteorologists rely on advanced models that calculate indices of susceptibility and propagation, incorporating factors such as wind, humidity, and hydro-climatic balance and the Haines Index, which evaluates atmospheric dryness and stability to predict fire growth potential.

Figure 36: Example of an AIB Wildfire risk bulletin (AIB - Antincendio Boschivo).

A key insight that emerged from the November 2024 workshops was that there is **limited signage and low public awareness of the wildfire bulletin** and inadequate engagement of tourists. The RWL stakeholders identified the need to increase targeted signage in at-risk areas and implement targeted information campaigns including distribution of leaflets, through schools and public events and social media. One idea that emerged was an illuminated information panel that shows localised information and possibly integrates loudspeakers. The discussions highlighted the need for dedicated communication experts, direct public notification systems, increased credibility, and better-trained personnel. They also recognised the need for more training around wildfires in relation to the Municipal Emergency Plans especially for mayors to understand their role. Specifically in relation to volunteers it was identified that they require increased visibility among the public during ‘ordinary’ times, enhanced coordination, new equipment, and more training exercises, including inter-agency drills. Furthermore, beneficial tools identified for communication included interoperable platforms combining different data, and radio infrastructure.

The next meeting between stakeholders online in February 2024 aimed to explore the implementation of the **Data Fabric for fire risk management**. During the discussion, the

idea emerged of developing a tool for civil protection that integrates meteorological data and fire spread models. The importance of having a model easily implementable for field operators and the need to test various models in real-world situations were emphasized. An integrated approach to fire risk management was discussed, linking regional databases and historical information. The importance of simulating realistic scenarios, considering factors such as vegetation and natural barriers, was highlighted to understand fire spread. It was proposed to integrate vegetation maps into the database to improve simulations, using historical fire data. The creation of a high-resolution map to characterize fuel and the need to limit the analysis to recent events were discussed. This would require collaboration with the Italian Forestry Corps to collect information on past fires, highlighting the importance of an integrated approach to improving fire preparedness and response. As such, the **user story** developed in Deliverable 5.2 (Pontius et al., 2025) related to wildfire risk focused on the territorial civil protection officers based in the municipalities and providing them with a rapid wildfire modelling tool and interoperable web platform via the Data Fabric that integrates real-time data to provide near-real time and short-term forecast of wildfire evolution. However, given the strong interest in communication emerging from the stakeholders, the development of the wildfire communication products were initially prioritised over the advancement of the Data Fabric for wildfires.

The next RWL activity focused on testing wildfire communication and response procedures during the **Forest Fire Fighting Emilia-Romagna exercise** (May 2025). The exercise involved over 80 participants, including volunteers, professionals, firefighters, Regional and Municipal Civil Protection officials, the Carabinieri Forest Fire Investigation Unit, and representatives from GECOsystema. The scenario was based on the Comacchio Municipality Civil Protection Emergency Plan and simulated a fire affecting a 6.8-hectare pine forest in Lido degli Estensi, an area with several campsites, hotels, residential buildings, and beach resorts.

The objectives were to evaluate the functionality and effectiveness of regional warning and communication systems, identify critical issues, test fire modeling for potential integration into the Data Fabric platform, and assess volunteer management and emergency response. The scenario simulated a severe wildfire, with strong southern winds and an ORANGE-level Wildfire (AIB) bulletin issued by ARSTPC. Activities included extinguishing a real controlled fire, evacuating nearby campsites and homes, and testing communication channels, including updates to the mayor of Comacchio Municipality.

Figure 37: Lido degli area in the Comacchio Municipality for the wildfire simulation.

The debriefing after the exercise highlighted both the strong response capacity and collaboration among actors, as well as persistent challenges in communication and coordination. Radio communication proved problematic, as different volunteer coordination areas operated on separate channels, requiring multiple radios to connect. Suggestions included reprogramming radios to include frequencies from all provinces and placing a Ferrara volunteer coordinator within the Fire Brigade’s advanced command post to serve as an intermediary. Another issue concerned inconsistent use of symbology: firefighters relied on a shared set of symbols displayed on flip charts to update volunteers and actors, while civil protection used different symbols despite their role in supporting and coordinating with the fire service. The simulation also received national media coverage, underscoring the importance of fire prevention activities and raising public awareness⁴⁰.

Figure 38: Impressions of the wildfire simulation exercise (May 2025).

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https://www.rainews.it/tgr/emiliaromagna/video/2025/05/prove-di-emergenza-estiva-lesercitazione-a-lido-degli-scacchi-98325046-0e3c-4940-aff9-da28aae67b92.html?wt_mc=2.www.wzp.rainews
[25.09.2025]

Output - Communication Kit for Wildfire Risk

To strengthen wildfire risk communication, the Emilia-Romagna RWL focused on developing a comprehensive communication kit. The kit is designed to support multiple organizations, including RWL stakeholders, in disseminating information on wildfire risks and prevention measures to the public—particularly tourists.

The communication kit will include posters, brochures, cards, dedicated web pages, apps, and videos, all designed in open formats so they can be easily adapted to different local contexts. The most effective communication channels were identified during the RWL workshop in November 2024 and refined through further stakeholder consultations. Based on this, the partners initiated a graphic design, content development, and prototyping process.

Content on wildfire risks and rules of conduct for citizens was provided by ARSTPC-ER. Draft versions of the materials were reviewed in Summer 2025 by stakeholders in the Ferrara area, the Regional Fire Brigade Directorate, and the Provincial Directorate of the Forest Police. A digital communications company Dinamica Media enterprise supported the graphic design of the communication products.

Information panels were developed (in Italian and English), see [Figure 39](#), and will be installed in high-risk areas in Mesola and Comacchio in September 2025. Social media cards have already been finalized ([Figure 40](#)). Additional materials, including flyers, are under development, alongside a dissemination plan tailored to guide different organizations in using the communication products. In parallel, the RWL is working on a more accessible version of the existing forest fire bulletin, including an English-language edition, to ensure broader reach.

Figure 39: Information board for wildfire risk communication (English and Italian) - draft as of 26/08/2025.

Figure 40: Social media cards for the wildfire risk communication campaign.

Output - Data Fabric for wildfires

The Data Fabric for wildfires aims to integrate meteorological data and fire spread models to simulate realistic scenarios, taking into account factors such as vegetation and natural barriers, to understand the spread of fires. The web platform will integrate real-time data (both nowcasting sensors and weather forecasts) to produce high resolution data of near-real time and short term forecast of wildfire evolution. The Interoperability Fact Sheet 2 for RWL 2 - Wildfire Hazard is available in Annex 2 which provides details on the operational workflow between different data sources.

The tool is expected to be used by Provincial Civil Protection staff based in the municipalities of Mesola and Comacchio to improve disaster preparedness and deployment of resources. The co-development will now be prioritised in the project as the Data Fabric for flooding is near completion. A mock-up of the Wildfire Data Fabric is shown in [Figure 41](#). The finalised tool is expected in the summer of 2026.

Figure 41: Mock up of the Wildfire Data Fabric.

Additional Output - Virtual Reality Flood Experience

In addition, a planned output via a citizen application developed through the project partner Oasis was initiated. Consultation with the project partners suggested that standard Apps have a low uptake by citizens, but that risk communications to citizens remained a problem. It was thought that immersive technology may add a more realistic environment to implement flood safety drills with citizens to create a better learning and flood safety outcome.

Thus OASIS developed a Virtual Reality Flood Safety Experience that shares the key messages and guidelines on the actions to take before, during and after a flood event, as well as climate adaptation actions post the Emilia-Romagna 2023 extreme flood event, through an interactive method. The App also highlighted information about the extreme flood in July, 2023. This was developed in collaboration with the RWL hosts and tested among 50+ participants including regional and local civil protection representatives, local authorities and NGOs at the ECCA Conference in Rimini, June 2025. Based on the collected positive feedback, this experience was further refined and the regional agency tested the Flood Safety App with wider disaster management professionals at Remtech in September 2025, as well as with key stakeholders across the agency.

The RWL stakeholders have also indicated they may like to trial a wildfire safety experience in addition to the flood experience. An important outcome using immersive experiences is that large amounts of information can be transferred quickly in a simulated experience, that is remembered through a full body experience and safety steps taught in a flood simulation, thus making what feels like a real experience but in a safe environment. Safety protocols were developed to ensure users use immersive experiences safely.

Figure 42: Virtual Reality Application Demonstration at ECCA 2025 in Rimini.

3.2.3 Learn Phase

Emergent Lessons - knowledge co-production

Collaborative mechanisms

Overall this RWL had strong existing relationships between GECOsystema, the Civil Protection agency, and ARPAE. The pre-existing understanding of their needs made the co-design process smoother and quicker to produce outputs for the Data Fabric for flooding. It is evident that the strong relationship foundations of this lab has supported them in quickly and coherently identifying their collective goals. Additionally, the RWL hosts understanding of their RWL stakeholders has aided them in their design and facilitation of collaborative spaces and processes suitable for the RWL context and stakeholders. The strength of the reflexive and collaborative capacities of the RWL hosts and participants was highlighted by researchers after RWL post workshop debriefing sessions - *“This RWL was very good at having internal debriefings with the key colleagues involved in hosting - incl. GECOsystema - I think this helped them progress, prioritize - a learning again around their strength as a hosting ‘team’ rather than it being an individual or two.”* These relationships have been allowed to further grow through the RWL activities but it is unclear to what extent the institutionalized mechanisms will change and if the RWL interactions can be continued in some informal way. This is for further exploration in the Sustain Phase.

Overall, the RWL process saw strong participation and openness from institutional actors, but engaging public stakeholders such as hoteliers and beach hut owners remains a

challenge, despite repeated invitations to workshops and simulations. Similarly, owners of camping areas were invited to the wildfire exercise but did not respond, likely due to competing priorities during the busy summer tourist season. In the wildfire simulation debrief, the RWL hosts emphasized their commitment to continue reaching out to these groups and to use the new communication materials as a way to spark their interest and involvement.

Goals of co-production

The RWL has two distinct goals or priorities linked to the two different hazards of flooding and wildfires. The RWL has aimed to achieve interventions across governance, communication, and data/models and tools (connected to the Data Fabric). These goals have continued to be aligned and iteratively reflected on.

The RWL hosts' strong understanding of stakeholders and context informed their decision on when participatory methods were most appropriate. Given time constraints, stakeholders prioritised testing the communication products for the 2025 wildfire season. With consensus that the remaining DIRECTED project time should focus on other outputs, the hosts opted for a simplified consultation process rather than a full co-design approach.

Capacity and skills for co-production

The Emilia-Romagna RWL designed a workshop (September 2023) embracing systems thinking after receiving the training on exploring complex risk (May 2023, online) and creative methods training (September 2023, in-person). [Figure 43](#) highlights the differences between the first and second workshops in the Emilia-Romagna RWL, demonstrating the development of their creative capacity. The RWL hosts were very satisfied with their capacity to facilitate the workshop using World-Café style group interactions indicating, *“The discussion went very well. We were able to collect a lot more information, starting with our own questions but then evolved more than expected. The lack of face-to-face presentations in the workshop was positive but we needed more time to explore all the ideas that emerged.”*

After feeling motivated by the game-based training (September 2024) combined with growing interest from RWL stakeholders emerging around conducting a real-exercise with simulated flood events, the RWL designed and facilitated a Flood Exercise in Rimini in June 2024. The exercises demonstrated the collaborative capacity of the RWL hosts to bring together authorities, volunteers and citizens, and highlight the potential to improve early warning, data and modelling tools for DRR, and communication with citizens and situational volunteers. Reflecting on the exercise, the hosts shared how implementing this type of collaborative exercise would not be prioritised without the RWL set up in the project. The success of this exercise then led to motivation to develop a second simulation exercise for wildfires (May 2025).

The RWL hosts gradually strengthened their capacity for co-production through a series of trainings and workshops. Following online training on exploring complex risk (May 2023) and in-person creative methods training (September 2023), the hosts designed their 2nd workshop to embrace systems thinking and used World-Café style group interactions. The

hosts reflected positively on the approach, noting: *“The discussion went very well. We were able to collect much more information, starting with our own questions but then evolving further than expected. The lack of face-to-face presentations in the workshop was positive, but we needed more time to explore all the ideas that emerged.”* Their progression is illustrated in [Figure 43](#).

Building on this momentum and inspired by the game-based training (September 2024) as well as stakeholder interest in practical exercises, the RWL designed and facilitated a Flood Simulation Exercise in Rimini (June 2024). This activity demonstrated the hosts’ growing collaborative capacity, bringing together authorities, volunteers, and citizens to test early warning systems, data and modelling tools, and communication strategies with the public and situational volunteers. The hosts reflected that such exercises would likely not have been implemented without the framework and support provided by the RWL. Encouraged by this success, the team was motivated to design a second Wildfire Simulation Exercise (May 2025).

Figure 43: Comparison between the 1st and 2nd meetings in the Emilia-Romagna RWL.

Emergent lessons - risk management / knowledge

Learning that emerged from the co-design of the Data Fabric included the importance of facilitating knowledge coproduction between different stakeholders to identify new sources of local data that can then be made interoperable. As a result the HERA radar and monitoring network data (multi-utility owned service provider) is now available in the Data Fabric platform and agreements are being developed to ensure continued access. By integrating SaferPlaces into the Data Fabric, the Emilia-Romagna RWL now enables direct interaction with real-time and forecast data (e.g. radar, ICON2) and provides interoperable outputs via user-friendly web interfaces, supporting rapid damage assessment, and identification of exposed assets. Although the tool can easily integrate economic damage assessments, based on needs from civil protection officers, the focus for the damage assessment is on evaluating the number of affected receptors. Additionally, the officers demonstrated interest in including social vulnerability data from the municipal level, which once collected can be integrated into the Data Fabric in the form of a social vulnerability index.

Furthermore, for wildfires, although modelling capabilities did not formally exist within the consortium, there was still scope to capture synergies with other wildfire related projects working on fire propagation models (via partner Danish Technical University). Continuing to exchange learning with other wildfire projects will be important to inform the Data Fabric.

In relation to public wildfire risk communication, the practical challenges of installing the information boards in the park areas was a challenge for the ARSTPC-ER which meant it was not available for the 2025 wildfire season. Additional feedback would have been helpful for the iterative design of the wildfire communication campaign but was limited by time and availability of stakeholders to engage. However, RWL hosts will now allow for further revisions after it has been tested with the public to integrate additional feedback.

3.2.4 Sustain Phase

Data Fabric Institutional Integration

The Data Fabric for flooding has high potential to be institutionally integrated into the ARSTPC-ER Regional Office in Bologna and made accessible for the Provincial Civil Protection Officers based in Rimini. The SaferPlaces Platform already exists at the ARSTPC-ER Regional level (used by Hydraulic's sector team) and this could be expanded out to include the Data Fabric. Currently the Data Fabric is hosted by GECOsystema but an agreement can be made between GECOsystema and ARSTPC-ER to establish the system locally in Bologna. This would allow for wider scaling up of the system to not only include Rimini, but all other municipalities if there was sufficient interest and capacity at the regional level. To support a potential pathway towards this, additional training and demonstration will be offered to civil protection across the region based on the Rimini example of the Data Fabric for flooding.

Next steps for the RWL for the Data Fabric are to finalise agreements related to data sharing between the platform and others (HERA SpA) and to develop related training (in-person) and a step-by-step guide targeting the Civil Protection Officers. Furthermore, the possibilities for having the Data Fabric focused on Flooding and Wildfire connected will be further explored.

Wildfire risk communication kit implementation

The wildfire risk communication kit (information boards, social media cards, leaflet) will be further tested and disseminated over the final year of the project. New channels for dissemination will be explored and promoted via the communications team in ARSTPC-ER. Feedback from users of these messages (e.g. tourists in the parks interacting with signboards) and agencies disseminating the messages (e.g. fire service) will be collected to guide future activities and integrate improvements where possible.

Towards improved coordination and sustained relationships

The pre-existing Simulation Guide from ARSTPC-ER will be packaged as a good-practice in organizing simulations, highlighting examples from DIRECTED where the Data Fabric enabled interoperable data, models, and tools to support more effective decision-making for flooding and wildfires. This can help to encourage continued and regular simulations being organised to maintain and strengthen relationships between the key actors involved in the RWL.

Furthermore, the Virtual Reality Flood Experience application offers more opportunities to improve public awareness and flood preparedness by the ARSTPC-ER which can be further exploited beyond the project.

Overall, the RWL offered a space for more engagement and highlighting of issues around coordination - the impact of which is hard to document at this stage but may become more clear in the final evaluation.

3.3 Real World Lab 3: Vienna & Zala

Given the size and multi-nationality of the Danube Region, the DIRECTED consortium has decided to focus its efforts on two main areas within that region, also tied to the availability of RWL representatives and collaborators. The Vienna Region in Austria and the Zala Region in Hungary share the Danube as a common geographical area at risk of fluvial flooding and drought. The two regions present very different socio-economic, development and political considerations for DRM and CCA.

Figure 44: Map of the Danube Region including the sub-regions of Vienna, Austria and Zala, Hungary.

3.3.1 Vienna

Figure 45: This overview map of Vienna; extends approximately 32 km in east-west and 24 km in north-south direction. The city=RWL area is 415 km². Source: [basemap.at](https://www.basemap.at) (CC-BY 3.0 AT).

The RWL in Vienna is characterized by a strong sense of preparedness for fluvial flooding through the public sector's network of flooding infrastructure. This preparedness stems from clearly set authorities, rules, and regulations with which the local Viennese water governance magistrate (Wiener Gewässer, MA 45) interacts with other public actors, such as the local emergency services or Viadonau (self spelling: *via donau*), a state-owned company coordinating all construction and maintenance operations on the Austrian waterways. These structures are importantly also situated within the historico-political context of clear hierarchies and responsibilities dating back to the Austro-Hungarian empire of the 19th and early 20th Century. Besides the public sector, the Vienna RWL also consists of numerous insurers and reinsurers as well as various public research institutes. However, there is only partial interaction and outreach between all these actors, which impedes integrated decision-making and planning surrounding disaster risks. Importantly, there is no institutionalized link between DRM and CCA. In short, the RWL in Vienna can be summed up as boasting numerous high-quality information and data producing agents, while not having enough space and means for more intense exchange and information sharing.

Figure 46 below presents the overview of the Risk-Tandem application for the Danube RWL in Vienna. Overall the key priorities for the RWL identified in the Foundation Phase are to strengthen knowledge sharing and collaboration between public, private and research sectors in Vienna and the Danube Region, and the integration of climate data into existing flood modelling. The RTF application of the Growth and Learn phases has been taking place through a variety of engagement activities including workshops, interviews and questionnaires, which can be found in Annex 1. The Sustain Phase aims to foster continued public-private sector collaboration through Risk-Tandem forums and continue the Data Fabric development to support the insurance sector with pluvial modelling.

Figure 46: Overview of Risk-Tandem application for Danube - Vienna Region RWL.

3.3.1.1 Foundation Phase

Overall, Vienna has stringently structured flood preparedness governance mechanisms and infrastructure, albeit overly focused on fluvial flooding through the Danube and its feeding rivers. The challenge of droughts remains rather underrepresented, and there is little cohesion between DRM and CCA decision-making. While the accessibility and immediacy of the national flood map HORA⁴¹, available online in a browser, is an impressive tool, it is only partially useful for assessing actual floods and emergency situations. Further, the insurance and reinsurance companies as stakeholders play a central role with regard to the communication, financing, and ultimate responsibility for DRM decisions made in the densely populated Vienna area.

⁴¹ <https://hora.gv.at> [28.09.2025]

3.3.1.1.1 Actor Networks/Setting the Scene

Figure 47: Stakeholder Map of Vienna; The Vienna RWL consists of a variety of public and private stakeholders. The high amount of valuable assets found in the RWL make Vienna a specifically interesting case study for the insurance industry and the role it plays in DRM and CCA.

The Vienna RWL is hosted by Genillard & Co., a private company with expertise in risk management and reinsurance. This expertise guided the consortium’s focus towards engagement with various representatives of the insurance sector. Specifically, the hosts have facilitated engagement with UNIQA, GRAWE, Generali, Allianz, and the Vienna Insurance Group all of which represent important stakeholders in the insurance industry.

A second important group of stakeholders within the Vienna RWL are the academic and research institutions. The BOKU (*Universität für Bodenkultur Wien*), a Life Sciences University, has hosted all of the RWL’s stakeholder engagement meetings so far at its *Wasserbaulabor* in Vienna. The Disaster Competence Network Austria (DCNA), serves as a connecting platform and interlocutor between various DRM experts and practitioners in the Austrian context.⁴² Finally, the ESSL, the European Severe Storms Laboratory provides training for experts in the field of severe storms, seeking to build resilience against such events.⁴³

Bridging the space between the public and private domain, the RWL also has contacts with Viadonau, Geosphere, and the European Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC). Viadonau is a public-private waterway operator, responsible for the Danube in Austria. Their legal remit includes the planning, allocation, and control of water infrastructure, as well as the regulation, conservation, and development of flood protection systems on the Danube in Austria. GeoSphere Austria is Austria’s national weather service, also reporting on the geological and geophysical (including earthquakes) situation of the country, especially

⁴² <https://dcna.at/index.php/en/home.html> [10.09.2025]

⁴³ <https://www.essl.org/cms/about-us/> [10.09.2025]

with regard to resilience building, precaution, and disaster readiness.⁴⁴ Finally, Austria is also part of the ERCC, which coordinates relief and assistance for European regions hit by large-scale disasters.

Within the regional confines of Vienna, there are further connections to two Municipal Departments. The Municipal Department 45 (MA 45) is responsible for water management in Vienna, both underground and surface level. Importantly, the Danube and Danube Canal are not part of the MA 45's jurisdiction, but are part of the federal government's (and Viadonau's) responsibility. The Municipal Department 68 (MA 68) represents the Viennese fire brigade.

Overall, the Viennese RWL consists of an interesting diversity with regard to its stakeholders and involved actors. The specific focus on the insurance industry makes it unique in comparison to other RWLs, and has provided an illuminating and fruitful perspective for the DRM and CCA conversation, and highlighted previously less considered challenges and solutions regarding early warning systems and communication. Naturally, such a focus also comes with its own limitations, especially in the field of public participation.

3.3.1.1.2 Governance and Institutional Context

Legal framework

There are clear legal frameworks that guide both the DRM and CCA process in Austria, and have a direct influence on how the two relate to one another in the context of Vienna. The central decision-making power surrounding Disaster Risk Management is placed both on the local and regional level, consisting of the federal state of Vienna and its local agencies (Vienna Crisis Management Agency, MA 45, MA 68). On a federal level, there is a shared DRM agency, the Federal Crisis and Catastrophe Management agency (SKKM) which supports and helps coordinate responses in events that span beyond the regional level.⁴⁵ The SKKM is part of the Austrian Ministry of the Interior (*BMI*), and also provides the so-called "AT-Alert", which is a public warning system based on cell broadcast technology.⁴⁶ Building on the polycentric division of jurisdictions, Vienna has its own disaster support and management law (Wiener Katastrophenhilfe- und Krisenmanagementgesetz 2003).

with regard to climate adaptation, Austria and Vienna are also guided by the EU's climate adaptation policy (COM/2021/82). On a federal level, the Climate Protection Law of 2011 (Klimaschutzgesetz - KSG 2011), establishes a so-called "National Climate Protection Committee", a group of political and private stakeholders who are responsible for the development of strategies towards, among other things, adaptation of unavoidable climate change impacts (KSG, Section 4, 2). This relationship between climate change and disasters is also underscored in the Federal Crisis Security Act of 2024, which determines that constant monitoring of the climate and weather situation is a central part of national security concern (B-KSG 2024, Section 7, 4 - 7). A recent report by the Federal Ministry for Agriculture, Forestry, and Environmental Protection (BMULK), further highlights the need to account for the impacts of climate change on the intensification and increased frequency of

⁴⁴ <https://www.geosphere.at/de> [10.09.2025]

⁴⁵ <https://www.bmi.gv.at/204/skkm/start.aspx> [10.09.2025]

⁴⁶ https://www.bmi.gv.at/204_english/at-alert/start.aspx [10.09.2025]

extreme weather events (BMULK 2024, 31). Finally, in March of 2025 Vienna has introduced its own, state-wide Climate Protection Law (Wr. KG, Wiener Klimagesetz 2025), wherein the need for increased resilience and adaptation is highlighted (Section 1, 2).

With this structure in mind, it can be said that in general there are no legal hurdles when it comes to integrating DRM into CCA strategies. However, there are only vague references between the need to account for climate change when engaging in Disaster Risk Management planning. For this reason, the extent to which the legal frameworks enable DRM & CCA integration have scored 4 out of 5. The priority was rated as low, since this was not a central concern for the RWL hosts or stakeholders.

<p>Legal Framework: To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM & CCA integration?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Clarity of roles and responsibilities

Assessed separately, there is a clear delineation of roles and responsibilities with regard to who holds jurisdiction over which part of the DRM and CCA process, respectively. The Viennese Climate Law (Wr. KG), the national climate protection law (B-KSG), as well as the Federal Crisis and Catastrophe Agency (SSKM) all clearly assign responsibilities. For this reason, the clarity of roles and responsibilities scores 5 out of 5. In line with this scoring, the priority was rated as low.

<p>Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities for DRM & CCA clear within the legal framework?</p>	<p>5 [LP]</p>
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Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities

An important insight from engagements with the RWL hosts and stakeholders, was the limitations that certain institutions entailed with regard to furthering CCA goals, while working in the context of DRM. The need to account for a changing climate, for example highlighted by the insurance sector for financial reasons, did not translate into the public sector. Accordingly, while there is individual functionality, as CCA and DRM actors function well in their respective fields, the stakeholders and consortium agrees that there could be stronger engagement between DRM and CCA actors. For this reason, the extent of the functionality regarding the roles and responsibilities of various DRM and CCA actors was scored with 4 out of 5. This was further not an immediate concern for the RWL, which is why it was tagged with Low Priority.

<p>Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities functional for DRM and CCA in practice?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Multilevel/Polycentric Governance

The various levels of governance in play in the Vienna RWL range from the European level, all the way to the Vienna city/municipal level. In Vienna specifically, there is further a division of responsibility between the federal level (which is responsible for the Danube and the Danube Canal), the state level (Vienna being its own state, responsible for its waterways, as well as the encompassing state of Lower Austria, with whom close collaboration is necessary), and the city and individual district level (Vienna consists of 23 districts, who all have their respective councils).

On each level, there are policies in place that give some guidance with regard to CCA, ranging from the general guidelines set out in the climate protection law *KSG*, to the more specific regulations of the Viennese Climate Act (*Wr. KG.*, 2025) The laws concerning civil protection are structured in a similar, multi-level fashion. While there are some references towards the increased dangers of extreme weather events through climate change (B-KSG, Section 7, 4 - 7; BMULK 2024, 31), the actual connections, e.g. through a responsible institution or actor network, is vague, and left up to individual actors. For this reason, the extent to which multilevel/polycentric governance structures support integrated DRM and CCA is scored with a 3 out of 5. The governance structures were further an important factor for the way in which DRM and CCA strategies were synergized among stakeholders, which is why it was tagged with Medium Priority.

<p>Multilevel/Polycentric Governance: To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM and CCA processes?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Accountability

The main accountability concerns regarding the DRM and CCA relationship arise when it comes to the role that the insurance sector ought to play in the ever-increasing extreme floods. Conversations with representatives from the insurance industry during the Workshop in July 2024 (Annex 1), have highlighted that the insurance sector is keenly aware of the increasing risk and unsustainable costs that climate change-fueled extreme weather events incur, especially in vulnerable areas just outside Vienna. However, due to the government’s legal responsibility to support those affected in the case of a catastrophe, individual households may not have sufficient incentives to prepare on their own, or take flood risks into

account when looking for property. This legal context and accountability aspect is an important factor for the connection between DRM and CCA processes, which is why this indicator has been assessed as a 3 and it has been tagged with Medium Priority.

<p>Accountability: To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support decision-making DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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3.3.1.1.3 Risk Management/Knowledge

DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence

There is generally a strong sense of preparedness for flooding through the public sector’s stringent network of flooding infrastructure on both a physical and communicational level. This stringency and reliance can also be traced back to the long-spanning historical roots of Viennese flood risk management, dating back to the 1870s (see also, Blöschl 2024 for a good overview of the resilience of Vienna’s flood resilience).⁴⁷

Climate adaptation strategies in Vienna can be found in a variety of adaptation projects, ranging from reducing carbon emissions, circular resource management structures, to the expansion of public transport. Further, the city makes a clear connection between the increasing intensity of heatwaves, and resilient capacities, by providing climatized indoor areas during the months of July and August. Other projects further deal with the increase of heatwaves, such as the infrastructural adaptation to climate change (InKA).

In this sense, there is a strong coherence between adaptation planning and disaster risk strategies. However, the Climate Change Adaptation plans are very much focused on heatwaves and how to responsibly handle water as a finite resource, and does not explicitly focus on other hydrological extremes, such as fluvial and pluvial flooding. For this reason, the DRM/CCA policy plan coherence is scored with a 4 out of 5. Finding and building coherence between policies was further an important aspect for stakeholders both from the insurance sector and the administrative sector, which is why it was scored with Medium Priority.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent do objectives/goals and in plans at different levels align to address DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>4 [MP]</p>
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<https://blogs.egu.eu/geolog/2024/09/26/september-2024-flooding-in-central-europe-the-austrian-experience/> [10.09.2025]

Synergies/tradeoffs Interventions

A unique example of synergizing Disaster Risk Management strategies with Climate Change Adaptation can be found in the Viennese Danube Island (“*Donauinsel*”). Constructed between 1972 and 1988 in order to manage fluvial flooding from the Danube, this artificial island also serves as a nature reserve and public park.⁴⁸ Most recently, the impacts of climate change on the island itself have been investigated, and means to combat them were introduced through the EU LIFE DICCA project.

Throughout the DIRECTED and RWL host’s engagement activities (for list of engagement activities, see M13), there was a similar interest in finding DRM and CCA synergies. For example, there is a push by the construction planners, to take increasing climate extremes into account when building new industrial sites (e.g., a warehouse or storage unit) - a push that also relies on the integration of insurance partners during the construction phase. Here the emphasis was on highlighting the financial benefit of proactively accounting for intensifying weather extremes, such as hail storms or pluvial floods (discussion and presentation held during last RTF-Workshop in July 2025).

However, it should be highlighted that the push for such integrative thinking stems from the fact that the existing legal requirements do not necessitate accounting for extraordinary weather events. Overall, there is a strong sense of identifying such synergies. For this reason, the synergy and tradeoff indicator is scored 5 out of 5. Maintaining and further fostering these synergies is a crucial aspect of further developing DRM and CCA integration, which is why it was tagged with Medium Priority.

<p>Synergies/tradeoffs Interventions: To what extent are synergies maximized, and trades-offs minimized across DRM/CCA interventions?</p>	<p>5 [MP]</p>
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Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships

Due to the RWL host’s background, the actor relationships that were emphasized and assessed in the Vienna context primarily concern the connection between the insurance sector, public administration, as well as practitioners and researchers. By the time of this report’s publication, this relationship is still rather weak, as there are no institutional or legal regulations that would facilitate such engagement. Indeed, the stakeholder engagement meetings initiated by the RWL hosts and the DIRECTED project were seen as a welcome step towards creating such relationships, e.g., between experts from the insurance sector, who often have highly salient climate data, researchers from the Austrian meteorological services, and practitioners from the Disaster Risk Management sector.

⁴⁸ <https://www.wien.gv.at/umwelt/gewaesser/donauinsel/oekologie/> [10.09.2025]

For this reason, the strength of DRM and CCA actor relationships identified in the Vienna RWL has scored 2 out of 5. Developing this relationship was something that all stakeholders were adamant about, which is why this indicator was tagged with High Priority.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent do DRM/CCA actors interact at appropriate levels?</p>	<p>2 [HP]</p>
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At the same time, as mentioned there is a lot of openness and interest to further build collaboration and engagement among DRM and CCA actors. For these reasons, the willingness and openness for collaboration beyond formal requirements is scored 5 out of 5. As with the previous indicator, the stakeholders placed repeated emphasis on this aspect of DRM and CCA integration, which is why it was tagged with High Priority.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent is there willingness and openness towards collaboration beyond formal roles/requirements?</p>	<p>5 [HP]</p>
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Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools

The most prominent disaster tool in the Vienna context is HORA platform (*Natural Hazard Overview & Risk Assessment Austria*), a platform that was conceived as a public-private partnership between the BMLUK and the Austrian Insurance Association.^{49 50} In short, HORA shows an interactive, 3D map of any geographical location in Austria that allows the user to engage in online simulations of various extreme weather events, and how it would affect their area.

While HORA is at the forefront of innovation and engagement for public use, there is still a tangible lack of integrated climate change data, e.g. information procured from the insurance sector. This is further true for the use of modelling within the city of Vienna itself, wherein existing flood risk models do not account for the increased effect of floods through climate data, as was confirmed during the Workshop of July 2025 by a colleague from viadonau. For this reason, the extent to which existing modelling and data tools address key DRM and CCA challenges is scored 3 out of 5. The integration of climate change data into existing models was further pointed out to be extremely important by the stakeholders, which is why it was rated as a High Priority.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent are (existing) risk modelling data/models/tools fit-for-purpose to address key DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tool

With the general interest of all stakeholders being the further improvement of existing DRM tools to account for CCA, there is certainly a window of opportunity to do so through the various tools presented by the Data Fabric (for more on the Data Fabric, see Pontius et al., 2025). However, there are also important limitations regarding the difference in scale and granularity of the models. While the Danube model can account for the various climate impacts, it was generally regarded as too large-scale, and thus not precise enough for the detailed picture necessary in the urban context of Vienna. For this reason, the extent to which CCA and DRM plans can embrace innovative risk models is scored 3 out of 5, and was tagged with medium priority.

⁴⁹ <https://hora.gv.at/#/chwrz:-/bgrau/a-/@47.72463,13.50823.7z> [10.09.2025]

⁵⁰ <https://www.bmluk.gv.at/en/topics/water/protection-against-floods/hora-3d-the-new-form-of-risk-communication.html> [10.09.2025]

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent can DRM and CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools and interoperability across DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Reliability/suitability (fit-for-purpose) of data/models

The HORA platform is a useful tool for holistic site risk assessments in the medium and long term. Especially with regard to its accessibility and intuitive forms of use. At the same time, the tool provides limited support for guidance in an active flood scenario, also since there is a lack of CCA integration. For this reason, the fit-for-purpose of models and datasets is scored 3 out of 5. Given the interest and feedback of the stakeholders, this was further tagged with low priority.

<p>Reliability/suitability (fit-for-purpose) of data/models: To what extent are the available data/models/tools reliable/suitable for DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools

There seem to be no immediate legal limitations when it comes to the use of data. However, there is a challenge of data sharing when it comes to the existing institutional norms and beyond individual sectors. From an institutional perspective, there is only little interaction between the administrative branches of the Viennese waterworks and emergency services, and the research institutions and expert networks.

As was assessed throughout the engagement activities, this is mainly due to the fact that there simply is no common ground or norm that emphasizes such an interaction. Further, the insurance industry produces a lot of modelling that seeks to integrate climate data into existing hazard models that is so far not being shared or exchanged with the public sector.

For this reason, the extent to which legal mindsets and norms with regard to data and modelling support the DRM and CCA decision-making process is scored 3 out of 5. Since there was some interest in understanding the legal implications of the modelling tools, especially with regard to accountability, this indicator was further tagged with medium priority.

<p>Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools: To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support ‘best’ data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation

The existing Vienna Climate Act 2025 (*Wr. KG, 2025*), explicitly introduces a society climate council (*Klimarat - Gesellschaft*), which is meant to ensure citizen inclusion and engagement (*Wr. KG, Section 9 (1) & (2) - 6.*) The law further highlights the need for citizen engagement when it comes to decisions surrounding climate protection and adaptation (Section 1 (3)). The disaster risk law (*Wr. Katastrophenhilfe- und Krisenmanagementgesetz*) is comparatively restrained in its call for participation. Specifically, the legislation requires the individual districts to provide teaching opportunities and the fostering of self-help in the case of crisis and disaster (Section 8, (1) & (2)).

In sum, existing frameworks do require citizen involvement. However, this requirement is limited to the CCA decision-making process, and only requires top-down unilateral engagement on the DRM level. There is further no integration of the two. For this reason, the extent to which existing frameworks enable/require citizen involvement is scored 3 out of 5. Due to the limited interest and discussion of this subject, the indicator was further tagged as low priority.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent do frameworks enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation

So far there has not been an expression of immediate interest in increasing citizen inclusion and participation from the stakeholders when engaging with DIRECTED. However, this may also be due to the limited engagement the DIRECTED consortium and the RWL hosts had with relevant stakeholders for such engagement, given the host’s focus on the insurance sector. For this reason, the willingness to enhance citizen engagement has so far been scored 1 out of 5. Since this was not a major point of interest for the hosts and stakeholders, this indicator was tagged with low priority.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion/participation in decision-making?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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Public warning/Risk Communication

When it comes to public warnings, Austria has a central communications platform which provides crucial information in the case of a disaster, namely the Federal Warning Central (BWZ).⁵¹ This central is further in direct connection with the local warning centrals (LWZ), such as the LWZ of Vienna. This shows that there are clear forms of communication in place for salient information to be shared swiftly and effectively. DRM processes in Austria are further supported through the European Civil Protection Pool (ECPP), which is a collection of emergency response teams and assets that can be deployed internationally if requested through the European Commission. Finally, the Disaster Competence Network Austria (DCNA) hosts an Expertise Map (“Kompetenzlandkarte”)⁵² that lists experts from various fields of Disaster Risk Management and links them to their respective area and agency.

However, there is still room for improvement when it comes to leveraging the climate information and data that the insurance sector produces in order to translate that information into public risk communication. For this reason, the extent to which DRM and CCA actors effectively communicate risks is scored 3 out of 5, and it was tagged with high priority, since the issue of public warning as front and center of many discussions and workshops.

<p>Public warning/Risk Communication: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Social Justice

With the InKa project mentioned above, and the city’s engagement to combat extreme heatwaves, there is certainly some engagement with disenfranchised groups. In this sense, Vienna can be said to work towards improving social justice issues related to DRM and CCA. However, at least within the context of DIRECTED, there is little focus on issues regarding social justice explicitly, which is why this indicator was tagged with low priority and was scored with 3 out of 5.

⁵¹ <https://www.bmi.gv.at/204/SKKM/Bundeswarnzentrale.aspx> [10.09.2025]
⁵² <https://www.dena.at/index.php/de/kompetenzlandkarte.html> [10.09.2025]

<p>Social Justice: To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM and/or CCA?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Feasibility

Vienna has a remarkably well-prepared DRM structure, especially in regard to fluvial flooding events. CCA is also being integrated with regard to increasing heatwaves. In this sense, there seems to be a general interest from a political, economic, and social perspective to further build on these structures and strategies. The only slight hindrance may represent itself in a sense of already being prepared for most harms, and therefore potentially overlooking some gaps in the DRM and CCA process. For this reason, feasibility scores 4 out of 5. Questions of political feasibility were further not central to the conversation, which is why this was tagged with low priority.

<p>Feasibility: To what extent is the political, social, and economic situation supporting DRM or CCA action?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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3.3.1.1.4 Knowledge co-production

Collaborative Mechanisms

There are some collaborative arrangements (DCNA and the Vienna Insurance Group), which foster and enable transdisciplinary collaboration. However, there is still a lack of combining knowledge from the insurance sector with the public sector, and bringing in expertise from fields beyond modelling and economics. For this reason, the extent to which collaborative arrangements exist to foster transdisciplinarity has been scored 3 out of 5. The need to improve collaboration was highlighted at various points in time as an important leverage point, which is why this indicator was tagged with high priority.

<p>Collaborative Mechanisms: To what extent do collaborative mechanisms exist to foster diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders?</p>	<p>3 [HP]</p>
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Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production

While there is agreement on the need to increase transdisciplinary collaboration (see previous indicator), the level to which knowledge co-production is discussed and explored is limited. Immediate engagement during the stakeholder workshops via Mentimeter questions and group questionnaires, is to the extent to which co-production is understood in the context of the Vienna RWL. Furthermore, RWL 3 in Vienna has faced challenges in engaging stakeholders through co-production methodologies and workshops, due to the “bureaucratic” setting that limits creative engagement. The interactions with stakeholders have been less frequent and more formal in comparison to other DIRECTED RWLs.

For this reason, the goals/needs for knowledge coproduction indicator is scored 2 out of 5, and was tagged with low priority.

<p>Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production: To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production

Knowledge co-production as such is not a focal point of the Vienna RWL. While there was general interest and willingness to engage in such activities, there are yet no opportunities to institutionalize such engagement. For this reason, the extent to which DRM and CCA stakeholders have skills for knowledge co-production is scored 1 out of 5, and was tagged with low priority, due to its limited interest.

<p>Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production: To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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3.3.1.1.5 Key Risk Governance Gaps/Aligned Indicators

Concluding the application phase of the Risk-Tandem Framework for the Vienna RWL has produced two key risk governance gaps. Importantly, these gaps are not necessarily exhaustive points for improvement. Rather, they represent insights that can be leveraged for improvement within the confines of the DIRECTED project and beyond its lifespan, without necessitating legal action, or intensive use of resources.

First, is the extent to which DRM and CCA actors interact on appropriate levels. A central finding was that there are knowledge integration platforms, such as the Disaster Competence Network Austria, or the European Severe Storms Laboratory, which can provide transdisciplinary and integrative input for the existing DRM and CCA strategies. Further, the

insurance industry produces integrated hazard data that would be incredibly useful input for the authorities and public safety. However, there is very limited interaction between actors from those organizations, and the Viennese administrative bodies. Accordingly, fostering collaboration in this regard, e.g. via recurring meetings and workshops, is an important means to bridge this gap.

Second, is the leveraging of existing information and data to improve risk communication and CCA integration. Throughout the assessment, and in the stakeholder engagement meetings and workshops, most participants would always remark on how useful and inspiring such meetings were. Specifically, the engagement between the insurance sector, and their insights with regard to models that integrate climate change data, and the administrative and public sector, always lead to fruitful discussions and mutual learning. While there may be legal and motivational hurdles to transfer data from the insurance industry to the public sector, some form of collaboration and continuous engagement could ensure improved risk communication for the public, and a better understanding of climate change impacts for administrators and the Municipal Departments.

Based on these insights, the Growth Phase of the RTF explores and experiments with methodologies to close these gaps. Importantly, this phase serves as a baseline for both the Learn Phase and ultimately the Sustain Phase.

3.3.1.2 Growth Phase

With the information and assessment of the Foundation Phase in mind, the RWL hosts, together with the DIRECTED consortium, have identified the following governance priorities, as well as potential tools to further improve upon these challenges.

Priority 1: Strengthen relationships between the insurance sector, experts from research institutions and universities, and the public sector

A central priority identified by the RWL hosts and the consortium was to improve the relationship between the various actors involved. A lack of communication between the insurance sector on the one hand, and the research institutions and the public sector on the other hand was highlighted various times. For example, a set of interviews done with various stakeholders in January 2024 highlighted this need, which was also pointed out in the RTF-Governance interview: *“The greatest challenge to Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation [in Vienna] is the lack of communication between different sectors.”* (Annex 3). While there are economic and competitive motivations for the insurance sector to not share any and all information they produce, there is a general willingness to further cooperate and build on the existing networking events organized by DIRECTED and the RWL hosts so far.

Governance mechanism to facilitate interaction:

A first, straightforward means to improve this engagement is through the continuation of stakeholder meetings. The two events held so far have always received praise and interest from the stakeholders for the fact that they enable cooperation and provide space for discussion and mutual learning. Such an engagement, combined with the structural and

conceptual background of the RTF, has further led to the insight that it would be worthwhile to institutionalize such interactions.

Figure 48: Impressions from the first stakeholder workshop in Vienna held on 10 September 2024.

Building on this integration, there may be the opportunity to find an institutionalized form of sharing immediate climate hazard information with the affected public through a further development of the AT-Alert system, for example. A workshop held with stakeholders in Vienna in September 2024 highlighted this possibility, when participants were asked to find the major gaps and challenges with regard to integrating climate change scenarios with existing DRM processes. While there are important barriers, e.g., data protection and intellectual property regulations, to be taken into account, continuous engagement could serve as a first step towards a resolution.

Priority 2: Climate data integration and interoperability of existing flood models

Another important issue for the RWL Vienna is the integration of climate information into existing flood models. This includes accounting for pluvial flooding, since the main focus for Vienna's flood models is currently fluvial flooding. The Data Fabric can support this aspect through its pluvial flood risk models. Further, the fluvial flooding can be supported through the use of the Danube Model. In various stakeholder engagement events, a lack of this integration was highlighted. As was pointed out in one of the governance interviews, the application of the RTF has underscored the need to prepare existing DRM actors in the RWL for more extreme weather events, and a changing climate.

Governance and Technical Solutions to improve CCA and DRM integration

The continuation of the RTF stakeholder meetings aims to not just serve the purpose of building a closer relationship between the participants, but to also enable co-operation among experts with regard to improved modelling and data sharing. As the Interoperability fact sheet highlights, it is important to keep in mind that Vienna is already uniquely prepared

for fluvial flood risks, withstanding river runoff of about 14,000 m³/s whose average return interval, while not reliably estimateable, should exceed 1000 years (Annex 2, Section 3). For this reason, the focus in terms of technical solutions is placed on how to translate increased precipitation flooding through climate change-driven events into existing flood models.

Figure 49: Downscaled output of the Danube Model: flood depths during the centennial Danube flood in June 2013. Note the flooded areas being practically confined to the lowlands up- and downstream Vienna. However, stakeholders of the Viennese water administration signalled interest in simulated water levels transferred into the readings of actual river gauges. See Annex 2, Section 3 for more information.

3.3.1.3 Learn Phase

On the basis of the information derived during the Growth Phase, the Learn Phase now sets out to further develop and reflect on solutions. For the RWL Vienna case, this entails fostering the relationship between the insurance industry, the research institutions, and the public sector. Specifically, a key learning could be how this relationship could foster future public risk communication strategies. Further, it is important to further reflect on and develop the integration of climate data into existing flood models.

Developing and improving responses to Priority 1: Improve and further build on the relationship between the insurance sector, experts from research institutions and universities, and the public sector

While there is interest from virtually all stakeholders to engage in more informational exchange, there is no formalized process to accommodate this in the governance structure so far. A key insight from the learning process was that the engagement needs to be continuous, in order to ensure that the mutual connections and networks built in previous meetings can be maintained.

Importantly, further meetings should continue to be guided by the RTF process to make sure that the engagement leads to more structural improvement, and that the goals and plans of the various actors are made clear and, where possible, aligned.

Developing and improving responses to priority 2: Climate data integration into existing flood models

A challenge that the Data Fabric team faced when trying to account for this priority, was the level of granularity needed in order to make the integrated climate models useful for the local context of the Vienna RWL. In short, the small scale at which the model had to be in order to be applicable for urban areas, was not available for the Danube Model. While the model incorporates disaster management (damage reduction) measures, the resolution is still too coarse to simulate the levees or other DRR methods, and it focuses solely on river flood hazard information.

Accordingly, in the most recent stakeholder engagement workshop in July 2025, there was a general consensus that exact integration of the climate change models cannot be achieved. Rather, the ways in which the Data Fabric presents the modelling output on the map may be adjusted, since the information is still valuable. While the intensity of the flooding input which SaferPlaces considers may be, on the safe side, for example overestimated by not taking sewage and canals into account, it can still reasonably well highlight areas that are prone to flooding in a pluvial event.

Insights from July 2025 workshop:

To further develop learning and reflection, during the July 2025 workshop, a survey was conducted by the consortium members, asking the workshop participants regarding the interoperability gap, using Mentimeter. As part of the RTF’s toolkit, the interoperability gap explores the flow of information and data among and between modelling and governance structures, as well as localizing that flow (e.g. on a local, or a national scale).

Accordingly, the participants were asked the following first set of questions:

Table 5: Results of first round of Mentimeter questions, Vienna Workshop July 2025.

<i>For which dimension can an interoperability gap be identified?</i>	<i>On what scale does the gap exist?</i>
Modelling - 5 votes Governance - 3 votes Between Modeling/Governance - 12 votes	Local - 0 vote Regional - 0 vote Country - 6 votes Between Local/Regional/Country – 12 votes

The results above indicate that many participants consider improving the alignment between models and governance to be more important than enhancing consistency among models. Furthermore, it was pointed out that at the spatial scale, the interoperability gap becomes most pronounced in ensuring consistency and coordination across different scales.

Additionally, the Risk-Layering Matrix was explained in the session. The matrix maps three disaster scales to three types of disaster countermeasures. It is known that the following relationship serves as the fundamental correspondence from the perspective of economic efficiency in many cases: namely, 1) disasters of the small-and-medium-scale range are addressed through “Risk reduction” (i.e., physical countermeasures via disaster prevention facility development), then, 2) disasters of the large-scale range are addressed through “Risk financing” (i.e., countermeasures through financial markets such as insurance), and 3) disasters of the catastrophic-scale range, “Assistance” (i.e., countermeasures through mutual cooperation with other countries, etc.).

Table 6: Risk-Layering Matrix: Categorization scheme for range of disaster magnitude and cost-effective countermeasures from economic perspective (The intensity of the color indicates the degree of effect.).

	Risk reduction	Risk financing	Assistance
Frequent event layer: disasters of the small-and-medium-scale range	Structural measures: e.g., construction of a levee, house elevation		
Infrequent event layer: disasters of the large-scale range		Non-structural measures: e.g., insurance, contingent credit, post-disaster special loan	
Catastrophic event layer: disasters of the catastrophic-scale range			International (or inter-governmental) support/cooperation: e.g., natural disaster funds, European Solidarity Fund, grant

In a second round of questions, the participants were asked to identify under which “layer” they accordingly spotted an interoperability gap, and what kind of instrument they would connect that gap to.

Table 7: Results of the second round of Mentimeter questions, Vienna Workshop July 2025.

<i>In which Risk-Layer do you identify an interoperability gap?</i>	<i>To which generic instruments the interoperability gap can be related to?</i>
10-100 year event (frequent and small-and-medium-scale events) - 6 votes 100-250 year event (infrequent and large-scale events) - 3 votes Above 250 year event (catastrophic events) - 8 votes	Risk Reduction - 14 votes Risk Financing - 2 votes Assistance - 2 votes

The results above suggest that the greatest potential for improvement lies in countermeasures against catastrophic-scale range disasters, while also pointing to the potential role of physical risk reduction as a means to achieve this. At first glance, this finding appears to contradict the relationship observed in many cases described above. Several reasons may explain this discrepancy. One possibility is that the participants in this workshop may not have a concrete vision of the necessary processes or other requirements for achieving greater intergovernmental coordination.

On the other hand, a more plausible reason may be as follows. It is likely because, in recent years, amid increasingly severe disasters under climate change, the dominant narrative has become that the risk of losing one's life to disasters is rising. In order to protect lives, the advancement of disaster prevention facilities is required. Insurance and foreign aid represent post-disaster monetary compensation and cannot mitigate irreversible risks, such as loss of life. Traditionally, compared to earthquakes and tsunamis, the risk of loss of life from floods was considered smaller, and the primary focus was on economic damage. However, this is no longer the case. This contemporary narrative is likely reflected in the present results. Furthermore, from a methodological perspective, this finding also highlights the importance of combining Risk-Layering and the storyline approach.

In sum, two key capacities can be highlighted that the RWL hosts have continued to build since the start of the DIRECTED project. One is the improved capacity to identify and map stakeholders, especially with regard to finding synergies among their goals and using these as leverage points to develop DRM and CCA integration. This improved capacity shows itself especially in the workshop planning and facilitation process, as well as in the way in which the hosts ensure fruitful engagement between the participants. Second, the RWL hosts are making use of the RTF to structure and plan workshop activities, which in turn ensures that these activities are geared towards DRM and CCA integration. An important example here is the increased focus on accounting for extreme weather events intensified through climate change in local flood models, and emphasizing the role that the insurance sector can play in regard to public communication.

3.3.1.4 Sustain Phase

There are two focal points that define the context of the Sustain Phase for the Vienna RWL. One, is improving the public private partnership between the public sector and the insurance sector, as well as with scientists, researchers, and practitioners. This entails developing a sustained and institutionalized stakeholder engagement meeting between the insurance industry, the research institutions, the practitioners, and the administrative bodies in the context of Vienna (and in Austria in general, when applicable). This engagement would also seek to grow and learn, trying to not just maintain existing relations but looking for new solutions with regard to DRM and CCA integration, e.g., by looking at new ways of public risk communication with the support of the insurance industry.

Two, is developing and applying a feasible way of accounting for flooding via the existing flood risk models, as well as through the Data Fabric. This entails accounting for the difference in granularity when it comes to the available data provided by the Danube Model, when applying it to the higher resolution local flood models of the Vienna Region.

Success & Expected Outcomes for the Vienna Sustain Phase

For the first goal to be a success, the consortium, RWL hosts, and stakeholders will work together to find a suitable host. This host would be responsible to continue the stakeholder engagement meetings, applying the tools of the RTF and the Data Fabric, to facilitate and foster DRM and CCA actor networking. There should also be a pathway towards further improving public risk communication.

For the second goal to succeed, the current flood maps should be able to reflect climate change data, and deliver adequate information for the DRM decision-makers.

3.3.2 Zala

Figure 50: Location map of the Zala Region.

The Risk-Tandem application in Zala, Hungary as part of the Danube RWL involved identifying priority gaps in the Foundation Phase, implementing knowledge co-production activities in the RWL including workshops, bilateral meetings and events to identify user stories, collect relevant data to work towards technical and governance solutions that can be sustained beyond the project - including the multi-risk and climate information platform (Data Fabric) and the Climate Festival to support multi-stakeholder collaboration and public engagement around DRM and CCA. Further details on the application in each of the phases is presented in the following sections and summarised in [Figure 51](#).

Figure 51: Overview of the Risk-Tandem application for the Zala RWL.

3.3.2.1 Foundation Phase

3.3.1.2.1 Actor Networks/Setting the Scene

The **Zala Special Rescue Team (ZSRT)**, a volunteer first responder organisation, are the hosts of the Zala Region in the Danube RWL. Zala County is exposed to multiple compounding hazards including extreme weather (intense rainfall, hailstorms and windstorms), flash flooding, river floods, landslides (and mudflows), and drought connected to forest fires. The Zala River, a tributary of the Danube, passes through Zalaegerszeg, the administrative county city, and enters Lake Balaton a few kilometers north of the City of Kesthely near the Kiz-Balton wetlands. There are 258 municipalities (cities, towns and villages) in Zala County, the majority of which represent small rural villages (Hungarian Central Statistical Office, 2024).

There are many different actors involved in DRM and CCA in Zala County. The mayor acts as the head of the local disaster management in each municipality and operates under guidance from the **Zala County Disaster Management Directorate (ZCDMD)** but retains autonomy for local action unless the county or national intervention is needed. The ZCDMD is the state authority at the county level that coordinates Disaster Risk Management. ZSRT has a specialist operational role in disaster response, working in close cooperation with municipal mayors and the ZCDMD. The **Zala County Territorial Protection Committee (TVB)** chaired by the county government commissioner, includes the head of the ZCDMD, mayors, police and fire services, utilities and other key sectoral agencies. ZSRT is not officially a member of TVB but can be involved as a cooperating partner in disaster response and planning. The TVB approves local disaster and civil defense plans, and in an emergency leads strategic decision-making (including mobilizing county/state resources) and coordination between municipal and national authorities including the **National Directorate General for Disaster Management (OKF)** and **General Directorate of Water Management (OVF)** in the Ministry of Interior.

The National Directorate **General for Disaster Management** (OKF) is responsible for the national disaster response, preparedness planning, risk assessment, and coordination.⁵³ It also maintains the operational readiness of Hungary's civil protection and disaster response teams and exercises control over the preparation of regional (capital), settlement (district capital) and workplace emergency plans.

The **Hungarian Meteorological Service (HungaroMET)**⁵⁴ provides weather forecasts and early warnings for thunder/wind-storms, extreme temperature and flooding (in cooperation with water management bodies).

The **Lake Balaton Water Management Directorate** is the regional water management authority responsible for managing Lake Balaton and its catchment including monitoring rivers, lakes and flood defences and coordinating responses to drought, flood, and water quality. Agriculture and tourism are the main economic sectors in Zala, which rely heavily on water management, and are at risk from disaster and climate impacts.

Overall in Zala there is a multi-hazard focus, with the ZSRT volunteers and mayors in the municipalities in West Balaton region (especially the City of Keszthely) identified as the key actors for engagement in the Risk-Tandem process locally.

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https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/national-disaster-management-system/hungary_en [19.08.2025]

⁵⁴ <https://www.met.hu/> [25.09.2025]

Figure 52: Overview of RWL stakeholders in Zala: Municipalities, National Directorate for Disaster Management (OKF) and General Directorate of Water Management (OVF) in the Ministry of Interior, Hungarian Meteorological Service (HungaroMET), Zala County Disaster Management Directorate (ZCDMD), Lake Balaton Water Management Directorate, Zalaerdö Plc. (state owned Forest Management company operating under the Ministry of Agriculture), Hungarian Road Department (National company with Zala County Directorate), Hazardous material transport company and Mouldtech Systems, Voluntary associations as Zala Special Rescue Team, Association of volunteer firefighters, and National Association for Radio Emergency and Infocommunications.

3.3.1.2.2 Governance and Institutional Context

Legal framework

Hungary operates a centralized institutional system with legal frameworks in place nationally to support DRM and CCA. The **Disaster Management Act 2011** serves as the overarching legislative framework, providing a structured guideline for the management of disasters, the establishment of emergency preparedness measures, and the orchestration of responses to crisis situations in Hungary. The ZSRT operates as part of the **HUN02 Medium Urban Search and Rescue (USAR) framework** governed by agreements with the National Directorate for Disaster Management.

In order to address the challenge of climate change, Hungary has a Law on Climate Protection adopted in 2020 including a goal on climate neutrality for 2050 and devised a **2nd National Climate Change Strategy (NCCS-2)**⁵⁵ for the 2018–2030 period which includes an adaptation strategy and action plan on climate change awareness raising (see for example, Walmsley et al., 2024). This framework is for the integration of Climate Change Adaptation considerations into its DRM policies. The strategy includes measures for Disaster Risk

⁵⁵ https://climate-laws.org/document/law-on-climate-protection_3a0f [28.09.2025]

Reduction, such as the development of flood protection infrastructure, the establishment of early warning systems and public education initiatives. The **National Adaptation Plan**, to be implemented by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology, sets out the country's strategy for adapting to the impacts of climate change.

During the multi-stakeholder workshop in Keszthely, challenges were identified by NGO and agricultural representatives that the agricultural legislation and related subsidies (Common Agricultural Policy) do not encourage sustainable land use and adaptation of crops. Furthermore, stakeholders identified the challenges of development and planning for expansion of the tourism sector which do not require adequate consideration of sustainability, climate and disaster resilience.

Overall the DRM and CCA legal frameworks exist at the national level, over which the mayor has important powers to influence, however, the lack of specific implementation measures, backed up with funding, limits their effectiveness to enable integration locally. This is identified as a Low Priority for the RWL as it is difficult to address within the scope of the project.

<p>Legal Framework: To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM & CCA integration?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities

The **roles and responsibilities for DRM and CCA** are relatively clear within the legal framework, however, their functionality is highly dependent on the motivation, capacity/skills and resources available to staff at the county level, as well as the political leadership. Municipalities have a high dependence on voluntary organisations like ZSRT to support municipalities in response efforts, while climate adaptation remains a low priority for many municipalities unless there is strong political leadership (like in the case of Keszthely). Patkós et al., (2019) highlight that financial pressure is the main barrier for municipalities in Hungary. For these reasons. An European Investment Bank (EIB) Climate Survey identified that 80% of Hungarians surveyed believe that they are more concerned about the climate emergency than their government, demonstrating a lack of action on climate change at the local level.⁵⁶ However, it was also identified that municipalities require additional support and guidance is needed at the local level for the development of climate adaptation strategies, and organisations like the Alliance of Climate Friendly Municipalities have emerged to support

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<https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2021-404-a-magyarok-67-a-tamogatna-tovabbi-intezkedeseket-amely-ek-magatartasbeli-valtozasokra-sarkallnanak-a-klimaveszhelyzet-kezelese-erdekeben> [10.09.2025]

this, as well as initiatives like the Climate Change Platform in the Komárom-Esztergom County⁵⁷.

For these reasons the clarity of the roles and responsibilities is rated as intermediate (3) and the functionality rated lower as having potential for growth (2), both identified as Low Priority for the RWL as these are difficult to address in the scope of the project.

<p>Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities for DRM & CCA clear within the legal framework?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
<p>Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities functional for DRM and CCA in practice?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>

Multilevel/Polycentric Governance

The centralised top-down institutional system in Hungary presents challenges for multi-level/polycentric governance of DRM, whereby the political party in power dictates the direction. Integrated DRM and CCA requires collaboration with multiple sectors, responsibilities of which are divided across many ministries in Hungary. This fragmentation and frequent changes to responsibilities limits vertical and horizontal coordination and hinders an integrated mindset towards solutions, such as nature based solutions (OECD, 2023). These challenges are compounded by limited funding distribution to the local level, and limited capacity and awareness among staff for effective implementation, especially among small municipalities. Furthermore, lack of political buy in and uncertainty around supporting climate adaptation results in a lack of resources and capacity at the municipal level. For these reasons it is identified as having potential for growth (rated at 2) and is a Medium Priority for the RWL as although the centralised system cannot be changed in the project, relationships and more informal collaboration could be enabled.

<p>Multilevel/Polycentric Governance: To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM and CCA processes?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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<https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/climate-change-platform-of-komarom-esztergom-county> [10.09.2025]

Accountability

Under the Disaster Management Act, mayors are given responsibility for decisions made during disaster response. However, Hungary has adopted a top-down approach to policy, which appears to make it difficult in practice to hold decision-makers accountable.

Political motivation for CCA and DRM is dictated by those in charge, and elections decide if past policy will be reversed. Moreover, each political party has different beliefs regarding climate adaptation. There is discussion regarding the lack of specificity in the law, allowing the government more flexibility, but obscuring who is accountable and what the threats are. This is problematic as these decision-makers may focus on short-term solutions rather than long-term resolutions. For example, the workshop in Keszthely highlighted the challenge of sewage overflow in Hévíz following heavy rainfall events (around 20 mm/hr), which can contaminate drinking water. While there is awareness of the issue, a lack of political will has prevented long-term solutions from being pursued, with responses instead focusing on short-term measures such as providing free water tanks. Following this approach, elections are the main way that the public can hold decision-makers accountability for the policy decisions made. However, a lack of public interest means that there will be a lack of accountability for those making decisions around DRM/CCA.

It is unclear to what extent accountability concerns arise and how these are managed to support DRM/CCA decision-making. Consequently, this indicator has been assessed as 1 [Low Priority], as this is an area with high potential for growth.

<p>Accountability: To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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3.3.1.2.3 Risk Management/Knowledge

DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence

Cooperation is taking place between CCA and DRM, but only when legally required. Outside the legal framework, there is a general lack of coherence, as many do not consider cross-sectoral interaction as part of their role. Experts from the CCPI cite that due to a lack of coordination and the abolishment of price capping gas and electricity for homes, Hungary inadvertently created more climate risk as people instead burned wood or even waste, which is illegal but not enforced, creating worse impacts to the environment. The OVF is the primary authority responsible for implementing the EU Floods Directive (2007) (including risk assessment, flood hazard and risk mapping, flood risk management plans) and the Lake Balaton Water Management Directorate is responsible for its regional implementation.

Sectoral water management and agricultural practices are interlinked with DRM and CCA in Zala. Poor agricultural practices in certain areas, coupled with intensive cultivation, have led to the degradation of the upper soil layer, and with intense rainfall can result in mudflows. These floods damage homes in rural settlements and wash sediments into the Zala River and the filtration system of Lake Balaton, potentially damaging the region’s water protection infrastructure.

The risk management challenges the tourism sector, development of built-up areas, urban management pressures, and the need to protect designated conservation sites, including Ramsar and Natura 2000 areas, as well as forests, reed beds, and aquatic ecosystems. These combined pressures heighten the demand for preparedness, resilience-building, and decision-support systems to address the complex interplay of environmental, economic, and social factors. Given the gaps in coherent DRM and CCA policy, this has been rated a 2 and is Low Priority because it is difficult to address within the scope of the project.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent do objectives/goals in plans at different levels align/cohere to address extreme climate events?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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Synergies/tradeoffs of interventions

There is scope for more integration of DRM and CCA by considering tradeoffs and synergies across the different sectoral plans and practices especially, agriculture, tourism, health, development and water management. For example, the challenge of poor agricultural practices and land management increases the risk of land degradation and mud flows. After heavy rainfall silt from the fields ends up in nearby rivers affecting water quality, and soil erosion. Integrated measures like tree planting and increased soil coverage would reduce impacts, while incentivising drought resistant crops.

Another challenge identified (during Zalaegerszeg workshop) is that firefighters can only pump water if private households have been affected by floods or mudflows, and if the roads have only been affected then the public has to wait. This demonstrates a lack of integrated thinking to capture efficiencies and maximise synergies around pumping areas affected. Another gap identified was around the need for coordination around negative environmental impacts and damage from disasters, which shows the lack of alignment between DRM and environment. Furthermore, the Nature-based solutions (NbS) offer opportunities for co-benefits across adaptation, mitigation, biodiversity and recreation (OECD, 2023) however, in Zala these are underexplored within existing plans.

There is considerable room for improvement around capturing synergies and managing tradeoffs across DRM and CCA interventions, thus it has been rated at 1. The collaboration within the RWL is likely to facilitate knowledge sharing around such synergies/ tradeoffs,

however it will be difficult to improve within the scope of the project. As such, it has been identified as Medium Priority.

<p>Synergies/tradeoffs of interventions: To what extent are synergies maximized, and trades-offs minimized across DRM & CCA interventions?</p>	<p>1 [MP]</p>
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Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships

Overall, the DRM and CCA actors interact where they are formally required to do so. However, given the cross-cutting nature of the risks and impacts across sectors, cross-sectoral interaction especially at the local level would be an area to improve.

The difficulty in organizing multi-stakeholder workshops is that cross-sector collaboration is not customary within Hungary, presenting a challenge for RWL engagement. ZSRT has an extensive network with regional and local stakeholders across public administration, scientific, advocacy and civil society organisations in the region, and would have regular interaction with them. However, additional effort was required to build up the relationships at the National level with the Disaster Management Agency compared to others.

Often there can be a lack of willingness and openness towards collaboration as the top-down approach heavily depends on the political party in power and the culture is very hierarchical in nature. As such, the level of interaction and their willingness towards collaboration between actors is rated at 1 and is a High Priority to be addressed through the RWL engagements in Zala.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent do DRM & CCA actors interact at appropriate levels?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>
<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent is there willingness and openness towards collaboration beyond formal requirements?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>

Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools

Keszthely is particularly vulnerable to extreme weather events, including forest fires in the Keszthely Hills due to invasive pine species, as well as reed fires in the extensive reed beds along the lakeshore. The OKF is responsible for preparing an annual national disaster risk assessment in collaboration with the county-level directorate for disaster management. The

OVF and Lake Balaton Water Management Directorate prepare flood risk assessments and maps.

A gap identified is the need for decision-support tools including those that can help visualise different historic impacts from past multi-hazard events and modelled/projected risks and future impact scenarios. During the multi-stakeholder workshop in Keszthely, it was identified that there is a lot of good data and models available related to drought and forestry/wildfires. However, the data visualisation and analysis is missing to support adaptation planning. Furthermore, there is a lack of collaboration between forestry stakeholders to share their different models for forest fires. There is a lot of data available, but it is housed under different agencies for specific purposes and there is no simple mechanism for data-sharing to support wider applications of the data. A challenge compounded by the siloed nature of the different Ministries responsible for collecting data and official systems for data sharing. Currently, the RWL host has to physically collect data at different ministries. There is an openness to explore collaboration with innovative SMEs such as MyDroneMet who collect meteorological data through drones to develop sector specific and more precise weather forecasts.⁵⁸

There is demand for data/models and tools that can facilitate more disaster preparedness and Climate Change Adaptation, which enable efficient use of local financial resources and ensure the resilience of local public services. Scope for embracing new innovations and interest in improving interoperability exists as there is interest and willingness to engage in European Innovation projects like DIRECTED, thus it has been identified as High Priority.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent are (existing) risk data/models/tools fit-for-purpose to address key DRM/CCA challenges?</p>	<p>2 [HP]</p>
<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent can DRM and CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools and interoperability across DRM and CCA?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>

Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools

Given the hierarchical and top-down governance system in Hungary, normal practices would strictly follow the related rules for using government supported monitoring data, hazard models and tools. Insights around the legal implications or perceived implications from governance agencies of using more innovative and advanced data, models and tools (such as those being proposed within DIRECTED and from local SMEs like MyDroneMet is unclear.

⁵⁸ <https://www.wohnderdrone.hu/english/mydronemet/> [25.09.2025]

As such this indicator has been rated as 1 and is Low Priority as it is difficult to address within the scope of the project.

<p>Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools: To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support ‘best’ data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation

Citizen inclusion and participation is generally very limited in DRM and CCA decision-making and the willingness to enhance this is highly dependent on the individual motivations and interest of the mayors. Regarding the citizens influence in the decision making process there is little to no impact, as only 18% of the citizens even believe they have a personal responsibility to aid in CCA & DRM while the vast majority believe the government is the one responsible (EPRS, 2025). This cultural framing of the issue as someone larger than one self can also be seen as there is no information sharing platform where the public can participate in the adaptation of climate change. Furthermore, 95% of Hungarian respondents in an EIB Adaptation survey recognise the need to adapt to climate change (similar to the EU average), while 46%, close to the EU average of 50% view Climate Change Adaptation as a priority for Hungary in the coming years.⁵⁹ This demonstrates the need to find ways to improve the engagement and participation of citizens in DRM and CCA decision-making, which are actively being explored by some mayors, like the mayor of Kezsthely in Zala.

The extent to which frameworks enable citizen involvement has been rated at 1 and Low Priority as this is difficult to change within the project’s scope. The willingness of DRM/ CCA actors to improve this has been rated at 2 and Medium Priority given the proactive nature of the current mayor and the possibility to address through the RWL activities.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent do frameworks enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion/participation in decision-making?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>

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<https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2024-437-nearly-two-thirds-of-hungarians-respondents-recognise-that-they-will-have-to-adapt-their-lifestyle-due-to-climate-change-eib-survey-finds> [24.09.2025]

Public warning/Risk Communication

Weather forecasts and warnings are available but not at the scale and resolution that is useful for decision-making locally and not for a wide range of hazards and timescales.⁶⁰ During the workshop it was identified that a 5-day forecast exists as a pilot project for the Mora River. Stakeholders felt that the weather forecasts are not accurate enough and have slow communication channels to the local level due to the hierarchical governance system. Even though the reaction time on the ground is quick and the information is accurate, it does not reach the local level quick enough to take effective action. Increased public awareness of risk requires improvements in the communication of risk and warning information. As such this indicator is rated as 1 and is Medium Priority with some scope to address it within the RWL activities.

<p>Public warning/Risk Communication: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?</p>	<p>1 [MP]</p>
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Social Justice

ZSRT identified that poor communities in the villages have homes with poor building standards making them more vulnerable to the impacts of flooding and storms, and in more need of their support. Given the funding constraints within municipalities these needs are not proactively considered to enable them to retrofit buildings that are more resilient to such natural hazards. Motivated citizens, even from disenfranchised groups can engage through NGOs, for example, becoming volunteer first responders.

Overall this indicator is rated at 1 as there is a lot of room for improvement and is a Low Priority for the RWL as it is beyond the scope of the project to address this challenge.

<p>Social Justice: To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM and/or CCA?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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Feasibility

The political situation in Hungary is a challenge however, the agency of individuals can surpass this as identified in Keszthely when the mayor was appointed in October 2024. For development Hungary relies heavily on financial support from the EU, while Patkós et al., (2019) recommends that any financial support from EU sources should require multi-level governance, to enable local-level resources and ideas to realize climate-informed and

⁶⁰ <https://www.met.hu/> [10.09.2025]

sustainable development. There is a high dependency on seasonal tourism in the Balaton region of Zala. There is a lot of pressure on growth via the tourism sector and doing so sustainably has a lot of competing interests with other sectors - economic, social and environmental.

This indicator is rated at 2 and identified as Low Priority as it is not possible to address within the scope of the project.

<p>Feasibility: To what extent is the political, social, and economic situation supporting DRM or CCA action?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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3.3.1.2.4 Knowledge co-production

Collaborative Mechanisms

Formalised collaborative arrangements exist at the county level that support multi-agency preparedness and response to disasters, however these are not linked with alignment with broader sectoral issues and climate change for strengthening climate resilience in the region. There is an Alliance of Climate-Friendly Municipalities (Klimabarát⁶¹), including 88 local government members that raise climate awareness and support developing climate strategies. This includes representatives from Gyenesdiás municipality in Zala who have the vice presidency of Climate-Friendly Municipalities and have engaged in the RWL activities. A regional development council exists in West Balaton but does not have a focus on climate or resilience.

As identified in the first RWL workshop in Keszthely (March, 2025), there is a lot of scope for new more informal collaborative governance arrangements to enable more transdisciplinary knowledge coproduction, such as that being initiated through the RWL. As such, this indicator is ranked at 1 and is High Priority.

<p>Collaborative Mechanisms: To what extent do collaborative mechanisms exist to foster diverse and relevant engagement of stakeholders?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>
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Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production

Given the lack of interaction of stakeholders across DRM, CCA and related sectors there is a lack of a vision for the goals and understanding of the needs to enable climate resilience in

⁶¹ <https://www.klimabarát.hu/> [24.09.2025]

the region. However, this is what aims to be addressed and supported via DIRECTED. Therefore, this is rated at 1 and is Medium Priority.

<p>Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production: To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>1 [MP]</p>
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Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production

ZSRT has an extensive network with regional and local stakeholders and was able to formalise their support via Letters of Engagement, creating a strong base for transdisciplinary collaborations. However, they struggled to initiate multi-stakeholder workshops given the cultural norms, and instead focused on bilateral discussions within their network, to understand the gaps and needs around data/modelling, communication and governance for DRM and CCA. ZSRT had previously no experience organising multi-stakeholder workshops and no experience in using creative and interactive methods. The capacity and skills for knowledge co-production is rated at 1 and identified as High Priority as there is significant scope for improvement through the knowledge co-production capacity development process.

<p>Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production: To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>1 [HP]</p>
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3.3.1.2.5 Key Risk Governance Gaps/Aligned Indicators

Zala in the Danube RWL represents an interesting case bringing out the challenges of a multihazard context, interdependency of interventions and cross-sectoral impacts, and economic and political constraints hindering sustainable and risk-informed development.

Overall, the key gaps (areas for improvement) identified through the assessment include **governance** in relation to the functionality of roles and responsibilities for DRM and CCA, which are not working at different levels to support integrated DRM and CCA, **risk management/knowledge** in relation to a lack of alignment of different objectives/goals across DRM and CCA plans, and lack of synergies captured across interventions, as well as poor interaction between DRM and CCA actors and limited openness towards collaboration. High potential for improvement was also identified for citizen inclusion and participation, social justice, and public warning and risk communication.

From the above gaps, the highest priorities identified were to strengthen **actor relationships** and build an **openness for collaboration**, and a pathway towards more **collaborative mechanisms**. An important indicator for enabling this is improving the **capacity/skills for knowledge co-production** through the RWL host. Thus, the development of the RWL itself and working towards multi-stakeholder knowledge co-production workshops is an important achievement in itself for this RWL.

Another high priority for the Zala RWL is improving access to **multi-hazard risk data, models and tools** and **enabling innovation and interoperability** through a shared platform. This would support better preparedness of first responders and improve communication of climate/disaster risk and impacts to mayors and other governmental officials to encourage more action.

3.3.2.2 Growth Phase

The Foundation Phase identified two key priorities for the Zala sub-regional RWL, through ongoing bilateral exchange with stakeholder in the region, by the ZSRT focal point.

- Priority 1: Support better preparedness of **first responders (volunteers)** for extreme climate events
- Priority 2: Engage/communicate with **mayors and government officials** about climate impacts to stimulate action

The RWL host focused on bilateral engagement of stakeholders and presenting the project at various events like the Regional Defense Committee meeting in April 2023 Zalaegerszeg and Zala Special Rescue Team anniversary event, April 2024, Zalaegerszeg. In March 2025 (24th to 28th) two multi-stakeholder workshops were organised in the Zala Region, one in Zalaegerszeg focused on first responders and DRM engagement, and the second in Keszthely focused on mayor and wider actor engagement. These workshops were supported and attended by DIRECTED researchers. See further documentation on the RWLs co-production activities in Annex 1.

Multi-hazard Data Fabric

These priorities informed the design of the Data Fabric, through the **user story development** (see Pontius et al., 2025). There was interest in a **technical solution** whereby risk information for multiple hazards, at different temporal and spatial scales, is available to support first responders to become more prepared for future climate extremes. The proposed technical solution is a Multi-hazard Data Fabric targeting voluntary members of ZSRT to view multi-hazard maps (fluvial, pluvial flooding, drought, wildfires, storms) to support short-term and medium-term planning for future climate and weather extremes by voluntary organisations and these risk communication outputs can be used to facilitate stronger collaboration with municipalities (to advocate for additional resources). The aim of the Data Fabric and information within it is that it can also support better engagement and dialogue with key government actors like the National Disaster Management Directorate and mayors

to encourage adaptation and preparedness activities, to support economic growth and tourism in the region.

In terms of the **data and modelling workflows** the Data Fabric includes the visualisation of past disaster impacts (forest and vegetation fires, water damage, storm damage and timber cutting), Zala River fluvial flood modelling (Danube Model), SaferPlaces model for pluvial flooding in the City of Keszthely, visualization of climate projection data and integration of seasonal forecasts from copernicus and long-range forecasts from ECMWF. The workshop in Zalegerszey (24th March 2025) hosted by ZSRT focused on priority 1 by bringing together first responders and disaster management agency representatives to reflect on the prototype of the Data Fabric and prioritise next steps. A **Risk-Tandem storyline** was developed to help demonstrate the different capabilities of the different models in the Data Fabric. For example, it included the event database ([Figure 53](#)), flooding in the Zala Region in 2014 using FutureDanube model ([Figure 54](#)) and pluvial flood simulation at thermal lake of Hévíz of 100mm in 3 hours with water depth and damage estimation using SaferPlaces.

Figure 53: Event database integrated into the Data Fabric.

Figure 54: 2014 flooding (Danube Model reanalysis) used in the Risk-Tandem storyline.

Feedback from the workshop highlighted the strong interest in going beyond hazard data to embed **Census data** (e.g. age, persons with disabilities) to support their decision-making. This data is available at the municipality level however, and an action was noted for it to be requested but this has not yet been retrieved. A social vulnerability layer can easily be embedded if the data is provided. There was also interest in **short- and medium term forecast data for extreme weather events** (thunderstorms, extreme cold/heat, rainfall) to improve effectiveness of their preparedness and response efforts e.g. equipment procurement. The user friendliness of the Data Fabric was also highlighted to ensure it can be used by individuals without high technical skills.

The feedback from workshop participants showed that all strongly agreed (14) or agreed (6) that their awareness of data, models and tools to support your decision-making developed through participation in the workshop. Reflecting on the facilitation of the workshop in K, the Risk-Tandem storyline was difficult to focus on in the group work given the limited time and complexity of the information within. As such, the conversations focused more on the broader data/modelling, governance and communication challenges among stakeholders present.

Challenges

Through the engagement of different stakeholders, different opportunities for supporting specific actors emerged and it became difficult to prioritise the focus. For example, the foresters and fruit growers, but concerns emerged over to what extent the models and data available could support the decision-making of these actors. Furthermore, There are a range of interests in multiple hazards, where the modelling/tools needs are not directly linked to the available DIRECTED models but there is some scope by capturing synergies with other projects e.g. for wildfire risk connection with DTU project.

Governance mechanisms - stimulating and maintaining collaboration

A major challenge for DRM/CCA that became clear during the workshops in March is the lack of space for collaborative and open dialogue for multiple actors across public, private and NGO sectors to exchange knowledge and set visions and ambitions for climate adaptation and resilience at the local level.

As such the workshops were seen as a huge success in bringing together these key actors and creating an atmosphere for shared learning and exchange. The workshops included over 40 participants from national to local levels across multiple sectors. The feedback from the workshop showed that all respondents (20) either strongly agreed (12) or agreed (8) that their understanding of Disaster Risk Management, climate adaptation and resilience increased through their involvement in the workshop. All respondents either strongly agreed (13) or agreed (7) that their willingness to collaborate and communicate with other organisations and disciplines improved through the workshop. This demonstrates the interest and willingness of stakeholders to get involved but the need for leadership and convening power to do so, which works in this case because of the DIRECTED project. The feedback results from the workshops (20 respondents) highlighted that 19 respondents indicated they would be willing to engage in future RWL activities. Participants also shared ideas for people to involve in future workshops.

Furthermore, the workshop integrated creative and interactive activities which were new for the RWL host and the participants. This included an ‘play-based’ introduction exercise that required all participants to make something to introduce what climate resilient west Balaton means to them. This helped to break down hierarchies in the room and create an open environment for sharing experiences. Furthermore, feedback showed that participants enjoyed the groupwork as a means for sharing knowledge and it was a new experience for them.

Figure 55: Impressions from interactive activities in Keszthely multistakeholder workshop March 2025.

Another positive result from the workshops was that the RWL host (ZSRT) was invited to meet with the chair of the scientific board of the national disaster management authority (Dr. Bognár Balázs) which resulted in their support for the project.

One recommendation that emerged from the workshop was to create an informal collaboration between multiple actors to achieve climate resilient development in the Balaton region. A potential name was floated - **Climate Alliance Balaton**. The mayor agreed to continue to support interactions and work towards such an initiative which would be followed up by ZSRT.

Furthermore it was agreed that DIRECTED would consider hosting their next General Assembly in the region to help mobilize more engagement by local government actors and the public. The workshop received significant interest from local media raising the importance of the issue publicly.⁶²

Challenge:

Securing hosting and chairing commitment for a collaborative arrangement like Climate Alliance Balaton that ensures it remains neutral to political shifts. Intermediate steps like project supported workshops are more realistic in the short-term and this can be returned to continued interactions with the mayor and other stakeholders. In the meantime, other opportunities for bringing people together that align with the spirit of collaboration and creativity like a Climate Festival (see more in the Learn Phase) can support in stimulating public awareness and engagement while also connecting different professional stakeholders.

⁶²

<https://tvkeszthely.hu/news/12318-elorejelzo-rendszerek-segithetnek-hogy-megelozzuk-a-katasztrofakat> [10.09.2025]

3.3.2.3 Learn Phase

Key emergent lessons - Knowledge coproduction

Capacity development of RWL hosts: Overall the Zala RWL struggled to get started with a multi-stakeholder workshop and organised its workshops in March 2025 (two in one week). Multiple reasons for this were identified. Firstly, the RWL host, although having a lot of experience and knowledge with the different actors, had no experience in convening them in a multi-stakeholder workshop and felt concerned about doing so as this was not the ‘norm’ culturally. To overcome this we identified the need for project researchers to jointly organise the workshops to attach additional importance locally and to offer scientific and facilitation support to the host for the workshop. Furthermore additional one-to-one training for knowledge co-production was provided to support the design of the workshop materials. This additional support proved necessary to help the RWL host progress the knowledge co-production activities and helped to build their skills in designing and facilitating workshops using creative and interactive materials. Investing in supporting the capacity development of RWL hosts can support more collaboration in the long-term to sustain the collaborations developed within the project.

Key emergent lessons - Governance

Aligning to change in political leadership: Another important mobilizing factor was the election of Dr. Tóth Gergely as mayor of Keszthely in October 2024, a strong environmental and sustainability advocate who actively engages with academia. This was noted by the RWL host as a critical moment and that the project needed to wait to organise a workshop together as he would act as a mobilizer to gain participation from other key actors.

Remaining flexible to emerging ideas and opportunities:

Building on the interest and learning emerging from workshops on public engagement around climate action, an idea emerged during the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference where **Climate Festivals** were promoted as good practice through the DIY manual on engaging stakeholders and citizens in climate adaptation.⁶³ This idea was pitched by RWL host to the mayor in June 2025 and he has provided his support. He has also allocated funding to co-organise it for April 2026 to align with the General Assembly of DIRECTED.

Another opportunity that emerged from the process was a **funding opportunity** via the Pathways2Resilience grants.⁶⁴ A proposal was then submitted by Zala Special Rescue Team in August 2025 entitled “*West-Balaton Climate Resilience Transformation in collaboration*” with partners City of Keszthely, Cholofeel Art Meetup, Gersei Pethő Community Foundation and 52°North as a technical partner to build on the existing Data Fabric and a support letter from DIRECTED to build on other collaborative activities.

⁶³ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual> [25.09.2025]

⁶⁴ <https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/second-open-call> [25.09.2025]

3.3.2.4 Sustain Phase

As DIRECTED moves into the Sustain Phase of Risk-Tandem, we recognise that Zala has progressed less in terms of building continued form for engagement of key actors during the first three years. However, it has built a strong foundation especially with political support from Keszthely who is committed to transdisciplinary collaboration to realise his vision for the city. As such, the Risk-Tandem process has built some very strong relationships (mayor and ZSRT) and has allowed for space to connect people who would not have had the opportunity to meet and exchange otherwise.

The vision is to support the **Climate Festival in April 2026** and develop a 'blueprint' for continuing such a festival on a yearly basis and encouraging other municipalities and their mayors to embrace it. This can act as a governance mechanism to sustain engagement and commitment of key actors especially mayors and their role for engaging the public.

Further ideas on **additional mechanisms** for continuing collaboration, like the Climate Alliance that was suggested in the first workshop, will be further explored to identify how these could be organised, hosted and maintained. The RWL host is seeking further **funding opportunities** to collaborate with the key stakeholders involved in the RWL to build on the momentum from the DIRECTED project.

The **multi-hazard Data Fabric**, although it is a technical solution, is expected to facilitate dialogue between ZSRT, mayors and other government officials (priority 2) while also supporting ZSRT in understanding how it can become more prepared (priority 1).

3.4 Real World Lab 4: Rhine-Erft

Figure 56: Rhine-Erft Region Real World Lab.

The Rhine-Erft RWL is hosted by the Erftverband, i.e., a regional water board. The *Erftverband* is operating in an area of 4216 square kilometres, consisting of five districts, and stretching all the way to the Dutch border. The waterboard researches and monitors the hydrological situation of the region, supports the construction and restoration of the *Erft* river and its subsidiaries, and deals with sewage, waste water, and canals.⁶⁵ The Erftverband, alongside the State Agency for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection (LANUK - formerly *LANUV*) and the German Weather Service (DWD), serves as a central information hub for hydrological data. Germany is divided into sixteen federal states (“Länder”), with the state of Northrhine-Westphalia being the focal point of the DIRECTED project. Specifically, the project focuses on the Erft catchment, which consists of four main districts, namely Euskirchen, Rhine-Erft, Rhine-Sieg, Rhine-Neuss, and Düren. These districts are characterized by mainly small scale rural settlements and towns, alongside agricultural and industrial areas.

[Figure 57](#) provides an overview of the Risk-Tandem application for the Rhine-Erft Region RWL covering the priority gaps in the Foundation Phase, the key activities during the Growth

⁶⁵ <https://www.erftverband.de/> [27.09.2025]

and Learn Phases and the governance mechanisms/technical solutions being prepared for the Sustain Phase.

Figure 57: Overview of Risk-Tandem application for Rhine-Erft Region RWL.

The Risk-Tandem Framework application has been taking place via the following co-production and engagement activities.

3.4.1 Foundation Phase

The Rhine-Erft RWL, hosted by Erftverband, is composed of numerous administrative bodies, who all share some involvement on the municipal, district, and regional level, and agenda-setting capacities on the federal level, as presented in Figure 58. In particular, the Erftverband focuses on the district engagement and flood protection corporation (hwsErft) to access municipalities and leverage their impact.⁶⁶ The original aims of the Rhine-Erft RWL set out in DIRECTED were to improve flood management procedures, improve DRM communication between actors, as well as to strengthen the interface between the waterboard and DRM and CCA actors. A less focused but poignant issue is drought awareness and its relation to climate change in the region.

⁶⁶

<https://hws-kooperation.erftverband.de/zentrale-hochwasserschutzmassnahmen-im-erft-einzugsgebiet/> [10.09.2025]

3.4.1.1 Actor Networks/Setting the Scene

Figure 58: Stakeholder Map of Rhine-Erft RWL.

The *Erftverband* serves as a connection point between all the surrounding districts and their municipalities, as well as the intermunicipal flood protection corporation (*hwsErft*), which seeks to bring the various municipalities together in terms of flood risk prevention and management.⁶⁷ Importantly, the districts comprising the municipalities all have their own civil protection services, such as fire departments and emergency services. The Rhine-Erft Catchment is home to a number of districts and 21 municipalities that are all engaged in their respective capacities as local authorities in the DRM process, and to a lesser extent, CCA measures.

The Ahrtal flood of 2021 revealed the challenges inherent in such a broad actor network, with siloed responsibilities and jurisdictions. For these reasons, the federal Ministry of the Interior along with the Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development developed the KRITIS-Dialog Project.⁶⁸ KRITIS-Dialog seeks to create disaster resilient regions through intermunicipal coordination and collaboration, with a focus on protecting critical infrastructure such as roads, telecommunications, and power grids. The project accordingly brings together a variety of stakeholders, ranging from energy and telecom providers (private) to road construction and maintenance services (public).

⁶⁷<https://interkommunales.nrw/projekt/interkommunale-hochwasserschutzkooperation-erft-hwserft/> [10.09.2025]

⁶⁸ <https://kritis-dialog.de/das-projekt> [10.09.2025]

3.4.1.2 Governance and Institutional Context

Legal framework

Legal frameworks exist in Germany for DRM and CCA. While the respective federal states are responsible for DRM and CCA, based on Germany's "Grundgesetz", or constitution, disaster assistance is organized by the federal government (Section II, Art. 35). Civil protection in particular is subdivided into two categories, namely civil defense and disaster control. Civil defense is handled by the federal government, and the individual districts are responsible for the control and management of disasters (Federal Office for Civil Protection 2023). Another important pillar of civil protection in Germany is further the "Technische Hilfswerk", the federal volunteer organization which provides assistance through technical expertise in the case of an event.⁶⁹ In the context of the Rhine-Erft RWL, this division entails that the planning, management, and prevention of extreme hydrological events, such as fluvial flooding, is handled by the local districts and their municipalities, while the federal government provides assistance in the case of overburdened resources. The Rhine-Erft RWL is under the jurisdiction of the federal state of Northrhine-Westphalia, in which regional DRM is generally guided by the regional disaster protection law, namely the "Gesetz über den Brandschutz, die Hilfeleistung und den Katastrophenschutz (BHKG)", which was adopted in 2015.

Various policy agendas outline the need for localized DRM and CCA strategies (Resilience Strategy 2022; Critical Infrastructure Protection 2009; Climate Adaptation Act 2023; EG-Hochwasserrisikomanagementrichtlinie 2007). The Climate Adaptation Act of 2023 further provides a binding framework for the federal government, states, and municipalities on the implementation of DRM and CCA measures. Accordingly, there are two separate national policy agendas for DRM and CCA, namely the aforementioned Climate Adaptation Law of 2023 and the Federal Civil Protection and Disaster Relief Act, which specifies DRM responsibilities. Further, the "EG-Hochwasserrisikomanagementrichtlinie" of 2007 (i.e., a European guideline for flood risk protection and management), is implemented on different administrative levels, ensuring the determination of risk water, development of flood risk plans, and the creation of flood risk and flood hazard maps. These guidelines are updated every 6 years.⁷⁰

A central piece of legislation with regard to CCA and its integration into DRM plans is the German Strategy for Strengthening Resilience to Disasters of 2022. This strategy seeks to implement the Sendai Framework, an international Disaster Risk Management agenda aimed at reducing disaster risks on a global scale.⁷¹ Further, the National Strategy for Critical Infrastructure Protection 2009 (CIP) acknowledges the threat climate change poses to critical infrastructure. However, there is still a lack in resources and know-how when it comes to the localized and synergistic implementation of CCA strategies alongside DRM.⁷²

⁶⁹ https://www.thw.de/DE/THW/Organisation/organisation_node.html [11.09.2025]

⁷⁰ <https://www.flussgebiete.nrw.de/hochwasserrisikomanagement-plaene-und-karten> [15.09.2025]

⁷¹ <https://www.bmz.de/en/issues/disaster-risk-management> [11.09.2025]

⁷² <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/kommunalbefragung-klimaanpassung-2023> [11.09.2025]

As the Actor-Network context of the Rhine-Erft RWL shows, there are various institutional levels to be taken into account when analysing its governance structure. From a policy perspective, the highest level of impact can be found on the level of the European Union, with the EU Adaptation Strategy adopted in 2021 (COM/2021/82). This communication, though not legally binding, serves as a reference point for Climate Change Adaptation processes and resilience building on a European level. On a federal level, this strategy is emulated through the German Climate Adaptation Law, or the “Bundes-Klimaanpassungsgesetz (KAnG)” from 2024 (KAnG 2024; also Schink, 2024).

The KAnG implies an integrated understanding of CCA and DRM, naming Disaster Risk Management and civil protection as one of the clusters in need of Climate Change Adaptation considerations (KAnG, Section 3, 4a). Importantly, while the KAnG highlights the possibility for cooperation between the federal and state level (i.e., the “Länder”), the main responsibility for acting on CCA and monitoring regional climate impacts lies with the federal states themselves (KAnG, Section 4). Noticeably, the federal state of Northrhine-Westphalia preceded the federal government in adopting a climate adaptation law in 2021, the “Klimaanpassungsgesetz Nordrhein-Westfalen”, or KIANG. In this piece of legislation, the state committed to the implementation of a climate adaptation strategy (KIANG Section 4, (4)), which was first presented in 2024. The implementation of this strategy, especially with regard to its monitoring and knowledge producing aspects, is also part of the LANUK’s responsibilities. The LANUK further offers climate adaptation consulting for the various municipalities throughout the federal state of Northrhine-Westphalia.⁷³ In summary, the overarching legal framework encourages the integration of CCA strategies with DRM planning.

From a policy perspective, there seems to be a strong understanding of the need to integrate Climate Change Adaptation measures into Disaster Risk Management strategies. From the guidance set out in the European Climate Adaptation Strategy, to the ratification of such guidance in the German federal Klimaanpassungs Gesetz, and more regionally, the Klimaanpassungsgesetz from Northrhine-Westphalia, one can find coherence in terms of bringing the two issues together. For the reasons outlined, the legal framework is scored as good/strong (4) for enabling DRM and CCA integration. Given the context of the Erftverband and its stakeholders, this indicator was tagged with a low priority.

<p>Legal Framework: To what extent are legal frameworks working to enable DRM & CCA integration?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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⁷³ <https://www.klimaatlas.nrw.de/beratung-klimaanpassung/beratung> [11.09.2025]

Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities carved out through the various policy documents give a clear outline of who has authority over which decision-making space, and how that authority is to be carried out. The federal system and its concomitant polycentricity further entails a division of responsibility with regard to spatial scales, ranging from immediate responsibilities to act on a local level, to more strategic and long-term thinking on a federal level. Based on the engagements of the DIRECTED consortium, and Workpackages 3 and 4 with the RWL host and stakeholders, the general division of responsibilities is functional with regard to most Disaster Risk Management processes. However, there are two important caveats. One, is a lack of institutional dynamism that has restricted the degree to which knowledge and expertise (in this case from the *Erftverband*) could be shared. Since the *Erftverband* is legally not permitted to *warn* the districts, but can only *inform* about the current hydrological situation, there is generally a sense of erring on the side of caution when it comes to exchanges with the districts. It is important to note that the *Erftverband* is obliged to share information, and that information sharing has always worked well (also before DIRECTED). However, the RWL hosts have made clear that there is room for improvement, especially given the fact that the line between informing and warning is thin.

Two, is the practical limitation of municipal actors to implement long-term CCA strategies due to a lack of resources. This has ultimately led to a siloed understanding of how individual institutions, namely the municipalities and expert institutes, operate on a daily basis. For these reasons, the clarity of roles and responsibilities is scored as good (4) and functionality scored at intermediate (3). With both these aspects playing a role when it comes to the DRM and CCA integration in the Erf context, they were scored with medium priority.

<p>Clarity of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities for DRM & CCA clear within the legal framework?</p>	<p>4 [MP]</p>
<p>Functionality of Roles and Responsibilities: To what extent are roles and responsibilities functional for DRM and CCA in practice?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>

Multilevel/Polycentric Governance

While the polycentric/multi-level governance structure works well with regard to the division of responsibilities in terms of DRM, there is room for improvement when it comes to the implementation of CCA processes alongside DRM thinking. Although the need for climate adaptation is commonly understood and highlighted in various regional and federal policy documents and institutional agendas, this understanding is not always translated into the local context.

In the case of the Rhine-Erft Catchment, and especially the *Erftverband* and its surrounding actor network, there is much more immediate focus on handling upcoming floods and generally managing the daily hydrological context. On the one hand, this focus can be traced back to the stakeholder selection so far. Most of them are water management actors, who are professionally much closer to DRM actions and processes than to CCA. On the other hand, this focus may still cause a disconnect in the agenda-setting regarding CCA on higher levels, and immediate concerns for DRM on the local level. A comparative study, analyzing the various degrees of CCA in all sixteen federal states of Germany, concludes that Northrhine-Westphalia has a comparatively high level of institutionalized CCA strategies (King, 2022). However, the study also finds that in general, CCA strategies are based on non-committal sets of recommendations, which on the one hand allows for some flexibility in how individual states respond to climate change, but also impedes the implementation of more stringent policies that might prove necessary, especially with regard to long-term implementation of integrated DRM and CCA solutions.

In summary, both the desktop reviews and RWL host engagements suggest that there may still be room for improvement when it comes to integrating Climate Change Adaptation strategies into the municipal DRM planning. Importantly, the RWL hosts are currently working on receiving feedback from the local stakeholders to better understand and further this integration. While the catastrophic floods 2021 (DKKV, 2024; Fekete et al., 2021) have led to increased awareness and a sense of immediacy to act on DRM (e.g., through the construction of flood protection infrastructure such as dams and levees, as well as the partial restoration of various rivers), there seems to be a lack of long-term thinking that would align DRM with increasing climate extremes. For these reasons the multi-level/polycentric governance is scored as 2 out of 5. Importantly, this indicator serves as an insightful and highly relevant point of interest for further improvement of DRM and CCA integration in the Erft context, which is why it was tagged as high priority.

<p>Multilevel/Polycentric Governance: To what extent are the actor roles at different levels working to support integrated DRM and CCA processes?</p>	<p>2 [HP]</p>
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Accountability

Concerns surrounding accountability have an important impact on DRM/CCA decision-making for this RWL, especially for the RWL host (*Erftverband*). In particular, the *Erftverband* has no official mandate to issue public warnings of a potentially hazardous hydrological situation developing. Instead they are legally restricted to informing the various districts about the current state of the various gauges, dams, etc. Importantly, this limitation is due to *Erftverband's* official mandate, which in turn limits the *Erftverband's* ability to share critical information directly with the public.

Further, the strict operational structures can, at times, prove cumbersome - especially when quick acting and potential improvisation become necessary. The tabletop exercise conducted in January 2025 underscored this potential bottleneck, when various stakeholders and actors were put into roles they do not usually hold. This allowed them to see how other actors during an event might not have the same kind of information available to themselves, and might have to make decisions on a different basis than they would assume. Accordingly, the exercise helped the participants in understanding accountability concerns in their decision-making that they usually do not have.

For these reasons accountability structures are scored as 3 Medium Priority. This indicator has been tagged as Medium Priority, as it is a relevant indicator that should be considered, but it has not been identified as a High Priority by this RWL.

<p>Accountability: To what extent are accountability concerns managed to support decision-making DRM/CCA?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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3.4.1.3 Risk Management/Knowledge

DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence

In general, with the Ertfverband’s establishment in 1958, there is an acute understanding of the relevance of hydrological events, in particular with regard to floods. Knowledge creation and sharing works centrally through the Ertfverband on topics related to hydrological planning, alongside the LANUK. The risk management structure spans from the regional to the international level.

There is a structural context within which DRM and CCA should be synergized on a federal and local level. On an international scale, the German Strategy for Strengthening Resilience to Disasters of 2022 seeks to implement the Sendai Framework, an international Disaster Risk Management agenda aimed at reducing disaster risks on a global scale.⁷⁴ The Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development seeks to improve cooperation through the clear definition of responsibilities, data-sharing, as well as coordinating reporting systems and aligning financial instruments. Risk assessment on a federal level is done through the BMU with its sexennial report on climate change effects, the most recent being from 2021 (Eisemann, 2021).

Beyond the global and international perspective, the European Union as well as the German government have presented strategies for the protection of critical infrastructure, which acknowledge the impact of climate change, and extreme weather events in particular (Lindström, 2009). The German strategies accordingly reads that global climate change

⁷⁴ <https://www.bmz.de/en/issues/disaster-risk-management> [28.09.2025]

“[w]ill entail additional and, in part, extreme burdens on critical infrastructure [...]” (CIP 2009, p. 10).

The focus on critical infrastructure has further gained traction within the academic community researching Disaster Risk Management and resilience in Germany, and in particular in Northrhine-Westphalia and the Erft-Catchment. Among other things, the research focus thereby lies with understanding how critical infrastructure vulnerability can be analyzed on a local level (Fekete, 2020), how regional flood risks can be mitigated through land use planning (Greiving et al., 2023). Further, authors like Becker and colleagues present improved models for flood risk management in the region, emphasising the need for polycentricity, participation, and the anticipation of uncertainty (Becker et al., 2015).

An important moment in the development of regional and federal DRM in Northrhine-Westphalia and Germany was the catastrophic floods of the Ahr-Valley in 2021. The flood led to over 190 casualties, ten thousands affected or displaced, and economic damages of around 30 billion Euros, and is considered one of the most catastrophic events in modern Germany’s history (DKKV, 2024).

Based on the various levels of governance wherein both DRM and CCA strategies presented, there are plans and concepts of how both could be integrated at the appropriate levels. At the same time, there is a lack with regard to implementing these plans and making use of the policy context in order to improve DRM and CCA policy coherence. For this reason, we scored the appropriateness of governance levels to deal with DRM and CCA challenges with a 3 out of 5, and its priority was tagged as medium.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent do plans exist at appropriate levels to address DRM & CCA challenges?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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There exists a wide array of scholarly engagement, from both the governance perspective as well as the modelling community that seeks to better understand and improve disaster preparedness in the Rhine-Erft Region. Engagement from the *Erftverband* via HOWIS, and the interest in further fostering the engagement among various actors and institutions highlights a push towards a coherent DRM and CCA strategy that is however, inhibited by data availability and sharing, as well as institutional barriers.

On a national and individual state level, there is a clear goal of integrating both DRM strategies and CCA planning. The policy analysis carried out so far suggests that the challenge lies on the immediate municipal level. Namely, how can these large-scale strategies be translated into local level policy. At the same time, this assessment needs to be qualified by the fact that there has been little discussion surrounding CCA with the stakeholders and municipalities by the RWL hosts so far. A set of planned interviews will provide further insight.

What has been highlighted by studies from the Federal Environmental Ministry, is that there is still a lack in resources and know-how when it comes to the localized and synergistic implementation of CCA strategies alongside DRM (Friedrich et al., 2024). There is general agreement on the federal and state level that CCA needs to be part of DRM. However, this agreement comes in the form of recommendations rather than stringent policies, which allows for quite some leeway on a regional level as to how much climate change planning is part of the disaster risk thinking process.

With the disparity between national and state level agendas, and the local implementation of DRM we scored the alignment and coherence of policy objectives to address extreme climate events a 2 out of 5. In the long term, this coherence may prove to be of high priority, but given the existing temporal frames of reference, it was tagged as medium priority.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent do objectives/goals in plans at different levels align/cohere to address extreme climate events?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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This disparity also leads to a lack of assessing and synergizing trade-offs between DRM and CCA interventions in practice. Specifically, there are no institutional means to facilitate this synergy. Accordingly, we scored the extent to which trade-offs are minimized a 1 out of 5. Since this was not of central concern in the workshops and discussions, it was further tagged as a low priority.

<p>DRM/CCA policy and plan coherence: To what extent are synergies maximized and trade-offs minimized across DRM & CCA interventions?</p>	<p>1 [LP]</p>
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Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships

The desktop research and literature review so far suggests that there are only limited interactions between DRM practitioners and CCA actors. Such a lack of interaction may in part be driven by the fact that CCA represents a joint action problem, namely an issue that concerns everyone but over which no singular entity has complete authority, given its far reaching impacts (see for example, Thomas & Knüppe, 2016). There are further no institutional guidelines that would facilitate this engagement. Meetings organized by DIRECTED and the RWL host represented such opportunities, and were always extremely welcomed by the stakeholders.

At the same time, the RWL hosts are currently in the process of developing a set of interviews to directly learn from the stakeholders, how their understanding of the current

CCA strategy in the Erft region is. These interviews will further shine light on these actor relationships. Preliminarily, the extent to which DRM & CCA actors were able to interact was thus scored a 2 out of 5 and tagged as a medium priority.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent do DRM & CCA actors interact at appropriate levels?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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Perhaps because of the lack of institutionalized opportunities, there is a great interest and willingness for collaboration by the RWL host and the stakeholders. The establishment of the so-called “WebEx-Meeting”, an informal, adhoc meeting set up by the *Erftverband* to exchange views on the current hydrological situation in the case of an event with local district authorities, is an example that proves initiative and enthusiasm from all actors, if the space and resources are provided.

There was some initial skepticism by a few participants when engaging in the various exercises and workshops. However, this skepticism was quickly overcome once the activities started and showed to be useful and provided a learning space for each participant. For this reason, the willingness and openness towards collaboration was scored 4 out of 5. Further developing these relationships was also seen as an important part of developing CCA and DRM integration, which is why it is tagged as a high priority.

<p>Strength of DRM/CCA actor relationships: To what extent is there willingness and openness towards collaboration beyond formal requirements?</p>	<p>4 [HP]</p>
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Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools

Risk assessment data/models and tools are available to address DRM/CCA challenges, and play a critical role for the *Erftverband* and their surrounding region. However, some major findings from the catastrophic floods of the Ahr-Valley in 2021 concluded that there was a lack in adequate early warning system information (Thieken et al., 2023), a lack that was compounded by the rarity and unpredictability of the event (for a detailed, interdisciplinary overview of the event, see also Mohr et al., 2023 and Ludwig et al., 2023). The unavailability of data and the sharing thereof was further seen as an important inhibitor that exacerbated the flood and its impacts (Fekete et al., 2021). Also, when it comes to the concept of “building back better”, i.e. increasing climate and disaster resilience after an event, there is a lot of room for improvement. Birkmann et al., (2023) for example argue that structures are often already unstable before an event, and that floods reinforce and highlight that instability.

The availability and sharing of data is also a focal point of the RWL hosts. Accordingly, the *Erftverband* provides an interactive flood information map on their website, the so-called *HOWIS*, or “**Hochwasser**informations- und Warnsystem Erft (flood information and warning system Erft)”. This flood information and warning system provides information on actual and forecasted precipitation within the Erft catchment area. It is primarily intended to support the internal flood operation management of the *Erftverband* and is also available for other authorities as a voluntary service

HOWIS provides the following services:

- It gives an overview of the current and forecasted weather situation in the Erft catchment,
- It shows current water level and discharge of river gauges in the Erft catchment,
- It gives an early warning of critical amount of discharge at the gauges in the catchment area, based on precipitation forecast and a rainfall-runoff-model (NASIM by Hydrotec),
- It provides links to further information (e.g. website with the hydrological situation report from the State Agency for Nature, Environment and Climate North Rhine-Westphalia (LANUK)),
- It gives a general assumption about the near future flood risk situation and the *Erftverband's* internal flood operation level,
- It aims to support the information exchange between actors in case of flood

With the broad availability and high level of modelling tools in mind, the extent to which existing risk modelling tools are able to address key DRM and CCA challenges was thereby scored with 4 out of 5, and was tagged as a low priority.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent do (existing) risk modelling data/models/tools address key DRM and CCA challenges?</p>	<p>4 [LP]</p>
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Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools

With regard to DRM, the RWL has access to a strong network of models and data that provide a strong foundation for decision-making in the event of a disaster. However, there is very little integration of CCA thinking, e.g. through climate data that would support the DRM process on a more long-term basis. There is a general interest and willingness for further innovation and evolution of the RWL’s DRM and CCA process by individual actors from a variety of the institutions involved. However, there are institutional and legal barriers to how much agency these actors have in actually bringing about change.

For this reason, the extent to which DRM and CCA plans/practices can embrace innovative models/data/tools, has been scored a 3 out of 5, and tagged as a medium priority based on feedback and discussions with the stakeholders.

<p>Risk Assessment Data, Models, & Tools: To what extent can DRM and CCA plans/practices embrace innovative risk models/data/tools across DRM and CCA?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Reliability/suitability (fit-for-purpose) of data/models

During an onsite visit of one of the dams in September 2023, the local engineers explained to the consortium that after the 2021 flood, the flood infrastructure was rebuilt to the same level as before 2021 rather than accounting for a potentially increased return period. This was because the regulations and laws in place upon which the planning of flood infrastructure is based, has not yet caught up with the increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events fuelled by climate change. This lag in updating the models which serve as a decision-baseline for the planning of flood infrastructure therefore shows a poor link between DRM and CCA models.

With this in mind, the reliability and suitability of data and models for DRM and CCA decision-making has been scored a 2 out of 5. The tag for medium priority is further the result of the input that integrating existing climate data into DRM processes was deemed an important part for the integration process in the Ertf context.

<p>Reliability/suitability (fit-for-purpose) of data/models: To what extent are the available data/models/tools reliable/suitable for DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools

Further, there is a self-restraint by the *Erfverband* in particular due to its legal remit and self-understanding that it is cautious what kind of information to share when. This is a crucial hurdle that the RWL host has sought to overcome through the implementation of the so-called “WebEx Meeting”. For this reason, we scored the extent to which the legal implications of data and modelling tools support the best use of data a 3 out of 5, and tagged as a medium priority.

<p>Legal Implications of Data and Modelling Tools: To what extent do legal mindsets or norms support ‘best’ data/models use in DRM/CCA decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation

There are no legally binding forms of citizen inclusion and participation when it comes to the planning of DRM and CCA strategies. While North Rhine-Westphalia's climate adaptation law does state that there should be communication, information, and advice provided from the government for its citizens (KlAnG Section 4, (2)), these are limited to ensure meaningful participation. As the RWL hosts have noted, there are important challenges with regard to the engagement activities. Specifically, the expectations between authorities and the public differ after an extreme event, as there is a disparity between how much support the government should provide, and how much the citizens ought to “help themselves”. Legally, personal preparedness in relation to flooding is part of the water resources act (Section 5, 2).

At the same time, there are inclusion and participation processes in place. For example, citizen workshops are taking place as part of the development of the intermunicipal flood protection concept in the *hwsErft*. While these are not required by law, they have been included in *hwsErft* procedure based on the initiative of the *Erfverband*.

Thus, there have been some attempts by the RWL hosts to create citizen engagement opportunities (see for example, Tag der offenen Tür in Gymnicher Mühle, 28.08.2025, listed in Milestone 13). However, there are still possibilities to improve upon these activities, especially aiming to make them more interactive and based on knowledge co-creation and sharing. For these reasons citizen inclusion and participation have both scored 3 out of 5. While citizen inclusion and participation play a role, hence the medium priority tag, the willingness to further enhance this participation is a low priority for the RWL.

<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent do frameworks enable/require citizen involvement in decision-making</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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<p>(Citizen) Inclusion and Participation: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors willing to enhance citizen inclusion/participation in decision-making?</p>	<p>3 [LP]</p>
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Public warning/risk communication

When it comes to communicating and warning, the *Ertfverband* plays a crucial role as interlocutor among the various districts. There are continuous engagement processes with the public in place, to also highlight the risks that come with intensifying extreme weather events and disasters due to climate change. However, this aspect was not a crucial point of focus for the RWL, and was therefore tagged as a low priority.

<p>Public warning/risk communication: To what extent are DRM/CCA actors effectively communicating risk and warnings/forecasts to the public?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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Social Justice

When it comes to active engagement, there is very little work done on a local level to include disenfranchised communities in the DRM and CCA process. In the case of the Rhine-Ertf RWL, these communities might refer to the elderly population, as well as people who do not speak German, and people who have disenfranchised socio-economically. This is also not a central concern for most stakeholders in the region. The RWL hosts have shown interest in questions of justice, however, especially with regard to the overlapping issues between DRM and CCA processes. This interest has also led to a shared publication on justice concerns regarding resilience building in the region (Hofbauer et al., 2025). For these reasons, the extent to which disenfranchised groups can engage in DRM and CCA strategies is scored with a 2 out of 5, and tagged as a low priority.

<p>Social Justice: To what extent can or do disenfranchised groups engage in DRM and/or CCA?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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Feasibility

The political, social and economic situation in Germany has had limited influence on DRM and CCA action. There is limited leeway with regard to structural changes, e.g. by focusing on the various legal authorities and jurisdictions set out by law. At the same time, actors such

as the RWL hosts have shown a lot of interest in further building on the capacities they have to improve upon their DRM and CCA strategy, in particular with regard to establishing a shared communication basis and developing an informal communication channel. For these reasons, the feasibility of how the political, social, and economic situation is supporting DRM and CCA action is scored a 3 out of 5. The degree to which existing structures support DRM and CCA action, was further deemed as relevant by the stakeholders, and therefore scored as a medium priority.

<p>Feasibility: To what extent is the political, social, and economic situation supporting DRM or CCA action?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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3.4.1.4 Knowledge co-production

Collaborative Arrangements and Institutional Setting

The general workflow with regard to DRM is structured in a way that does not foster transdisciplinary collaboration. Given the clear structure set out by the state law on fire protection, aid, and disaster protection (BHKG - see previous section), the districts are the main actors when it comes to disaster protection (BHKG Section 2, 3). This entails a heavy focus on modelling expertise, with an emphasis on hydrological expertise. While crucial for DRM in the region, the sole focus on hydrological information leads to a weaker focus on societal implications, that would be necessary to account for more long-term and holistic thinking along the lines of CCA.

At the same time, there is generally an interest in collaboration between fields of expertise, when the opportunity is given, as various workshops have shown. Further, the implementation of the flood protection cooperation (the *hwsErft*) is a clear step towards increasing both intermunicipal cooperation on flood risk management, with a partial emphasis on citizen engagement through workshops and information events. Similarly, the KRITIS-Dialog project is built on, among other things, immediate public engagement and collaboration.⁷⁵

While there are structures to enable collaboration between municipalities and engagement with citizens, there is no immediate focus on fostering transdisciplinary collaboration. For this reason, the collaborative arrangements and institutional settings have scored 2 out of 5. This was not front and center for the stakeholders, and therefore tagged as low priority.

<p>Collaborative Arrangements and Institutional Setting: To what extent do collaborative arrangements exist to foster transdisciplinary collaboration?</p>	<p>2 [LP]</p>
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⁷⁵ <https://kritis-dialog.de/das-projekt> [11.09.2025]

Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production

Initially, there has been no real understanding of the need for or value of knowledge co-production among the stakeholders of the Rhine-Erft RWL. Through collaboration with DIRECTED, in particular through the activities arranged by both Work Package 3 and Work Package 4, there now is a slowly growing interest in further developing co-creative skills, e.g., via interactive workshops and various exercises. This is especially driven by the RWL hosts. However, overall there is a broad shared understanding between RWL 4 stakeholders of the problems and challenges they need to address. In RWL 4, much of the discussion has centered on governance and communication challenges, while interest in technical aspects such as the Data Fabric has remained limited.

Although there was no clear recognition at the outset of the specific need for knowledge co-production, stakeholders did express a shared goal of improving collaboration and working more effectively together. For this reason, the extent to which there is a shared understanding for knowledge-coproduction is scored 2 out of 5 and its priority tagged as medium.

<p>Goals/Needs for knowledge co-production: To what extent is there a shared understanding of problems/challenges and needs for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>2 [MP]</p>
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Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production

Within the Capacity Needs Assessment the RWL hosts stated that they had not collaborated with CCA practitioners before DIRECTED and had no experience of knowledge co-production. However, they were open to trying it and said that they believed it to be an essential and highly effective mode of working. This is mostly reflective of the wider lab experience. The hosts have shown general interest and openness to engage with engagement activities such as workshops, serious games, and tabletop exercises. This general attitude can be further built upon through the hosts' knowledge and past successful means of convening a diverse set of stakeholders and interest groups. These factors combined lead to a score on the extent to which DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production of 3 out of 5.

<p>Capacities/skills for knowledge co-production: To what extent do DRM/CCA stakeholders have capacities or skills for knowledge co-production?</p>	<p>3 [MP]</p>
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3.4.1.5 Key Risk Governance Gaps/Aligned Indicators

In summary, researchers from DIRECTED, alongside collaboration and iteration with the RWL hosts of the Rhine-Erft Region, have identified three key risk governance gaps. This identification is based on these aspects having been rated with the highest priority and potential for improvement in the foundation and application phase of the RTF's indicators.

One is the integration of CCA considerations into DRM policies and modelling. The gap here consists of a general willingness to bring CCA considerations into the DRM process, but not having the legal remit to do so. This integration is importantly limited due to legal constraints. However, there may be space to bypass these limitations via stronger inter-institutional communication settings (e.g. stakeholder engagement workshops, or the WebEx meeting), and by leveraging individual interest and expertise to enable pro-active involvement.

Two, the flow of sharing information and knowledge between the various actors involved could be improved, especially on an institutional level. More specifically, the existing communication channels between *Erftverband* and the representatives of the districts can be further enhanced by making them more guided and uniform.

Three, there are the limited knowledge co-production processes, as well as citizen engagement and social justice considerations. While there have been some efforts made to increase citizen engagement (e.g. via the *hwsErft* flood cooperation), the degree to which issues surrounding social justice and vulnerable communities are being taken into account is very limited.

In sum, it became clear that there is a clear gap when it comes to the way in which information surrounding DRM is shared. This gap was owed to the institutional context of the actors involved. Specifically, the *Erftverband* has been sharing hydrological information with local municipalities, without a streamlined process. Based on both the interaction with the RWL host and stakeholders, as well as the governance analysis carried out by Workpackage 3 that the issue of Climate Change Adaptation has so far been only discussed within certain parts of the *Erftverband*. It should be noted that this also stems from the fact that the *Erftverband's* role is to analyse hydrological extremes in water bodies and their immediate surroundings, as well as monitor groundwater. Accordingly, there is of course little attention paid on how to integrate CCA concepts with DRM measures. Finally, questions of social justice with regard to the implementation of DRM and CCA processes are barely considered.

3.4.2 Growth Phase

With the Foundation Phase as a basis, the Rhine-Erft RWL has been engaged in the Growth and Learn Phases of the RTF. This engagement entails the setting of priorities on how to further improve and evolve the existing Disaster Risk Management processes, and align them with Climate Change Adaptation strategies. With the baseline assessments and

indicator application in mind, the following priorities have been identified for the Rhine-Erft RWL.

Priority 1: Improving Interinstitutional Communication and Information Exchange between the *Erftverband* and the Districts

As became clear throughout the various engagement activities co-organized and facilitated with the RWL hosts, RWL hosts alongside DIRECTED researchers identified a critical gap with regard to the communication between the *Erftverband* and the various local stakeholders involved in the DRM process. While there have been and will continue to be numerous RWL engagement activities, the following two serve as insightful examples as to how qualitative information and data have been gathered, and engagement among and with the stakeholders has been fostered.

Addressing this gap was supported by the knowledge co-production capacity development activities w facilitated with the RWL host. Specifically, the serious game training exercise held in September of 2023 alongside the General Assembly was an invaluable first step towards realizing that such a gap existed to begin with. The exercise simulated the various strands and authorities of decision-making of multi-level governance structures, and highlighted the need for cooperation and communication in the context of preparing for, dealing with, and learning from an event.

Figure 59: Template for Serious Game Training Exercise carried out in September 2023.

Each player group took the role of a different stakeholder, ranging from emergency services, to local authorities, researchers, and national entities, and had to act according to their best understanding of their role. This exercise proved to be an engaging learning and networking experience for the participants, and built a strong foundation for further engagement.

Importantly, it gave input for the further tailoring and adjustment of the RTF for the Rhine-Erft context, by providing key insights on how the participants saw their own role within their respective institutions, and what responsibilities and communication channels were open to them. This was a crucial step towards identifying a gap between the kind of information that different organizations, such as the *Erftverband*, had access to, and how that information was shared with other institutions.

This experience was further built upon in the tabletop exercise of January 2025, also held at the *Erftverband*. Here, another scenario of a flood event was played out by stakeholders from the districts, district government, and the LANUK (Northrhine-Westphalia's Environmental Agency). This exercise allowed everyone involved in the DRM process of the region to see how other organizations go about their business, and how they act in case of an event. This, in turn, showed some openings on how information could be better shared and communicated between the stakeholders.

Figure 60: Impressions from the tabletop exercise conducted with stakeholders in January 2025.

Both of these engagement activities were further guided by the user storylines and model workflows that have been developed in Work Package 5 for the Data Fabric. These storylines served as an input for the parametrization of the scenarios used in the tabletop exercises, to ensure that the exercise was closely linked to the challenges faced by the various actors present at the workshop.

Governance Mechanisms to Improve Communication

Based on these engagement activities and the data collected, two central governance mechanisms have been devised for the improvement of the communication gap. First, the RWL hosts have implemented an online meeting, wherein they informally share hydrological information with potentially affected districts before and during a (possible) event. The

meeting is an exchange, in which all participants are actively involved and which results in a better understanding and assessment of the situation for all attendees. This engagement serves two purposes. On the one hand, it provides immediate information that may be relevant to the decision-making process of the district and enables a joint assessment of the situation. On the other hand, it will improve collaboration and trust-building in the long run between the *Erftverband* and the engaging districts.

Figure 61: Example of decision-process outcome during tabletop exercise.

Second, it is planned that RWL hosts will host periodic stakeholder engagement activities in the form of scenario workshops and tabletop exercises. The first instances of such engagement activities have produced great interest from the engaged actors. Importantly, representatives from the local and regional governments, emergency services, as well as flood risk experts participated, which ensured a fruitful and inspiring dialogue (for an overview and reflection, see Annex reflection notes RWL 4 TTX). It is important to note that this will depend on available resources and input. This also includes improving the communication of hydrological data and forecasts with the authorities (see also [Annex 2](#), section 4).

Priority 2: Define and understand the *Erftverband's* role in climate adaptation/climate extremes (including drought)

A major insight that has been drawn from the application of the RTF to the Rhine-Erft RWL was the gap between a general willingness and interest of individual actors to integrate

Climate Change Adaptation strategies into Disaster Risk Management processes, and the lack of possible points of intervention to do so. The governance interviews conducted in July 2025 with the RWL hosts highlighted the fact that CCA strategies are often neglected when it comes to discussions and decisions surrounding DRM. (see Annex 3)

As identified through the indicators, this is due to a lack of coherence when it comes to shared policy objectives and goals from various authorities. While the state level and federal government may seek to facilitate CCA, local administrators in the Rhine-Erft Region are faced with the immediate consequences of potential disasters. They therefore may act more in accordance with short-term effective measures, such as rebuilding and maintaining dams and infrastructure in accordance with flood return periods that are no longer in line with climate data.

Governance and Data Mechanisms to Improve CCA and DRM Integration

An important activity driven by the Data Fabric development, is therefore the ongoing effort towards offering realistic scenarios that account for climate change, which can then serve as a basis for future tabletop exercises and workshops. There is further a plan to integrate green roofs and other “sponge city” adaptation plans into existing flood models, in order to account for more long-term CCA strategies in a given flood scenario. Using these scenarios as input for the tabletop exercises and workshops allows us to explore potential situations that are highly relevant to the participants.

Priority 3: Improving Public Engagement and Social Justice

A final note with regard to governance in the Rhine-Erft RWL is of public engagement, participation, and social justice considerations. As the application of the indicators shows, there is only modest engagement of the public through institutionalized means, and little discussion surrounding vulnerable communities and justice concerns. Public participation is partially practiced within the context of the flood protection cooperation (*hwsErft*). The cooperation consequently serves as an important partner for the RWL hosts and DIRECTED to further host initiatives that include public voices. With participation being an integral part of the feasibility and ethical justifiability of DRM and CCA action, improving this engagement has been central to the RWL hosts and Work Packages 3 and 4.

Governance Mechanisms to Increase Public Engagement and Social Justice

One important means to increase this engagement co-organized by the RWL hosts and supported by Work Packages 3 and 4 is through public events that invite local communities to engage with the work of the *Erftverband* and the *hwsErft*. One such event was hosted at the end of August 2025. It included talks and a poster booth from the DIRECTED project, as well as the presentation of an art project that ‘sonified’ the flood data. This experience should bring the local public closer to the ways in which they experience floods, and move beyond the data and research driven expertise to a more visceral interaction with extreme weather events.

Specifically, the sonification event provided input for further WP 4 activities by generating a specific example of knowledge co-production through arts-based community engagement.

Additionally, it informed WP 3 activities by exploring arts-based engagement as a new ‘governance mechanism’ to enhance citizen-authority communication, which will also support the production of Deliverable 3.4 Guidance on good practices regarding interoperability of governance mechanisms. Throughout the Foundation Phase, it also became clear that there was little emphasis on issues regarding social justice, and the inclusion of disadvantaged communities in the participation process. This lack has further been pointed out for the DIRECTED project as a whole (see DIRECTED Ethics Report for more information).

3.4.3 Learn Phase

With the priorities for the Rhine-Erft RWL having been clarified throughout the Growth Phase, the next step in the RTF’s application is the Learn Phase. Here, the focus is on reflecting on and further developing the solutions that have emerged for the challenges of CCA and DRM integration, inter-institutional communication, and public engagement in the context of the Rhine-Erft Region. Importantly, the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning process plays an important role for this phase, allowing for the iterative improvement and revision of the RTF’s application in the Rhine-Erft context.

Developing and Improving Priority 1: Interinstitutional Communication and Information Exchange between the *Erftverband* and the Districts

The RWL hosts are seeking to tackle the lack of interinstitutional communication and information exchange through the WebEx-meeting. The WebEx-meeting is a video call which goes out to the respective districts by the *Erftverband* in the case of a potential flood event. This approach shows a lot of creativity and willingness to problem-solve within the institutional and legal boundaries they find themselves in.

Importantly, the WebEx meeting now needs to be tested on various occasions, giving insights into how well it works, and who is willing to use this offering. It may be helpful to provide formal protocols for how to go about it for future use, especially once the DIRECTED project has ended, and the RWL hosts need to continue their work in this field without the organizational space to develop such tools. In order to finalize the structure and content of the meeting and to determine how this exchange can be made as meaningful and manageable as possible for all participants, several test runs have already been conducted. Feedback rounds were used to establish a structure for the meeting and organizational procedures. The Webex meeting has already been integrated into the official processes of the *Erftverband*. The final step is now to finalize an official agreement containing all important information about the process, structure, and organization of the meeting, which will be signed by all parties and sustains this approach also after the DIRECTED Project.

Developing and improving responses to Priority 2: CCA and DRM Integration & Scenarios

The Data Fabric demonstration that has been proposed for improved scenario building is still a work in progress. Currently, both the RWL hosts and the DIRECTED consortium, are testing whether improved dam break scenarios, as well as introducing green roof approaches

into the flood damage models would prove useful for the connection of DRM planning and long-term CCA considerations. Accordingly, the recurring meetings of the Rhine-Erft RWL taskforce are currently seeking to provide improved modelling that is more specifically tailored to the interests of the *Erftverband* and the affected districts. There may be further collaboration between the RWL hosts regarding potential green roof strategies with members of the state government, in order to discuss its application, which in turn will give DIRECTED a better understanding towards the governance feasibility and information on how it could be integrated into the modelling process. This is still tentative, however.

With improved and more salient modelling data available, the scenarios used for the tabletop exercises developed throughout the Growth Phase can be more geared towards the specific challenges faced by the participants. Embedding new data points explored by the modelling team and the Data Fabric, such as green roofs and dam break scenarios, will further increase the potential learning of the exercise, and inspire new forms of reiterating and evolving the exercise itself. Future exercises and meetings will be an apt space to explore how the futures affected by climate change impact existing scenarios, and subsequently motivate the integrated thinking of CCA in DRM strategies.

Developing and Improving Priority 3: Public Engagement and Social Justice

Improving public engagement and social justice considerations within the Rhine-Erft RWL is complex, due to the wide variety of districts and stakeholders who all have their own jurisdictions and roles. However, one way that DIRECTED and the RWL hosts have sought to improve this priority is through the inclusion of artistic communication and engagement via public events.

The most recent action taken here was the addition of artist, who is part of the DIRECTED consortium's wider network, to generate a 'sonified' experience for citizens partaking in the *Erftverband's* and *hwsErft's* "Aktionstag Hochwasserschutz" on the 29th of August. In general, the RWL hosts agree that it is valuable to further build on and rely on such forms of public engagement that go beyond traditional scientific information sharing, and relay a more immediate experience of the waterboard's work. Activities like the artist engagement will help foster public trust and community building, which in turn may increase the interest and likelihood by the public to engage with the work of the waterboard.

Capacity development of RWL hosts

The RWL hosts in *Erftverband* demonstrated growth and skills development around interactive workshop design and facilitation. Their initial workshops followed a typical formal pattern as inter-organisational meetings, and based on feedback in the workshop debriefing session, this was due to the desire to keep meetings as similar as possible to the past, to keep stakeholders on board. There was a concern amongst hosts that creating unfamiliar levels of interaction, or creative methods, could make participants uncomfortable and risk reducing their participation. Working with the RWL hosts during the game-based and creative co-exploration training, a seed of interest was planted with the RWLs and their willingness to explore these approaches grew. On a personal level, a RWL host felt that the creative activity during the training helped them to break down the formal communication barrier and share

ideas in a tactile way indicating that *“I feel like this could work in our RWL to break down the formal roles of the stakeholders.”* The hosts decided to organise a workshop using creative and interactive methods (March 2024) to map out communication flows across stakeholders for an imminent or actual flooding which drew on experiences on the 2021 flooding, taking a more systems-thinking approach. As captured in the facilitators self-reflection, the RWL host highlighted positive and negative aspects, *“Stakeholders were interested and engaged during the workshop and gave positive feedback, but I felt like I didn’t collect all the relevant information from the group members.”* This potentially demonstrates some ambiguity around responsibilities and/or fear of attributing blame to others, and desire to avoid tension or conflict.

In January 2025 the hosts conducted a tabletop exercise which demonstrated their development in knowledge co-production capacities. This was reflected within the capacity needs assessment in which the host scored themselves, in response to ‘How would you rank your confidence to facilitate co-production workshops before DIRECTED?’ a ‘2. Low – I had some confidence, but felt unsure’. When asked ‘How would you rank your confidence to facilitate co-production workshops now?’, the host scored themselves a ‘4. High – I am confident in my ability to enable knowledge co-production’.

Figure 62: Impressions from the Rhine-Erft RWL hosts engaging in the co-exploration training (a) and the knowledge co-production workshop in March 2024 with their RWL stakeholders mapping communication flows and procedures (b).

3.4.4 Sustain Phase

The Sustain Phase constitutes the final phase of the RTF’s application process, and focuses on how to continue the deployment and evolution of the various tools developed throughout the previous phases. For the Rhine-Erft context, this means understanding how the tabletop exercises can be continued and scenarios updated, and finalizing the institutionalization of the WebEx meeting. The Sustain Phase further seeks to establish means of improving upon

the existing tools, for example through the implementation of Intellectual Property agreements of the Data Fabric and the RWL hosts, or increased outreach and dissemination activities with policymakers and stakeholders beyond the immediate context of the Rhine-Erft Region.

WP 3 and 4, in collaboration with WP 5 is currently working to establish a repository for the instructional material of how to set up such an exercise for the future. This will ensure that the exercise can be held even after the DIRECTED project's lifespan. Building on this idea, the upcoming tabletop exercise will also provide fruitful testing grounds for the further refinement and evaluation of the WebEx meeting. Further, the RWL hosts and affected districts are working on the signing of an agreement with regard to the protocol of the meeting.

Success & Expected Outcomes for the Rhine-Erft Sustain Phase

Based on the indicator application, and the findings from the Growth and Learn Phases, the RWL hosts and the DIRECTED consortium have defined the following key enablers for the successful continuation of the RTF beyond the project's lifetime. There are further a variety of means presented to achieve sustainable success throughout the final phase of the DIRECTED project, which rely on the MEL strategy.

One is the increased CCA integration by further building on modelling and stakeholder engagement workshops. This goal entails that the workshops and modelling tools provided by the DIRECTED project will continue to be in use, and be further developed. The upcoming half-day workshop co-organized by the RWL hosts and consortium partners at the end of September 2025 will serve as a means to further this goal. Specifically, topics surrounding Multi-Criteria Decision-making tools and co-design will be discussed, which will help the participants (local stakeholders) to learn how and where to implement their needs into the modelling and decision-making process.

Second, is the development of institutionalized forms of recurring engagement between stakeholders to improve communication and knowledge exchange before and during flood events. For this goal to succeed, further focus will be placed on the institutionalization of the WebEx meeting, refining and planning the approach.

4 Cross-Cutting Issues: Interoperability Gaps

Based on the findings throughout the preceding analysis, this section now explores what issues are prevalent in all RWLs, and whether certain enablers can be identified to both help individual actors achieve their set goals more easily, and improve the DRM and CCA approach in each RWL overall. In line with the RTF’s conceptual basis, these cross-cutting issues are described as “Interoperability Gaps” (e.g. Schröter et al., 2025). These gaps obstruct the seamless exchange of information between social processes and natural science-based data, which is a crucial function of any risk governance process (Vercruyssen et al., 2019; Tomas et al., 2015). Different types of interoperability gaps may exist, either across scales (e.g. between local and regional levels), between scales (e.g. between regions), with regard to data (e.g. availability), modelling (e.g. to estimate impacts) or governance processes (e.g. to deal with risks) (see Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2025). Note, these gaps may change depending on the type of risks the focus is on, e.g. for frequent, less frequent or catastrophic events (e.g. for different Risk-Layers).

Based on these insights throughout the application of the indicators, two major gaps have been identified. We are only able to present an overview of them here as each gap varies in size and scale and is ultimately context specific. However, the framework applied within Risk-Tandem was the same for all RWLs (see the discussion in Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2025). The first is an implementation gap, which refers to a rift between the knowledge, information and data available, and the translation of that knowledge into practicable action. Reasons for such a gap can often be traced back to the institutional and legal barriers, which were identified in the first dimension (the Governance and Institutional Context) of the RTF indicators.

Figure 63: Interoperability Gaps according to Model/Governance/Scale or Risk-Layers.

Secondly, the application of the indicators has highlighted the existence of institutional communication gaps, in addition to gaps in data/models and tools especially for interoperability. These gaps can be traced back to impeded information flows between governmental bodies, research institutions, NGOs, and community organizations. This, in turn, decreases the resilience of these institutional networks, hindering rapid mobilization during crises, and coordinated long-term adaptation strategies.

4.1 Implementation Gap (Knowledge-to-Action)

A key insight from the analysis is that quantitative data from models often cannot be translated into useful information for governance processes. This translation barrier creates a significant divide between technical information and actionable knowledge. In the context of the RTF, this entails a challenge for the RWLs' DRM and CCA processes. Namely, the challenge is how one can move from gaining new information on challenges and priorities (i.e., information gathered during the Foundation Phase) into actionable solutions (e.g., during the Growth Phase), and iterative improvements (in the Learn Phase). In short, there is a gap between the production of new information, knowledge and tools, through the application of the RTF, and the implementation of that information to improve existing governance structures. This implementation gap varies in size between the different RWLs, and was addressed to varying degrees. This gap was influenced by various factors including pre-existing relationships, staff turnover and regulation changes.

In RWL 1, the Capital Region of Denmark, the RWL stakeholders identified many challenges cutting across data/modelling, communication, and governance, making it difficult to set priorities. Although the overarching challenge was a governance issue (to systematically improve knowledge exchange and coordination between intermunicipal and emergency management agencies), this was initially addressed through a technical solution focusing on the co-design of the Data Fabric to demonstrate what is possible as a shared tool to support collaboration. The regulatory shifts during the project present an opportunity to delve deeper into the formal or informal governance mechanisms that are needed to sustain such collaboration, and institutionalise the Data Fabric in the Roskilde Fjord area beyond the project.

In RWL 2, Emilia-Romagna, the strong pre-existing relationships between the RWL hosts and technical support partner GECOSistema, created a strong foundation for co-designing a technical solution with RWL stakeholders. This solution needed to fit the local needs and have a clear pathway for being institutionally embedded into the civil protection system, to support more informed decision-making for pluvial and coastal flooding. As a result of the knowledge co-production process, the Data Fabric for flooding integrates higher resolution

data and is interoperable with radar and monitoring data from other service providers (Hera SpA). The RWL process enabled new collaborations (inc. fire fighters and forest park Police) to co-identify and develop solutions for public wildfire risk communication which are being physically installed in forested areas and social media assets for agencies to disseminate to the public. This RWL demonstrates clear successes in bridging the implementation gap.

In RWL 3, the Danube Region, the gap shows itself in two ways. **In the Vienna Region** the gap becomes most clear in the relationship between existing information from the insurance industry, the research institutes, and the public sector. While there is a general agreement among all stakeholders, that the insurance sector's data should be better integrated into the DRM and CCA decision-making process, legal barriers, as well as institutional norms inhibit this. Legal barriers, relating to potential liability claims, are difficult to clear, and would require political action. However, individual actors are willing and ambitious to overcome existing institutional norms, e.g. by the public sector deliberating together with stakeholders from the insurance industry and the research community, on how to best improve existing flood models in Vienna (see Workshop 2025).

In the Zala Region (RWL 3) the main implementation gap persists in the challenge to engage government and non-governmental actors in collaborative workshop settings, hindered by the cultural norms and perceived knowledge co-production capacity of the RWL host. In the beginning of the project, engagement processes with individual stakeholders were mainly done through bilateral commitments. This changed with an important shift in the political landscape, wherein the interests in sustainability and engaging with academia from a newly elected mayor led to broader and more comprehensive engagement opportunities in Year 3 (see workshops March 2025). However, as the strong engagement during the workshop in March has shown, there is generally a keen interest among those DRM/ CCA actors engaged to continue interactions and explore partnership opportunities. Building on this interest through further engagement activities is therefore key to eventually close this gap. This is being prioritised by the RWL, by identifying funding opportunities, organising a Climate Festival (April 2026), and bringing different actors on board to share data within the Data Fabric. However, the potential volatility of political shifts creates some uncertainty around sustaining the gains in collaboration generated through the RWL.

Finally, **in RWL 4, the Rhine-Erft Region**, the gap shows itself in the form of a not-yet defined role and institutional authority with regard to the *Erftverband's* responsibility in CCA and weather extremes. While there is interest from the *Erftverband* to integrate CCA into DRM strategies, this goal is not explicitly part of their institutional mandate. This is further complicated by the fact that local municipalities often need to focus on immediate DRM action, such as dam and infrastructure maintenance, and have less capacity to focus on mid- to long-term CCA strategies. The *Erftverband* may be capable of providing some such capacities, but this would require a shift in institutional norms, and an openness to explore and experiment within the existing governance structures. Initiatives and movements towards such an openness are emerging, with the *Erftverband* also building expertise surrounding

droughts, sponge cities, and the modelling of dam break scenarios to update existing models and improve climate resilience.

Reflecting on all these challenges, there are two central mechanisms from the RTF's toolbox that help close these gaps. First, upon identification of the hurdles it seems crucial to further develop and build upon co-creative and co-learning processes. What the governance analysis shows is that the implementation gap looms largest when there is a lack of mechanisms to facilitate knowledge exchange, and help clarify the various roles, responsibilities, and interests of the stakeholders involved (and beyond). In each of the RWLs this entails further building on the workshops and exercises practiced so far, specifically with RTF as a backdrop.

4.2 Communication Gap

Aside from the challenge of implementing knowledge and producing actionable insights from data, the effective and swift exchange of knowledge is key for effective DRM and CCA. Specifically, for the integration of DRM and CCA, knowledge sharing is not merely a technical challenge, but a crucial socio-political process shaped by institutional mandates, professional cultures, and resource constraints. The application of the RTF, including the assessment of related indicators, has allowed us to identify such communication gaps in each of the RWLs.

In the Capital Region of Denmark, the initial focus was on the development of the Data Fabric. However, the importance of intermunicipal and interagency communication was raised in relation to developing (and implementing) plans for disaster response and CCA. It was acknowledged that many large-scale events impacted more than one municipality, so communication around both planning and response was critical. In particular, as difficulties with communication then translated into challenges around coordinated action. However, the current system lacks a formal mechanism to enable communication, so it is up to individuals to build relationships and communicate in an ad-hoc manner.

Regarding the communication gap, interoperability is not merely about data availability, but about making information contextually relevant for governance processes. **In Emilia-Romagna**, the civil protection officers have access to a tool that provides information targeted to their needs operationally and for planning. The information generated from the tool (e.g. high resolution pluvial flood maps) can support their communication with the municipal mayors to decide which actions to take e.g. water storage tank operation, volunteer distribution or sandbag application. However, during the RWL activities, hosts identified the difficulty to engage certain non-governmental stakeholders (e.g. hoteliers and camping area owners) in their RWL workshops and simulation activities which could have further improved the resulting outputs and opened up new avenues for citizen engagement.

In the Vienna, Danube RWL, despite the abundance of high-quality data from insurance companies, reinsurance companies, universities, research centres, and government agencies, information sharing remains fragmented due to the lack of dedicated mechanisms

for knowledge sharing. Importantly, this gap does not arise from a lack of willingness to share, but rather from the lack of a structured platform that facilitates the exchange of knowledge.

For the Zala case there is a communication challenge between the municipality and volunteer first responders such as Zala Special Rescue Team, who are tasked to prepare and respond to citizens amidst a hazardous event. There is an information gap in early warning and forecasting information for multiple hazards that would enable responders to operate faster and more effectively, as well as having access to (near) real-time information of the evolving situation on the ground. The potential for the Data Fabric to address this challenge is being explored

In the Rhine-Erft Region, the communication gap shows itself in the form of reduced capacity to engage directly in the CCA and DRM process. While the *Erftverband* has advanced local models, there are some struggles to integrate them into the Disaster Risk Management process. Despite their ability to support municipalities in adapting to climate change, their role in disseminating flood warning information has initially not been fully developed.

The preliminary identification of these cross-cutting issues, based on the interoperability gap analysis, sets the stage for further development of the RTF and its application in the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning phase of the project. A manuscript describing the interoperability gap implementation approach is currently in review within the *Progress in Disaster Science* journal.

5 Conclusion: An Updated Risk-Tandem Framework

The application process of the RTF was a crucial step in its development. Having had its inception as an integrative, co-design framework, the RTF has been updated to show its practical applicability, as well as its conceptual dynamism when being applied to the various RWL contexts. With the refined indicators, the updated RTF can be applied in a modular manner, meaning that it is highly malleable to a given local context, while remaining grounded in its movement towards integrating DRM and CCA through its procedural and iterative nature, as well as risk management and co-creative substance. Through the application, the consortium, the RWL hosts, as well the involved stakeholders, have had a number of key insights.

First, the consortium has been able to refine and mold the RTF to the specific needs and interests, both practical and conceptual, of the RWLs. This, in turn, necessitated the Framework be geared towards different ends, while maintaining its foundation as a risk governance approach embedding transdisciplinary knowledge co-production that integrates

DRM and CCA thinking. The close engagement activities and constant interaction between researchers, hosts, and stakeholders, provided the consortium with the necessary input to refine the initial set of indicators described in Deliverable 3.1 (as well as Parviainen et al., 2025). The application and refinement of the indicators has further empirically grounded the RTF's practical design, which is geared towards operationalizability and dynamism, both of which have been tried and tested throughout the Foundation, Growth, and Learn Phases of the project. In short, the application of the RTF to the specific contexts of each RWL, yielding gaps, learnings, and ways forward has resulted in a framework that is empirically grounded, co-created and adaptive.

Second, this process of application and shared learning has helped the RWL hosts to act as facilitators and co-developers of empirically grounded and conceptually sound forms in combining DRM and CCA strategies. As hosts, the RWL partners play a quintessential role in the process of connecting the practical skills, needs, and interests of the immediately impacted communities and stakeholders, with the scientific goal of making DRM decision-making more sustainable and inclusive by accounting for the impacts of climate change. The RTF gives them a conceptual frame of reference, answering questions such as “why should we do this?”, while also giving practical guidance when faced with questions such as “how can we achieve this?” Overall, the updated RTF serves as a tool that supports those decision-makers and practitioners, who seek to improve their DRM approach through the introduction of CCA strategies.

Third, the application of the RTF has supported local stakeholders with developing insights into the importance of integrating DRM and CCA thinking. Throughout the various engagement activities, workshops, exercises, and presentations that were founded in the RTF, the mutual learning between the stakeholders, consortium members, and RWL hosts, has driven the implementation of practical solutions and on-the-ground change for the stakeholders. The RTF served as a shared baseline and language for stakeholders to think and act beyond their respective disciplinary silos, which in turn sets the stage for the institutional development towards a more integrated way of decision-making with regard to DRM and CCA.

Beyond these insights, there were also some important lessons learned. Between the relationship of the consortium, the RWL hosts, and the stakeholders, it became apparent that the translation of scientific findings and academic concepts into operationalizable action points was not always straightforward. This issue also arose for the translation of practical issues for on-the-ground practitioners into research goals. While the RWL hosts played a crucial role as translators and interlocutors for the consortium and stakeholders, it remains an important aspect (and at times challenge) to keep in consideration when applying the RTF in the future.

Finally, the engagement with a broad range of stakeholders has also shown that the way in which the RWLs are set up will crucially form the co-creative approach inherent in the RTF. This was especially clear when it came to the ethical aspects of citizen participation and engagement. An important criticism that the project received from the ethics report was the lack of active citizen engagement and improvement of social justice aspects, such as

diversity and equity. However, due to the actors that are involved in the RWL processes, i.e. mainly administrative, private, and research institutions, there was little space for proactive inclusion due to the limited legal remit that each of the hosts held in this regard. This flaw can be overcome, however, by incorporating other stakeholders, such as NGOs and policy makers, in the design of the RTF application process.

6 Outlook: The Risk-Tandem Toolbox

Looking forward towards the end of the project, here we reflect on the potential tools that will be associated with the “Risk-Tandem Toolbox”, i.e. how the various modelling and governance tools can help guide users through the process of integrating DRM and CCA. As such, the RTF’s toolbox supports DRM and CCA practitioners to implement a collaborative process to address DRM and CCA challenges in an integrative manner, and identify risk governance solutions in their context.

The Risk-Tandem Toolbox is expected to bring together different resources and guidelines emerging across the DIRECTED project targeting DRM and CCA practitioners, connecting risk governance, knowledge co-production and risk data, models and tools. Specifically, emerging from WP 3 it will make the following accessible to support legacy and implementation beyond the DIRECTED project’s lifetime. The Risk-Tandem Toolbox consists of the following tools:

- **The Risk-Tandem indicators.** In short, the indicators offer a set of guiding questions that enable the user to identify key risk governance challenges in a given Disaster Risk Management context, while also supporting the integration of DRM and CCA. With their simple applicability, modularity, and iterative character, the Risk-Tandem indicators represent a key tool in the Risk-Tandem Toolbox.
- **A Policy brief on risk governance in the context of DRM and CCA** (Deliverable 3.3). This policy brief will build on the findings and learnings developed throughout the application of the Risk-Tandem indicators, and offer the user a possibility to further evolve and refine the DRM and CCA process.
- **Finally, the toolbox provides guidance on good practices** regarding interoperability of governance mechanisms and recommendations for institutionalising project outcomes and the interoperable platform into existing systems (Deliverable 3.4). This is especially useful for users who may not be applying the entire Framework, but still seek to find strategies with which DRM and CCA strategies can be better integrated.

The Risk-Tandem Toolbox further serves an additional purpose as a means to bridge and link to a range of other parts of the DIRECTED project, beyond Work Package 3. Specifically, the following outputs fall within this range:

- **The Knowledge co-production training** through the set of Tandem modules and updated Tandem guidance⁷⁶ being prepared as part of Deliverable 4.1.
- **The e-Learning modules**, which demonstrate RWL experiences of applying the RTF to address specific challenges like interoperability for operational decision-making, integrated DRM and CCA planning and risk communication (Deliverable 6.5) including storylines emerging from RWLs.
- **The Data Fabric demo, training guides and interoperability fact sheets, which are** available on GitHub and Jupyter notebooks for interested users to gain deeper knowledge on setting up such platforms locally for interoperable data/models and tools. This includes D5.7 User training per role and D2.3 Interoperability fact sheets.
- **The Modelling Assumptions Framework and taxonomy**, which will deconstruct models used for the Data Fabric and communicate uncertainties and modelling assumptions. These will contribute to explaining the outputs of the Data Fabric to ensure that stakeholders understand and utilize data in meaningful ways. The taxonomy will contribute to comparing the use of relevant terms to their local usage, in efforts to examine and manage potential sources of misunderstanding and miscommunication occurring during “translation”. to add)
- **Risk-Layering and storyline module**, which clarifies the perception between and within multiple types of stakeholders, in the need and performance of CCA and DRM measures corresponding to ranges of potential disaster scales. It also clarifies the interoperability gaps between model characteristics and policy focus, and derives implications for improving governance schemes.
- **Evaluation and Reflection methods**, which will be based on the RWL outcomes in multirisk governance (Deliverable 1.4), as well as the governance interview guide (Annex 3)

The objective is to make the Risk-Tandem Toolbox available via a dedicated micro site that will be designed and developed by RIFS, and agreements put in place such that it is hosted infinitely by RIFS. Figure 64 provides a first initial mockup of such a toolbox.

⁷⁶ <https://weadapt.org/tandem-demo/> [10.09.2025]

Risk Tandem Toolbox
 Guiding practitioners towards integrated and interoperable
 DRR and CCA decision-making

Figure 64: Initial Visualisation of Risk-Tandem Toolbox.

The RTF was developed through experience of the RWL hosts in DIRECTED who had specific roles in waterboards, first responders, civil protection and regional agencies. However, the framework and its tools are flexible enough for wider applications by many different practitioners or researchers working on different aspects of DRM and CCA with their specific contextual challenges and priorities. For example, NGOs who want to advance citizen engagement and climate justice, or policy makers who are looking to develop a set of policies for the integration of CCA and DRM. How the RTF and the toolbox can be used to further these alternative goals, and how it can be further developed, will be the central focal point for the final year of the project.

References

- Agenzia per la sicurezza territoriale e la protezione civile. (n.d.). Regione Emilia-Romagna. Centro operativo regionale (COR).
<https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/agenzia/centro-operativo-regionale>. La pianificazione in protezione civile.
<https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/pianificazione-ptc>. Le principali convenzioni per attività di previsione e prevenzione.
<https://protezionecivile.regione.emilia-romagna.it/gestione-emergenze/convenzioni-e-protocolli-d2019intesa/convenzioni-per-attivita-di-previsione-e-prevenzione>
- Alexander, M., Priest, S., & Mees, H. (2016). A framework for evaluating flood risk governance. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 64, 38–47.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.06.004>
- Aznar-Siguan, G., & Bresch, D. N. (2019). CLIMADA v1: A global weather and climate risk assessment platform. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12, 3085–3097.
<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-3085-2019>
- Becker, G., Huitema, D., & Aerts, J. (2015). Prescriptions for adaptive comanagement: The case of flood management in the German Rhine basin. *Ecology and Society*, 20(3).
<https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07562-200301>
- Bharwani, S., Gerger Swartling, Å., André, K., Santos Santos, T. F., Salamanca, A., Biskupska, N., Takama, T., Järnberg, L., & Liu, A. (2024). Co-designing in Tandem: Case study journeys to inspire and guide climate services. *Climate Services*, 35, 100503.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2024.100503>
- Birkmann, J., & von Teichman, K. (2010). Integrating Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation: Key challenges—scales, knowledge, and norms. *Sustainability Science*, 5(2), 171–184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-010-0108-y>
- Birkmann, J., Schüttrumpf, H., Handmer, J., Thieken, A., Kuhlicke, C., Truedinger, A., Sauter, H., Klopries, E.-M., Greiving, S., Jamshed, A., Merz, B., Solecki, W., & Kirschbauer, L. (2023). Strengthening resilience in reconstruction after extreme events – Insights from flood affected communities in Germany. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 96, 103965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2023.103965>
- Blöschl, G. (2024). September 2024 flooding in Central Europe: The Austrian experience. *GeoLog – EGU Blogs*.
<https://blogs.egu.eu/geolog/2024/09/26/september-2024-flooding-in-central-europe-the-austrian-experience/>
- Bovens, M. (2010). Two Concepts of Accountability: Accountability as a Virtue and as a Mechanism. *West European Politics* 33(5) 946.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2010.486119>
- Bundesgesetz über die Sicherstellung der staatlichen Resilienz und Koordination in Krisen (Bundes-Krisensicherheitsgesetz – B-KSG). (2023). BGBl. I Nr. 89/2023. (Gesetzesnummer 20012321)
- Bundesgesetz zur Einhaltung von Höchstmengen von Treibhausgasemissionen und zur Erarbeitung von wirksamen Maßnahmen zum Klimaschutz (Klimaschutzgesetz – KSG) (2011). BGBl. I Nr. 106/2011 (in der Fassung vom 20. September 2023).
- Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Energie, Mobilität, Innovation und Technologie. (2024). Die Österreichische Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel: Executive summary. [The Austrian Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation: Executive summary]

- Wien, AUT: BMLUK.
<https://www.bmluk.gv.at/service/publikationen/klima-und-umwelt/die-oesterreichische-strategie-zur-anpassung-an-den-klimawandel-executive-summary.html>
- Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Energie, Mobilität, Innovation und Technologie. (n.d.). HORA 3D – The new form of risk communication. AUT: BMLUK.
<https://www.bmluk.gv.at/en/topics/water/protection-against-floods/hora-3d-the-new-form-of-risk-communication.html>
- Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI). (2025). Hungary – Climate Performance Ranking 2025. <https://ccpi.org/country/hun/>
- Colocci, A., Pietta, A., & Bagliani, M. (2024). Exploring the formal development of regional policies and their potential to drive local change: Insights on Climate Change Adaptation in Italy. *The Geographical Journal*. 191. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12614>
- Cubie, D., & Natoli, T. (2022). Coherence, Alignment and Integration: Understanding the Legal Relationship Between Sustainable Development, Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Reduction. In S. Flood, Y. Jerez Columbié, M. Le Tissier, & B. O’Dwyer (Eds.), *Creating Resilient Futures: Integrating Disaster Risk Reduction, Sustainable Development Goals and Climate Change Adaptation Agendas* (pp. 45–64). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80791-7_3
- Cumiskey, L., Parviainen, J., Bharwani, S., Ng, N., Bagli, S., Drews, M., Genillard, C., Hedderich, D., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Hofbauer, B., Huszti, L., Kropf, C. M., Löhrlin, J., Macià Pou, A., Mazzoli, P., Pedersen, J., Rosa, A., Schweizer, P.-J., Steinhausen, M., Struck, J., & Håkansson, V. W. (2025). Capacity development for locally-led knowledge co-production processes in Real World Labs for managing climate and disaster risk. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 125, 105398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2025.105398>
- Daniels, E., Bharwani, S., Gerger Swartling, Å., Vulturius, G., & Brandon, K. (2020). Refocusing the climate services lens: Introducing a framework for co-designing “transdisciplinary knowledge integration processes” to build climate resilience. *Climate Services*, 19, 100181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2020.100181>
- Danish Emergency Management Agency. (2021). Crisis management in Denmark. Danish Emergency Management Agency. <https://www.brs.dk/globalassets/brs---beredskabsstyrelsen/dokumenter/krisestyring-og-beredskabsplanlagning/2021-crisis-management-in-denmark-.pdf>
- Danish Emergency Management Agency. (n.d.). [Official website]. <https://www.brs.dk/en/>
- Danish Meteorological Institute. (2025). Vejledning i anvendelse af udledningsscenarioer til klimatilpasning [Guidance on the use of emission scenarios for climate adaptation]. https://www.dmi.dk/fileadmin/klima/klima-atlas/rapporter/Vejledningsrapporter/Vejledning_i_anvendelse_af_udledningsscenarioer_til_klimatilpasning.pdf
- Danish Meteorological Institute. (n.d.). DMI [Official website]. <https://www.dmi.dk/>. Data i Klima-atlas: Temperatur [Data in Climate Atlas: temperature]. <https://www.dmi.dk/klima-atlas/data-i-klima-atlas?paramtype=temp&maptype=kom>
- Danish Ministry of Health. (2024). Agreement on Health Reform 2024. Ministry of Health. https://www.ism.dk/Media/638682281997250085/01-Aftale-om-sundhedsreform-2024_TILG.pdf
- Danmarks Miljøportal (in collaboration with WSP Danmark). (n.d.). Vandportalen [Interactive web tool]. <https://vandportalen.dk/>
- Danmarks Miljøportal & Miljøstyrelsen. (n.d.). KAMP – klimaforhold og arealanvendelse for plan- og miljømedarbejdere [Web tool]. <https://kamp.klimatilpasning.dk/>

- DKKV (Hrsg., 2024). Governance und Kommunikation im Krisenfall des Hochwasserereignisses im Juli 2021.[Governance and Communication during the Flood Event in July 2021]. DKKV-Schriftenreihe Nr. 63. January 2024. Bonn, GER.
- Eisemann, L. (2021). Climate impact and risk assessment 2021 for Germany (Summary). Umweltbundesamt. Retrieved July 28, 2025, from <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/KWRA-English-Summary>
- Regione Emilia-Romagna. (2024, June 24). Delibera n. 1212 del 24 giugno 2024: Approvazione schema di convenzione tra l’Agenzia regionale per la sicurezza territoriale e la protezione civile e l’Agenzia regionale per la prevenzione, l’ambiente e l’energia dell’Emilia-Romagna, Struttura Idro-Meteo-Clima per la collaborazione alle attività tecniche ai fini del potenziamento del sistema di protezione civile e alla gestione del sistema di allertamento regionale. GPG/2024/1351. https://serviziisr.regione.emilia-romagna.it/deliberegiunta/servlet/AdapterHTTP?action_name=ACTIONRICERCADELIBERE&operation=leggi&cod_protocollo=GPG/2024/1351&ENTE=1
- Erbach, G., & Meinardi, C. (2025). Hungary’s climate action strategy. European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS). [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/769532/EPRS_BRI\(2025\)769532_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/769532/EPRS_BRI(2025)769532_EN.pdf)
- Erftverband. (n.d.). Erftverband [Official website]. <https://www.erftverband.de/>
- EU Floods Directive (2007) Directive 2007/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2007 on the assessment and management of flood risks. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/60/oj>
- EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change. (2025, April). DIY manual on engaging stakeholders and citizens in climate adaptation: Tools, good practices and experiences [PDF]. Climate-ADAPT, European Environment Agency. <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual>
- European Commission (EC). (2022, June 24). Hungary – National disaster management system. Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations. https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/civil-protection/national-disaster-management-system/hungary_en
- European Commission (2009). Critical Information Infrastructure Protection. "Protecting Europe from large scale cyber-attacks and disruptions: enhancing preparedness, security and resilience".
- European Commission (2021). Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change.
- European Investment Bank (EIB). (2021, November 12). 67% of Hungarians support additional measures to prompt behavioural changes to address the climate emergency. EIB survey finds [Press release]. <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2021-404-a-magyarok-67-a-tamogatna-tovabbi-intezkedeseket-amelyek-magatartasbeli-valtozasokra-sarkallnanak-a-klimaveszhelyzet-kezelese-erdeken>
- European Investment Bank (EIB). (2024, November 11). Nearly two-thirds of Hungarians respondents recognise that they will have to adapt their lifestyle due to climate change. EIB survey finds [Press release]. <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2024-437-nearly-two-thirds-of-hungarians-respondents-recognise-that-they-will-have-to-adapt-their-lifestyle-due-to-climate-change-eib-survey-finds>
- Federal Climate Adaptation Act (Bundes-Klimaanpassungsgesetz – KAnG) (2023). BGBl. 2023 I Nr. 393.

- Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ). (n.d.). Preventing disasters – enabling sustainable development. Disaster Risk Management. GER. <https://www.bmz.de/en/issues/disaster-risk-management>
- Federal Office for Civil Protection (2023): Zivilschutz versus Bevölkerungsschutz.[SW12]
- Fekete, A., Hufschmidt, G., & Kruse, S. (2014). Benefits and Challenges of Resilience and Vulnerability for Disaster Risk Management. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 5(1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-014-0008-3>
- Fekete, A. (2020). Critical infrastructure cascading effects: Disaster resilience assessment for floods affecting the city of Cologne and Rhein-Erft-Kreis. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 13, e312600. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12600>
- Fekete, A., & Sandholz, S. (2021). Here comes the flood, but not failure? Lessons to learn after the heavy rain and pluvial floods in Germany 2021. *Water*, 13, 3016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13213016>
- Friedrich, T., Stieß, I., Sunderer, G., Böhmer, C., Murawski, W., Knirsch, F., Otto, A., Wutzler, B., & Thieken, A. (2024, September). Climate change (Report No. 34/2024, 87 pp.). Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/kommunalbefragung-klimaanpassung-2023>
- German Strategy for Strengthening Resilience to Disasters (2022). Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance.
- Gesetz über den Brandschutz, die Hilfeleistung und den Katastrophenschutz (BHKG) (2015). SGV. NRW. https://recht.nrw.de/lmi/owa/br_text_anzeigen?v_id=61120160624160758031
- Gram-Hanssen, I., Aall, C., Drews, M., Juhola, S., Jurgilevich, A., Klein, R. J. T., Mikaelsson, M. A., & Mik-Meyer, V. L. (2023). Comparison and analysis of national Climate Change Adaptation policies in the Nordic region (TemaNord 2023:525). *Nordic Council of Ministers*. <https://doi.org/10.6027/temanord2023-525>
- Greiving, S., Kruse, P., Othmer, F., Fleischhauer, M., & Fuchs, M. (2023). Implementation of risk-based approaches in urban land use planning—The example of the city of Erftstadt, Germany. *Sustainability*, 15, 15340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115340>
- Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland in der im Bundesgesetzblatt Teil III, Gliederungsnummer 100-1, veröffentlichten bereinigten Fassung, das zuletzt durch Artikel 1 des Gesetzes vom 22. März 2025 (BGBl. 2025 I Nr. 94) geändert worden ist. <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/gg/BJNR000010949.html>
- Hiwasaki, L., Luna, E., Syamsidik, & Shaw, R. (2014). Process for integrating local and indigenous knowledge with science for hydro-meteorological Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation in coastal and small island communities. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 10 (Part A), 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2014.07.007>
- Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2025). Enhancing Interoperability for Managing Climate Risks: A Gap Approach using Systemic Risk Thinking. [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- Hochrainer-Stigler, S., & Reiter, K. (2021). Risk-layering for indirect effects. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 12(5), 770-778. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-021-00366-2>
- Hochrainer-Stigler, S. (2020). *Extreme and Systemic Risk Analysis: A Loss Distribution Approach*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-2689-3>
- Hochwasserschutzkooperation Erft. (n.d.). Zentrale Hochwasserschutzmaßnahmen im Erft-Einzugsgebiet. GER. [Website]. <https://hws-kooperation.erftverband.de/zentrale-hochwasserschutzmassnahmen-im-erft-einzugsgebiet/>

- Hofbauer, B., Einhäupl, P., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Löhrlin, J., Bittner, D., & Schweizer, P.-J. (2025). Just systems or justice in systems? Exploring the ethical implications of systemic resilience in local climate adaptation. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-025-00653-2>
- Hungarian Central Statistical Office. (2024). Main data of municipalities, 1 January 2024. https://www.ksh.hu/stadat_files/fo/en/fo0010.html
- Interkommunale Hochwasserschutzkooperation Erft (hwsErft). (n.d.). Interkommunales.NRW.GER. <https://interkommunales.nrw/projekt/interkommunale-hochwasserschutzkooperation-erft-hwserft/>
- IRGC. (2017). Introduction to the IRGC Risk Governance Framework. EPFL. <https://doi.org/10.5075/EPFL-IRGC-233739>
- Irvine, T., Mazzoli, P., Pancioli, V., Löhrlin, J., Bharwani, S., Schweizer, P., Parviainen, J., Ng, N., Cumiskey, L., Conradt, T., Bagli, S., Renzi, F., Luzzi, V., Renzi, M., Nanni, S., Struck, J., Hofbauer, B., & Steinhausen, M. (2025). D1.3 Case Study: A Comparative Case Study of Two Extreme Floods: Rhine Erft 2021 and Emilia Romagna May 2023. Directed Project.
- ISDR. (2009). Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction. United Nations, Geneva, Switzerland.
- ISPRA (2023) Report on Municipal Waste 2023: urban waste data and environmental management (Rapporto 394 bis/2023). Roma: Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale. Available at: https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/files2024/pubblicazioni/rapporti/rapportorifiutiurbani_ed-2023_n-394bis_ver-sionedati-di-sintesi-en.pdf
- King, J. P. (2022). Sixteen ways to adapt: A comparison of state-level Climate Change Adaptation strategies in the federal states of Germany. *Regional Environmental Change*, 22(2), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01870-3>
- Klímaparát Települések Szövetsége. (n.d.). [Association of Climate-Friendly Municipalities]. [Official website]. <https://www.klimabaratu.hu/>
- Klimaanpassungsgesetz Nordrhein-Westfalen (KlAnG) (2021). SGV. NRW. https://recht.nrw.de/lmi/owa/br_bes_text?anw_nr=2&bes_id=46233&aufgehoben=N
- KRITIS-Dialog. Kreis Euskirchen. (n.d.). Das Projekt – KRITIS-Dialog. GER. [Official Website] <https://kritis-dialog.de/das-projekt/>
- Kystdirektoratet (Danish Coastal Authority). (n.d.). Oversvømmelsesloven [Flooding Act]. <https://oversvømmelse.kyst.dk/>
- Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz Nordrhein-Westfalen (LANUV NRW) (n.d.). Climate adaptation advisory service. GER. [Website]. <https://www.klimaatlas.nrw.de/beratung-klimaanpassung/beratung>
- Lauta, K. C., Albris, K., Zuccaro, G., Grandjean, G., (Eds.) (2018). ESPREsSO Enhancing Risk Management Capabilities Guidelines. Available at: www.espressoproject.eu.
- Law on Climate Protection. (2020). Hungary – National climate legislation. *Climate Change Laws of the World*. https://climate-laws.org/document/law-on-climate-protection_3a0f
- Lendvai, B. (2025, March 27). Előrejelző rendszerek segíthetnek, hogy megelőzzük a katasztrófákat [Forecasting systems may help prevent disasters]. *Keszthelyi Televízió*. <https://tvkeszthely.hu/news/12318-elorejelzo-rendszerek-segithetnek-hogy-megelozzuk-a-katasztrofakat>
- Lind, M. H., & Hansen, K. E. E. (2024, April). Adaptation approaches in Danish municipalities' climate action plans [Report]. CONCITO; prepared in collaboration with

- Anja Wejs (Niras) & Mikkel Suell Henriques (Realdania).
https://concito.dk/files/media/document/Adaptation_approaches_in_Danish_municipalities_climate_action_plans_2024.02.05_red.pdf
- Ludwig, P., Ehmele, F., Franca, M. J., Mohr, S., Caldas-Alvarez, A., Daniell, J. E., Ehret, U., Feldmann, H., Hundhausen, M., Knippertz, P., Kpfer, K., Kunz, M., Mhr, B., Pinto, J. G., Quinting, J., Schfer, A. M., Seidel, F., & Wisotzky, C. (2023). A multi-disciplinary analysis of the exceptional flood event of July 2021 in central Europe – Part 2: Historical context and relation to climate change. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 23, 1287–1311. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-23-1287-2023>
- Matauschek, C., Irvine, T., Yeates, W., Whitaker, D., Steinhausen, M., Wortmann, M., Schrter, K., Dworak, T., Hattermann, F., & Romanovska, L. (2020). Policy brief: The future Danube model. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23519.69281>
- Mercer, J., Kelman, I., & Dekens, J. (2009). Framework for Integrating Indigenous and Scientific Knowledge for Disaster Risk Reduction. *Disasters*. 34. 214-39.
- Ministerium fr Umwelt, Naturschutz und Verkehr Nordrhein-Westfalen. (2024). Klimaangepassung Nordrhein-Westfalen 2024–2029 (Art.-Nr. K031).
<https://broschuereenservice.nrw.de/munv/shop/klimaangepassung-nordrhein-westfalen-2024-2029%7C2246>
- Mohr, S., Ehret, U., Kunz, M., Ludwig, P., Caldas-Alvarez, A., Daniell, J. E., Ehmele, F., Feldmann, H., Franca, M. J., Gattke, C., Hundhausen, M., Knippertz, P., Kpfer, K., Mhr, B., Pinto, J. G., Quinting, J., Schfer, A. M., Scheibel, M., Seidel, F., & Wisotzky, C. (2023). A multi-disciplinary analysis of the exceptional flood event of July 2021 in central Europe – Part 1: Event description and analysis. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 23(2), 525–551. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-23-525-2023>
- Municipality of Reggio Emilia. (2020). Proposed local strategy for Climate Change Adaptation. Emilia-Romagna Region. Public consultation from July 15 to August 24, 2020. ITA.
<https://consultazione.gov.it/it/le-consultazioni/le-consultazioni-regionali-e-locali/emilia-romagna/strategia-locale-adattamento-ai-cambiamenti-climatici-reggio-emilia/>
- Ng, N., Parviainen, J., Bharwani, S., Cumiskey, L., Steinhausen, M., Mazzoli, M., Bagli, S., Irvine, T., Schweizer, P., Pancioli, V., Hedderich, D., Lhrlein, J., Chebrol., N, Conradt, T., Drews, M., Pedersen, J., Renzi, F., Luzzi, V., Renzi, M., Nanni, S., Genillard, C., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Huszti, L., Apel, H., Ghomash, S., Grler, B., Kraatz, J., Kropf, C., Stuck, J., Hofbauer., B. (2025). Capacity Development Modules: ToT workshops in designing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes.
- Nielsen, A. B., Bonati, S., & Andersen, N. B. (2023). Discover the dynamics: An intersectional analysis of overt and hidden vulnerabilities to flood risk in urban Denmark. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 237, 104799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2023.104799>
- NIRAS & LYTT Architecture. (2024, May)Frederikssund mder vandet – livet mellem by og fjord [Frederikssund meets the water – life between town and fjord]. Realdania. DK.
<https://realdania.dk/publikationer/faglige-publikationer/frederikssund-moeder-vandet---livet-mellem-by-og-fjord>
- Norstrm, A. V., Cvitanovic, C., Lf, M. F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Bednarek, A. T., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., de Bremond, A., Campbell, B. M., Canadell, J. G., Carpenter, S. R., Folke, C., Fulton, E. A., Gaffney, O., Gelcich, S., Jouffray, J.-B., Leach, M., ... sterblom, H. (2020). Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(3), 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2019). Regions and Cities at a Glance 2018 – DENMARK.
https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/01/oecd-regions-and-cities-at-a-glance-2018-country-notes_a745da06/denmark_2f2cbdec/3260f4cd-en.pdf

- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). Promoting nature-based solutions in municipalities in Hungary (OECD Environment Policy Paper No. 39).
https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2023/12/promoting-nature-based-solutions-in-municipalities-in-hungary_e9aa368f/d81fb09f-en.pdf
- Ostrom, E. (2011). Background on the Institutional Analysis and Development Framework. *Policy Studies Journal*, 39(1), 7–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2010.00394.x>
- Pancioli, V., Hedderich, D., Löhrlein, J., Mazzoli, P., Steinhausen, M., Parviainen, J., Cumiskey, L., Mau, J., Conradt, T., Drews, M., Nielsen, E. R., Laursen, A., Bagli, S., Renzi, F., Schweizer, P.-J., Nanni, S., Genillard, C., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Struck, J., Huszti, L., Apel, H., Grähler, B., Kropf, C., Håkansson, V. W., Irvine, T., & Bharwani, S. (2024). D1.1 – Real World Labs description and setup. Directed Project.[SW7]
- Parviainen, J., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Cumiskey, L., Bharwani, S., Schweizer, P. J., Hofbauer, B., & Cubie, D. (2025). The Risk-Tandem Framework: An iterative framework for combining risk governance and knowledge co-production toward integrated Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 116, 105070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.105070>
- Parviainen, J., Bharwani, B., Ng, N., Pontius, M., Kraatz, J., Bredel, H., Gräler, B., Jürrens, E., Bagli, S., Renzi, F., Luzzi, V., Renzi, M., Mazzoli, P., Pancioli, V., Hedderich, D., Löhrlein, J., Cumiskey, L., Conradt, T., Drews, M., Pedersen, J., Nanni, S., Genillard, C., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Huszti, L., Apel, H., Ghomash, S., Kropf, C., Struck, J., Hofbauer, B., Steinhausen, M., Irvine, T. (2025a). D4.2 Assumptions Framework: A framework for distilling assumptions in different modelling approaches with recommendations for replication.
- Pathways2Resilience. (2025). Second open call for European regions and communities. [Official website]. <https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/second-open-call>
- Patkós, C., Radics, Z., Tóth, J. B., Kovács, E., Csorba, P., Fazekas, I., Szabó, G., & Tóth, T. (2019). Climate and Energy Governance Perspectives from a Municipal Point of View in Hungary. *Climate*, 7(8), 97. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli7080097>
- Pietrapertosa, F., Salvia, M., De Gregorio Hurtado, S., Geneletti, D., D'Alonzo, V., & Reckien, D. (2021). Multi-level climate change planning: An analysis of the Italian case. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 289, 112469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112469>
- Polski, M. M., & Ostrom, E. (2017). An Institutional Framework for Policy Analysis and Design. In D. H. Cole & M. D. McGinnis (Eds.), *Elinor Ostrom and the Bloomington School of Political Economy (Vols 3, A Framework for Policy Analysis)*. Lexington Books.
<https://ostromworkshop.indiana.edu/doc/teaching/iad-for-policy-applications.pdf>
- Pontius, M., Kraatz, Julia., Bredel, H., Gräler, B., Jürrens, E., Bagli, S., Renzi, F., Luzzi, V., Renzi, M., Mazzoli, P., Bharwani, S., Pancioli, V., Hedderich, D., Löhrlein, J., Parviainen, J., Cumiskey, L., Conradt, T., Drews, M., Pedersen, J., Nanni, S., Genillard, C., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Huszti, L., Apel, H., Ghomash, S., Kropf, C., Struck, J., Hofbauer, B., Steinhausen, M., & Irvine, T. (2025). D5.2 Low-Level Design: The architecture of the DIRECTED Data Fabric. Directed Project.
- Prall, M. C., Brandt, U. S., Halvorsen, N. S., Hansen, M. U., Dahlberg, N., & Andersen, K. J. (2024). A comprehensive approach for assessing social flood vulnerability and social flood risk: The case of Denmark. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 111, 104686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2024.104686>
- RaiNews. (2025, May 24). Prove di emergenza estiva, l'esercitazione a Lido degli Scacchi. TGR Emilia-Romagna. ITA.
<https://www.rainews.it/tgr/emiliaromagna/video/2025/05/prove-di-emergenza-estiva-lesercitazione-a-lido-degli-scacchi-98325046-0e3c-4940-aff9-da28aae67b92.html>

- Rivera, C., Tehler, H., & Wamsler, C. (2015). Fragmentation in Disaster Risk Management systems: A barrier for integrated planning. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 14, 445–456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2015.09.009>
- SaferPlaces (2020). Rimini and climate change: the added value of the Sea Park “Parco del Mare.” <https://saferplaces.co/rimini-and-climate-change-the-added-value-of-the-sea-park-parco-del-mare/>
- Schink, A. (2024). Das Bundes-Klimaanpassungsgesetz (KAnG). [The Federal Climate Adaptation Act (KAnG)]. *Natur und Recht* 46 (10): 670–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10357-024-4451-7>
- Schröter, K., P.-J. Schweizer, B. Gräler, et al. 2025. “Invited Perspectives: Fostering Interoperability of Data, Models, Communication, and Governance for Disaster Resilience through Transdisciplinary Knowledge Co-Production.” *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 25 (9): 3055–73. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-3055-2025>.
- Schweizer, P.-J., & Renn, O. (2019). Governance of systemic risks for disaster prevention and mitigation. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 28(6). <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPM-09-2019-0282>
- Serra, V., Ledda, A., Ruiu, M. G. G., Calia, G., Mereu, V., Bacciu, V., Marras, S., Spano, D., & De Montis, A. (2022). Adaptation to climate change across local policies: An investigation in six Italian cities. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 8318. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148318>
- Stadt Wien (n.d.). Ökologie der Donauinsel [Ecology of the Danube Island]. Wiener Gewässer. AUT. [Official Website]. <https://www.wien.gv.at/umwelt/gewaesser/donauinsel/oekologie/>
- Technisches Hilfswerk. (n.d.). Organisation. [Official Website]. https://www.thw.de/DE/THW/Organisation/organisation_node.html
- Thieken, A. H., Bubeck, P., Heidenreich, A., von Keyserlingk, J., Dillenardt, L., & Otto, A. (2023). Performance of the flood warning system in Germany in July 2021 – insights from affected residents. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 23(2), 973–990. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-23-973-2023>
- Thomas, F., & Knüppe, K. (2016). From Flood Protection to Flood Risk Management: Insights from the Rhine River in North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany. *Water Resources Management*, 30(8), 2785–2800. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-016-1323-9>
- Tomas, R., Harrison, M., Barredo, J.I., Thomas, F., Llorente Isidro, M., Pfeiffer, M. and Čerba, O., 2015. Towards a cross-domain interoperable framework for natural hazards and Disaster Risk Reduction information. *Natural Hazards*, 78(3), pp.1545-1563.
- Togebly, S. (n.d.). New research leads to the inclusion of vulnerable groups in flood risk assessments. Institut for Bæredygtighed og Planlægning, Aalborg Universitet. <https://www.plan.aau.dk/new-research-leads-to-the-inclusion-of-vulnerable-groups-in-flood-risk-assessments-n125342>
- United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR). (2022). Our World at Risk: Transforming Governance for a Resilient Future. Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction (GAR2022). <https://www.undrr.org/gar/gar2022-our-world-risk-gar>
- Vercruyssen, K., Dawson, D. A., & Wright, N. (2019). Interoperability: A conceptual framework to bridge the gap between multifunctional and multisystem urban flood management. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 12(S2), e12535
- Walmsley, S., Cumiskey, L., McCullagh, D., Larkin, P., Burns, C., Dixon, L., Dennehy, L., & Murphy, K. (2024, November 4). Extract from BluePrint sound installation “In at Midnight and Away by Morning: The Uninvited Guest” (Version v1) [Video/audio]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14036832>

Wiener Katastrophenhilfe- und Krisenmanagementgesetz (W-KKG). (2003, 22. Dezember).
LGBI. für Wien 2003/60. Land Wien, Rechtsvorschriften-Portal: PDF "B450-000"

Wiener Klimagesetz (Wr. KG) (2025). Wiener Landtag.(Vienna Climate Act 2025FRMP)

Annex 1: Documentation of Co-Production Activities (Milestone 13)

This Milestone documents the various knowledge co-production activities carried out related to the Risk-Tandem Framework in connection with the Real World Labs (RWLs). While this list aims to be as comprehensive as possible, there may be smaller, informal and ad-hoc meetings that have not been added. Specifically, the following outline specifically focuses on activities that relate to the development, application, and iteration of the Risk-Tandem Framework and its governance implications.

The Risk-Tandem Framework, and the DIRECTED project in general, rely heavily on continuous, reciprocal learning and development between the consortium, the RWL hosts, and the local stakeholders involved in the RWLs. As such, the following activities all represent these modes of shared learning in one way or another, for example through workshops, training, or tabletop exercises. These activities are broken down per RWL and organised into two separate tables. Firstly, RWL activities refers to any activity that engaged stakeholders and participants beyond DIRECTED and the RWL host. Secondly, RWL support activities focus on shared learning and exchange between the hosts and the DIRECTED consortium through various work package tasks.

Table 1: Activities RWL 1: The Capital Region of Denmark

Table 1.1: RWL Activity Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
1st Multi-Stakeholder RWL Workshop	17 Participants incl. Region Hovedstaden, DTU, municipalities, emergency management services, Region Zealand and Danish Emergency Mgmt. Agency	3rd, March 2023
Stakeholder interview	4 Participants incl. municipality and fire department from Roskilde who could not attend first workshop	5th, May 2023
Stakeholder group interviews with	8 Participants incl. municipalities of Egedal, Frederikssund, and Halsnæs	16th, April 2024
Stakeholder group interviews	4 Participants incl. Frederiksborg Fire and Rescue	30th, April 2024
Stakeholder group interviews	8 Participants incl. Municipality of Roskilde and Roskilde Fire Department	7th, May 2024
Stakeholder group interviews	4 Participants, Municipality of Lejre and Lejre Fire and Rescue	13th, May 2024
Stakeholder interview	3 Participants, Danish Emergency Mgmt. Agency	9th, July 2024
2nd RWL Stakeholder Workshop	18 Participants incl. Region Hovedstaden, DTU, municipalities, emergency management services, Region Sjælland, Danish Emergency Mgmt. Agency	20th, August 2024
Online meeting and Data Fabric Questionnaire	10 Participants incl. DTU, Region Hovedstaden, municipalities, emergency mgmt. services.	11th, November 2024
3rd RWL Workshop	15 Participants incl. DTU, Region Hovedstaden, municipalities, emergency mgmt. services, DMI, Region Sjælland, Danish Emergency Mgmt. Agency	10th, April 2025
Presentations from Danish RWL stakeholders during the General Assembly	4 Participants incl. Danish Meteorological Institute, Danish Emergency Management Agency	2nd, September 2025

Field visit to Roskilde Fjord during the General Assembly in Denmark	35 Participants including municipalities, emergency services and utility companies and DIRECTED consortium	3rd, September 2025
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Table 1.2: RWL Support Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
Internal RWL hosts meeting	WP 1, 5 Participants	6th, December, 2022 and 3rd, February, 2023
Briefing Note on Risk-Tandem/ Recorded Presentation/ Powerpoint	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	3rd, January 2023
Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 3/4, 6 Participants	17th and 28th, February 2023
1st workshop debrief interview	WP 3/4, 7 Participants	9th, March 2023
Jour-fix Risk-Tandem Presentation	WP 3, all, 25 Participants	16th, March 2023
First Capacity Development Module (Complex Risks)	15 Participants	15th, June 2023
Scoping consultation and needs analysis for Data Fabric	WP 5, 6 Participants	18th, August, 2023
Support consultation: 2nd workshop planning	WP 3/4, 7 Participants	25th, August 2023
Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st, September 2023
Scoping consultation on needs	WP 4, 6 Participants	13th, December 2023
Support consultation: 2nd workshop planning and briefing new staff	WP 3/4, 6 Participants	30th, January 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on Citizen Engagement	WP 4/3, 21 Participants	23th, March 2024
Group Interviews and Discussion Guidance	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	11th, April 2024
Debrief on stakeholder interviews and support consultation on needs	WP 3/4, 7 Participants	24th, April 2024
Interviews on RIM2D Model in Relation to Risk-Layering	WP 3/2, 4 Participants	6th, May 2024

Capacity Development: Monitoring, Evaluation, and Knowledge co-production	WP 4, 15 Participants	16th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar and Ideas Exchange- Lessons from the Civil Protection of Service	WP 4, 14 Participants	21st, May 2024
User needs exploration/ Debrief on Stakeholder Interview Results	WP 3/5/ 4, 6 Participants	30th, May 2024
Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change	WP 4, 10 Participants	11th, June 2024
RWL User needs process discussion (General Assembly)	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	15th, June 2024
Support consultation: 2nd Workshop Planning and Draft Agenda	WP 3/4, 7 Participants	27th, June 2024
Support consultation: 2nd workshop design and engagement	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	11th, July 2024
Capacity Development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	WP 4, 15 Participants	25th, July 2024
Support for workshop design	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	16th, August 2024
Scoping Consultation and Needs Analysis for Data Fabric	WP 4/5, 7 Participants	18th, August 2024
Workshop Debrief	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	12th, September 2024
Scoping: Tailoring of Risk-Tandem and Capacity Development Needs	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	11th, October 2024
Support consultation: Debrief on online dashboard meeting / End-of-year catch up and planning	WP 4, 6 Participants	9th, December 2024
RWL Task Force Meeting to Discuss prioritization and refinement of user stories, and data sources	WP 5, 6 Participants	10th, December 2024
Task force meeting to discuss survey results, datasets from DMI, and next steps	WP 5, 6 Participants	17th, January 2025
RWL Peer 2 Peer Learning exchange	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, January 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss finalization of user stories and mock-ups	WP 5, 6 Participants	31st, January 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss results of the survey, and workshop #1	WP 5, 6 Participants	13th, February 2025
Capacity development co-explore to co-design	WP 4, 15 Participants	21st, February 2025

Task Force Meeting to discuss integration of survey results into D5.2	WP 5, 6 Participants	25th, February 2025
Task Force Meeting regarding workshop progress of data integration and model outputs	WP 5, 6 Participants	13th, March 2025
Support: RWL Workshop planning	WP 4, 5 Participants	21st, March 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss workshop and plan next steps	WP 5/3/4, 6 Participants	27th, March 2025
Support: RWL Workshop planning	WP 4, 5 Participants	4th, April 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss de-brief from 3rd workshop	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	24th, April 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss status updates regarding M24, MCMD, and to plan next step	WP 5/3/2, 6 Participants	22nd, May 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss MCDM and M24	WP 5/3/2, 6 Participants	6th, June 2025
Capacity development co-designing interventions	WP 4, 15 Participants	2nd, July 2025
Task Force Meetings to discuss MCDM and General Assembly planning	WP 1/5/2, 6 Participants	3rd, July 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss General Assembly and RWL planning	WP 1/5, 6 Participants	13th, August 2025
Task Force Meeting to debrief on MCDM workshop	WP 5/2, 6 Participants	11th, September 2025
Task Force Meeting to plan 4th RWL workshop	WP 1/3/4, 7 Participants	25th, September 2025

Table 2: Activities RWL 2: The Emilia-Romagna Region

Table 2.1: RWL Activity Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
1st RWL Meeting	42 Participants (in-person or remotely) incl. ARPAE, ARSTPC, GECOSistema, municipalities, HERA SpA, regional soil defence sector, provincial volunteer coordination, Po Delta Parks and biodiversity mgmt. body, regional protected areas, forest and mountain areas development sector	21st, March 2023

2nd RWL Workshop	15 Participants incl. ARPAE, ARSTPC, GECOSistema, municipalities alities, HERA and provincial volunteer coordination	28th, September 2023
Webinar Regarding Data and Tools for Risk Management	18 Participants incl. ARPAE, ARSTPC, GECOSistema, TUBS	20th, November 2023
Flood Exercise/ Simulation in Rimini alongside DIRECTED General Assembly	60 Participants incl. ARPAE, ARSTPC, GECOSistema, ARPAE-SIMC, municipalities, HERA SpA, provincial volunteer coordination, Regional Land Reclamation Consortium and DIRECTED consortium	13th-15th, June 2024
3rd RWL Workshop	32 Participants incl. ARSTPC-ER. GECOSistema, ARPAE, municipalities, Coordination of Civil Protection Volunteer Associations of Ferrara and Rimini, the Regional Fire Brigade Command, the Carabinieri Biodiversity Unit of Punta Marina	20th, November 2024
Demo of Data Fabric	30 Participants incl. ARPAE, ARSTPC, regional civil protection officers, GECOSistema	14th, April 2025
Wildfire Simulation Exercise in Comacchio	80 Participants incl. volunteers, professionals, firefighters, Regional and Municipal Civil Protection officials, the Carabinieri Forest Fire Investigation Unit, and representatives from GECOSistema.	24th, May 2025

Table 2.2: RWL Support Focus.

Activity	Work package and number of participants	Timeline
Briefing Note on Risk-Tandem/ Recorded Presentation/ Powerpoint	WP 3/ 4, RWL hosts	3rd, January 2023
RWL hosts 1st Internal Meeting	WP 1, 8 Participants	20th, January 2023
RWL hosts preparation Meeting	WP 1, 16 Participants	16th, February 2023
Jour-fix Risk-Tandem Presentation	WP 3, all, 25 Participants	16th, March 2023
1st Workshop Debrief	WP 4/3, 10 Participants	30th, March 2023

RWL hosts 2nd internal meeting	WP 1, 10 Stakeholders	3rd, May 2023
RWL hosts 3rd Stakeholder Meeting	WP 1, 6 Stakeholders	23rd, May 2023
First Capacity Development Module (Complex Risks)	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, June 2023
Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st September 2023
Debrief of 2nd Workshop	WP 4/3, 10 Participants	16th, October 2023
Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 4, 5 Participants	23rd, January 2024
Simulation Planning for GA in Rimini	WP 3/4, 8 Participants	13th, March 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on Citizen Engagement	WP 4/3, 19 Participants	26th, March 2024
Group Interviews and Discussion Guidance	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	11th, April 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on RiskPACC	WP 4/3, 21 Participants	23rd, April 2024
Support consultation for Rimini Flood Exercise	WP 4, 10 Participants	6th, May 2024
Interviews on Safer Places Model in Relation to Risk-Layering	WP 3/2, 4 Participants	6th, May 2024
Rimini Planning Meeting with Italian RWL and Simulation	WP 3/4, 8 Participants	8th, May 2024
User Needs Discussion for RWL	WP 5/3/4, 8 Participants	9th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Monitoring, Evaluation, and Knowledge co-production	WP 4, 15 Participants	16th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar and Ideas Exchange- Lessons from the Civil Protection of Service	WP 4, 14 Participants	21st, May 2024
RWL User needs process discussion (General Assembly)	WP 3/5, 10 Participants	15th, June 2024
Support for Workshop	WP 3/4, 8 Participants	22nd, June 2024

Design and Engagement		
Capacity Development Training : MEL and Establishing a Theory of Change	WP 4/3, 10 Participants	4th, July 2024
Scoping on Wildfire Risk Management to Support Workshop	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	9th, July 2024
Capacity development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	WP 4, 15 Participants	25th, July 2024
Scoping: Tailoring of Risk-Tandem and Capacity Development Needs	WP 4/3, 10 Participants	7th, October 2024
End of year reflections and planning next steps RWL 2 (Debrief on 3rd RWL workshop)	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	11th, December 2024
RWL Peer 2 Peer Learning exchange	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, January 2025
Meeting to discuss Data Fabric	WP 1/5, 13 Participants	30th, January 2025
Capacity development co-explore to co-design	WP 4, 15 Participants	21st, February 2025
Scoping meeting on RWL next steps	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	25th, February 2025
RWL hosts meeting regarding the Implementation of Data Fabric	WP 1/5, 11 Participants	19th, February 2025
Check-in on RWL support/needs for workshop planning	WP 3/4, 5 Participants	11th April 2025
ECCA preparation meetings	WP 1/6/5/4, 8 Participants	16th, 23rd, 30th May 2025 and 6th, June 2025
Debriefing on Wildfire Exercise	WP 4/3, 10 Participants	11th, June 2025
ECCA Conference Training for Impact session	WP 6/1, 25 Participants	18th, June 2025
Capacity development co-designing interventions	WP 4, 15 Participants	2nd July 2025
General Assembly RWL breakout discussions	WP 1, 10 Participants	2nd, September 2025

Table 3: Activities RWL 3: The Danube Region

Table 3.1: Vienna

Table 3.1.1: RWL Engagement Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
Interview with Danube Stakeholders	Viadonau Water Management	9th, January 2024
Interview with Danube Stakeholders	Salzburg Region	18th, January 2024
Presented DIRECTED and Risk-Tandem; looking for ways to integrate DIRECTED models into regional disaster and climate models	12 Stakeholders Event: Sustainability in building resilience for extreme events	10th, September 2024
Meeting with Stakeholders to create presentations for user stories and mock-ups	2 Stakeholders	10th-13th, February 2025
Interactive Presentation from consortium and stakeholders focused on modelling tools from DIRECTED	12 Stakeholders	9th, July 2025
Risk-Tandem Workshop: On Sustainability in Building Resilience for Extreme Events	12 Stakeholders from the Insurance Sector	9th, July 2025
Risk-Tandem Workshop	20 Stakeholders	9th, July 2025

Table 3.1.2: RWL Support Focus.

Activity	Work package and number of participants	Timeline
Briefing Note on Risk-Tandem/ Recorded Presentation/ Powerpoint	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	3rd, January 2023
Jour-fix Risk-Tandem Presentation	WP 3, all, 25 Participants	16th, March 2023
1st RWL debrief	WP 3/4, 5 Participants	12th, June 2023
First Capacity Development Module (Complex Risks)	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, June 2023

Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st September 2023
Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 4, 5 Participants	14th, December 2023
Scoping Consultation and Needs Analysis for Data Fabric	WP 5, 8 Participants	17th, August 2024
Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st September 2023
Scoping Interview on Needs	WP 4, 6 Participants	14th, December 2023
Capacity Development: Webinar on Citizen Engagement	WP 4/3, 19 Participants	26th, March 2024
Workshop Debrief/RWL Update	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	9th, April 2024
Group Interviews and Discussion Guidance	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	11th, April 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on RiskPACC	WP 4/3, 21 Participants	23rd, April 2024
Discussing Workshop agenda and support needs	WP 4, 6 Participants	26th, April 2024
Interviews on DANUBE Model in Relation to Risk-Layering	WP 2/3, 4 Participants	2nd, May 2024
RWL Preparation Meeting / User stories	WP 5/4/3, 5 Participants	10th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Monitoring, Evaluation, and Knowledge co-production	WP 4, 15 Participants	16th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Webinars and Ideas Exchange- Lessons from the Civil Protection of Service	WP 4, 14 Participants	21st, May 2024
RWL Support Meeting	WP 4/3, 4 Participants	27th, May 2024
RWL User needs process discussion (General Assembly)	WP 3/5, 10 Participants	15th, June 2024
Capacity Development: MEL and Establishing a Theory of Change	WP 4, 6 Participants	28th, June 2024

Capacity development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	WP 4, 15 Participants	25th July 2024
Modelling/ Data Fabric rehearsal for RWL workshop	WP 5, all, 10 Participants	2nd September 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss goals, definitions, and discussion of user stories	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	11th, December 2024
End of Year Reflections and Planning Next Steps	WP 4/3, 6 Stakeholders	6th, December 2024
Task Force Meeting discussing future planning, milestones, and review previous information	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	8th, January 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss mock ups for D5.2 and D5.4	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	15th, January 2025
RWL Peer 2 Peer Learning exchange	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, January 2025
Task Force Meeting continued discussion on D5.2 and D5.4	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	29th, January 2025
Capacity development co-explore to co-design	WP 4, 15 Participants	21st, February 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss and review user stories, modelling, and data needs	WP 5/3, 4 Participants	24th, February 2025
Task Force Meeting to review mock up, and define parameters regarding flood datasets	WP 5, 3 Participants	12th, March 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss questionnaire from RWL's and discuss next steps	WP 5/4, 4 Participants	2nd, April 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss revision of questionnaire regarding flood scenarios	WP 5/3, 4 Participants	23rd, April 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss developments in the RWL Copenhagen simulation checklist, Data Fabric frontend	WP 5, 8 Participants	14th, May 2025
Task Force Meeting to	WP 5, 3 Participants	4th, June 2025

discuss the preparation of the upcoming workshop, the agenda, and Data Fabric testing		
Workshop Planning Meeting and discuss lasting goals once the DIRECTED project is over	WP 4/3/5, 10 Participants	12th, June 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss workshop planning	WP 5/3/4, 4 Participants	25th, June 2025
Task Force Meeting to recap and review workshop from July 9th	WP 5/3/4, 3 Participants	16th, July 2025
Governance Interview with Genillard & Co.	WP 3, 4 Participants	25th, July 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss model improvements	WP 5, 4 Participants	6th, August 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss the end of development phase of the Data Fabric	WP 5, 3 Participants	27th, August 2025

Table 3.2: Zala

Table 3.2.1: RWL Engagement Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
Presentation of the DIRECTED project and RWL	15 Participants at the Zala County Territorial Defense Committee	4th, December 2022
Discussion with city council's about needs/ support for DIRECTED	10 Participants Municipality/ Zalaegerszeg City Council	8th, January 2023
Discussion around vocational training curriculum and links to DIRECTED.	3 Participants at Zala County Vocational Training Center	13th, February 2023
Discussion with the mayor's secretariat on DIRECTED project	3 Participants at Lenti Municipality	20th, March 2023
Discussion regarding the integration of DIRECTED's Risk-Tandem Framework into existing risk management practices.	3 Participants at Zala Country Disaster Management Directorate	17th, April 2023

Discussion regarding DIRECTED's work improving communication in DRM.	3 Participants at Keszthely City Council	5th, September 2023
Introduce the DIRECTED project to teachers and students.	3 Participants at Zalaegerszeg Secondary School	26th, June 2023
Discussion regarding the DIRECTED project's potential to support the municipality's CCA efforts.	3 Participants at Zalaszentgrot Municipality	11th, July 2023
Presentation of the DIRECTED project	4 Participants at Regional Authority: West Transdanubia Water Directorate	16th, October 2023
Overview of DIRECTED and collaboration between first responders, researchers, and policymakers.	10 Participants at Assoc. of Volunteer Firefighters	22nd, November 2023
Introduction of DIRECTED's Risk-Tandem framework and its potential to enhance disaster resilience.	15 Participants Zala County Territorial Protection Committee	4th, December 2023
Press event discussing ZSRT's involvement in the DIRECTED project and their commitment to disaster resilience.	10 Participants at ZalaZONE Test Centre	18th, December 2023
Interview with Danube Stakeholder	EUSDR- Laszlo Balatonyi	5th, January 2024
Overview of DIRECTED's focus on data interoperability and the development of the Data Fabric.	5 Participants - Private Sector/ Industry: MTech Systems Climate Research Division	12th, January 2024
Presentation regarding DIRECTED's approach to enhancing community engagement and resilience building.	3 Participants in City of Nagykanizsa	1st, February 2024
Introduction to DIRECTED's focus on integrating DRM and CCA	3 Participants at Municipality of Zala County	29th, February 2024
Overview of DIRECTED's work on improving the interoperability of data and models for Disaster Risk Management.	3 Participants at National/ Regional Authority - Hungarian Road Department	15th, March 2024
Zala Special Rescue Team 20th anniversary event demonstrating successful projects including	30 Participants including first responders from ZSRT, local politicians, national authorities and county	18th April 2024

DIRECTED and RWL.	officials	
Introduction to new mayor about DIRECTED	3 Participants, Mayor of Keszthely	10th December 2024
Bilateral discussions/calls planning for multi-stakeholder workshops	Mayor of Keszthely Zala Special Rescue Team, other RWL stakeholders	January - March 2025
RWL Multi-stakeholder Workshop hosted by Zala Special Rescue Team in Zalaegerszeg focused on Data Fabric	15 Participants including first responders and disaster management agencies.	24th March 2025
RWL Multi-stakeholder Workshop on disaster and climate resilience in West Balaton hosted by City of Keszthely	25 Participants including municipality mayors, disaster management agencies, NGOs, regional agencies representing roads, tourism, private sector	26th March 2025
Field visit with DIRECTED researchers and ZSRT	7 Participants, Clorofeel, Lifelong learning Education Centre	25th March 2025
Field visit with DIRECTED researchers and ZSRT	5 Participants, Water Management Authority Kis Balaton	27th March 2025
Meeting with DIRECTED researchers about Data Fabric	3 Participants, National University of Public Service, Budapest	28th March 2025
Meeting with national disaster management authority about scientific collaboration in DIRECTED	3 Participants including chair of the scientific board of the national disaster management authority	15 April 2025
Follow up meetings with RWL stakeholders on data access	Forestry company, national disaster management agency, Localience project,	April - September 2025
Meeting with MyDroneMet Meteorological Data in the Data Fabric	7 participants including MyDroneMet, ZSRT, TUBS, UCC, GECOSistema, CLIMADA, 52-North	7th July 2025

Table 3.2.2: RWL Support Focus.

Activity	Work package and number of participants	Timeline
Briefing Note on Risk-Tandem/ Recorded Presentation/ Powerpoint	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	3rd, January 2023

Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	16th March 2023
Jour Fixe Risk-Tandem Presentation	WP 3, 25 Participants	16th, March 2023
Stakeholder interactions debrief interview and support consultation	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	12th June 2023
Capacity development training: Complex risks	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th June 2023
Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st September 2023
Scoping: Tailoring of Risk-Tandem and Capacity Development Needs	WP 4, 6 Participants	18th, October 2024
Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 4, 6 Participants	14th December 2023
Scoping consultation on needs for workshop planning	WP 4, 6 Participants	23rd, January 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on Citizen Engagement	WP 4/3, 19 Participants	26th, March 2024
Stakeholder interactions debrief interview and support consultation	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	9th April 2024
Group Interviews and Discussion Guidance	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	11th, April 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on RiskPACC	WP 4/3, 21 Participants	23rd, April 2024
Support and ideas for Stakeholder Interviews	WP 3/4, 7 Participants	24th, April 2024
User Story Development / Data Fabric	WP 5/2/4/3, 10 participants	30th April 2024
Support for Workshop Planning Reflection on Interviews	WP 3/4, all, 6 participants	10th May 2024
User Needs Discussions, Data Fabric	WP 5/3/4, 6 Participants	14th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Monitoring, Evaluation, and Knowledge co-production	WP 4, 15 Participants	16th, May 2024

Capacity Development: Webinar and Ideas Exchange- Lessons from the Civil Protection of Service	WP 4, 14 Participants	21st, May 2024
User Needs Discussion, Data Fabric	WP 5/3/4, 6 Participants	27th, May 2024
Scoping consultation on needs and support	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	31st, May 2024
RWL User needs process discussion (General Assembly)	WP 3/5, 10 Participants	15th, June 2024
Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change	WP 4, 6 Participants	28th, June 2024
Capacity development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	WP 4, 15 Participants	25th, July 2024
Scoping consultation and user needs for Data Fabric	WP 5/ 4, 6 Participants	17th, August 2024
Scoping: tailoring of Risk-Tandem and capacity development needs	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	16th, October 2024
End of year reflections and planning next steps	WP 4/ 3, 7 Participants	6th, December 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss the implementation of Data Fabric	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	12th, December 2024
Scoping consultation on needs and support	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	13th, December 2024
Task Force Meeting to review user stories and discuss mock ups 5.4	WP 5/ 3, 7 Participants	14th, January 2025
RWL Peer 2 Peer Learning exchange	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, January 2025
Task Force Meeting to review and discussion of mock ups for D5.4	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	30th, January 2025
Scoping: RWL workshop planning meeting	WP 4, 6 Participants	14th, February 2025
Task Force Meeting to review user stories in D5.2	WP 5/3, 7 Participants	20th, February 2025
Capacity development co-explore to co-design	WP 4, 15 Participants	21st, February 2025
Support: RWL Workshop	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	27th, February 2025

planning		
Task Force Meeting to coordinate new mock ups, and review user stories	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	12th, March 2025
Support: RWL Workshop planning	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	6th, 10th, 14th and 18th March 2025
Task Force/ Workshop Planning and identifying possible datasets: weather stations in Balaton and census data	WP 5/3/4, 8 Participants	4th, April 2025
Debrief and evaluation of RWL workshop	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	14th April 2025
Task Force/ Workshop Debrief to review mock ups from D5.4	WP 5/ 4, 7 Participants	24th, April 2025
Task Force/ Workshop debrief to integrate crop yield outputs	WP 5/2, 8 Participants	5th, June 2025
Task Force/ Workshop Planning to review for upcoming workshop	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	26th, June 2025
Capacity development co-designing interventions	WP 4, 15 Participants	2nd July 2025
Task Force/ Data Fabric updates and data integration	WP 5/3, 3 Participants	14th, August 2025
Task Force Meeting/ Workshop Planning for year 4 and D3.2	WP 5/3/4, 6 Participants	29th, August 2025
Climate Festival planning meeting	WP 3/4 6 Participants	1st September 2025
Task Force Meeting - next steps Data Fabric and RWL engagement	WP 5/4, 6 Participants	18th September 2025

Table 4: Activities RWL 4: The Rhine-Erft Region

Table 4.1: RWL Engagement Focus.

Activity	Target groups and number of participants	Timeline
1st DIRECTED Meeting introducing the project, and establishing expectations	9 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, and Rhine-Erft, and Erftverband Staff	19, April 2023
Flood Protection Cooperation meeting, presentation of DIRECTED	35 Participants including municipalities	April 2023
RWL DIRECTED Questionnaire	5 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, and Rhine-Erft.	April 2023
2nd Stakeholder Meeting	15 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, and Rhine-Erft, Erftverband Staff	29, June 2023
3rd Stakeholder Meeting to discuss education and training programs; regional disaster control network(H-Kat-Net), district level discussion on disaster control, and present on planning and preparation techniques from the Fire Department	14 Participants including Districts of Erftstadt, Euskirchen, Rhein-Sieg, and Rhine-Erft, Erftverband Staff, and RPTU	20, November 2023
4th Stakeholder Meeting to discuss RWL progress and the introduction of KRITIS-Dialogue	14 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, Rhine-Erft, Rhein Neuss, and Erftverband Staff	18, March 2024
5th Stakeholder Meeting to discuss the organization and structure of Germany's operational forces reporting	10 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, Rhine-Erft, Rhine Neuss, and Erftverband Staff	19th, August 2024
Tabletop exercise- Flooding information	9 Participants	20th & 21st, January 2025
6th Stakeholder Meeting to discuss Flooding tabletop exercise and update Webex Meeting for Situation Assessment	21 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, Rhine-Erft, Rhine Neuss, Rhine Sieg, Erftverband Staff	20th January 2025
7th Stakeholder Meeting to discuss upcoming Resilience Expo	12 Participants including Districts of Euskirchen, Rhine-Erft, Rhine-Sieg, Erftverband Staff	19th, June 2025
Governance Interview	RWL hosts: 52° North	14th, July 2025

Public engagement activity	public participants; Artist engagement; RWL hosts; stakeholders	29th August 2025
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Table 4.2: RWL Support Focus

Activity	Workpackage and number of participants	Timeline
Briefing Note on Risk-Tandem/ Recorded Presentation/ Powerpoint	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	3rd, January 2023
Risk-Tandem Introduction/ Guidance on RWL Set Up/ First Workshop	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	13th, March 2023
Jour Fixe Risk-Tandem Presentation	WP 3, 25 Participants	16th, March 2023
First Capacity Development Module (Complex Risk)	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, June 2023
Risk-Tandem RWL training at General Assembly (World Cafe exercise, serious game, creative exercise)	WP 4/3, 25 Participants	19th and 21st September 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss user stories in D5.2, mock ups in D5.4	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	7th, January 2024
Scoping Interviews on Needs	WP 4, 5 Participants	22nd, January 2024
Task Force Meeting to review user stories	WP 5/3, 7 Participants	28th, January 2024
Task Force Meeting to establish new milestones and discuss dam break scenario adjustments	WP 5/3, 8 Participants	18th, February 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss user stories	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	25th, February 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss mock ups and milestones D5.2	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	18th, March 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on Citizen Engagement	WP 4/3, 19 Participants	26th, March 2024
Workshop Debrief	WP 4/3, 7 Participants	27th, March 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss the limitations of models and draft mockups for model boundaries	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	1st, April 2024

Group Interviews and Discussion Guidance	WP 3/4, RWL hosts	11th, April 2024
1st Workshop Debrief	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	21st, April 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss milestones and mock-ups	WP 5/3, 6 Participants	23rd, April 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar on RiskPACC	WP 4/3, 12 Participants	23rd, April 2024
Interviews on RIM2D Model in Relation to Risk-Layering	WP 3/2, 4 Participants	6th, May 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss RWL frontend and dam break scenario in RIM2D	WP 5/3, 4 Participants	13th, May 2024
Capacity Development: Monitoring, Evaluation, and Knowledge co-production	WP 4, 15 Participants	16th, May 2024
User Needs Discussion, Data Fabric	WP 5/3/4, 5 Participants	21st, May 2024
Capacity Development: Webinar and Ideas Exchange- Lessons from the Civil Protection of Service	WP 4, 14 Participants	21st, May 2024
Capacity Development: MEL and Establishing a Theory of Change	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	25th, June 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss feedback on first drought data visualization	WP 5/2/ 3, 5 Participants	3rd, June 2024
RWL User needs process discussion (General Assembly)	WP 3/5, 10 Participants	15th, June 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss RIM2D testing phase and API development	WP 5/3, 8 Participants	15th, July 2024
Capacity development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	WP 4, 15 Participants	25th July 2024
Task Force Meeting for API process with RIM2D configuration	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	5th, August 2024
Scoping Consultations and Needs Analysis for Data Fabric	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	11th, August 2024
Workshop Debrief	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	19th, September 2024

Scoping: Tailoring of Risk-Tandem and Capacity Development Needs	WP 4/3, 8 Participants	7th, October 2024
Deep Dive into Theory of Change establishing a Model Case	WP 4, 6 Participants	14th, October 2024
Development of TTX	WP 4, 3 Participants	6th, December 2024
Development of TTX	WP 4, 3 Participants	13th, December 2024
Task Force Meeting to discuss implementation of Data Fabric	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	13th, December 2024
Development of TTX	WP 4, 3 Participants	14th, January 2025
Development of TTX	WP 4, 3 Participants	14th, January 2025
RWL Peer 2 Peer Learning exchange	WP 4, 15 Participants	15th, January 2025
Support in Facilitating Workshop	WP 4, 6 Participants	21st, January 2025
Capacity development co-explore to co-design	WP 4, 15 Participants	21st, February 2025
Evaluation of Workshop	WP 4, 6 Participants	22nd, February 2025
Task Force Meeting	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	1st, April 2025
Development of Workshop	WP 4/3, 6 Participants	8th, April 2025
Task Force Meeting	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	23rd, April 2025
Task Force Meeting	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	13th, May 2025
Task Force Meeting to develop damn break scenario	WP 5/3, 5 Participants	3rd, June 2025
Support with CCA and Drought interview preparation	WP 4/3, 4 Participants	5th June, 2025
Capacity development co-designing interventions	WP 4, 15 Participants	2nd, July 2025
Development of Workshop	WP 4/3, 12 Participants	5th, August 2025
Task Force Meeting to discuss results from damn break scenario and finalize planning for the next year	WP 5/3, 9 Participants	26th, August 2025

Annex 2: Interoperability Fact Sheets

Real World Lab 1 - Copenhagen Capital Region, Denmark

Interoperability Fact Sheet #1: Roskilde Fjord

Hazard and impact assessments for Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management

About the Real World Lab: The national flood risk assessment carried out by the Danish Coastal Authority in 2024 in the context of the EU Floods Directive has for the first time identified the Roskilde Fjord region (including its connection to the nearby Arresø lake) as a high-risk area, related mainly to coastal flooding, urban areas and economic impacts. The region is indicated in orange on the map of Zealand, Denmark. Real World Lab #1 spans the five municipalities bordering Roskilde Fjord (Halsnæs, Frederikssund, Egedal, Roskilde and Lejre) as well as the three local emergency management services (fire services). In Denmark, Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management are principally separated, although at the local level both are fixed at the municipal level. In Lejre and Roskilde municipality, the local emergency management service is linked directly to the municipality. In Halsnæs, Frederikssund, and Egedal the local emergency service is jointly owned and operated (together with two municipalities outside the Roskilde Fjord region). Climate Change Adaptation in Denmark is anchored in the municipalities, and the framework conditions for working together across municipal borders are poor. Those municipalities that are singled out by the national flood risk assessment are legally responsible for preparing risk management plans towards the negative consequences of coastal and riverine flooding on human health, cultural heritage, economic activities and the environment, involving dual aspects of Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management. So, this is the first time that the five municipalities in Roskilde Fjord have the legal obligation to prepare such plans.

1. Background and interoperability challenges

In general, local Danish emergency management services do not utilize or maintain expertise with advanced digital tools but rely on assistance from municipal GIS specialists in case of an emergency. Conversely, in several of the municipalities around Roskilde Fjord there is essentially only a single individual with the technical skills to provide the necessary

map information. In cases where this individual is absent, e.g. during a vacation, updated and high-quality flood maps are therefore often not accessible. Local emergency management services receive early warnings, weather and water level forecasts from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) in document formats and are left to find supplementary information on their public website. In the future, DMI will also provide simple flood maps with this reporting; while superior maps typically exist at the municipal level as part of Climate Change Adaptation planning, they are often generated from a future climate scenario perspective, which makes it difficult to match them with the hazard information received from DMI.

The flood maps and impact assessments used by Danish municipalities for Climate Change Adaptation are highly heterogeneous and differ highly across municipalities. Hence, modelling of coastal, pluvial, and fluvial flooding and their local impacts are often carried out by different model providers and using different assumptions, e.g. in terms of climate scenarios, future time periods, and land surface. The latter is exacerbated by the framework conditions: coastal (and linked riverine flooding) is addressed under the EU Floods Directive, whereas rain and rising groundwater levels are handled by public and private utility companies. The inherent heterogeneity makes it difficult to assess the uncertainty of the results. Several municipalities in this Real World Lab are users of SCALGO Live, which is a simple, for-screening, cloud-based terrain model that can be used to model flooding from several different water sources.

2. Objectives

- Enable the use of digital tools by the local emergency management services, providing them with access to updated, high-quality map resources without involving municipal GIS specialists and with a minimum of training (User Story 1.1).
- Facilitate the interoperability and consistency of data for dual use in emergency management and Climate Change Adaptation.
- Facilitate uncertainty / sensitivity analyses, considering multiple hazard severities, multiple flood models, and multiple sectors (User Story 1.5).

3. Description of the workflow

[Figure 1](#) shows a schematic of the proposed workflow. To facilitate the use of advanced data by non-specialists, the data accessible to the user has been standardized and the different modelling components are made to be interoperable.

The left part of the schematic illustrates the production of flood maps. Any number of flood models can be included. In the schematic, Saferplaces, SCALGO Live, and RIM2D have adopted the same assumptions (e.g. digital elevation model), whereas existing calculations carried out by the user through a commercial actor (using the same or different assumptions) could also be added. Model output is generated by regularly increasing water levels (e.g. 0-3 m) and rain intensities (0-150 mm/day) and stored in a database. For each flood map in this

ensemble, the corresponding exposure and impacts are calculated using DamageCost and also added to the database from where users can access all the “raw” data.

The central part of the schematic (light blue background) depicts the user interface of the Data Fabric, which provides the interface to the database. The user interface has been tailored for both Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management applications. In the Data Fabric the user can initially choose between pluvial and coastal flooding; or shallow groundwater levels. In the second step, the user sets the water level (cm - for coastal flooding) or rain intensity (mm - for pluvial flooding). For emergency management applications, the Data Fabric provides a facility to display real-time DMI forecasts accessed via DMI’s Open Data interface, including for sea levels. These can readily then be translated by the user into flood maps. Likewise, the Data Fabric has a facility for listing scenario results from the Climate Atlas that can be transferred into flood maps at the request of the user. As content from the Climate Atlas cannot be directly accessed through the Open Data interface, a static text box informs the user about the link between SSP/RCP scenarios.

Figure 1: Schematic workflow.

The flood maps in the Data Fabric are organized by hazard severity, e.g. the sea level or rain intensity, to allow for better integration with real-time forecasting but also to allow for comparing multiple flood models. By organizing the set of flood maps by severity (pluvial or coastal), e.g. a water level of 2 meters, rather than by scenario (as in the Climate Atlas) the user can import and compare flood maps from any model, even one that adopts a different set of assumptions, based on hazard severity.

To the right, the schematic illustrates imports from external data sources. As mentioned above, climate change information (scenarios, extreme statistics) is retrieved from the Danish Climate Atlas and displayed in the Data Fabric. An automatic database query collects real-time forecasts of rain, water level, wind, etc. from DMI where they are shown graphically to the user.

Finally, to accommodate analyses of “water from all sides” and compound climate events, we import maps of shallow groundwater levels under current and future climate conditions from the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS). This process is not automated.

4. Models and data

- Saferplaces
- RIM2D
- SCALGO Live
- DamageCost (“SkadesØkonomi”)
- Danish National Climate Atlas
- DMI Open Data Portal (including weather forecasts)
- HIP (hydrological) data
- Digital elevation model (DEM) for Denmark
- Asset maps, e.g. official building maps / layers

Real World Lab 2 - Emilia-Romagna - Rimini Province Italy

Interoperability Fact Sheet #1

Pluvial /Coastal Flood hazard

About the Real World Lab:

The Emilia-Romagna Region's Real World Lab (RWL 2) is led by the Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region (ARSTPC-ER), which is responsible for DRM related to climate risks, including early warning systems and CCA planning. Partnering with ARSTPC-ER is the ARPAE Hydrometeo Service Civil Protection Functional Centre, which supports the monitoring and forecasting of weather and climate conditions critical for emergency management.

Municipal governments play a pivotal role in this setup, with several municipalities involved, including Riccione, Rimini, Bellaria Igea, Misano Adriatico, and Cattolica. These municipal entities are the first responders in emergencies and are tasked with implementing the municipal civil protection plans. Their responsibilities are complemented by the provincial civil protection voluntary coordination in Rimini, which provide essential support during emergencies.

The needs identified for RWL 2 in this area emphasize the importance of enhanced coordination among various first responders and stakeholders to ensure an effective and timely response to emergencies. This includes sharing monitoring networks and forecasting tools to improve early warning and disaster management. There is a critical

need for interconnected real-time data to support decision-making during emergencies, which calls for the development of platforms and tools for data acquisition and integration.

RWL 2 experiences frequent heavy rains and high tides, leading to widespread flooding. Both DRR and CCA have to tackle these hazards on different administrative levels and time frames. Thus the works in Directed for RWL 2 focus on supporting early warning for an improved DRR, but also CCA planning related to pluvial and coastal floods.

Involved stakeholder expectations, as captured so far include:

- Update of the Civil Protection Plan where benefits from the DIRECTED activities, data, models and tools are seen as beneficial.
- Providing interconnected observed data and forecasts in real time, which is currently missing.

To strengthen emergency coordination the following actions have been identified:

- Sharing of gauging stations monitoring data and forecasts among the various actors involved in the project (Hera, Reclamation Consortium, Municipalities).
- Development of a protocol of actions that provides information and data through an automated tool or an App, a website for planning, coordinating and illustrating Citizen Science actions, involving, for example, citizens and schools.
- Organize exercises for coastal risk management.

1. Background and interoperability challenges

Operational context and coordination needs.

RWL 2 brings together municipal and provincial Civil Protection authorities, the Regional Operations Centre (**COR**), and **ARPAE** (regional environmental agency), and first responders. The common need is **better and faster coordination** across agencies, sharing monitoring networks, forecasts, and actionable maps, in order to move from warnings to **operational decisions** (e.g., staging volunteers, placing temporary barriers, planning road closures) within minutes rather than hours. This requires **interconnected real-time data** and an interoperable toolchain capable of turning observations and forecasts into **near-real-time pluvial/coastal flood hazard and impact information** that non-specialists can use during an emergency.

Interoperability in RWL 2 hinges on two ingredients:

- (i) observed data streams (sensors, radar HERA, tide gauges)
- (ii) short-term forecasts/nowcasts (rainfall, sea level, wave conditions).

Interoperable solutions like **SaferPlaces** and the **DIRECTED Data Fabric** must be able to ingest these feeds, translate them into severity-based flood extents, and publish simple, trusted operational views (maps, time-series, thresholds/ “traffic lights”).

The approach developed in DIRECTED proved its value during the May 2023 flood event, when SaferPlaces supported Civil Protection ad-hoc with rapid flood mapping and early warning products. RWL 2 aims to institutionalise this capability and transform it into an operational routine.

Pre-project baseline (before DIRECTED)

As captured with local stakeholders, the base line in RWL 2 shows clear strengths in monitoring, but significant last-mile gaps in DDR:

- **Real-time data latency:** sensor/radar/gauge data are generally available with only a few minutes of delay but not orchestrated for operational modelling.
- **No automatic nowcast/forecast exploitation:** data are not automatically transformed to be used in hazard nowcasting and short-range forecasting.
- **Resolution limitations:** the spatial and temporal resolution of available products is often insufficient for **street-level flood decisions** (e.g., barrier placement, local diversions).
- **Operational UI gap:** there is no user-friendly, unified interface tailored for emergency operators for “one-click” access to flood hazard maps, evolution plots, and alerts.
- **No standard “hazard x receptors” routines:** there is no automated overlay of flood maps with sensitive receptors/critical resources (hospitals, schools, care homes, lifelines, etc.) to produce actionable flood impact forecasts.
- **Fragmented responsibilities:** early-warning information from COR/ARPAE is used locally, but a dedicated nowcasting/forecasting application that rapidly maps approaching pluvial or coastal floods is missing.
- **Compound events:** workflows to handle coincident coastal surge + cloudburst are immature.
- **Data/metadata mismatches:** differences in vertical datums, DEM versions, symbology, thresholds, and access permissions slow down cross-agency use.
- Disseminate results via maps, time-series, and traffic-light dashboards, all accessible through a unified, operator-friendly interface.

2. Objectives

O1 — Reduce observation-to-visualization latency.

Minimize the total lag from data acquisition to on-screen visualization. **Target: ≤ 5-10 minutes** end-to-end from source update to map/dashboard refresh; **≤ 5 minutes** to translate a forecast value into a flood map via severity bins.

O2 — Increase spatial resolution and early-warning capacity.

Deliver operational pluvial and coastal flood forecasts for **Rimini Province** at decision-ready scales and lead times.

O3 — One unified, operator-friendly web application.

Integrate **real-time and short-term forecasts** with **rapid hazard models** in a single mapping app → DIRECTED **Data Fabric** + **SaferPlaces**:

- **Maps, time-series, dashboard of exposed receptors, traffic-light thresholds, calendar/scheduling widgets.**
- **Role-based access** and audit logs for municipal/provincial/regional users.

O4 — Rapid, actionable insight for emergency operations.

Automate the “hazard × receptors” last mile so operators can answer, within seconds:

- **Who/what is affected?** (Population estimates, buildings, critical facilities, roads, utilities).
- **How many to evacuate and where to place shelters?** (Counts by zone, triage of vulnerable sites).
- **What resources are needed now?** (e.g., **sandbag** estimates by frontage length and target height; indicative **pump** capacity from ponding volume and drawdown time).
- **What to brief?** (auto-generated **PDF** situation summaries and map sheets).

O5 — Self-service for local emergency services.

Enable non-specialists to access **updated, high-quality maps** without a GIS specialist and with minimal training. **Targets: ≤ 2 hours** onboarding; common symbology and workflows; **≥ 90%** of trained operators can reproduce a standard task unaided (load forecast → select severity → generate map → export impact table).

O6 — Interoperability for dual use (operations & adaptation).

Standardize **CRS and vertical datums**, metadata, layer names, and severity bins so the same datasets support **emergency management** and **climate adaptation**. Provide stable **APIs** to and from COR/ARPAE and municipal systems; document provenance so planning studies and operational maps are comparable.

O7 — Uncertainty & sensitivity analyses (User Story 2.2).

Expose **model/parameter uncertainty** with **low/central/high** envelopes; allow comparisons across multiple models/providers and hazard severities. Enable overlays by **sector**

(transport, health, utilities) and simple **what-if** toggles (e.g., add temporary barrier, change threshold) to support robust decisions.

DIRECTED Data Fabric + SaferPlaces

The purpose of DIRECTED's **Data Fabric** is to **operationalise interoperability**: put real-time/short-term forecasts and observations in the hands of operators and convert them—via SaferPlaces and companion tools—into rapid pluvial/coastal flood maps that support early warning and emergency operations (e.g., displacement, barrier placement, traffic management). The Data Fabric offers:

3. Ingestion of COR/ARPAE feeds and local sensors.
4. Translation of flood forecast into pre-agreed severity bins.
5. Retrieval or computation of the corresponding flood extents.
6. Intersection with receptors to produce impact forecasts.

7. Description of the workflow

The RWL 2 workflow turns **real-time observations** and **short-term forecasts** into **operator-ready hazard and impact views** for pluvial and coastal events. It does this through five coordinated layers: **(1) Data sources, (2) Ingestion & orchestration, (3) Processing services, (4) Common data store, (5) Visualization & decision products**. The blue “API” connectors in the figure indicate machine-to-machine calls between layers.

(1) Data sources — real-time observations of rainfall, ocean water levels, river water levels, receptors as critical infrastructure, road network, vulnerable places, etc., and rainfall and sea level forecasts from a large number of different sources are collected (left in [Figure 1](#))

(2) Ingestion & orchestration: data are processed and streamlined (center in [Figure 1](#))

(3) Processing services via PyGEOAPI: triggering of simulation tools (SaferPlaces, RIM2D, CLIMADA, SVI) and collection of model output in a harmonized format (right-center in [Figure 1](#))

(4) Common data store: S3 bucket for all data for ensuring versioning, provenance and reproducibility (right in [Figure 1](#))

(5) Visualization & decision products: Unified web app consisting of Data Fabric and SaferPlaces for visualization of data, forecasts and simulation results (top-right in [Figure 1](#))

Example operational flows (as implied by the [Figure 1](#))

- **Pluvial event (Rimini).**
HERA radar nowcasting + ICON21 rainfall → Ingestor → SaferPlaces (pluvial bin) → **Pluvial extent** → CLIMADA/SVI → **Impact dashboard** (people to evacuate, vulnerable sites) → **PDF briefings & WMS.**
- **Coastal event (Rimini coast).**
Tide gauge (Cattolica/Rimini) + SWAN/ADRIAC sea levels/waves + beach profile (XBeach) + coast slope → Ingestor → SaferPlaces (water-level bin) → **Coastal extent** → CLIMADA/SVI → **Barrier placement & road closures view.**

Figure 1: RWL 2 operational schematic workflow.

4. Models and data

- [SAFERLACES](#)
- [CLIMADA](#)
- [RIM2D](#)
- HERA radar nowcasts / ARPAE radar rainfall intensity
- ICON21 weather forecasts (rainfall)
- SVI. Social vulnerability indicators to help prioritise assistance (e.g., elderly populations, healthcare facilities).
- SWAN/ADRIAC sea forecasts (waves, water level)
- Tide/sea-level gauge stations (Cattolica, Rimini)
- Sea state / wave buoy data (e.g., Cesenatico)
- Rain-gauge network and river level gauges
- Coastal morphology inputs (coast-slope transects, XBeach beach profiles)
- Digital Elevation Model (DEM) / LiDAR
- Land use, lithology, building footprints.
- Exposure/receptor layers (critical facilities, roads, shelters, utilities)
- Population/census data
- Copernicus EMS/CDS reference layers

Real World Lab 3 - Danube River Basin

Interoperability Fact Sheet #1

Hazard and impact assessments for Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management regarding river floods in and around the city of Vienna

About the Real World Lab:

RWL 3, coordinated by Genillard & Co, is principally defined by the Danube River Basin as shown in the above map. Due to its vast area of more than 800,000 km² stretching over 19 national jurisdictions and the difficulties in communicating across 11 different major languages spoken in this domain, two focus regions had been selected: the city of Vienna and the Zala Region in Western Hungary. The Belgrade area, also highlighted in the map, was originally considered as the third focus region but dropped in the beginning of DIRECTED.

On the whole-basin level, the insurance industry plays an important role. Since it is necessary to understand and measure the risk to determine the premium for a particular insurance benefit, the insurance industry as a stakeholder has a wealth of experience that should be leveraged during the project.

The City of Vienna, which covers an area of 415 km² in total, is traversed by the Danube, Europe's second largest river. It overlaps the downstream part of the Vienna River Basin (unfortunately not visible in the above map), which contributes to the potential for significant run-off and water accumulation within the built-up quarters. Rapid snow melt or heavy rainfall events in the upstream mountainous region of the Wienerwald, mostly in spring or early summer, regularly cause a rise in water levels, potentially resulting in localized or even widespread flooding. Climate change projections indicate an increase in temperature as well as shifts in precipitation patterns, with an increased risk of extreme weather events in the future.

However, fluvial flood risks are well controlled by dikes, retention basins as well as the Danube Canal to mitigate damage by flooding. Vienna's flood and drought risk management landscape is a diverse network of both public authorities and private institutions and organizations active at national, regional, and local levels. The government of Vienna is responsible for developing and implementing protection policies and infrastructure projects. Environmental agencies and water management authorities also collaborate closely to monitor water levels and implement warning systems. On a national level, various ministries are involved in the development of comprehensive protection plans.

1. Background and interoperability challenges

For Vienna, there do exist already very advanced protection measures against fluvial (Danube) floods since the Austrian capital exposes an extreme concentration of valuables and irrecoverable treasures of Central European cultural history, and there were already inconvenient experiences with Danube river floods in the past. Principal elements of Vienna's flood protection are

- Straightening of the originally meandering course of the Danube river (first regulation, 1870–1875). This increases the hydraulic gradient and minimizes the channel roughness, both factors increase the flow velocity and minimize the hydraulic cross section for a given discharge.
- Doubling the straightened river channel by a parallel canal (Neue Donau), this was the second regulation (1972–1988). The canal is usually locked providing a long lake of high water quality used for recreation purposes. During flood events, it is opened to discharge a good part of the flood wave which can now reach 14,000 m³/s without doing much harm to the city.
- Installation of polder dams in the Wien River upstream the city centre (between Hadersdorf and Hütteldorf) and
- Canalization of the Wien River in an artificial bed plastered smoothly with mortar reducing the hydraulic roughness to a minimum. The Wien River regulation went together with the construction of a metro line in the years 1895–1899. The design maximum runoff of 600 m³/s was never exceeded yet.

Since 1825 there have been five major Danube floods (1862, 1899, 1954, 2002, and 2013) with discharges of about 10,000 m³/s; the 2013 flood reached just over 11,000 m³/s and caused damages to buildings and infrastructure up- and downstream of Vienna, but not in the well-defended capital. The recurrence interval of the 14,000 m³/s which could be maximally sustained here cannot be reliably estimated but should exceed 1000 years.

Considering the practical irrelevance of river flood hazards in Vienna the respective efforts of DIRECTED with flood modelling and stakeholder interaction in this focus region may seem irrelevant as well – but how Austria deals with river flood risks could be a role model for other countries in the Danube basin, and this was a major take from our first stakeholder event in Vienna in 2024:

The Austrian government and federal state authorities run an internet platform called HORA (Natural Hazard Overview & Risk Assessment Austria) which maps all kind of natural hazards, namely (river) floods, surface runoff (i.e. pluvial floods), avalanches, earthquakes, landslides, wind gusts, lightning, hail, and snow loads. The user can zoom into a map of the country down to single homes and property lots. For each spot in Austria which can be selected arbitrarily the system will produce a “HORA Pass” within a few seconds after the push of a button; this is a two-page PDF listing the individual hazard in each category.

Alternatively, a 3D visualization of an extreme flood can be generated. This is a valuable aid for prospective buyers of real estate or architects: while only a few protective measures are mandatory for construction, extra protection can be ordered individually in a responsible way or an intended construction project located in a dangerous place can be said off altogether. But even a tenant who needs to move can check the location of apartment offers before renting.

HORA's flood risk map over the south-eastern outskirts of Vienna including the Schwechat international airport. Practically all flood-prone areas are outside the city limits.

Example of a HORA 3D flood visualization for a chosen location.

2. Objectives

Among the user stories for the Data Fabric identified in WP 5 (see Deliverable D5.2) those involving fluvial flood modelling relevant for Vienna and the federal state of Lower Austria are (with user personas in parentheses):

- Fluvial flood modelling upstream and downstream of Vienna (all personas),

- Climate projections of flood risk (all personas),
- (Selected) natural hazard overview for the Danube basin (all personas), and
- HORA-like tool for “nearcasting” and early warning in the Danube River basin (insurance industry)

Except for the demand for nearcasting and early warning which cannot be fulfilled by the Danube Model due to the lack of adequately available input data, all user stories boil down to two objectives:

O1 — Provision of flood hazard maps directly readable by end-users

O2 — Provision of flood hazard statistics for further analysis and risk estimation, e.g. through CLIMADA

3. Models and data

The only model in DIRECTED dealing with fluvial flood hazards is the Danube Model (DM). The DM (formerly known as Future Danube Model and misleadingly dubbed Seamless Forecasting Tool in the Grant Agreement) is a combined eco-hydrological and hydrodynamics model simulating landscape water fluxes and river discharges including flood stages and runoff velocities. It contains a detailed landscape representation including soil profiles, land use or land cover data considering crop growth dynamics, and subbasin and channel geometries. Calibrated with weather (gridded daily observations) on water stage and river runoff measurements from several gauges it generates detailed maps on flood events under climate scenarios. A more detailed description is given in Deliverable D2.2.

The model input can be divided into static – usually raster maps or derived from these – and variable time series data. Important static inputs are (the list may not be exhaustive):

- Subbasin / unit catchment geometries with
- Correspondence table between subbasins and unit catchments
- Elevation (here: MERIT rasters of 3 arc-seconds resolution)
- Digital soil map with profile data associated to the mapping units
- Land use map (here: CORINE Land Cover, CLC 2018)
- Wetland map
- Subbasin parameters for groundwater dynamics
- Upstream-downstream relations of subbasins
- River and floodplain geometries in the unit catchments
- Bifurcation parameters for unit catchments
- Levee parameters (protected area, levee crown height) for unit catchments

Time series inputs are raster fields of daily averages or sums of six meteorological variables, provided in form of NetCDF files:

- Air temperature 2 m above ground
- Daily maximum of air temperature

- Daily minimum of air temperature
- Precipitation
- Downwelling short-wave solar radiation
- Relative air humidity

In addition to these model-driving variables, time series of water level stages and river discharges are needed from numerous gauging stations. They serve as indispensable reference for calibration.

4. Description of the workflow

After the Danube Model had been overhauled and improved (see Deliverable D2.2 for details), final calibration runs were driven by W5E5 v.2.0 weather data (Lange et al. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.342217>), a gridded product resembling the actual weather of the 41-year period 1979–2019. Setting the levee heights according to pre-defined return intervals of levee overtopping by floods was one of the final adjustments in this preparation step. The W5E5 data were chosen because they had also been used for bias adjustment of the ISIMIP climate scenarios.

These climate scenarios in the form of ten realizations each – daily weather variables until the year 2100 – were then used as input, specifically for SWIM, the runoff-generating part of the Danube Model. Running the model cannot be initiated by a single mouse click but requires several steps:

- The SWIM run comes first. Each scenario, e.g. SSP 370, takes about 144 hours of computation time which can be shortened by parallelization.
- The resulting daily runoff values for each of the ~13,000 SWIM subbasins are then redistributed to the ~50,000 unit catchments of the Danube basin used by CaMa-Flood; this step is done in less than one hour by a converter developed within WP 2 which also changes the file format from CSV (used by SWIM) to NetCDF (used by CaMa-Flood).
- The third step are respective CaMa-Flood runs which require about 84 hours on 32 CPUs working simultaneously. Simulating the hydrodynamics is the computationally most demanding step.
- A sub-program of CaMa-Flood has to be started for downscaling CaMa-Flood outputs from unit catchments (on average approx. 2200 ha) to elevation grid cells (less than 1 ha each) in the focus regions. Postprocessing delivers flood hazard (water depth, flow velocity) maps for specific return periods or dynamic maps (video files) for single flood events.
- An extra postprocessing program developed in WP 2 allows for translating the raw NetCDF output of CaMa-Flood to vector maps of the river system with aggregated statistics fed into river reach attributes, e.g. flood heights for specific return intervals or the shift of return intervals in the course of climate change.

The two final steps produce the outputs forwarded to the Data Fabric, either directly for hazard mapping (addressing objective O1) or after further processing through CLIMADA for displaying flood risk (addressing objective O2).

RWL Donau-Region

A colour-coded river network output visualized through the Data Fabric.

A downscaled flood height map for Vienna and its surroundings; this is a Danube Model reanalysis of the centennial flood event in June 2013.

These examples and climate scenario-specific products of the Danube Model may serve as first steps towards extending the HORA capabilities with climate change related projections and to forwarding the idea of the Austrian HORA platform to other parts of the Danube basin.

Real World Lab 3 - Danube River Basin

Interoperability Fact Sheet #2

Hazard and impact assessments for Climate Change Adaptation and emergency management regarding river floods in Zala County

About the Real World Lab:

RWL 3, coordinated by Genillard & Co, is principally defined by the Danube River Basin as shown in the above map. Due to its vast area of more than 800,000 km² stretching over 19 national jurisdictions and the difficulties in communicating across 11 different major languages spoken in this domain, two focus regions had been selected: the city of Vienna and the Zala Region in Western Hungary. The Belgrade area, also highlighted in the map, was originally considered as the third focus region but dropped in the beginning of DIRECTED.

On the whole-basin level, the insurance industry plays an important role. Since it is necessary to understand and measure the risk to determine the premium for a particular insurance benefit, the insurance industry as a stakeholder has a wealth of experience that should be leveraged during the project.

Zala County, situated in the western corner of Hungary, exhibits a diverse and intriguing geographical composition over an area of 3784 km². The terrain is characterized by undulating hills and low mountains, creating a visually captivating landscape with very significant agricultural cropping and production. The road network is of average quality connecting a very scattered village structure: There are almost 300 settlements housing the more than 250,000 inhabitants of the county. Many of the small settlements are spread over a large area of intensively farmed land with varied topography. This is where extreme rainfall promoted by climate change hits: in recent years, unprecedented mudslides have developed; floods wash muddy soil from agricultural land into the public areas, residential yards, and road networks; this is a constant challenge for water and disaster management professionals involved in the cleaning up and remediation of damage. The water authority's staff have not yet devised a permanent solution to this new type of threat; it is likely that protective structures and changes in cultivation methods will have to be introduced in several areas to reinforce natural water retention, and to divert floodwater away from populated areas.

DIRECTED is grateful to be well connected to many Zala Region stakeholders through Levente Huszti from Zala Special Rescue, the Hungarian partner of UN INSARAG, a first responder organisation of civilian volunteers with a nationwide coverage, and the regional lead organisation of Zala County.

1. Background and interoperability challenges

As already described in the RWL introduction box, Zala County occasionally suffers from mud floods. These are typically local, pluvial events, but there are also many settlements on the Zala River, a major tributary of Lake Balaton, including Zalaegerszeg, the largest town and seat of the county administration with approx. 55,000 inhabitants.

Being a small and relatively natural river (without dams) in an undulated landscape, Zala floods come with big deviations from the average discharge (typically more than 100 m³ instead of the typical 2–10 m³/s) but recede after just 2–3 days. There are some measures in place (discontinuous levees in strategically important locations) and some prepared (deployable flood walls), but effective flood protection regularly requires instant action by civil protection agencies.

Remarkable flood events along the Zala River occurred on 5 August 1987 (the highest water levels on record) and 31 March 2013, the latter triggered by a combination of sustained rain and snow melt.

The relatively small size of the river system (1521 km² in total; approx. 600 km² upstream Zalaegerszeg) and the consequently instant reaction of the runoff regime to precipitation events causes short forecast lead times, a major challenge for civil protection deployment planning. Flood alerts rely on warnings by the Hungarian weather service, see <https://www.met.hu/en/idojaras/veszelyjelzes/index.php>, and real-time observations of river gauging stations, see <https://www.vizugy.hu/>. The weather warning site notes [grammatical number errors kept from the original]:

“[I]n spite of using most relevant technology, methodology and meteorological knowledge, it is not possible to issue warning for all severe atmospheric event at the appropriate level and with the necessary time lead!”

As there are no machine forecasts of river flood stages except those from the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) whose outputs are however rather coarse (1 arc-minute tiles) and not immediately released to the public, decision making for the most effective protection efforts (when to mobilize the teams, where to put the sandbags) is constantly challenged by uncertainty. Another problem is the lack of a map viewer showing the hazard landscape comparable to the Austrian HORA system:

The Austrian government and federal state authorities run an internet platform called HORA (Natural Hazard Overview & Risk Assessment Austria) which maps all kind of natural hazards, namely (river) floods, surface runoff (i.e. pluvial floods), avalanches, earthquakes, landslides, wind gusts, lightning, hail, and snow loads. The user can zoom into a map of the country down to single homes and property lots. For each spot in Austria which can be selected arbitrarily the system will produce a “HORA Pass” within a few seconds after the push of a button; this is a two-page PDF listing the individual hazard in each category. Alternatively, a 3D visualization of an extreme flood can be generated. This is a valuable aid

for prospective buyers of real estate or architects: while only a few protective measures are mandatory for construction, extra protection can be ordered individually in a responsible way or an intended construction project located in a dangerous place can be said off altogether. But even a tenant who needs to move can check the location of apartment offers before renting.

HORA's flood risk map over the south-eastern outskirts of Vienna including the Schwechat international airport. Practically all flood-prone areas are outside the city limits.

Example of a HORA 3D flood visualization for a chosen location.

2. Objectives

Among the user stories for the Data Fabric identified in WP 5 (see D5.2) those involving fluvial flood modelling relevant for the Zala Region are (with user personas in parentheses):

- Climate projections of flood risk (all personas),

- (Selected) natural hazard overview for the Danube basin (all personas),
- HORA-like tool for “nearcasting” and early warning in the Danube River basin (insurance industry),
- Multi-hazard dashboard at the municipal level in the Western Balaton region (mayors), and
- Municipality flood risk mapping and mitigation strategies (hydrologist at the national water management authority).

Except for the demand for nearcasting and early warning which cannot be fulfilled by the Danube Model due to the lack of adequately available input data, all user stories boil down to two objectives:

O1 — Provision of flood hazard maps directly readable by end-users

O2 — Provision of flood hazard statistics for further analysis and risk estimation, e.g. through CLIMADA

3. Models and data

The only model in DIRECTED dealing with fluvial flood hazards is the Danube Model (DM). The DM (formerly known as Future Danube Model and misleadingly dubbed Seamless Forecasting Tool in the Grant Agreement) is a combined eco-hydrological and hydrodynamics model simulating landscape water fluxes and river discharges including flood stages and runoff velocities. It contains a detailed landscape representation including soil profiles, land use or land cover data considering crop growth dynamics, and subbasin and channel geometries. Calibrated with weather (gridded daily observations) on water stage and river runoff measurements from several gauges it generates detailed maps on flood events under climate scenarios. A more detailed description is given in Deliverable D2.2.

The model input can be divided into static – usually raster maps or derived from these – and variable time series data. Important static inputs are (the list may not be exhaustive):

- Subbasin / unit catchment geometries with
- Correspondence table between subbasins and unit catchments
- Elevation (here: MERIT rasters of 3 arc-seconds resolution)
- Digital soil map with profile data associated to the mapping units
- Land use map (here: CORINE Land Cover, CLC 2018)
- Wetland map
- Subbasin parameters for groundwater dynamics
- Upstream-downstream relations of subbasins
- River and floodplain geometries in the unit catchments
- Bifurcation parameters for unit catchments

- Levee parameters (protected area, levee crown height) for unit catchments

Time series inputs are raster fields of daily averages or sums of six meteorological variables, provided in form of NetCDF files:

- Air temperature 2 m above ground
- Daily maximum of air temperature
- Daily minimum of air temperature
- Precipitation
- Downwelling short-wave solar radiation
- Relative air humidity

In addition to these model-driving variables, time series of water level stages and river discharges are needed from numerous gauging stations. They serve as indispensable reference for calibration.

4. Description of the workflow

After the Danube Model had been overhauled and improved (see Deliverable D2.2 for details), final calibration runs were driven by W5E5 v.2.0 weather data (Lange et al. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.342217>), a gridded product resembling the actual weather of the 41-year period 1979–2019. Setting the levee heights according to pre-defined return intervals of levee overtopping by floods was one of the final adjustments in this preparation step. The W5E5 data were chosen because they had also been used for bias adjustment of the ISIMIP climate scenarios.

These climate scenarios in the form of ten realizations each – daily weather variables until the year 2100 – were then used as input, specifically for SWIM, the runoff-generating part of the Danube Model. Running the model cannot be initiated by a single mouse click but requires several steps:

- The SWIM run comes first. Each scenario, e.g. SSP 370, takes about 144 hours of computation time which can be shortened by parallelization.
- The resulting daily runoff values for each of the ~13,000 SWIM subbasins are then redistributed to the ~50,000 unit catchments of the Danube basin used by CaMa-Flood; this step is done in less than one hour by a converter developed within WP 2 which also changes the file format from CSV (used by SWIM) to NetCDF (used by CaMa-Flood).
- The third step are respective CaMa-Flood runs which require about 84 hours on 32 CPUs working simultaneously. Simulating the hydrodynamics is the computationally most demanding step.
- A sub-program of CaMa-Flood has to be started for downscaling CaMa-Flood outputs from unit catchments (on average approx. 2200 ha) to elevation grid cells (less than 1 ha each) in the focus regions. Postprocessing delivers flood hazard (water depth, flow

velocity) maps for specific return periods or dynamic maps (video files) for single flood events.

- An extra postprocessing program developed in WP 2 allows for translating the raw NetCDF output of CaMa-Flood to vector maps of the river system with aggregated statistics fed into river reach attributes, e.g. flood heights for specific return intervals or the shift of return intervals in the course of climate change.

The two final steps produce the outputs forwarded to the Data Fabric, either directly for hazard mapping (addressing objective O1) or after further processing through CLIMADA for displaying flood risk (addressing objective O2).

RWL Donau-Region

A colour-coded river network output visualized through the Data Fabric.

A downscaled flood height map for the Zala Region; this is a Danube Model reanalysis of the flood event on 12 September 2014.

These examples and climate scenario-specific products of the Danube Model may serve as first steps towards extending the HORA capabilities with climate change related projections and to forwarding the idea of the Austrian HORA platform to other parts of the Danube basin.

Real World Lab 4 – Rhine-Erft Region

Interoperability Fact Sheet #1

About the Real World Lab:

The Rhine-Erft Region is located in the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany. There is a high risk of flooding from the Erft and its tributaries. In addition to river flooding, events involving heavy rainfall are becoming more frequent, which also leads to flooding. The Erft-catchment is shaded in blue on the map. Real World Lab #4 spans the districts of Euskirchen and Rhine-Erft as well as the intermunicipal flood protection cooperation (hwserft). In Germany, river-management, operation of flood protection systems and early warning are separated. The Erftverband as a waterboard in North Rhine-Westphalia is responsible for the waterway maintenance of most rivers in the catchment, for the operation of flood retention basins and gauges as well as the precipitation-runoff monitoring and forecasting for internal control of the flood protection basins. In the event of flooding, warnings are issued in accordance with the federal structure, from the state office to the district governments, via the districts to the municipalities. However, the Erftverband is not part of the official warning chain. As operator and forecaster of the precipitation-runoff system, Erftverband has expertise in interpreting hydrological data and is able to share this information with disaster control authorities. This exchange of information takes place independently of the official warning and helps decision-makers to assess hydrological flood situations. The official introduction of an online meeting tool provides an opportunity for exchange, joint assessment of the situation, and interpretation of the data.

1. Background and interoperability challenges

In general, local German disaster management authorities of the districts do not use or maintain their own measurement networks and hydrological system forecasts. Furthermore, most district disaster control authorities are not in a position to interpret hydrological data and forecasts adequately, with the handling of statistical uncertainties in particular causing problems in early warning systems. During a flood event, they rely on official warnings from the state of North Rhine-Westphalia (state office → district government → district) or bilateral exchanges with a waterboard (e.g., the Erftverband). Official warnings are issued when specified water level thresholds are exceeded. This procedure has very little preparation time, which has a negative impact on the timely issuance of warnings, particularly in the

southern catchment area of the Erft. The Erftverband operates an extensive network of gauges in the catchment area as well as a flood information system (HOWIS). While the gauge measurements are open to public access, the precipitation runoff forecast ensembles are mainly used internally to control the Erftverband's flood retention basins and are not publicly shared.

The interoperability challenge One of the challenges is to communicate hydrological data and forecasts to the relevant authorities in a comprehensible manner without encroaching on their responsibilities. Although the Erftverband is not part of the warning chain, it is well positioned to pass on the relevant information to the target group in an appropriate manner.

2. Objectives

- Mapping of all stakeholders involved in flood warning and management and their responsibilities
- Development of an internal structure for flood information dissemination and introduction of an alert level in the Howis service.
- Official agreement between Erftverband and districts for data and forecast sharing.
- Introduction of a suitable exchange platform and agenda for joint assessment and interpretation of hydrological data.

3. Description of the workflow

In a first step a mapping of the stakeholders was conducted. [Figure 1](#) shows the outcome of this mapping with all stakeholders involved and the connections.

Stakeholder mapping in RWL Rhine-Erft.

Serious game and tabletop exercises were held in 2023 and 2025 respectively, set the ground for better connecting the various stakeholders. Importantly, these exercises highlighted the distinct decision-spaces in which the individual stakeholders find themselves in, by putting actors into roles they do not normally have. In the tabletop exercise held in 2025 in particular, this approach helped local actors from the administrative and flood organization part of the actor network, to engage with one another and discuss the management of a flood event outside their usual authorities. This helped foster better understanding between the actors, and highlighted potential gaps in information and data sharing, and interoperability between agencies.

Tabletop exercise (left) and serious game (right) to simulate information flow and responsibilities for flood alarming in the RWL Rhine-Erft.

Flood alarm workflow derived from Risk-Tandem and tabletop exercises

River monitoring provides the basis for flood warning. However, triggering an alert and setting an alert level does not solely depend on reaching a critical water level, but also on the professional assessment and expertise of the hydrologist on duty as well as the precipitation forecast. When the alert level is set, the district control centers and the lower water authorities of the districts are contacted by the Ertverband via email and invited to a joint Webex meeting. When the Webex meeting is set up, a digital conference room is established at Ertverband as a multi-lateral situation control center. Present are the head of the Water Division, the (deputy) head of the Water Operations Department, the (deputy) head of the River Basin Management Department, the hydrologist on duty, and representatives from the public relations department.

During the meeting, the current discharge and precipitation measurements and forecasts are discussed. In addition, the uncertainties resulting from the measurements or forecast calculations are discussed. This is intended to help decision-makers make informed decisions and take timely action in case of an imminent flood. This procedure is a direct outcome of Directed activities, highlighting the importance of a thorough mapping of actors

and responsibilities, and the orchestration of the information and decision flow through a structured framework like Risk-Tandem.

4. Models and data

- Risk-Tandem
- Webex
- Howis

Annex 3: Risk-Tandem

Governance Interview Guide

Risk-Tandem Governance Assessment – Interview Questions for RWL hosts

Version 29.09.2025

Purpose: Evaluation and Outcomes/Impact monitoring of the Risk-Tandem Framework's Application to the RWLs throughout M16-M48

Output: Qualitative evaluation of the Risk-Tandem Framework's performance in the RWLs, as seen from the RWL hosts perspective

Target Group: Real World Lab hosts

The RWL Context

- What do you see as the most crucial Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation Challenges that your region faces?
- How, if at all, has the engagement with the DIRECTED project supported your work within your institution to deal with these challenges?
- Are there any particular aspects of the Risk-Tandem Framework, or the DIRECTED project more broadly that are especially relevant to the context of your region?

Stakeholders and Affected Actors:

- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework helped you identify any partners within your institution that you were previously unaware of or less aware of their role?
- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework helped you identify any partners external to your institution that you were previously unaware of or less aware of their role?
- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework helped you understand the relationship and role you play better with other partners in the Disaster Risk Management process?

Co-creation and DIRECTED Consortium Engagement:

- Do you think that the Risk-Tandem Framework was shaped by your needs and interests as a RWL host?
- Do you feel that you have enough opportunities to give input on the Risk-Tandem Framework's development?

- What kinds of engagement & learning activities by the DIRECTED project have you found to be most effective? Why?
- Do you think there are any limitations or issues with the approach taken?

Data & Interoperability

- Do you think the Risk-Tandem Framework has supported the simplification of your decisions surrounding Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaption? If so, how?
- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework highlighted any frictions or incompatibilities between your institution and other institutions involved in the local Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation process?

Communication & Coordination

- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework made you aware of any institutional barriers (due to differences in authority, or responsibility, for example), that affect your role?
- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework made you aware of or supported your outreach to the general public?
- Was the Risk-Tandem Framework helpful in highlighting the relationship between Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation measures?

Resources/Finance

- Did the Risk-Tandem Framework help highlight the existing resources (financial, political, human) that go into your current risk governance infrastructure?
- Can the Risk-Tandem Framework be used to identify any potential unrealized resources?

Other

- What do you think works well with regards to implementing the Risk-Tandem Framework?
- What could be improved?
- Has the Risk-Tandem Framework been sufficiently presented to you? What informational gaps do you think there are?

Partners

